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UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURE AND
ENVIRONMENTAL SCIENCES (UAES),
UMUAGWO, IMO STATE.**

**Theme: Innovative Solutions for Sustainable
Development: Bridging Agriculture, Environment and
Technology**

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CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

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CONFERENCE PAPERS

**SUB-THEME 1:
SUSTAINABLE AGRICULTURAL PRACTICES
FOR FOOD SECURITY**

Farmers' Perception of Drama as a Tool for Agricultural Information Dissemination in Imo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Effective information delivery is crucial for sustainable agriculture. However, the current information delivery system often falls short, hindering the adoption of sustainable practices. Although drama has proven effective in disseminating information, its use in agriculture remains limited. This study explores Farmers' Perception of drama as a tool for Agricultural Information Dissemination in Imo State, Nigeria. The Specific objectives were to: identify Farmers' social economic characteristics, Farmers' sources of agricultural information; Farmers Perception of drama as an agricultural information dissemination tool; and Farmers' preferred medium of drama. A multistage sampling procedure was used to select 180 respondents from Owerri, Orlu and Okigwe agricultural zones. Data were analyzed using frequencies, percentages, and mean scores. Most farmers (73.3%) sourced agricultural information from the listed sources of agricultural information, but drama ranked 16th. In-depth interviews showed that ADP staff in Orlu zone use drama for information dissemination, while those in Owerri do not. Respondents perceived drama (M = 3.1) as appropriate and effective. Picture story (90%) and storytelling (89.4%) were the most preferred forms. Most respondents were open to various participants in drama, with students (86.7%) and farmers from other communities (85.6%) most preferred. The study recommends increased awareness, sensitization, and advocacy for the use of drama as a viable tool for agricultural information dissemination.

Keywords: Agricultural Extension, Agricultural Information Dissemination, Drama, Perception.

Introduction

Agriculture, encompassing the cultivation of food crops and the production of raw materials for agro-industries, remains a cornerstone of economic development. It supports the growth of secondary and tertiary sectors by providing inputs, employment, and demand linkages (Sinha, J. K., 2025). Gelgo et al. (2023) affirm its centrality to poverty reduction, food security, and rural livelihoods. However, in recent years, its contribution to the nation's economy has been on the decline. This can be deduced from the result of an empirical study, that the agricultural sector's contribution to GDP rose from 29.2% to 37% between 1970 and 2002 but significantly decreased to 23.4% in 2021. (World Bank, 2022).

It has been observed, however, that the problem is not a lack of agricultural information, but rather its dissemination, as research has found that the missing link between research and sustainable production is a lack of effective delivery services. This can be seen in the statement of Ajani and Onwubuya (2013) that communication strategies used by extension agents in disseminating information to farmers seem to be ineffective because field observations indicate that the desired results are yet to be achieved. This also corroborates the statement of Abenga et al (2022) that to impart agricultural knowledge to farmers, extension staff must employ efficient communication strategies. There is therefore a need for the use of a veritable tool for agricultural information dissemination.

Drama has long been recognized as an effective method for teaching, learning, and entertainment because it captures attention and deepens understanding, making it a valuable means of sharing information and educating audiences. As stated by Ojemudia (2013), drama acts as a medium for information dissemination, communication, entertainment, conscientization and education. For instance, initiatives aimed at combating AIDS and drug abuse can be conveyed using drama. Drama captivates audiences because of the degree it mirrors real-life situations, making it relatable and engaging. According to Wakesho et al. (2018), drama is used to educate, demonstrate a principle, and illustrate a point of practice.

Drama utilizes varied mediums such as stage performances of plays, dances, musicals, mimes, dramatic presentations, films and so on to communicate (Ojemudia, 2013). These mediums are forms through which drama can be performed. Some of them are: audio drama/play, stage drama, storytelling (narrative drama), picture story (picture leaflet/book) with or without dialogue, and, agricultural video/movie clips.

The need for the incorporation of drama in agricultural information dissemination can be seen in Agrictoday (2020), that to ensure adequate dissemination of information in agriculture value chain, the World Food Programme has urged stakeholders to use drama as a means of educating farmers and producers in the value chain. Lauds in Agrictoday (2020), insinuates that using drama within the agricultural value chain offers a creative avenue for promoting important and timely messages, including post-harvest losses, nutrition, and encourage the youth to venture into the sector. Although drama is widely recognized as an effective medium for communication and information sharing, its application in the dissemination of agricultural information has not been well explored. This therefore, necessitates an investigation into the perception of farmers on the use of drama for agricultural information dissemination.

Methodology

The Study Area

The study was carried out in Imo State, Nigeria. Imo State is in the South-East zone of Nigeria. Imo State came into existence on February 3rd, 1976 along with other new states created under the leadership of the late military ruler of Nigeria, Murtala Muhammad. Imo State lies between latitude 5^o12¹ and 5^o56¹ North of the equator and between longitudes 6^o38¹ and 7^o25¹ east of the Greenwich meridian. It is bordered by Abia State to the East, by Anambra State to the North and River State to the South (Imo State Government (IMSG), 2001).

Sampling Technique

A multistage sampling procedure was adopted in the selection of farmers. The first stage comprised a purposive selection of two (2) Local Government Areas (LGAs) each, from the three agricultural zones, making a total of six (6) LGAs; this is because of their high involvement in agriculture. The second stage was the random selection of two (2) communities from each of the LGAs selected, making a total of twelve (12) communities. The third stage was a random selection of fifteen farmers from the twelve selected communities, making a total of one hundred and eighty (180) farmers.

Data Collection

A structured questionnaire was used to collect primary data from the one hundred and eighty (180) selected farmers, and an in-depth interview (IDI) was used to collect data from ADP staff in the three agricultural zones. Data collected from ADP staff were to assist the researcher in cross-checking the answers obtained from the farmers on the use of drama for agricultural information dissemination in Imo State.

Data Analysis

Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequency distribution, percentage and mean)

Result and Discussion

Socio-Economic Characteristics of Farmers

The variables considered as presented on Table1 were sex, age, marital status, level of education, annual income, household size and farming experience in years.

Sex

The result in Table1 shows that 52.2% of the farmers were male while 47.8% were female. This indicates that there was not much difference between the number of males and the number of females. That is to say that both sexes were well represented in the population. This therefore means that if agricultural information is presented in the form of drama, there are a good proportion of men and women that can implement the information received through drama. It also means that the opinions of the male and the female respondents regarding their perception on the use of drama for agricultural information dissemination are well represented in this study.

Age

The mean age was 45 years. This implies that they were mostly young and fall within economically active age group. Such group is most likely active in farming and tends to develop more interest in sourcing for agricultural information to improve their practices, and will therefore appreciate any suitable means of information dissemination. It can also be noted that the respondents from 11 – 20 years and 21 – 30 years ranked 6th and 5th respectively, only greater than the percentage of those who are 71 – 80 years. This indicates that the percentages of younger youths are small. This implies that there is need to make agriculture more interesting so as to keep these younger ones.

Marital Status

As shown in Table 1, a larger percentage (60.0%) of the respondents were married while 26.1% were single, 2.2% were divorced, and 11.7% widowed. This result implies that most of the respondents were married and as married people, they are not just responsible for the upkeep of themselves, but that of their family. This therefore, necessitates the use of every necessary means, especially drama to reach them with agricultural information which can help them increase productivity.

Level of Education

The result in Table 1 shows that majority (48.9%) of the farmers attained secondary education, while up to 25.6% of them attained tertiary education. This shows that up to 74% of the respondents attained either secondary or tertiary education. This implies that they will likely understand information disseminated using any medium of drama, it also implies that they will be disposed to accepting information, innovation or technology disseminated. This is in line with the work of Etim & Udoh (2020), which suggests that acquiring a secondary and tertiary education can make farmers faster and better adopters of agricultural technologies and innovations.

Annual Income

The result in Table 1 shows that majority (53.3%) of the respondents had annual income of between ₦1,000 - ₦200,000, and few of them had annual income of above ₦600,000. The mean annual income was ₦344,944. This is relatively low. This result implies that agriculture is not quite profitable in the area. There is therefore need to device means of achieving agricultural productivity, and drama is one way to ensure this, at least by making the information interesting and desirable.

Household Size

As shown in Table 1, the mean household size was 7. This implies that with adequate information on innovations and technologies, and with proper application of the knowledge, their standard of living will be high.

Farming Experience

The result in Table 1 shows that the mean farming experience in years was 22 years. This indicates that the respondents had a good farming experience. This implies that, having been in agriculture, the respondents will appreciate innovations when well-presented, and drama is a veritable tool for this.

Table 1: Socio-economic characteristics of farmers

Socio-economic Variable	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Sex			
Male	94	52.2	
Female	86	47.8	

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Age (years)			
11 – 20	19	10.6	
21 – 30	20	11.1	
31 – 40	38	21.1	
41 – 50	32	17.8	45 years
51 – 60	36	20.0	
61 – 70	21	11.7	
71 – 80	14	7.8	
Marital status			
Married	108	60.0	
Single	47	26.1	
Divorced	4	2.2	
Widowed	21	11.7	
Level of Education			
Primary	44	24.4	
Secondary	88	48.9	
Tertiary	46	25.6	
No formal education	2	1.1	
Annual income (₦)			
1,000 – 200,000	96	53.3	
201,000 – 400,000	17	9.4	
401,000 – 600,000	27	15.0	₦344,944
601,000 – 800,000	17	9.4	
801,000 – 1,000,000	17	9.5	
1,001,000 –	6	3.3	

1,200,000			
Household size			
1 – 5	67	37.2	
6 – 10	82	45.6	
11 – 15	20	11.1	7 persons
16 – 20	11	6.1	
Farming experience (years)			
1 – 10	41	22.8	
11 – 20	64	35.6	
21 – 30	28	15.6	22 years
31 – 40	24	13.3	
41 – 50	13	7.2	
51 – 60	10	5.6	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

N = 180

Sources of Agricultural Information

The result on Table 2 shows that the respondents received agricultural information from all the sources enumerated. The result also shows that fellow farmers ranked 1st among sources of agricultural information. It further shows that radio ranked 2nd. This implies that incorporating audio drama (radio drama) in the use of radio for agricultural information dissemination will be productive and excellent. This can be deduced from Perkins in Harvest Plus (2016) that radio drama can be an excellent way to share information with hundreds and thousands or even millions of small-scale farmers; the farmers can be entertained and learn alongside the character depicted in the story.

The result also shows that drama ranked 16th among the sources of agricultural information listed, which implies that the use of drama for agricultural information is not totally foreign in the study area, but it is not very well utilized either. This can be deduced from the difference in the response of ADP Staff in Orlu agricultural Zone during the In-depth interview that:

We use drama for agricultural information dissemination,

and the response of ADP Staff in Owerri agricultural zone, that:

We do not use drama for agricultural information dissemination

Table 2: Farmers’ Sources of Agricultural Information

Sources of agricultural information: Options	*Frequency	Percentage	Rank
Radio	155	86.1	2 nd
Television	138	76.7	4 th
Friends/Neighbours	154	85.6	3 rd
Fellow Farmers	170	94.4	1 st
Agricultural Cooperatives	93	51.7	11 th
Print Media example Newspapers, bulletins, leaflets	102	56.7	8 th
Internet example Google	95	52.8	10 th
NGO	88	48.9	12 th
Family Members	133	73.9	5 th
Private Sector	72	40.0	17 th
Telephone	80	44.4	15 th
Community Leaders	110	61.1	7 th
Extension Agents	98	54.4	9 th
Research Institutes	59	32.8	18 th
Video	105	58.3	6 th
Drama	75	41.7	16 th
Social Media Apps: WhatsApp, Twitter, Instagram, LinkedIn etc.	85	47.2	13 th

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

***Multiple responses recorded**

Farmers’ Perception of Drama as a Tool for Agricultural Information Dissemination

Farmers’ awareness of drama as a tool for agricultural information dissemination

The result on Table 3.1 shows that the majority (63.9%) of the respondents were not aware of drama as tool for agricultural information dissemination, and had not seen it, while 36.1% were aware of drama as a tool for agricultural information dissemination and had seen it. This implies

that drama is not a popular means of agricultural information dissemination in the study area. This supports the findings in Table 4.3, where drama ranked 16th as a source of agricultural information dissemination.

The respondents saw agricultural information being disseminated using drama on television, by agricultural organizations, in the church, and some by Shell Oil Company.

Table 3.1. Farmers’ Awareness of drama as a tool for agricultural Information Dissemination

Awareness status	Frequency	Percentage%
Aware	65	36.1
Not Aware	115	63.9
Total	180	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

Appropriateness of drama as a tool for agricultural information dissemination

Farmers’ perception of the appropriateness of drama as a tool for agricultural information dissemination is shown on Table 3.2. The respondents strongly agreed (3.6) that with the use of drama, they will be more productive in agriculture, as the information shared will not be easily forgotten. This implies that drama can encourage information retention. They strongly agreed (=3.6) that entertainment catches their attention, so the use of drama for agricultural information dissemination is welcome. Also, the respondents agreed (=3.4) that they usually do not have patience to listen to agricultural information, so the use of drama will make a difference. This implies that the respondents consider drama as interesting and a good tool for agricultural information dissemination. The respondents agreed (3.1) that picture story will make reading an agricultural content enjoyable. This implies that the respondents will be receptive of picture story for agricultural information dissemination. The respondents agreed (3.1) that they find storytelling engaging, and believe it will be nice if used in communicating agricultural information.

The table further shows that the grand mean was 3.1 and was accepted. This implies that on the whole, drama was perceived as a suitable tool for agricultural information dissemination. This is in consonance with CABI (2020) that art, music, dance, drama, humour, storytelling and other forms of entertainment can serve as effective tools for helping to share information on agricultural best practices with small holder farmers.

Table 3.2: Appropriateness of drama as a tool for agricultural Information Dissemination

Appropriateness Options	4 SA	3 A	2 D	1 SD	2.5 Mean	Remark
Drama is not a new thing to us in the community so applying it to agriculture would be a good idea	116	72	6	2	3.9	Accept
There has been times drama has been used to communicate to us in other aspects of life	115	38	19	8	3.4	Accept
We do not see anything wrong with the use of drama as a community	128	35	10	7	3.6	Accept
I will prefer to be given information plainly, I do not care about the use of drama.	64	29	40	47	2.6	Accept
I see drama as a waste of time, why go through all that stress	56	19	52	53	2.4	Reject
Using drama to disseminate agricultural information will seem like child's play.	92	46	19	21	3.1	Accept
Entertainment catches my attention, so the use of drama for agricultural information dissemination is welcome.	129	36	8	7	3.6	Accept
Information sticks more when it is performed, so using drama for information dissemination will be appreciated.	106	49	17	8	3.5	Accept
I think we should maintain other means of agricultural information dissemination that has been in use.	50	37	39	54	2.5	Accept
We have been getting adequate agricultural information so I do not see any need for using drama	31	28	49	72	2.1	Reject
I think the best way to communicate to us as a community will be through drama	66	78	25	11	3.1	Accept
Drama allows for experimental learning as farmers can relate more with what is being communicated	116	42	14	8	3.5	Accept
The use of drama is not the solution to the challenges to agriculture in our community	79	64	35	2	3.2	Accept
I have a not forgotten most things I saw through drama so I believe using drama to disseminate agricultural information will help me remember it more.	84	46	30	20	3,07	Accept

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Appropriateness Options	4 SA	3 A	2 D	1 SD	2.5 Mean	Remark
There are much to gain from the use of drama for agricultural information dissemination, so I like the idea.	93	63	14	10	3.3	Accept
I love it when drama is used to pass across information, especially when I am participating in it	96	75	7	2	3.5	Accept
The activities involved in the use of drama example participating in video productions will be detrimental to us, especially our young ones	40	40	55	45	2.4	Reject
The use of drama will give us exposure and better our lives	111	55	10	4	3.5	Accept
I am busy and will not have time for receiving agricultural information using drama, I will prefer to be communicated plainly	45	23	78	34	2.4	Reject
I believe using drama to communicate agricultural information will help me understand it more	120	32	21	7	3.5	Accept
I usually do not have patience to listen to agricultural information, I believe the use of drama will make a difference	110	49	10	1	3.4	Accept
I do care what is used in disseminating agricultural information	46	30	68	36	2.5	Accept
Drama is engaging. I believe applying it in agriculture will help me adopt more technologies	108	51	11	10	3.4	Accept
I understand things more when it is communicated through drama	97	69	14	0	3.5	Accept
I see drama as a good tool for agricultural information dissemination	86	59	30	5	3.3	Accept
Drama sounds childish and should not be used in a serious thing such as agriculture	51	22	69	38	2.4	Reject
Appropriateness Options	4 SA	3 A	2 D	1 SD	2.5 Mean	Remark
Drama does not engage me	17	23	67	73	1.9	Reject

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Participating in drama during trainings will be entertaining.	62	76	33	9	3.1	Accept
I do not see any relationship between agriculture and drama	72	18	44	46	2.6	Accept
Participating in drama during agricultural trainings will be embarrassing.	49	35	50	46	2.4	Reject
I believe that participating together in drama will improve the relationship of farmers	77	62	35	6	3.2	Accept
The use of drama will not only positively affect our agricultural activities but our lives generally because it engages the mind	98	59	20	3	3.4	Accept
Using drama for agricultural information dissemination will engage farmers and stimulate self-activity and direction	129	51	0	0	3.7	Accept
I believe that drama arouses and sustains interest and curiosity throughout the process	114	52	10	4	3.5	Accept
I believe that drama encourages creativity	105	65	10	0	3.5	Accept
Picture story will make reading an agricultural content enjoyable	71	61	35	3	3.1	Accept
I find storytelling engaging. I believe it will be nice if used in communicating agricultural information.	73	67	25	15	3.1	Accept
Communicating agricultural information with videos will be impactful since it is a combination of audio and video	116	54	8	2	3.6	Accept
Total	3406	1914	1153	731	3.11	Accept

N = 180. Discriminatory index = 2.5, SA – Strongly Agreed, A – Agreed, D – Disagreed, SD – Strongly Disagreed

Farmers’ preferred medium of drama

Preferred medium of drama

The result on Table 4.6 indicates that the respondents will appreciate receiving agricultural information from all the listed mediums of drama (audio drama, video clips, storytelling, picture

story, and stage drama). However, majority (90.0%) preferred picture story, this is followed by storytelling (89.4%)

Table 4.1: Farmers’ preferred medium of drama

Preferred medium/form of drama	*Frequency	Percentage %
Audio (from radio, podcast etc.)	138	76.7
Video Clips (from CDs, Memory cards, TV channels etc.)	130	72.2
Storytelling	161	89.4
Picture Story	162	90.0
Stage Drama	160	88.9

Source: Field Survey, 2023.

***Multiple responses recorded**

Preferred people to participate in drama

The result in Table 4 shows that the respondents would appreciate receiving agricultural information through drama from all the listed options (extension agents, farmers’ residents in that community, a combination of both, farmers from other communities, research institutes, students, and professional actors). However, the majority (86.7%) indicated interest in receiving agricultural information through drama from students.

Table 4.2: Preferred people to participate in drama

Preferred people to participate in drama	*Frequency	Percentage %
Extension Agents	131	72.8
Farmers i.e. the resident farmers in the community	152	84.4
A Combination of the Both	145	80.5
Farmers from other communities, towns, nations, but with similar agricultural environment or content	154	85.5
Research institutes	137	76.1
Students (Secondary school or University)	156	86.7
Professional actors	150	83.3

Source: Field Survey, 2023

***Multiple responses recorded**

Conclusion

The study shows that the farmers consider drama as a suitable and appropriate tool for agricultural information dissemination. Also, the farmers will want to receive agricultural information through all the media used in this study. Furthermore, farmers will appreciate agricultural students participating in the drama production, and that farmers will be willing to participate as well. It is therefore recommended to promote greater awareness, education, and advocacy for using drama as an effective means of communicating agricultural information.

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A Review on Adoption of Human Urine as Organic Liquid Fertilizer for Crop Production in Smallholder Farmers to Curb Food Insecurity in Nigeria

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Abstract

Human urine has been recognized as valuable resources for agriculture, a sustainable solution compared to the use of chemical fertilizer to enhance soil fertility for crop production particularly for small holder farmers. Rich in nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium, human urine is an underutilized resource that can serve as an effective organic fertilizer especially for crop production. Undiluted or diluting urine with water at a ratio of 1:3 to 1:10 and allowing the mixture to sit in a tank or can with lid for 1-6 months will significantly help in eliminating odor and creates a nutrient-rich, fertilizer that addresses soil fertility issues sustainably. This paper reviews the adoption of human urine as organic liquid fertilizer for crop production in small holder farmers to curb food security. Recent studies revealed that these approaches not only recycles waste materials but also offer several benefits, including cost-effectiveness, convenience/feasible, increase in crop yield and safe/nutritive food. However, it presents challenges such as unpleasant odor and cultural perception regarding its use. Proper handling, storage and application method are crucial to maximizing its benefits while minimizing the risks. Adoption of this fertilizer can contribute to more sustainable agricultural practices for food security. Awareness and training programs to educate farmers on application are essential for safety usage of this fertilizer. In conclusion, this innovation presents a promising opportunity for small holder farmers to enhance soil fertility and crop yield in a sustainable and cost effective manner for sustainable food system.

Keywords: Adoption, human urine, liquid fertilizer, sustainable, innovation.

Introduction

Food insecurity is a pressing global issue particularly in the face of surging population, climate instability and urbanization. A growing global population, compounded by low incomes, has led to an increasing demand for food production (Elferink and Schierhorn 2016). In the Sub-Saharan Africa region, agriculture is dominated by small holder farmers that continuously struggle to maintain the productivity of their land (Anderson, 2015). With decreasing availability of arable land, the challenge will be to increase production on existing agricultural lands, in part by adoption of new and innovative methods that improve soil fertility and water management

(Elferink and Schierhorn 2016; FAO 2014). Nearly 90% of the 525 million farms worldwide are small scale (defined as < 2 hectares) (IAASTD 2009) and often run by families. These family farms produce more than half of the world's total food (Graeub et al., 2016). Leveraging food production in small holder farmers through improved production practices is therefore increasingly seen as a solution to global food insecurity and rural poverty (Graeub et al. 2016) These farmers make up to 80% of farmers in Nigeria and produce a substantial percentage of the food consumed by Nigerians (Mgbenka&Mbah 2016). Low yield is the most critical factor affecting profitability and competitiveness of smallholder farmers. The traditional use of inorganic fertilizers to enrich their farms though expensive, have adverse environmental, soil and human health implications.

Who are the smallholder farmers? They are producers who cultivate, rear livestock or raise fish on a limited scale, typically on family-owned enterprise operating on less than 10 hectares of land. Smallholder farmers in most of sub-Saharan Africa still produce in agricultural system that is characterized by low input and low outputs (Mgbenka&Mbah 2016). Plant nutrition is a key factor, which determines plant growth and development, therefore, fertilizer application has become a common practice in agriculture. The macronutrients such as nitrogen, phosphorous and potassium are the frequently required for plant nutrition in large proportions than micronutrients (Ranasinghe et al., 2018). Though each macronutrient is important for all plants, nitrogen requirement is greater than the total use of other macronutrients and micronutrients together. However, plant nutrients are depleting in the soil at an alarming rate due to unplanned continuous farming practices. Therefore, most of the farmers have adapted to apply chemical fertilizers in order to increase the available nutrients and hence the land productivity.

While inorganic or chemical fertilizer is applied to the soil to boost its fertility, research has shown that it is damaging many properties of the soil that, in the long-term, will reduce its fertility and make it more challenging to grow healthy, high (Moore, 2022). Also, when fertilizers are applied to land, there are several potential routes to human exposure. A key pathway is via food products, as crops can accumulate harmful contaminants. Certain contaminants and secondary fertilizer compounds have adverse effects on human health, including neurotoxicity, infectious diseases, carcinogenicity and endocrine-disrupting effects (EEA, 2025). For instance the overuse and misuse of chemical fertilizers attributed to critical environmental and health problems such as Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) in Sri Lanka.

Human urine is a valuable, yet underestimated and under-utilized, resource for plant fertilization that has been used in agriculture since ancient times, not least in intensive farming systems in various parts of Asia (Goldstein, 2012). Nevertheless, in much of sub-Saharan Africa such as Ethiopia, Uganda, Nigeria etc. its use in agricultural production is not a common practice (Winblad and Simpson-Hérbert, 2004).

What is in human urine? When we eat food, our kidneys filter out excess nutrients that our body is unable to use, and these nutrients are then expelled from the body as urine. Our urine contains significant levels of 3-7g nitrogen as well as 1-3g of phosphorous and 2-4g potassium per liter. It shows that an adult's urine contains enough nutrients to fertilize 50-100% of the crops needed to feed one adult. Urine is the major product of ecological sanitation toilets such as urine diversion dry toilets (UDDTs) and its utilization as an agricultural input is a current challenge in developing countries. Urine contains plant nutrients that may supplement or replace commercial

fertilizers for crop production (Jönsson et al. 2004). In many regions, especially African and Asian countries, pilot studies have demonstrated its effectiveness in improving crop yields, reducing fertilizer costs and promoting circular nutrient economy practice. Despite these benefits, the adoption of urine fertilizer remains limited due to cultural, health, logistical and regulatory challenges. This paper aims to review on the use of human urine as organic liquid fertilizer in crop production in smallholder farmers to curb food insecurity with specific objectives on (i) the assessment of its effectiveness as a liquid fertilizer, ii) to identify barriers to adoption (iii) evaluate its potential contribution to food security in low-income and resource limited setting. (iv) Research gap and further studies (v) Summary and conclusion

Methodology

This review adopts a narrative approach, combining peer-reviewed literature, institutional reports and case studies on the use of human urine as fertilizer. Literature were sourced primarily from data based studies including Google Scholar, Scopus, ScienceDirect, and PubMed using keywords such as 'human urine, smallholder farmers, liquid fertilizer, innovation, and food security.

Studies published between 2000 and 2024 were prioritized focusing on those with empirical evidence from Africa and Asia. Grey literature such as publications by the Stockholm Environment Institute, World Health Organization (WHO) and EcoSanRes were also reviewed for their relevance to practical applications, health guidance and policy. Publications were also selected based on relevance scientific rigor and its application to smallholder agriculture and food security contexts.

Literature Review

The assessment of human urine effectiveness as a liquid fertilizer

a. Nutrient composition and agronomic value of human urine: Ranasingheet al.,(2016) revealed that most of the nutrients present in the urine are readily available for the plants. Urine is considered to be a well-balanced nitrogen rich fertilizer and 75 – 90 % of the nitrogen present in the urine is in the available forms (either urea or ammonium), which becomes ammonium ions in an aqueous solution at neutral pH. phosphorous and potassium present in the urine are in an inorganic form and are directly plant-available. An average of human urine contains approximately 9-15g/liter of nitrogen, 1-2g/liter and 2-5g/liter of potassium depending on diet, hydration and individual metabolism (Heinonen-Tanski&wijk-Sijbesma2005). Additionally, urine contains micronutrients like sulphur, magnesium and calcium in smaller but beneficial quantities (Prodhan et. al, 2007)

Compared to traditional compost, urine offers a more concentrated and fast acting nutrient source. Research in sub-Saharan Africa has shown that applying stored urine to maize, sorghum and vegetable crops significantly improves yields often comparable to result from chemical fertilizers (Adeoluwa&cofie 2014). However, researchers did discover that urine fertilization increased the relative amounts of nitrifying and denitrifying groups compared to synthetic fertilizer - implying that more nitrogen oxides could be emitted when fertilizing with urine

Fresh urine is composed of 95 % water with the remaining 5% made up of amino compounds, such as urea or creatinine, organic anions and inorganic salts making it a source of bioavailable nutrients and micronutrients for plant growth. After 12 months of storage, urine had a depleted microbiome but contained few common strains of urine. Thud storing urine for several months, with the resulting increase in its pH value (about 9 rather than 6.5 for fresh urine) and its free

ammonia concentration is considered sufficient to inactivate most human pathogenic bacteria and break down extracellular DNA. Soil bacterial communities were resistant to urine fertilization with only 3% of groups of organisms impacted. The urine's high salt concentration had little discernible effect on the bacterial community (Adeoluwa & Cofie 2014).

However, nutrient variability across individuals and populations requires some standardization or blending before large scale application. Despite this urine's high nutrient density makes it a practical and accessible input for farmers

b. Effects of urine fertilizer on crop yield and soil health

Several field and green house studies have shown that human urine significantly boost crop yield often matching or exceeding those obtain in conventional synthetic fertilizer across various agro-ecological zones. Its high nitrogen content enhances vegetative growth while phosphorus and potassium contribute to root development and fruiting. In a comparative trial, Pradhan et. al (2007) reported that cabbage fertilized with stored urine performed equally well as artificial fertilizer with no negative effect on taste or appearance.

Research in Zimbabwe, Guzha et al (2005) observed that urine application increased maize yield by 30-50% compared to non-fertilized control plots. Similarly, in Ghana and Nigeria, urine applications in vegetable farming (e.g. amaranth, tomatoes and cabbage) produced yields compared to urea treated plots while reducing input cost (Adeoluwa & Cafie, 2012).

However excessive or continuous application without dilution can lead to ammonia toxicity, increase in salinity or nitrate leaching (Richert et al 2010). To avoid this, urine is often diluted at a 1:3 to 1:10 ratio with water before use.

c. Urine handling, storage and application technique

The safe and effective use of human urine in agriculture depends heavily on proper collection, storage treatment and application. Fresh urine is generally sterile but once excreted, it can be contaminated if not properly handled. The safe storage and application practices are crucial to minimize health risks and nutrient loss.

i. Collection and storage:

Urine is typically collected using urine-diverting toilets, jerry cans or tanks fitted with closed lids to minimize odor and contamination. To improve safety, the World Health Organization (WHO) recommends storing of urine at least 1-6 months depending on ambient temperature to inactivate pathogens (WHO, 2006). Storage also leads to urine hydrolysis, converting urea to ammonia thereby increasing its fertilizing effect (Jonsson et al., 2004)

ii. Dilution and Application

Urine can be applied:

Neat (undiluted) for high demand crops especially during active growth stages. According to Hoglund et al., (2002) urine is considered sterile and can be used as a liquid plant fertilizer directly without further treatment. To overcome this problem, a urine diversion (UD) or no mix toilet have been designed by Larsen et al., (2001) to separate human urine at source. UD technology have used successfully in many developing and developed countries such as Ethiopia, China, Ecuador, El Salvador, Guatemala, India, Mexico, South Africa, Thailand, Vietnam, Zimbabwe, Finland Sweden and Germany

Diluted (1:3 to 1:10 with water) to reduce risk of plant burn and odor especially in seedlings or light feeders (Richert et al. 2010). Application is usually done by furrows placement or around the root zone avoiding contact with leaves. This method improves nutrient uptake and reduces ammonia volatilization.

iii. Integration with Organic materials

To enhance nutrient retention and reduce leaching or odor, urine is sometimes combined with biochar, ash, compost or even sawdust (Pradhan et al.2010). These mixtures can also serve as slow-release fertilizer and improve soil structure.

iv. Safety Measures

Farmers are advised to wear gloves and wash hands after handling stored urine. Crops that is consumed raw like lettuce, should not be fertilized with fresh urine unless there's a waiting period of 1-2months before harvest (WHO, 2006)

Barriers to Adoption

a. Perceptions, acceptance and cultural barriers

Despite its agronomical significance and benefits, the adoption of human urine as fertilizer is strongly influenced by cultural beliefs, social norms and perception of hygiene. In many societies, urine is considered a taboo or 'waste' making its acceptance in agriculture a major challenge (Muriwah&Amoah, 2010)

Studies from sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia reveals mixed reaction; while some farmers are open to using urine due to its low cost and visible yield benefits. Other rejects it due to concerns of smell, disease transmission or religious beliefs (Dogerskag&Bonzi, 2010; Mehta et al., 2013) for example in Ghana, women farmers were more reluctant to handle urine due to social stigma even when they were aware of its benefits (Mariwah&Drangert 2011)

Education and demonstration trials have been shown to increase acceptance especially when farmers can observe improved crop performance and economic savings. Where community-led sanitation or ecosan projects have promoted urine reuse through training, perceptions tend to improve overtime (Kvarnstraim et al. 2011)

Religious views also play a role. In some Muslim communities, the use of urine in agriculture is seen as impure, however, scholars have debated whether stored, sanitized urine may be accepted for non-edible crops. Therefore, context-specific awareness campaigns and local leader involvement are crucial to addressing resistance.

b. Health, Sanitation and Regulatory Considerations

The safe use of human urine in agriculture must align with public, health and sanitation standards to minimize potential risks. Although fresh urine is typically sterile in healthy individuals, contamination can occur during collection, storage, or handling especially in settings with poor hygiene practices (WHO, 2006). To ensure safety, the World Health Organization recommends storing urine for 1-6 months depending on temperature, before use on food crops. This period allows for the inactivation of pathogens particularly in urine that may be mixed with small amount of faeces or collected in non-sanitary conditions (Schonning & Stenstram, 2004).

c. Environmental and Economic Implications

Using human urine as fertilizer offers significant environmental and economic advantages especially in the context of sustainable agriculture and climate smart practices.

i. Environmental Benefits

Urine diversion and its uses reduce the nutrient load in the waste water, helping to prevent eutrophication of water bodies caused by nitrogen and phosphorus run-off (Winker et al., 2009). By recycling nutrients, locally urine-based fertilization, contributes to close-loop nutrient cycles, thereby reducing the demand for synthetic fertilizer which are energy and cost-intensive to produce and often contribute to greenhouse gas emissions (Mourer et.al., 2006)

Urine application particularly when paired with carbon-rich materials like biochar or compost can improve soil fertility, reduce nutrient leaching and enhance soil organic matter retention, hence, contributing to long-term land productivity (Nartey & Zhoa, 2014).

ii. Economic Advantages

From an economic perspective, human urine is free and locally available, making it especially attractive to resource –poor small-holder farmers. Studies in sub-Saharan Africa have shown that farmers who replace synthetic fertilizers with stored urine can reduce cost by 50-80% while maintaining or improving yields (Adeoluwa&Cofie 2012).

Additionally, adopting urine system of fertilization can reduce household and municipal sanitation costs by lowering the volume of wastewater needing treatment. In Urban area setting, integrating urine into the eco-sanitation models could create economic opportunities through decentralized fertilizer production and sales. However, scaling up remains limited by the lack of formal market structures investment in collection infrastructure and public awareness. Government incentives and demonstration projects may help unlock these benefits at scale.

Potential Role in Food Security and Sustainable Agriculture

The adoption of human urine as a liquid fertilizer aligns strongly with the principle of sustainable agriculture and offer viable pathway to improve food security especially in low-income and resource constrained setting.

a. Improving food accessibility and Affordability: Human urine provides a cost-free source of essential nutrient making it highly accessible for smallholder and subsistence farmers who struggles to afford commercial fertilizer. In countries like Ghana and Burkina Faso, urine application has led to increase yields in maize, vegetables, and legumes, thus enhancing household food availability (Dogerskag&Bonzi, 2010;Guzha et.al., 2005).

By reducing dependency on costly external inputs, urine-based fertilization can stabilize food production during economic shocks, supply chain disruption , or inflation, all of which threaten food security.

b. Enhancing sustainability and resilience: The use of urine supports circular agriculture – integrating human derived nutrients into the food system. This practice conserves resources, minimizes environmental pollution and support climate-smart agriculture by reducing fossil-fuel-based fertilizer use and enhancing soil health (Jonsson et al., 2004; WHO, 2006).

In areas facing land degradation, drought, or nutrient depletion, urine can serve as a quick response solution for soil recovery when combined with organic matter thereby promoting agroecological resilience.

c. Community and Institutional Integration: Programs that integrate the use of urine in school gardens, urban farming or community-led sanitation can offer both food and education. By involving farmers, local leaders and extension agents in participatory models, awareness and acceptance of the practice can increase leading to broader uptake (Kvarnström et al. 2011). Ultimately scaling urine fertilizer use, when supported by policy, education and health safeguards can contribute to local and national food security targets in line with SDG 2 (Zero Hunger) and SDG 6 (Clean water and Sanitation).

Summary and Conclusion

4.1: Summary of Key Studies on Human Urine Used in Crop Production

Authors	Crop studied	Method of Application	Location	Key Findings
Guzhaet al.(2005)	Maize	Direct application to root zone	Zimbabwe	30-50% yield increase over control. Similar to chemical fertilizer
Adeoluwa&Cofie (2012)	Amaranthuscaudatus	Urine + Water (1:3)	Ghana	Comparable yield to urea fertilizer
Prodhan et al. (2010)	Potato	Urine + Compost	Finland	Increased tuber weight and nutrient content
Mariwah&Drange rt (2011)	Mixed vegetables	Stored Urine	Ghana	Increased yield
Richert et. al., (2010)	Various crops	Stored and diluted	Multi country	„
Nartey&Zhoa (2014)	Soil studies	Urine + biochar	China	Enhanced soil Properties

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Pandarf et al., (2019)	Beans	Urine only	USA	Matched synthetic fertilizer yield
Heinonen-Tonski&Pradhan, (2010)	Beets	Urine combined with wood ash	Finland	Increased yield more than that of artificial fertilizer
ESAFF Uganda, (2024)	Maize, banana, leafy greens	Fermented urine	Uganda	Crop vigor and yield. Reduced harvest time and cost effective farming practice
Heinonen-Tanski et al.,(2007)	Cabbage	Human Urine only at 180kgN/ha	Finland	Increased yield, no significant hygienic threats or flavor.
Akpan-idiok et al., (2012)	Okra(<i>Abelmaschusesculentus</i>)	Human urine at the rate of 10,000. 15000 and 20,000L/ha	Cross River State	Increased in growth and yield compared to artificial fertilizer
Ekwere (2012)	Okra (<i>Abelmaschusesculentus</i>)	Cured human urine	Abak irrigation project. Akwalbom State	Significant in yield compared to inorganic fertilizer
Alamu et al., (2023)	Amaranth (<i>Amaranthushybridus</i>)	Diluted human urine	Nigeria	Enhances soil microbial density and

				amaranth yield outperforming artificial fertilizer
Sheneni et al., (2015)	Maize (Zea mays)	Male and female urine	Kogi	Influences maize growth and phytochemical content
AdeOluwa et al., 2016	Tomatoes (Solanumlycopersicum)	Human urine–compost mixture 2:1	University of Ibadan, Oyo State	Improved soil fertility, tomato yield and shelf life
Johansson et al. (2001); Richert et al., (2001); Lundstraim& Linden (2001)	Barley and Wheat	Human urine only. 40:80:120kgN/ha during growing season	Sweden	Increased yield. Urine nitrogen as effective as ammonium nitrate
Gensch& Miso (2008)	Maize	Human urine only. 60kgN/ha	Burkina faso	Increased yield
Sridevi, (2011)	Banana	Diluted human urine + water 1:5	India	Crops showed better yields, nutrient content and cost benefit ratio

Source: Field Study (2000-2024)

Conclusion

The use of human urine as liquid fertilizer presents a practical, low-cost, and environmentally sustainable strategy to enhance crop production and address food insecurity, particularly in low-income and agriculturally vulnerable regions. Its high nutrient content especially nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium make it a viable alternative to synthetic fertilizers, which are often unaffordable or inaccessible to smallholder farmers.

Evidence from various regions, demonstrate that urine can improve crop yields, reduce input costs and contributes to circular nutrient flows especially when paired with complementary organic materials like biochar, ash or compost. Additionally, the use of urine aligns with global for sustainable development, climate resilience and resource recovery.

However, adoption remains limited by cultural resistance, lack of policy-support, safety concerns and gaps in long term agronomic data. Overcoming these challenges requires a multi-sectoral approach involving farmers, researchers and policy makers. Community education, gender sensitive engagement, supportive regulation and innovation in collection and treatment systems are all critical to scale-up the use of urine safely and effectively.

In conclusion, integrating urine-based fertilization into sustainable agriculture offers a promising solution to improve soil fertility, strengthen food systems and close the nutrient loop. With targeted research, investment and public engagement, human urine can be repositioned from waste to resource supporting food security and environmental sustainability in the 21st century

Research Gaps and Further Studies

Despite growing knowledge of the use of urine for crop fertilization, several knowledge gaps and implementation barriers remain that limit its widespread adoption and impact on food system

a. Limited long-term field data: Most studies on the use of urine as fertilizer are short-term or conducted in controlled conditions. There is a lack of longitudinal field studies assessing the long term effects on soil fertility, microbial dynamics, salt accumulation and crop rotation impacts (Pradhan et al.2010)

Research is needed to explore sustainability over multiple impacts, growing seasons and under different agro ecological zones.

b. Standardization and dosage: Variability in urine nutrient content makes it difficult to define standard application rates. Further research is needed on blending, dilution practices and dose-response relationships across crop types to optimize use and reduce risks of over fertilization or nutrient run-off (Richert et al. (2010).

c. Pathogen risk and Sanitation links: More data are needed on the pathogen survival rate in diverse climates and sanitation behaviors among farmers.

d. Policy and economic research: Clear regulatory guidelines and economic feasibility models for large-scale collection, treatment and distribution are largely underdeveloped especially in underdeveloped countries (Larten et al., 2013)

e. Innovation opportunities

Emerging technologies like biochar-urine blends, decentralized urine-treatment blends, decentralized-urine units and mobile urine collection systems present promising innovation. Future research should assess their scalability, affordability and impact on circular farming systems (Nartey& Zhao, 2014)

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Effects of Climate-Smart Agricultural Practices on Rice Farmers' Resilience to Yield Loss in Kwara State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

Building resilience to yield loss is critical for sustaining rice production in the face of climate shocks in Nigeria. This study examined the effect of Climate-Smart Agriculture (CSA) adoption on rice farmers' resilience to yield loss in Kwara State, Nigeria. Primary data were collected from 450 rice farmers using a multistage sampling technique. The analysis combined descriptive statistics, logistic regression, ordinary least squares (OLS), quantile regression, and Propensity Score Matching (PSM) to estimate the determinants and effects of CSA adoption on resilience outcomes. Results from the logistic regression showed that credit access ($p < 0.01$), group membership ($p < 0.05$), and education ($p < 0.1$) significantly increased the likelihood of CSA adoption. The OLS results revealed that CSA adoption had a positive and significant effect on farmers' resilience index ($p < 0.01$). Quantile regression further indicated that group membership and adoption intensity consistently improved resilience across all quantiles, with stronger effects at the 75th quantile, suggesting that social participation enhances resilience among more adaptive farmers. The PSM estimates confirmed a positive and significant causal effect of CSA adoption on resilience, validating that adopters were better able to cope with yield shocks and maintain stable incomes. Overall, the findings highlight the transformative role of CSA practices and social capital in improving the adaptive capacity of smallholder rice farmers. Policy interventions should therefore promote farmers' access to credit, strengthen cooperative networks, and scale up CSA training to enhance resilience and ensure food system sustainability in Nigeria.

Keywords: Climate-Smart Agriculture, Resilience, Yield Loss, Rice Farmers, Propensity Score Matching, Quantile Regression

Background of the Study

Rice has gained increasing prominence as a vital component of National diets with its rapidly rising consumption as a result of the population growthurbanization and growing diet preference(Oluwaseun et.al. 2024, Bello et. al 2024). Despite its growing demand, domestic rice production still faces serious challenges associated with climate variability, declining soil

fertility, pest infestations, and erratic rainfall patterns which often result in substantial yield losses, threatened household welfare and food availability (Hussein et.al 2020). Kwara State however is not left out of these menace, their rice farming is predominantly rain fed, and largely practices by smallholder farmers who are highly exposed to climatic and environmental shocks (Akanbi et.al 2022).

Consequently, the effects of climate change have become more pronounced across Nigeria in the past decades, with increased occurrences of drought, flooding, unpredictable rainfall, and temperature extremes (Shiru et.al.2020).Mbuliet. al. (2021) submitted that these climatic disruptions have led to greater yield instability, reduced farm profitability, and heightened production risks for smallholder farmers. Adisa et.al. (2024) observed that rice farmers in Kwara State, who depend largely on natural rainfall and limited irrigation infrastructure, such conditions translate into frequent yield losses and economic vulnerability. According to Bowen et. al. (2020), building resilience to yield loss has become a major policy and research priority to safeguard livelihoods and ensure sustainable agricultural productivity in the face of climatic uncertainty.

To address these challenges, Climate-Smart Agricultural (CSA) practices have been promoted as an integrated approach aimed at achieving three interrelated goals: increasing productivity, enhancing resilience (adaptation), and reducing greenhouse gas emissions (mitigation) (Abhilash et.al. 2021, Zheng et.al. 2024). Practices such as improved seed varieties, conservation tillage, mulching, agroforestry, intercropping, fertilizer management, and irrigation efficiency help improve soil structure, enhance water retention, and stabilize crop yields under changing climatic conditions (Kabato et.al 2025). Empirical studies have shown that farmers who adopt these practices tend to recover faster from shocks and sustain higher productivity levels compared to non-adopters (Zheng et. al. 2024, Hussein et.al. 2021). Nevertheless, the extent to which CSA practices enhance farmers' resilience to yield loss remains underexplored, especially in the Nigerian context where adoption rates are uneven and influenced by socio-economic, institutional, and environmental factors.

Investigating the effect of CSA adoption on rice farmers' resilience to yield loss using Kwara State is particularly relevant due to its diverse agro-ecological conditions, increasing engagement in rice cultivation, and rising exposure to climate-induced risks such as irregular rainfall and flooding. Understanding how CSA adoption influence the resilience of rice farmers to yield loss in Kwara state is crucial for evidence-based policymaking and the increase climate-resilient agricultural innovations. Moreover, identifying the socio-economic and institutional factors that shape adoption decisions can guide the design of effective extension services, access to credit, and capacity-building programs tailored to farmers' specific needs.

Based on the aforementioned this study aims to investigate the effect of Climate-Smart Agricultural Practices on rice farmers' resilience to yield loss in Kwara State. Specifically, it seeks to assess the socio-economic determinants of CSA adoption, evaluate its impact on resilience outcomes, and provide empirical evidence using econometric techniques to estimate the causal relationship between adoption and resilience. The findings are expected to inform climate policy, agricultural development strategies, and rural livelihood programs that aim to promote sustainable and adaptive rice production systems in Nigeria and across similar agro-ecological zones

Empirical Review

Several studies have previously investigated the link between CSA adoption and farmers' adaptive capacity or resilience outcomes. Nkonya et al. (2024) examined the effects of CSA technologies on productivity and household welfare in Sub-Saharan Africa and found that farmers adopting multiple CSA components experienced higher yields and lower yield variability. Similarly, Nkhoma et al. (2017) analyzed conservation agriculture adoption in Zambia and reported that households adopting at least two CSA practices exhibited greater yield stability during drought years. Adeleye and Atere (2022) explored farmers' perception and adoption of CSA technologies in the South-West region and revealed that access to extension services and credit significantly influenced adoption decisions. Teklu et al. (2023) also noted that CSA practices enhanced farmers' resilience by improving soil moisture retention and reducing yield losses associated with erratic rainfall.

Furthermore, Adisa et al. (2024) assessed climate change adaptation strategies among rice farmers in North-Central Nigeria and found that households adopting improved seeds, irrigation, and conservation tillage achieved higher resilience indices than non-adopters. Their study also emphasized the importance of social capital through group membership and information sharing in fostering adoption and resilience outcomes.

Despite these contributions, few studies have explicitly linked CSAP adoption to quantitative measures of yield-loss resilience using causal frameworks such as PSM and quantile regression. Moreover, evidence focusing on rice farmers in Kwara State remains limited, despite the area's vulnerability to rainfall variability and its significance as a rice-producing region in Nigeria's Middle Belt. This study therefore fills this gap by combining micro-econometric analysis with resilience measurement to provide policy-relevant insights into how CSAP adoption enhances yield stability and livelihood sustainability.

Model Specification

This study employs a combination of econometric techniques to examine the effects of Climate-Smart Agricultural (CSA) practices on household resilience, productivity, and income. The analytical framework comprises Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), Propensity Score Matching (PSM), and Quantile Regression (QR) models, complemented by index construction and diagnostic tests.

Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) Model

The Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) model was used to estimate the average impact of CSA adoption on key household outcomes, namely resilience, crop yield, and income. The baseline specification is given as:

Y_i represents the outcome variable for household i (resilience index, yield, or income),

CSA_i Represents the outcome variable for household i (resilience index, yield, or income),

X_i is a vector of household, farm, and institutional characteristics (such as age, education, farm size, access to credit, and extension contact),

$\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2$ are parameters to be estimated, and

μ_1 is the error term

The coefficient β_1 captures the mean effect of CSA adoption on household outcomes.

Propensity Score Matching (PSM) Model

The potential selection bias arising from the non-random adoption of CSA practices was addressed using Propensity Score Matching (PSM). The propensity score, which is defined as the probability of adopting CSA conditional on observed characteristics, was estimated using a binary logit model:

$$P(CSA_i = 1 | X_i) = \frac{e^{X_i^T \alpha}}{1 + e^{X_i^T \alpha}}$$

Where

$P(CSA_i = 1 | X_i)$ is the probability that household i adopts CSA practices given covariates X_i and α is a vector of parameters to be estimated.

Rice farming households that adopted CSA were then matched with non-adopters with similar propensity scores using matching algorithms such as Nearest Neighbor and Kernel Matching. The Average Treatment Effect on the Treated (ATT) was estimated as:

$$ATT = E(Y_1 - Y_0 | CSA = 1)$$

Where

where $Y_1 - Y_0$ denote outcomes for CSA adopters and their matched non-adopters, respectively.

Quantile Regression (QR) Model

This study adopted Quantile Regression to examine the heterogeneous effects of CSA adoption across different points of the outcome distribution. This approach allows the impact of CSA practices to vary across rice farming households with different levels of resilience, yield, or income. The model is specified as:

$$Q_{Y_i}(\tau | X_i) = \beta_0(\tau) + \beta_1(\tau)CSA_i + \beta_2(\tau)X_i$$

where:

$Q_{Y_i}(\tau | X_i)$ denotes the conditional τ -th quantile i.e 0.25, 0.50, 0.75 of the outcome variable,

τ represents the quantile level ($0 < \tau < 1$), and

$\beta_1(\tau)$ Measures the effect of CSA adoption at quantile τ

This method helps to know whether CSA adoption has stronger effects among more vulnerable or more resilient households.

Composite Index Construction

Normalized indicators was used to construct household resilience and social trust indices to ensure comparability across dimensions. Each indicator x_i was transformed onto a 0–1 scale using the min–max normalization technique:

$$Z_i = \frac{x_i - x_{min}}{x_{max} - x_{min}}$$

The composite index for each dimension was computed as the weighted or unweighted average of the normalized indicators.

Diagnostic and Comparative tests

In other to compare differences between CSA adopters and non-adopters, independent samples t -tests and Mann–Whitney U tests were conducted for key outcome variables. Model diagnostics were performed to ensure robustness and validity of the estimates. These included Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) tests for multicollinearity, goodness-of-fit measures (such as pseudo- R^2), significance tests, and normality checks of residuals where applicable.

Data Analysis and Analytical Techniques

Both descriptive and inferential statistical methods were employed for the data analysis in other to ensure robustness and policy relevance of the results. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the socio-economic, demographic, and farm-level characteristics of the sampled households. Measures such as means, standard deviations, and percentages provided a comprehensive overview of key variables like age, education, farm size, household size, and income distribution. In order to capture latent constructs such as trust and resilience, an index construction method was applied. Individual indicators were normalized on a 0–1 scale and aggregated to form composite indices that facilitate comparison across various households. Because of possible selection bias in the adoption of CSA practices, PSM was used to control for observable differences between adopters and non-adopters. The PSM approach provided unbiased estimates of the Average Treatment Effect on the Treated (ATT), reflecting the net impact of CSA adoption on resilience and crop yield.

To further explore heterogeneity in the effects of CSA adoption, Quantile Regression (QR) was applied. Unlike Ordinary Least Squares (OLS), QR estimates effects at different points of the conditional distribution of resilience, revealing whether CSA practices benefit low- and high-resilience households differently.

Further more, to estimate the overall mean effects of CSA adoption on key outcomes such as household resilience, productivity, and income Ordinary Least Squares regression was employed. This provided a benchmark for comparing average relationships between variables. Model validity and robustness were ensured through a series of diagnostic tests, including multicollinearity checks (Variance Inflation Factor), goodness-of-fit indicators (pseudo R²), and significance tests (p-values).

Finally, comparative tests such as independent samples *t*-test and Mann–Whitney U test were conducted to assess mean differences in socio-economic and resilience indicators between CSA adopters and non-adopters.

The summary of the analytical techniques used for the purpose of this study is summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of Analytical Techniques

Analytical Method	Purpose	Key Output
Descriptive Statistics	Summarize socio-economic and farm characteristics	Mean, SD, percentages
Index Construction	Build composite indicators (trust, resilience)	Normalized indices (0–1)
Propensity Score Matching (PSM)	Control for selection bias and estimate CSA adoption effects	ATT (impact of CSA on resilience/yield)
Quantile Regression (QR)	Capture heterogeneous effects of CSA adoption across resilience levels	Quantile-specific coefficients
OLS Regression	Measure average effects	Mean effect estimates
Diagnostic Tests	Check model validity and robustness	VIF, pseudo R ² , p-values
Comparative Tests	Compare CSA adopters vs non-adopters	Mean difference (t-test, Mann–Whitney)

Methodology

Study Area

The study was conducted in Kwara State, located in the North-Central geopolitical zone of Nigeria. The state lies between latitudes 7°45'N and 9°30'N, and longitudes 2°30'E and 6°25'E, with an estimated population of about 3.5 million people (NPC, 2021). Kwara State is characterized by a tropical climate with distinct wet (April–October) and dry (November–March) seasons. Average annual rainfall ranges between 1,000 mm and 1,500 mm, while mean temperatures vary between 25°C and 30°C. The major occupations of the people are farming, trading, and artisanal work. Rice is one of the major staple crops cultivated both under rainfed and lowland conditions, contributing significantly to food security and income generation. However, the productivity of rice farmers has been affected by climate variability, including unpredictable rainfall patterns and flooding.

Data Collection and Sources

Primary data were collected through the use of a well-structured questionnaire administered to the sampled rice farmers with the aid of kobo tool kit. The questionnaire captured information on socio-economic characteristics, types of Climate-Smart Agricultural Practices (CSAPs) adopted, yield levels before and after climate shocks, income dynamics, access to institutional support, and coping mechanisms.

Sampling Procedure and Sample Size

A multistage sampling procedure was employed to select 450 rice-farming households from major rice-producing areas of Kwara State, Nigeria. The study focused on the five LGAs which are Edu, Patigi, Kaiama, Moro, and Baruten identified by the Kwara State Ministry of Agriculture as the leading rice-producing zones.

At the first stage, these five LGAs were purposively selected to capture geographical and agro-ecological variation in rice production across the state. In the second stage, three villages were randomly selected from each LGA based on records obtained from local agricultural extension offices, resulting in 15 villages:

- Edu LGA: Lafiyi, Shonga, Faigi
- Patigi LGA: Patigi, Kpada, Lade
- Kaiama LGA: Kaiama, Kemanji, Wajibe
- Moro LGA: Bode-Saadu, Jebba, Pakunmo
- Baruten LGA: Ilesha, Okuta, Gure

In the third stage, a systematic random sampling technique was used to select 30 rice-farming households from each village, yielding a total sample size of 450 households (5 LGAs \times 3 villages \times 30 households). Sampling frames were constructed through village-level listings of active rice farmers, verified by agricultural extension officers. Households were included if they cultivated rice in the 2024 cropping season. This sampling approach ensured spatial representation of rice producers across the main production zones of Kwara State while statistical accuracy and logistical feasibility were consciously maintained.

Results and Discussion

Summary Statistics of Farmers' Socio-economic Characteristics and Resilience Indicators

Table 2 presents the summary statistics of the variables used in the analysis. The sample consists of 14 smallholder farmers drawn from five Local Government Areas (LGAs): Patigi, Ifelodun, Edu, Moro, and Asa. The average age of respondents was 50.3 years, indicating that most farmers were in their economically active years. Males constituted approximately 71% of the sample, suggesting a male-dominated farming population in the study area. The mean years of formal education stood at 7.4 years, which implies a moderately educated farming population with the potential to understand and apply agricultural innovations. The average farm size was 3.72 acres, this confirms the smallholder nature of the farms. The mean annual income was ₦186,740, with a wide variation across households (SD = ₦71,564). Only 21% of farmers had

access to credit, and 57% belonged to at least one social or farmer-based group. The average number of extension contacts per year was approximately 2, reflecting relatively limited interaction between farmers and extension service providers. The mean trust score was 3.07 on a scale of 0–10, suggesting moderate social trust within farming communities.

With respect to climate-smart agricultural (CSA) adoption, 57% of the respondents had adopted at least one CSA practice, with an average adoption count of 1.6 practices per farmer. About 64% of the farmers reported experiencing a production shock such as drought, flood, or pest attack during the reference period. The average baseline yield prior to the shock was 3.08 tons per hectare, while the post-shock yield declined slightly to 2.94 tons per hectare, representing an average yield loss of 8.3%. The corresponding economic loss averaged ₦350,300, though values ranged from negative (indicating gains) to over ₦1.2 million, highlighting variability in the impact of shocks across farmers.

In terms of financial coping capacity, farmers had an average savings buffer of 1.4 months, meaning their savings could sustain household expenses for slightly over a month without additional income. The mean income change from the previous season was 1.64%, suggesting that incomes remained relatively stagnant or slightly declined during the period under review. The mean number of coping strategies employed was 1.9, indicating that farmers typically relied on more than one mechanism to deal with shocks.

Finally, the average resilience index was 0.52 (SD = 0.11), with values ranging from 0.35 to 0.72, implying a moderate level of resilience among the respondents. This suggests that while some farmers exhibited strong adaptive capacity, others remained vulnerable to shocks due to limited resources, low income diversification, or weak institutional support.

Table 2: Summary Statistics of Farmers’ Socioeconomic and Resilience Indicators

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Description
Age (years)	50.3	6.9	38	61	Age of respondent
Gender (1 = Male)	0.71	0.47	0	1	Sex of respondent
Education (years)	7.4	3.3	3	14	Years of formal schooling
Farm size (acres)	3.72	2.05	0.36	7.31	Total cultivated area
Annual income (₦)	186,740	71,564	75,570	318,246	Total annual income
Credit access (1 = Yes)	0.21	0.42	0	1	Access to agricultural credit
Extension contact (times/year)	1.93	0.80	1	3	Frequency of contact with extension agents
Group membership (1 = Yes)	0.57	0.51	0	1	Membership in social/farmer group
Trust score (0–10)	3.07	1.56	1	5	Composite social trust score
CSA adopter (1 = Yes)	0.57	0.51	0	1	Adoption of at least one CSA practice
Adoption count	1.57	1.80	0	6	Number of CSA practices

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Description
					adopted
Experienced shock (1 = Yes)	0.64	0.50	0	1	Experience of production shock
Baseline yield (t/ha)	3.08	0.74	1.82	4.34	Yield before shock
Post-shock yield (t/ha)	2.94	0.66	1.72	3.82	Yield after shock
Percent yield loss (%)	8.29	13.37	-12.49	31.20	Percentage yield reduction
Economic loss (₦)	350,300	482,200	-394,800	1,219,200	Estimated monetary loss
Savings buffer (months)	1.40	1.02	0.06	3.54	Months of expenditure savings can sustain
Income % change	-1.64	12.68	-28.09	15.64	Change in income relative to previous season
Coping strategies (count)	1.86	1.38	0	5	Number of coping mechanisms used
Resilience index (0–1)	0.519	0.111	0.345	0.724	Composite resilience index

Source: Author’s computation from field survey data, 2025.

Comparison of CSA Adopters and Non-Adopters

Table 3 compares the mean values of selected variables between CSA adopters and non-adoptersto further understand differences in socioeconomic characteristics and resilience capacity, respondents were categorized based on whether they had adopted at least one Climate-Smart Agricultural (CSA) practice.The results show that CSA adopterswere slightly younger (average 48.7 years) than non-adopters (52.3 years), and had more years of formal education (8.3 vs. 6.2). Although both groups cultivated similar farm sizes, adopters earned higher mean annual income (₦197,000) compared to non-adopters (₦172,000). Adopters also recorded more frequent extension contacts (2.1 vs. 1.6) and were more likely to belong to farmer groups.

In terms of production outcomes, CSA adopters experienced lower yield loss (6.1%) and smaller economic loss (₦265,000) compared to non-adopters (10.8%and₦461,000, respectively). Moreover, adopters had higher resilience indices (0.56 vs. 0.47), indicating better capacity to withstand and recover from shocks. Generally, CSA adopters exhibited stronger socioeconomic attributes, better access to information and networks, and higher resilience compared to their non-adopting counterparts.

Table 3: Mean Comparison Between CSA Adopters and Non-Adopters

Variable	CSA Adopters (n = 8)	Non-Adopters (n = 6)	Mean Difference
Age (years)	48.7	52.3	-3.6
Education (years)	8.3	6.2	+2.1
Farm size (acres)	3.84	3.55	+0.29
Annual income (₦)	197,000	172,000	+25,000
Credit access (1 = Yes)	0.38	0.00	+0.38

Variable	CSA Adopters (n = 8)	Non-Adopters (n = 6)	Mean Difference
Extension contact (per year)	2.1	1.6	+0.5
Group membership (1 = Yes)	0.75	0.33	+0.42
Trust score (0–10)	3.38	2.67	+0.71
Experienced shock (1 = Yes)	0.63	0.67	-0.04
Baseline yield (t/ha)	3.00	3.18	-0.18
Post-shock yield (t/ha)	2.86	3.05	-0.19
Percent yield loss (%)	6.1	10.8	-4.7
Economic loss (₦)	265,000	461,000	-196,000
Savings buffer (months)	1.52	1.24	+0.28
Income % change	0.48	-4.58	+5.06
Coping strategies (count)	2.00	1.67	+0.33
Resilience index (0–1)	0.56	0.47	+0.09

Source: Author’s computation from field survey data, 2025.

Note: CSA adopters are farmers who adopted at least one climate-smart agricultural practice during the previous survey year.

Analysis of Yield and Income Dynamics across CSA Adoption

Table 4 presents the mean baseline yield and annual income of farming households based on their CSA adoption status. The results indicate that CSA adopters recorded slightly higher baseline yields (3.17 t/ha) compared to non-adopters (3.07 t/ha). Similarly, the average annual income of adopters (₦196,497.75) was marginally higher than that of non-adopters (₦195,831.50).

Although the observed differences are relatively small, the pattern suggests that households practicing CSA tend to have better productivity and income performance even before accounting for external shocks. This may reflect the potential efficiency or better resource management associated with CSA practices, such as improved soil fertility, water management, or crop diversification.

Table 4: Mean Baseline Yield and Annual Income by CSA Adoption Status

CSA Adopter	Baseline Yield (t/ha)	Annual Income (₦)
Non-Adopters	3.070	195,831.50
Adopters	3.173	196,497.75

Source: Author’s computation from field survey data, 2025.

Distribution of Rice Farmers by Resilience Level and Yield Loss

Figure 1 illustrates the distribution of rice farmers in Kwara State according to their resilience levels and the corresponding average yield losses experienced during the last production season. The bar chart represents the proportion of farmers in each resilience category, while the line graph shows the average percentage yield loss associated with each group.

The results indicate that a majority of rice farmers (57 %) fall within the moderate resilience category, while 28 % exhibit high resilience and 15 % display low resilience. Yield loss declines consistently as resilience increases: farmers with low resilience recorded an average yield loss of 31 %, those with moderate resilience lost about 21 %, and those with high resilience experienced only 13 % yield loss. This pattern shows that farmers who were more resilient—those with better access to resources, stronger community ties, and greater ability to adapt—experienced fewer losses in yield. In other words, resilience helped them weather difficult conditions and keep their farms productive.

Differential effects of CSA adoption on farmers’resilience to yield loss across Quantile

This study applied quantile regression in order to capture the heterogeneous effects of CSA adoption and related factors on farmers’ resilience levels across the entire distribution of the resilience index. The quantile regression results (Table 5) reveal important distributional insights into how CSA adoption and socio-economic factors influence farmers’ resilience to yield loss.

At the 25th quantile (lower-resilience farmers), CSA adoption ($p < 0.05$) and adoption count ($p < 0.01$) significantly increase resilience, implying that even among less resilient farmers, engaging in multiple CSA practices enhances adaptive capacity. Similarly, group membership ($p < 0.01$) strongly improves resilience, underscoring the importance of social networks in cushioning yield shocks. At the 50th quantile (median), adoption count and group membership remain significant, indicating that the resilience benefits of CSA and social participation extend across the general farming population.

At the 75th quantile (highly resilient farmers), group membership ($p < 0.01$) and adoption intensity ($p < 0.01$) continue to exert strong positive effects. This suggests that social connectedness and continuous engagement in CSA practices are key for sustaining high levels of resilience among adaptive farmers. In contrast, education, age, gender, and income show no

significant effect across quantiles, implying that resilience gains are more closely tied to behavioral and institutional factors than demographic attributes.

Overall, the quantile results revealed that CSA adoption and group participation are consistent and powerful drivers of resilience across all resilience levels, with the strongest effects observed among the most adaptive farmers.

Table 5: Differential Effects Using Quantile Regression

Variable	25th Quantile ($\tau=0.25$)	50th Quantile ($\tau=0.50$)	75th Quantile ($\tau=0.75$)
Intercept	0.371 (0.295 – 0.454)	0.473 (0.427 – 0.521)	0.516 (0.443 – 0.553)
CSA Adopter	0.082 (0.014 – 0.113) **	0.012 (-0.005 – 0.029)	0.033 (-0.011 – 0.056)
Adoption Count	0.016 (0.011 – 0.028) ***	0.016 (0.012 – 0.020) ***	0.008 (0.004 – 0.019) ***
Age	0.000 (-0.001 – 0.001)	-0.000 (-0.001 – 0.000)	-0.001 (-0.001 – 0.000)
Gender (Male=1)	0.025 (-0.008 – 0.058)	0.007 (-0.007 – 0.026)	-0.011 (-0.028 – 0.014)
Education (Years)	-0.004 (-0.008 – 0.003)	-0.001 (-0.004 – 0.001)	0.000 (-0.002 – 0.003)
Farm Size (Acres)	-0.004 (-0.011 – -0.002) **	-0.002 (-0.007 – 0.002)	0.003 (-0.002 – 0.005)
Credit Access	0.006 (-0.024 – 0.038)	0.000 (-0.011 – 0.012)	0.005 (-0.008 – 0.024)
Group Membership	0.090 (0.066 – 0.118) ***	0.098 (0.085 – 0.118) ***	0.100 (0.085 – 0.113) ***
Trust Score	0.002 (-0.007 – 0.010)	0.002 (-0.002 – 0.006)	-0.000 (-0.008 – 0.006)
Annual Income (₹)	0.000 (-0.000 – 0.000)	0.000 (-0.000 – 0.000)	0.000 (-0.000 – 0.000)

Source: Author’s computation from field survey data, 2025.

Determinants of Climate-Smart Agriculture Adoption

The results of the logistic regression model identifying factors influencing CSA adoption among rice farmers are presented in Column (1) of Table 6. The model achieved convergence after five iterations with a satisfactory Pseudo R² of 0.302, suggesting that approximately 30% of the variation in CSA adoption is explained by the included variables.

Specifically, access to credit ($p < 0.01$) substantially increases the likelihood of adoption, highlighting the role of financial inclusion in facilitating technology uptake. This aligns with findings by [Retnoningsih](#) and Chung (2025) and Rehman et al. (2025), who observed that access to credit reduces liquidity constraints, allowing farmers to invest in climate-adaptive

technologies. Group membership ($p < 0.05$) also exhibits a positive and significant effect on adoption, emphasizing the importance of social capital in fostering knowledge diffusion and collective learning. Farmers engaged in social networks and cooperatives are more likely to access extension information, input subsidies, and peer influence that promote CSA practices (Abegunde et al., 2020). Furthermore, education ($p < 0.05$) positively affects CSA adoption, implying that educated farmers have more access to innovation and climate adaptation information. Farm size shows a weakly significant positive effect ($p < 0.10$), indicating that farmers practicing on large scale may be better positioned to experiment with new technologies and absorb associated risks. Conversely, age and trust score do not significantly influence CSA adoption, this suggests that people's decisions to adopt CSA practices are shaped more by their social, economic, and institutional surroundings than by their personal or demographic traits. This emphasizes the policy relevance of strengthening institutional support systems rather than focusing solely on farmer characteristics.

Effect of CSA Adoption on Farmers' Resilience to yield loss

The Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression results reported in Column (2) reveal that CSA adoption significantly enhances farmers' resilience to yield loss. The estimated coefficient of CSA adoption ($p < 0.01$) suggests that CSA adopters experience higher resilience index scores compared to non-adopters, even after controlling for socioeconomic and institutional variables. This supports the hypothesis that CSA adoption improves farmers' adaptive capacity to climate-induced shocks.

Similarly, the number of CSA practices adopted ($p < 0.01$) is positively associated with resilience, indicating that diversified adoption yields cumulative benefits. Farmers who combine several CSA practices like crop rotation, mulching, using improved seeds, and conserving water tend to enjoy more stable harvests and better income security. These findings corroborate empirical evidence from Teklu et al. (2023), who submitted that integrated CSA adoption enhances livelihood resilience and risk mitigation among smallholder farmers. Group membership ($p < 0.01$), access to credit ($p < 0.05$) also significantly increases resilience. Collective participation likely helps farmers get timely information, share labor, and support one another during difficult climate conditions. Conversely, farm size ($p < 0.05$) exhibits a negative effect, which imply that smaller farms may apply CSA techniques more intensively and efficiently than larger ones. The OLS model explains about 45.1% of the variance in the resilience index (Adjusted $R^2 = 0.438$), indicating that the explanatory variables jointly provide substantial explanatory power. The F-statistic (23.947, $p < 0.01$) further confirms the overall significance of the model.

Causal Effect of CSA Adoption on Resilience: Propensity Score Matching (PSM)

The Propensity Score Matching (PSM) technique was employed to address potential selection bias arising from observable characteristics, the matching results showed that adopters and non-adopters were well balanced in their characteristics, indicating that the estimated treatment effects are reliable.

The Average Treatment Effect on the Treated (ATT) from the PSM model indicates that CSA adopters recorded a 0.106–0.112 point higher resilience index compared to their non-adopting counterparts ($p < 0.01$). This finding is robust and statistically significant, implying that CSA adoption causally improves farmers' resilience to yield loss. The positive impact persists even after adjusting for confounding factors such as income, education, and social participation.

These results are consistent with recent studies Tadese et al., (2021); Adimassu et al., (2025) who found that CSA practices not only increase productivity but also stabilize agricultural systems by improving soil fertility, water retention, and crop diversity. This means that CSA practices play an important role in helping rice farmers in Kwara State build livelihoods that can better withstand the impacts of climate change.

Table 6: CSA Adoption determinant, Effect on Farmers' Resilience to yield loss and Resilience Match

Variable	(1) CSA Adoption (Logit)	(2) Resilience Index (OLS)	(3) PSM-Matched Resilience
CSA Adopter	—	0.041*** (0.011)	0.112*** (0.009)
Adoption Count	—	0.023*** (0.004)	—
Age	-0.002 (0.007)	0.0002 (0.0003)	0.0001 (0.0004)
Gender	0.288 (0.198)	0.006 (0.009)	0.008 (0.010)
Education	0.072** (0.033)	0.001 (0.002)	0.002 (0.003)
Farm Size (acres)	0.058* (0.034)	-0.004** (0.002)	-0.003** (0.001)
Credit Access	0.841*** (0.197)	0.107** (0.109)	0.006 (0.010)
Group Membership	0.402** (0.188)	0.089*** (0.010)	0.096*** (0.009)
Trust Score	-0.046 (0.066)	-0.002 (0.003)	-0.001 (0.003)
Annual Income (₦)	-0.00000 (0.00000)	-0.00000 (0.00000)	-0.00000 (0.00000)
Constant	-1.017** (0.509)	0.462*** (0.028)	0.481*** (0.007)
Observations	450	450	444
R ² / Pseudo R ²	0.302	0.451	0.187
F Statistic	—	24.212***	101.558***

Source: Author's computation from field survey data, 2025.

Model Diagnostics and Assumption Checks

Prior to interpreting the regression results, the assumptions of linear regression were rigorously assessed. The normality of residuals was evaluated using the Shapiro-Wilk test. After appropriate transformation of the dependent variable, the residuals were found to be approximately normally distributed ($W = 0.991$, $p = 0.215$), satisfying the normality assumption. This indicates that the model errors are symmetrically distributed around zero, supporting the validity of statistical inference.

Multicollinearity among the independent variables was assessed using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF). All VIF values were well below the commonly accepted threshold of 5, ranging from 1.01 to 1.06. This demonstrates that the predictors are not highly correlated, and ensures that the estimated regression coefficients are stable and interpretable. Heteroskedasticity was examined using the Breusch-Pagan test. The test results ($BP = 6.85$, $df = 6$, $p = 0.337$) suggest homoskedastic residuals, indicating that the variance of errors is constant across levels of the

independent variables. This confirms that the model's standard errors are reliable for hypothesis testing.

Collectively, these diagnostics indicate that the regression model meets the key assumptions of linear regression, providing a robust foundation for interpreting the effects of climate-smart agricultural adoption, trust, education, credit access, extension contact, and group membership on the outcome variable.

Shapiro.test(residuals(model2))

Shapiro-Wilk normality test

data: residuals(model2)
W = 0.9912, p-value = 0.215

Multicollinearity

vif(model2)

csa_adoptertrust_score	education
1.06	1.01
credit_accessextension_contact_per_year	group_membership
1.05	1.01

Heteroskedasticity

bptest(model 2)

studentizedBreusch-Pagan test

data: model3
BP = 6.65, df = 6, p-value = 0.337

The Diagnostic plots for regression model is presented in Figure 2.

1. Residuals vs Fitted – Checks linearity and homoscedasticity. Residuals scattered randomly around zero indicate a good fit.
2. Normal Q-Q Plot – Assesses normality of residuals. Points closely following the 45° line suggest residuals are approximately normally distributed.
3. Scale-Location Plot – Another check for homoscedasticity; a horizontal line with equally spread points is ideal.
4. Residuals vs Leverage – Identifies influential observations. Larger circles indicate higher influence (Cook's distance).

These plots visually confirms that the model meets the assumptions of linear regression

Figure 2: Diagnostic plots for regression model

Conclusion

The study provides strong empirical evidence that CSA adoption significantly enhances farmers' resilience to yield loss which may emanate from climate variability and other crop failure sources in Kwara State. Policies promoting CSA should therefore focus on improving access to credit through rural microfinance and input-support schemes. Additionally, strengthening farmer-based organizations and extension networks will foster social learning and collective resilience. Targeted financial inclusion and strengthening farmer groups can accelerate CSA uptake among rural households. Encouraging multi-practice adoption rather than single interventions can further maximize resilience gains, as the combined effect of integrated CSA practices is greater than individual techniques. Furthermore, capacity-building programs targeting smallholder farmers should emphasize education and awareness creation on the long-term benefits of CSA.

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**Integrating Environmental Management and Agricultural Development: Strategies for
Pollution Control and Sustainable Food Production**

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Abstract

This paper explored integrated strategies for aligning environmental management with agricultural development to achieve pollution control and sustainable food production. Extracting from peer-reviewed literature from 2015–2025 on harmonizing environmental management and agricultural development to control pollution while ensuring sustainable food production. It synthesized peer-reviewed evidence (2015–2025) on agro-ecology, precision agriculture, integrated pest management, nutrient management, riparian buffer strips, treated wastewater reuse and climate-smart agriculture to build a systems framework for decision making. A mixed-methods approach (combining systematic literature synthesis, conceptual modeling, and targeted meta-analysis), was used in evaluating the effectiveness, trade-offs, co-benefits, and barriers to adoption of these interventions. Findings showed that diversification in agro-ecology and integrated pest management (IPM) enhance ecosystem resilience and minimize chemical dependency, while precision agriculture technologies (such as sensor-based irrigation and variable-rate fertilization) reduced water and nutrient losses. Riparian buffer strips and constructed wetlands effectively reduced runoff contaminants, and safe reuse of treated wastewater enhanced water management and circular nutrient when integrated with strong public health safeguards. Evidence further showed social and economic co-benefits when supported by policy tools like capacity-building programs, payments for ecosystem services, and agricultural extension. However, adoption barriers persisted as a result of knowledge gaps, limited capital access, and weak alignment to policies. This paper proposed a combined implementation roadmap which incorporated landscape-scale planning, on-farm practices, performance monitoring, and participatory governance to advanced control of pollution and food security. It concluded that context-specific integrations of low-cost measures in agro-ecology focusing on technological innovations, supported by healthy regulatory frameworks, are important for transitioning toward sustainable, agricultural systems which safeguard rural livelihoods and ecosystems.

Keywords: Precision Agriculture, Integrated Pest Management (IPM), Nutrient Management, Riparian Buffer Strips, Pollution Control, Sustainable Food Production.

Introduction

Agricultural systems are major sources of non-point pollution, including nutrient runoff, pesticide residues, sediment load, and greenhouse gas emissions; these pressures degrade water quality, impair ecosystems, and undermine human health and food sustainability (Adegoke et al., 2018; Dunn et al., 2022). Integrated approaches that simultaneously address production and

environmental protection are therefore essential to meet sustainability targets while safeguarding yields.

Agro-ecological practices — crop diversification, intercropping, cover cropping, and soil health management have demonstrated reductions in input dependency and improvements in resilience and biodiversity, making them central to pollution-reduction strategies (Mouratiadou et al., 2024; Bergez et al., 2022).

Precision agriculture (variable-rate fertilization, sensor-based irrigation) and decision-support systems can reduce excess fertilizer and water use and therefore lower nutrient leaching and runoff when appropriately implemented (Getahun et al., 2024; Bahmutsky et al., 2024).

Landscape scale measures such as riparian buffer strips, constructed wetlands, and safe reclaimed wastewater reuse close nutrient cycles and intercept pollutants before they reach sensitive receptors; however, reuse must be paired with health safeguards and monitoring (Dunn et al., 2022; Crovella et al., 2024; Adegoke et al., 2018).

Adoption depends on socio-economic factors (costs, labour, knowledge) and supportive governance instruments (payments for ecosystem services, extension, regulation). Integrated policy frameworks and participatory governance enhance uptake and scalability (Mouratiadou et al., 2024; Chandra, 2018).

This paper synthesizes peer-reviewed evidence (2015–2025), applies a mixed methods synthesis to compare interventions' environmental and production outcomes, and proposes an operational roadmap for integrating pollution control and sustainable food production across farm and landscape scales.

Materials and Method

Overall approach

This is a mixed methods systematic review and synthesis combining: (1) a systematic literature review of peer-reviewed articles (2015–2025); (2) targeted meta-analysis of quantitative intervention outcomes where adequate data existed (e.g., percent reduction in runoff nutrients, pesticide application rates, yield changes); and (3) development of a conceptual, operational roadmap integrating on-farm and landscape-level interventions and governance levers.

Search strategy and databases

We searched Web of Science, Scopus, PubMed/PMC, and ScienceDirect for articles published between 1 January 2015 and 31 December 2025 using combinations of terms: (“agro-ecology” OR “agro-ecology” OR “agricultural diversification”) AND (“pollution” OR “nutrient runoff” OR “pesticide”) ; (“precision agriculture” OR “variable rate” OR “sensor irrigation”) AND (“environment” OR “nutrient loss”); (“riparian buffer” OR “constructed wetland”) AND (“runoff” OR “water quality”); (“wastewater reuse” OR “reclaimed wastewater” OR “effluent reuse”) AND (“irrigation” OR “health risk”); (“integrated pest management” OR “IPM”) AND (“pesticide reduction”).

Data extraction and synthesis

For each study, we extracted: intervention type, location and agro-ecological context, experimental design, sample size, outcome metrics (nutrient loss kg/ha, % reduction in pesticide use, yield change %, economic metrics), and study duration. For meta-analysis, standardized effect sizes (percent change, Hedges' g where appropriate) were computed when ≥ 5 comparable studies were available for an intervention. Heterogeneity was assessed using I^2 and random-effects models where heterogeneity was moderate to high. When meta-analysis was infeasible, we carried out narrative synthesis focusing on magnitude, consistency, co-benefits, and tradeoffs.

Conceptual modeling and roadmap design

We combined empirical findings with policy and governance literature to produce a systems road map:

- a. farm-level practices (agro-ecology, IPM, nutrient management, precision tools);
- b. landscape measures (riparian buffers, wetlands, spatial planning);
- c. resource reuse and circularity (reclaimed waste water); and
- d. governance and finance (incentives, regulation, monitoring).

Results and Discussion

The search returned 3,800 records; after screening and quality appraisal, 184 peer-reviewed studies and 28 systematic reviews/meta-analyses were included for synthesis across intervention types. Geographic coverage included temperate and tropical systems with a dominance of studies from Europe, North America, China, and parts of Africa and Latin America.

Agro-ecological diversification and soil management

Evidence shows that diversification (cover crops, intercropping, reduced tillage, and organic amendments) consistently reduces nutrient leaching and erosion, and improves soil organic carbon and resilience. Several syntheses found significant reductions in N and P losses and improved biodiversity metrics (Mouratiadou et al., 2024; Bergez et al., 2022). Agro-ecological systems often achieved similar or slightly lower yields initially but improved stability and reduced input costs over time. These practices offer low-capital options for pollution control in resource-constrained contexts.

Integrated Pest Management (IPM)

Multiple field studies and reviews indicate IPM can reduce pesticide applications drastically (some studies report up to 90% reduction in applied insecticides) without substantial yield penalties when monitoring and thresholds are used; however, success depends on extension capacity and farmer training (Pecenka et al., 2021). IPM also decreases off-target chemical loading and supports biological control as an ecosystem service.

Nutrient management and precision application

Targeted nutrient management—site-specific nutrient management (SSNM), slow release fertilizers, split applications and variable rate technologies reduces fertilizer over-application and nutrient runoff. Precision agriculture trials and LCAs indicate substantial reductions in nitrogen and phosphorus losses and water use, with trade-offs relating to capital cost and technical capacity (Getahun et al., 2024; Bahmutsky et al., 2024). Economic evaluations suggest positive returns in medium to large farms; smallholders require adapted, lower-cost sensor and decision tools.

Riparian buffer strips and constructed wetlands

Meta-analyses and field studies show that riparian vegetated buffer strips (width, vegetation type, seasonality) notably reduce suspended sediments, particulate phosphorus, and some dissolved nutrients, though efficacy varies with buffer width and hydrology; constructed wetlands can be highly effective for targeted pollutant removal when properly sized and maintained (Dunn et al., 2022; Kumwimba et al., 2023). Buffer strips also provide biodiversity corridors and carbon sequestration co-benefits.

Reclaimed wastewater reuse — opportunities and risks

Reclaimed wastewater presents opportunities for closing water and nutrient loops, especially in water-scarce regions; however, microbial hazards, pharmaceuticals, and emerging contaminants require robust treatment, monitoring, and public health frameworks (Adegoke et al., 2018; Crovella et al., 2024; Penserini et al., 2024). Studies modelling reclaimed wastewater show benefits for yield stability and reduced freshwater withdrawals but underscore the need for governance and risk mitigation.

Climate Smart Agriculture (CSA) linkages

CSA packages that combine improved varieties, efficient water use, soil health, and rotational practices contribute to emissions mitigation and adaptation, while often delivering pollution co-benefits by reducing overuse of inputs (Chandra, 2018; Bhatnagar et al., 2024). The framing of CSA emphasizes integrated metrics (productivity, adaptability, mitigation) which match the multi objective nature of pollution control and food production.

Socio-economic factors, governance and adoption barriers

Across intervention types, adoption barriers include upfront capital, access to information/extension, insecure land tenure, and misaligned policies. Instruments like payments for ecosystem services (PES), targeted subsidies for precision tools, farmer field schools, and participatory extension increase uptake and sustained practice change (Mouratiadou et al., 2024). Multi-stakeholder coordination at landscape scales is critical to align production and environmental objectives.

Meta-analysis highlights (selected interventions)

Where comparable quantitative results existed:

IPM: pooled studies indicated large mean reductions in pesticide application rates (median reported reductions of 60–80%) with negligible long-term yield loss when correctly implemented (Pecenka et al., 2021).

Riparian buffers: pooled studies suggest buffer widths >10–12 m achieve substantially higher pollutant removal than narrower strips; removal efficiency ranged widely but averaged >50% for particulate P and sediments (Dunn et al., 2022; Kumwimba et al., 2023).

(Notes: meta-analytic effect sizes were limited by inconsistent variance reporting in primary studies; heterogeneity was typically high ($I^2 > 60\%$).

Trade-offs and system interactions

Combining low-cost agro-ecological measures with selective technology deployment is often synergistic (e.g., cover crops reduce runoff while variable-rate fertilizer reduces nutrient application). However, trade-offs appear where high-cost technologies increase inequality if subsidies or financing are absent. Landscape measures require coordination among landholders; otherwise, benefits may be limited. Governance mechanisms that internalize environmental externalities (PES, regulation) help mitigate these tradeoffs.

Literature emphasizes temperate systems; tropical and smallholder evidence is less abundant. Inconsistent outcome metrics limit direct comparability and meta-analytic precision (e.g., inconsistent reporting of variance). Many experiments are short-term (<5 years), limiting inference on long-term soil and socio-economic outcomes. Wastewater reuse studies often lack long-term epidemiological data in many regions.

Conclusion

Integrated environmental management and agricultural development are mutually achievable objectives. The peer-reviewed evidence (2015–2025) shows that combining agro-ecological practices, IPM, targeted nutrient management, precision technologies, and landscape measures (riparian buffers, wetlands) substantially reduces agricultural pollution while maintaining or enhancing food production resilience. Safe reuse of reclaimed wastewater can provide resilient water and nutrient sources when matched with appropriate treatment and governance.

Policy, technical and social interventions should be coordinated in four pillars; Farm-level packages (low to high tech mix)-Promote agro-ecological practices as baseline strategies: cover crops, crop diversification, organic amendments, and reduced tillage to reduce runoff and build soil carbon. Scale IPM via farmer field schools, monitoring tools, and threshold-based decision making to reduce pesticide use while safeguarding yields, deploy precision nutrient and water management where feasible- for smallholders, prioritize low-cost sensor networks and decision support mobile apps. Landscape and infrastructural measures: incentivize riparian buffers and constructed wetlands in critical source areas-use spatial planning tools to prioritize interventions based on hydrology and land use. Circular resource use and safeguards: unlock safe reclaimed wastewater reuse through clear treatment standards, monitoring, and public health surveillance; integrate reuse into nutrient accounting to reduce synthetic fertilizer demand. Governance, finance and capacity building: Use PES, targeted subsidies, credit lines, and blended finance to lower adoption barriers for technologies and landscape measures. Strengthen extension systems and participatory governance to ensure equitable adoption.

Finally, transitioning to integrated, low pollution agricultural systems requires combinations of evidence based practices, enabling policy, and investment in human and institutional capacity. The pathway must be context-sensitive, equitable, and monitored through harmonized indicators that capture production and environmental outcomes.

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Exploring The Potentials of Globalization for Sustainable Agricultural Development in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper critically examines how the inherent potentials of globalization can serve as a transformative force in revolutionizing agricultural practices and promoting sustainable development in Nigeria. Using a qualitative content analysis, the study observes that notwithstanding Nigeria's abundance of natural and human resources, a large proportion of its population continues to live in conditions of abject poverty. A review of relevant literature generated mainly from secondary sources attributes this paradox to the nation's persistent reliance on traditional agricultural methods and outdated practices, which have constrained productivity and hindered integration into global value chains. This paper argues that the vast potentials inherent in globalization remain largely untapped in Nigeria especially within the agricultural sector. Unless these opportunities are critically explored and systematically harnessed, the nation's economy will continue to exhibit structural stagnation and developmental miasma. It therefore advocates a paradigm shift toward fully mechanized farming systems, supported by innovative policies, technological exchange, and educational reform.

Keywords: Globalization, Agricultural Revolution, Development, Mechanization, Nigeria.

Introduction

Globalization has become an essential aspect shaping the modern world order. Its influence transcends geographical boundaries, connecting economies, cultures, and even societies through a nexus of political, technological and economic relationships. According to Giddens (64), globalization is the intensification of worldwide social relations which link distant localities in such a way that local happenings are shaped by events occurring many miles away. Despite the remarkable progresses recorded in areas like technology, communication, and trade across the globe, the impact of globalization is minimally felt in Nigeria especially in agricultural sector.

Historically, agriculture was the mainstay of Nigeria's economy in the past. However, a lot of intervening variables contributed to the present precarious situation of the sector in the country. It is both disheartening and paradoxical that a country like Nigeria with vast arable land, a favorable climate, and a huge labour force is grappling with low agricultural productivity and persistent abject poverty. The continued reliance on outdated farming equipment and old-fashioned farming methods has constrained the country from exploring and benefiting from the massive opportunities that globalization presents. As Ike and Edoziem (22) observe, globalization in Africa is a process of integration without participation – a condition that aptly captures Nigeria's engagement in global agricultural innovations and value chains.

Globalization has not been accorded the deserved strategic significance especially in the agricultural sector in Nigeria despite the country's vast agricultural potentials, largely due to policy inconsistency, structural weaknesses, inadequate infrastructure and limited institutional capacity. This study aims to critically investigate the untapped potentials of globalization and their capacity to transform agricultural development in Nigeria, with a view to identifying strategies for enhancing productivity, sustainability, and economic growth. It is against this backdrop, that this paper adopts qualitative context analysis method aimed at investigating the potentials of globalization that is capable of revolutionizing the agricultural sector of Nigeria. It is the findings of this study that Nigeria's inability to engage fully with globalization in agriculture has resulted in low productivity, food insecurity, lost export opportunities, poverty, unemployment, technological lag, and limited competitiveness in the global market. It is the contention of this work that Nigeria must make a paradigm shift from dependence on outdated agricultural tools and subsistence farming method to a fully mechanized system of agriculture. For Nigeria to turn around its fortune on agricultural sector, the country must embrace globalization.

Conceptual Clarifications

Globalization: The term "globalisation" has manifold dimensions ranging from politics, economy, health, environment, security, social, cultural, technology, financial and others. It represents one of the most influential forces in the new world system. Hashemi-Pour and Lutkevich state that globalization is the process by which ideas, knowledge, information, goods and services spread around the world. Similarly, Friedman (9) describes it as the inexorable integration of markets, nation-states, and technologies to a degree never witnessed before. The United Nations Development Programme explains that the term globalization has to do with the interdependence of the world's people, combining the economy, culture, technology as well governance of different countries. It is the incorporation of independent state economies through trade and financial dealings. Due to globalization, governments everywhere have become more connected and more inter dependent than before so as to foster global peace and collective security interests.

Globalization, is not merely an economic phenomenon; it reshapes national sovereignty by linking domestic policies to international standards global institutions. Though, while globalization has created opportunities for economic growth and innovation, it has also generated inequalities, cultural homogenization, and dependency for developing nations like Nigeria.

Agriculture: Etymologically, the term Agriculture is derived from two Latin words: "ager" meaning field/land, and "cultura" meaning cultivation/tilling. Thus in its earliest usage, agriculture refers to tilling or cultivation of land. However, in contemporary understanding and usage, agriculture has expanded far beyond its etymological scope of land cultivation to encompass crop production, livestock management, forestry, fisheries, agricultural economics, agribusiness, and global food systems. These diverse agricultural practices contribute significantly to the global food supply and play a vital role in sustaining communities' overall economy and livelihoods (World Bank, 2020). According to Food and Agriculture Organisation (FAO), agriculture broadly includes rural development, food security, sustainable resource management, genetic research, and climate-change adaptation (5).

The evolution of agriculture from its etymological idea of simple cultivation of land to dovetail into other areas mirrors the broader trajectory of human civilization, technological innovation,

and the ever increasing quest for sustainable development especially in agricultural sector. This shows that no country can be self sufficient in terms of food production and processing, hence the need for cross-pollination of ideas and exchange of products and services.

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on Modernization Theory and Comparative Advantage Theory. These theories provide a conceptual and analytical basis for examining how global forces shape agricultural transformation in developing economies such as Nigeria.

Modernization Theory emerged in the mid-twentieth century as an explanation of how traditional societies transition into modern, industrial, and globally integrated economies. Scholars such as Walt W. Rostow, Talcott Parsons, and Everett Hagen argue that development results from the adoption of scientific knowledge, advanced production systems, modern institutions, and rational economic practices (Rostow 23; Parsons 41; Hagen 57). Within the context of globalization, modernization theorists maintain that global interconnectedness accelerates development by promoting the diffusion of technology, innovation, and modern values. This diffusion process enables developing countries to adopt new agricultural techniques, enhance productivity, and strengthen their economic structures (Black 14; Inkeles and Smith 89).

Applied to agricultural sector, modernization theory explains how globalization promotes technological advancement and structural transformation. Access to improved seedlings, biotechnology, mechanized tools, irrigation systems, digital extension services, and precision agriculture innovations is facilitated through global linkages and partnerships (FAO 112). International organizations, multinational agribusiness firms, and global research networks contribute substantially to the transfer of knowledge, modern technologies, and best practices (World Bank 67). Globalization also shapes agricultural policy by encouraging institutional reforms aligned with global standards and trade frameworks. This includes improved extension systems, enhanced market structures, quality assurance mechanisms, and export-driven agricultural strategies (Todaro and Smith 119). Modernization theory explains the mechanisms through which globalization stimulate agricultural development through technological diffusion, institutional strengthening, improved market integration, and enhanced production capacity.

Comparative Advantage Theory was introduced by David Ricardo in the nineteenth century. It argues that countries gain economically when they specialize in the production and export of goods they can produce relatively more efficiently than others (Ricardo 76). The theory provides a foundational framework for understanding how globalization influences agricultural specialization and trade patterns. When applied to Nigeria, the theory suggests that globalization enables the country to exploit its natural endowments such as fertile land, favourable tropical climate, and diverse agro-ecological zones in order to specialize in agricultural commodities where it enjoys efficiency and competitiveness (Oyejide 21; Akinlo 44). Examples include cocoa, palm oil, sesame, ginger, cashew, hibiscus, and cassava. Globalization enhances this specialization by exposing Nigerian agriculture to international market standards, quality requirements, and advanced production techniques. This encourages innovation, reduces inefficiency, improves value addition, and strengthens export competitiveness (Porter 53).

However, comparative advantage theory also draws attention to structural challenges that limit Nigeria's ability to maximize benefits such as inadequate infrastructure, poor storage systems, weak processing capacity, policy inconsistencies, and low mechanization (Adeboye and

Omolehin 108). Removing these constraints is essential if Nigeria is to fully exploit its agricultural comparative advantage. Comparative advantage theory provides the economic rationale behind Nigeria's engagement with global agricultural markets and explains how specialization and trade openness can drive agricultural development.

These two theories provide a robust theoretical foundation for analyzing the relationship between globalization and agricultural development in Nigeria. Modernization Theory explains how globalization introduces technology, innovations, and institutional reforms that modernize agricultural production. Comparative Advantage Theory explains why Nigeria should participate actively in global agricultural markets by specializing in sectors where it holds natural and economic advantage. These theories collectively illuminate both the transformational potential and economic logic underpinning globalization's influence on Nigeria's agricultural sector. By analyzing these theoretical perspectives, we gain insights into the complex relationship between globalization and agriculture, which is crucial for developing sustainable and equitable solutions in the face of global challenges.

Globalization Influences on Agriculture in Developing Countries

1. **Technology Transfer Through International Collaboration** Globalization enables partnerships between developing countries and technologically advanced nations, allowing the transfer of innovations such as improved seed varieties, biotechnology, irrigation systems, and precision farming tools. As Castells (2012) notes, "global networks facilitate the rapid dissemination of technological knowledge across borders."
2. **Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in Agriculture** Globalization attracts foreign investors who bring modern equipment, mechanized systems, and agro-processing technologies. This encourages local farmers and agribusinesses to upgrade their methods to remain competitive.
3. **Access to Global Agricultural Research and Innovations** Through international research bodies (e.g., CGIAR, FAO), developing countries gain access to advances in crop science, climate-smart technologies, and animal husbandry practices that they might not produce domestically.
4. **Importation of Modern Machinery and Inputs** Global trade policies allow developing countries to import tractors, harvesters, fertilizers, pesticides, drones, and greenhouse technologies at relatively affordable rates. Globalization reduces trade barriers, making access easier.
5. **Digital Globalization and Information Flow** The internet—one of globalization's strongest tools—exposes farmers to new practices via extension platforms, online training, agricultural apps, and remote sensing technologies. This has enabled the rise of e-agriculture, where farmers use mobile phones for soil testing, weather forecasts, and market information.
6. **Market Competition and Efficiency Pressure** Exposure to global markets forces local producers to improve quality and efficiency. This pushes governments and farmers to adopt modern technologies to meet international standards and remain competitive.

7. **Capacity Building and Human Development** Globalization supports international training programs, exchange visits, and academic collaborations that build the technical skills of farmers, researchers, and extension workers.
8. **Development of Agro-Value Chains** Globalized value chains introduce technologies for storage, processing, packaging, and distribution—helping farmers reduce post-harvest losses and meet export requirements.
9. **Policy Reforms Guided by Global Best Practices** Countries often reform agricultural policies to align with global norms on sustainability, food safety, biotechnology, and innovation. Such reforms create an enabling environment for modern technology adoption.

Towards Solutions for Nigeria's underutilization of Globalization in Agriculture.

1. **Adopt Full Mechanized and Modern Farming Techniques** Encourage mechanization, precision agriculture, improved seeds, and irrigation systems to increase productivity and reduce reliance on traditional methods.
2. **Invest in Infrastructure** Improve rural roads, storage facilities, electricity, and digital connectivity to facilitate efficient production, processing, and access to global markets.
3. **Strengthen Agricultural Policies and Institutions** Formulate consistent, long-term agricultural policies and strengthen institutions like agricultural extension services and regulatory bodies to manage globalization effectively.
4. **Promote Education, Research, and Knowledge Transfer** Develop agricultural research centers, training programs, and partnerships with international organizations to introduce innovative farming practices.
5. **Encourage Public-Private Partnerships and Foreign Investment** Attract responsible foreign direct investment (FDI) in agribusiness, agro-processing, and export-oriented agriculture while protecting smallholder farmers.
6. **Enhance Access to Finance** Provide credit facilities, subsidies, and incentives to farmers to enable adoption of modern technologies and participation in global value chains.
7. **Diversify Agricultural Production and Export Portfolios** Focus on high-value crops, processed foods, and cash crops with global demand to increase export earnings and reduce reliance on imports.
8. **Promote Policy Alignment with Global Standards** Ensure food safety, quality standards, and certification processes meet international requirements to compete effectively in global markets.
9. **Empower Rural Communities** Engage local farmers and cooperatives in decision-making and capacity building to reduce poverty and increase productivity.

Recommendations

1. Nigeria should actively pursue technology transfer agreements to acquire modern agricultural innovations—including mechanization, improved seed varieties, biotechnology, and precision-farming tools—that can significantly increase productivity.
2. The government should create policies that attract foreign direct investment (FDI) into key agricultural areas such as irrigation, mechanized farming, agro-processing, cold storage, and logistics to strengthen value-chain development.
3. Nigeria should deepen its participation in international and regional trade agreements, especially AfCFTA, to expand export opportunities for agricultural products and improve global market competitiveness.
4. Stronger partnerships with global research institutions should be established to enhance knowledge exchange, improve agricultural research capacity, and modernize extension services.
5. The country should integrate global best practices into its agribusiness sector, particularly in food processing, packaging, and preservation, to reduce post-harvest losses and meet international quality standards.
6. The Nigerian government should promote digital agriculture by investing in ICT infrastructure that supports mobile extension services, digital marketplaces, satellite imagery, and precision agriculture technologies.
7. Agricultural policy reforms should be aligned with global norms, including access to credit, land-use reforms, and supportive regulatory frameworks that encourage private-sector investment and innovation.
8. Government and private actors should utilize global partnerships to strengthen food security, reduce dependency on imports, and create sustainable rural livelihoods through modern farming practices.

Conclusion

Globalization presents massive opportunities for transforming Nigeria’s agricultural sector, yet these opportunities remain largely underutilized due to such factors like structural weaknesses, policy inconsistencies, and limited technological adoption. Despite the fact that Nigeria is endowed with abundant natural and human resources, the country’s agricultural sector continues to lag behind global standards, resulting in persistent low agricultural productivity, food insecurity, low competitiveness, and constrained economic growth. The analysis reveals that strategic engagement with globalization through technology transfer, foreign investment, knowledge exchange, and integration into global markets have the potentials to catalyze an agricultural revolution capable of repositioning the sector as a central pillar of national development.

However, realizing these benefits requires deliberate policy reforms, strengthened institutions, modernized farming practices, and sustained investment in digital and physical infrastructure. Ultimately, Nigeria’s ability to harness the full potential of globalization will determine the extent to which agriculture can serve as a pathway to sustainable development, poverty reduction,

and enhanced global competitiveness. By embracing global opportunities with a clear domestic strategy, Nigeria can transform its agricultural landscape and secure a more prosperous and resilient future.

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Effect of Groundnut Bran Biochar on Soil Fertility and Growth of Watermelon in Soils of Owerri, Imo State.

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Abstract

The need for cheap and affordable alternative sources of plant nutrients inputs to boost the nutrient level of degraded arable farmlands to enhance watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*) productivity has been a major concern for soil scientists. In 2024, a field experiment was conducted under irrigated conditions to evaluate the effects of groundnut bran biochar on soil fertility, as well as its impact on the growth of watermelon. The treatments consisted of T1 (control), T2 (5t/ha biochar), T3 (10t/ha biochar), and T4 (15t/ha biochar). These treatments were arranged in a randomised complete block design and replicated three times. Data were analysed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA), and significant differences among treatment means were determined using Fisher's Least Significant Difference (F-LSD) at 5% probability level. The relationship between soil properties and crop growth parameters was determined using correlation analysis. Results showed that biochar application significantly ($p = 0.05$) reduced soil bulk density by 15%, increased soil organic matter by 59.9%, increased total porosity by 7.1%, soil total nitrogen by 30.49% and total exchangeable bases by 19.52%. The number of leaves, vine length, and leaf area of watermelon were significantly higher in the amended plots than in the control plots after eight weeks of planting. All the plots amended with biochar had a uniform growth at the end of the study (8 weeks). Although 5t/ha treatment had the lowest application rate, it still performed comparably to the higher application rates of 10 t/ha and 15 t/ha, suggesting that the lower rate may be sufficient to achieve desired improvements in soil properties and watermelon growth. Correlation analysis identified bulk density, electrical conductivity, total porosity, moisture content, base saturation, and CEC as key soil properties influencing watermelon growth.

Keywords: Biochar, organic fertiliser, pyrolysis, soil amendment, ultisols, soil fertility, watermelon.

Introduction

Watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*) is a vital crop in Nigeria, providing essential nutrients like vitamin C, vitamin A, and potassium. Nigeria is the largest producer of watermelon in West Africa, accounting for over 50% of regional production (FAO, 2020). However, watermelon yields in Nigeria are significantly lower than the global average (35.6 t/ha vs. 55.6 t/ha) due to poor soil fertility and limited water availability (FAO, 2020).

Watermelon production in Nigeria faces significant challenges, primarily due to soil fertility decline. Soil fertility constraints, including low nutrient availability, high soil acidity, and poor soil structure, have hindered watermelon yields and productivity (Adekiya et al., 2017; Ojeniyi et al., 2018).

According to Kannan et al. (2016), biochar is a carbonaceous material generated from organic waste, by a process called pyrolysis. Pyrolysis (heating of organic materials under conditions of limited or zero oxygen) is the thermo-chemical decomposition of organic waste under different temperatures, in presence of little or no oxygen (Lehmann, 2007). This can be achieved in several different ways. Basically, pyrolysis can be slow or fast, yielding different quality of products. The relative quality of biochar as a soil amendment (McClellan et al. 2007) is solely dependent on the type of organic matter (or feedstock) that is used and the conditions under which the biochar is produced. In rating the quality of biochar, several workers (Liang et al. 2006, McClellan et al. 2007, McLaughlin et al. 2009) have determined that high adsorption and cation exchange capacities and low levels of mobile matter (tars, resins, and other short-lived compounds) are the most important factors in determining the quality of biochar. These measures have a lot to do with its nutrient retaining capacity for sustainable release over a longer period of time.

During the production of biochar, the process generally releases more energy than is consumed, depending on the moisture content of the feedstock (Lehmann 2007). Heat, oil and gas that are released can be recovered for other uses, including the production of electricity. A sustainable model of biochar production primarily uses waste biomass, such as green-waste from municipal landscaping, forestry, or agriculture (for example, bagasse and other refuse materials from processing of agricultural value commodities). Biochar is fast assuming the position of a one stop solution to all soil degradation problems associated with the sustainable management of plant nutrients for strategic increases in crop yields. This calls for a careful examination of the benefits and definite drawbacks of biochar.

The major aim of this study was to investigate the effects of groundnut bran biochar on soil fertility and watermelon performance in Owerri, Imo State. Specifically, the study focused on assessing the impact of groundnut bran biochar on the physical and chemical properties of the soil, evaluating its influence on watermelon growth parameters, and correlating soil physico-chemical characteristics with watermelon growth outcomes.

Methodology

Description of Study Location

The study was carried out at the Teaching and Research Farm of Federal University of Technology Owerri, Imo State, South-eastern Nigeria. The area lies between latitude 5°22'43"N and longitude 6°59'37"E. The area has a lowland geomorphology of about 55m above sea level. The area has a mean annual rainfall of 2000-2500mm and an annual mean temperature range of 25-30°C with average humidity of 79% (Onwudike et al., 2015).

Experimental Design

The experiment was arranged using a randomised complete block design (RCBD). The experimental plots were tilled and properly labelled based on the treatments. A total of 20m x 20m (400m²) of land was used for research.

Treatment Application

Treatments used were groundnut bran biochar at the rate of (i) 5t/ha, (ii) 10t/ha, and (iii) 15t/ha and the control was soil without biochar. Application of biochar in each treatment was done before

planting the watermelon seeds by incorporating it into the soil. All treatments were assigned at random and received the same agronomic practices.

Results and Discussion

Properties of the Soil before the Study

The selected pre-planting soil properties are presented in Table 3.1. The soil was texturally Sand with 934.3 g/kg sand, 47.2 g/kg silt, and 18.5 g/kg clay. These results were similar to the observations of Nwosu et al. (2017) who had a related report for soils of Owerri, Imo state, south-eastern Nigeria. The textural class may negatively affect plant growth by exhibiting low water and nutrient retention capacities. The soil was low in available phosphorus, low in pH (strongly acidic), total Nitrogen, and exchangeable bases. The bulk density was 1.20 Mg/m³, which was less than the critical limit for root restriction (1.75 - 1.85 Mg/m³) as described by Soil Survey Staff (2003). The organic carbon and organic matter of the soil were low. The organic matter content was deficient when compared to the critical level of 20-30 g/kg reported by Enwezor et al. (1989). Therefore, since the critical levels of this soil are lower than the critical limits recommended by FAO (2006), the fertility level of this soil requires effective nutrient management practices, such as biochar application.

Table 3.1: Properties of soil before the study

SOIL PROPERTY	VALUE
sand(g/kg)	934.3
silt(g/kg)	47.2
clay(g/kg)	18.5
Texture class	Sand
Bulk density (Mg/m ³)	1.2
Total porosity (%)	58.87
soil moisture content (%)	7.49
hydraulic conductivity(cm/s)	0.049
silt/clay ratio	2.55
pH(1:2.5 H ₂ O)	4.81
Organic carbon (g/kg)	9.58
Organic matter (g/kg)	16.52
Available Phosphorus (mg/kg)	13.24
Exchangeable Acidity (H ⁺ + Al ³⁺) (cmol/kg)	0.64
Exchangeable calcium (cmol/kg)	1.83
Exchangeable magnesium (cmol/kg)	1.04
Exchangeable sodium (cmol/kg)	0.61
Exchangeable Potassium (cmol/kg)	0.08
ECEC(cmol/kg)	4.2
Base Saturation (%)	84.76
Total Nitrogen (g/kg)	1.85

Chemical Properties of the Groundnut Bran Biochar

Proximate analysis of the biochar is presented in Table 3.2.

The high pH in the biochar material indicated that it could be effective as an alkaline material, which, when added to the soil, can increase the soil pH at the study site.

Table 3.2. Chemical properties of the groundnut bran biochar

Chemical Properties	Value
Organic carbon (g/kg)	127.91
Total nitrogen (g/kg)	1.44
Carbon/Nitrogen ratio	88.83
Available phosphorus (g/kg)	0.45
PH(1:5KCL)	10.41
Exchangeable Calcium (%)	1.71
Exchangeable Magnesium (%)	2.64
Exchangeable Sodium (%)	3.38
Exchangeable potassium (%)	4.92

Effect Of Biochar on Soil Physical Properties

The effect of the biochar on soil physical properties is presented in Table 3.3. No significant change was observed in soil texture. It supports previous work performed by Fitzpatrick (1986), who suggested that soil texture is a function of an inherent characteristic of soil which can be influenced by parent material and climatic conditions over time.

Table 3.3: Effects of biochar on soil physical properties

Treatment	Sand (g/kg)	Silt (g/kg)	Clay (g/kg)	Texture class	Bulk density (Mg/m ³)	Total porosity (%)	Silt/Clay ratio	Hydraulic conductivity (cm/s)	Moisture content (%)
T1	974	4.8	21.2	Sand	1.20	54.72	0.23	0.037	2.5
T2	974	4.8	21.2	Sand	1.34	49.43	0.23	0.011	3.58
T3	974	4.8	21.2	Sand	1.04	60.75	0.23	0.019	7.5
T4	974	4.8	21.2	Sand	1.02	63.02	0.23	0.031	7.52
LSD(0.05)	Ns	ns	ns		0.06	10.24	ns	ns	3.73

T1 = control T2 =5t/ha. T3 = 10t/ha. T4 = 15t/ha. Ns= Not significant.

Effect of Biochar on Soil Chemical Properties

Table 3.4 showed the effect of the biochar on soil chemical properties. The findings of this study on the effects of groundnut bran biochar on soil fertility and watermelon growth are consistent with previous research demonstrating biochar's positive influence on soil chemical properties and crop performance. For example, Abebe et al. (2012) reported that biochar application improved soil properties and nutrient uptake in lettuce grown in chromium-polluted soils, highlighting biochar's capacity to enhance nutrient availability even under stress conditions. Similarly, Ding et al. (2016) found that biochar amendments increased soil fertility and reduced nutrient leaching, which aligns with the observed increases in organic carbon, total nitrogen, and exchangeable bases in this study. The increase in soil pH and base saturation observed here also supports the findings of Glaser, Lehmann, and Zech (2002), who noted that biochar can ameliorate acidic tropical soils by raising pH and improving nutrient retention. Moreover, Masto et al. (2013) demonstrated that biochar enhances soil biological activity and nutrient-holding capacity, which corresponds with the significant improvements in cation exchange capacity (ECEC) and exchangeable calcium, magnesium, and potassium reported in this study. The consistent increase in available phosphorus contrasts somewhat with Abebe et al. (2012), who observed variable phosphorus responses depending on biochar type and soil conditions, suggesting that groundnut bran biochar may be particularly effective in phosphorus-limited soils like those in Owerri. These results also echo the broader reviews by Kuzyakov, Friedel, and Stahr (2009), who emphasized biochar's role in enhancing soil organic matter and nutrient cycling. Taken together, these studies reinforce the potential of biochar as a sustainable soil amendment to improve degraded soils and boost crop productivity, particularly in regions facing soil fertility decline such as Nigeria (Adekiya, Ojeniyi, & Adediran, 2017; Ojeniyi, Adekiya, & Agbaje, 2018).

Table 3.4. Effects of biochar on soil chemical properties

Treatment	PH (H ₂ O)	OC (g/kg)	OM (g/kg)	TN(g/kg)	AV.P (mg/kg)	TEA (cmol/kg)	Exch. Ca+(cmol/kg)	Exch.Mg+ (cmol/kg)	Exch. Na+ (cmol/kg)	Exch. K+ (cmol/kg)	TEB	ECEC	Base saturation (%)
T1	4.15	14.36	24.76	2.34	25.63	1.08	1.50	1.16	0.34	0.39	3.39	4.47	75.83
T2	3.83	17.36	29.92	2.46	16.04	1.12	1.30	1.02	0.36	0.49	3.17	4.29	73.89
T3	4.40	12.17	20.98	1.96	28.78	1.16	2.50	1.82	0.28	0.09	4.69	5.85	80.17
T4	4.79	17.36	29.92	2.89	15.83	1.40	2.00	1.32	0.25	0.25	3.82	5.22	73.18
LSD(0.05)	0.17	3.66	3.65	0.92	5.4	Ns	0.01	0.1	Ns	0.11	0.27	0.03	5.74

OC=Organic Carbon, OM=Organic matter, TN= Total Nitrogen, AV.P=Available phosphorus, Ca =Calcium, Mg = Magnesium, Na =Sodium, K=potassium, TEA = Total exchangeable acid, ECEC=Effective Cation Exchange Capacity, TEB =Total exchangeable base, T1= control. T2= 5t/ha. T3= 10t/ha. T4= 15t/ha. Ns = Not significant.

Effect of Biochar on Vine Length of the Watermelon

From Table3.5. there was a significant difference ($p<0.05$) between the control and the biochar-amended plots.

Table 3.5: The effect of biochar on the vine length of watermelon (cm)

Treatment	2WAP	4WAP	6WAP	8WAP
T1	23.83	64.00	144.75	163.00
T2	29.50	77.50	150.55	173.33
T3	25.38	65.50	150.55	173.33
T4	29.50	77.50	150.55	173.33
F-LSD($p<0.05$)	4.06	11.89	3.64	8.39

T1= control. T2= 5t/ha. T3= 10t/ha. T4= 15t/ha. 2WAP= 2 weeks after planting
 4WAP=4 Week after planting. 6WAP= 6 weeks after planting. 8WAP= 8 weeks after planting

Effect of Biochar on Number of Watermelon Leaves

From Table3.6, the comparative analysis of watermelon leaf development revealed a nuanced response to biochar amendments.

Table3.6. Effect of biochar on the number of watermelon leaves

Treatment	2WAP	4WAP	6WAP	8WAP
T1	20.00	15.00	60.00	80.00
T2	26.67	41.67	80.00	98.33
T3	23.75	36.25	80.00	98.33
T4	26.67	41.67	80.00	98.33
F-LSD ($p<0.05$)	5.06	5.08	18.33	16.72

T1= control. T2= 5t/ha. T3= 10t/ha. T4= 15t/ha. 2WAP= 2 weeks after planting
 4WAP=4 Week after planting. 6WAP= 6 weeks after planting. 8WAP= 8 weeks after planting

Effect of Biochar on Leaf Area of the Watermelon

From Table 3.7, the incorporation of biochar into the soil had a profound impact on watermelon leaf area expansion, with differences observed among treatments.

Table 3.7. Effect of biochar on leaf area of watermelon (cm²)

Treatment	2WAP	4WAP	6WAP	8WAP
T1	39.93	144.52	218.10	165.25
T2	46.77	262.97	285.00	324.35
T3	39.95	200.35	285.00	324.35
T4	46.77	262.97	285.00	324.35
F-LSD (p<0.05)	5.23	28.12	45.48	71.15

T1= control. T2= 5t/ha. T3= 10t/ha. T4= 15t/ha. 2WAP= 2 weeks after planting
4WAP=4 Week after planting. 6WAP= 6 weeks after planting. 8WAP= 8 weeks after planting

Effect of Biochar on Leaf Area Index of the Watermelon

From Table3.8, the results showed that the plots amended with 15 tons/ha and 10 tons/ha biochar had higher leaf area index (LAI) values compared to the plot amended with 5 tons/ha biochar. However, all biochar-amended plots had higher LAI values than the control plot.

Table 4.8. Effect of biochar on leaf area index of watermelon (%)

Treatment	2WAP	4WAP	6WAP	8WAP
T1	0.05	0.53	0.55	0.60
T2	0.12	0.66	0.71	0.79
T3	0.22	0.60	0.80	0.83
T4	0.25	0.66	0.82	0.85
F-LSD(p<0.05)	0.20	0.23	0.35	0.46

T1= control. T2= 5t/ha. T3= 10t/ha. T4= 15t/ha. 2WAP= 2 weeks after planting
4WAP=4 Week after planting. 6WAP= 6 weeks after planting. 8WAP= 8 weeks after planting

Relationship Between Growth Parameters with Soil Properties

From Table 3.9 below, we can see the relationship between growth parameters with soil properties.

Table 3.9. Relationship between growth parameters with soil properties

Property	Vine length	Leaf number	Leaf area index
Avail. P	-0.23	-0.23	0.23
BS	0.70**	0.10	-0.10
Bulk density	0.49	-0.59*	-0.49
ECEC	0.79**	0.39	-0.39
Exch Ca ₊	0.35	0.35	-0.35
Exch K ₊	-0.27	-0.27	0.27
Exch Mg ₊	0.35	0.35	-0.35
Exch Na ₊	-0.18	-0.18	0.18
Hydraulic conductivity	-0.89**	-0.89**	0.89*
OM	0.07	0.07	-0.07
pH H ₂ O	-0.04	-0.04	0.04
TEA	0.20	0.20	-0.20
TEB	0.38	0.38	-0.38
TN	-0.27	-0.27	0.27
Total porosity	-0.63*	0.63*	0.63*
Moisture content	0.55*	0.55*	-0.55**

* and ** = sig at 5 and 1% probability levels, respectively

The correlation data reveal important relationships between soil properties and watermelon growth parameters such as vine length, leaf number, and leaf area index (LAI). Notably, effective cation exchange capacity (ECEC) and base saturation (BS) show strong positive correlations with vine length ($r = 0.79^{**}$ and 0.70^{**} , respectively), indicating that improved nutrient retention and availability in the soil promote vegetative growth. This aligns with findings by Ding et al. (2016), who reported that biochar amendments enhance soil fertility and nutrient availability, thereby supporting better crop growth. Conversely, hydraulic conductivity exhibits a strong negative correlation with vine length and leaf number ($r = -0.89^{**}$), suggesting that excessive water movement may limit nutrient uptake or root stability, a nuance also discussed by Baver, Gardner, and Gardner (1972) in their soil physics work. Bulk density negatively correlates with leaf number ($r = -0.59^{*}$), consistent with the understanding that compacted soils restrict root growth and nutrient access (Jury & Horton, 2004). Interestingly, available phosphorus shows a weak negative correlation with vine length and leaf number but a positive one with LAI, reflecting complex nutrient dynamics that may depend on biochar type and soil context, as noted by Abebe et al. (2012). The positive correlation between moisture

content and both vine length and leaf number ($r = 0.55^*$) underscores the importance of adequate soil water for growth, echoing Kirkham's (2014) emphasis on water relations in plant development. The negative correlation of total porosity with vine length (-0.63^*) but positive with leaf number and LAI (0.63^*) may reflect trade-offs in soil aeration and water retention affecting different growth aspects. Overall, these correlations highlight that soil chemical properties such as ECEC and base saturation are critical drivers of watermelon vegetative growth, while physical properties like bulk density and hydraulic conductivity modulate these effects. These findings support the broader literature emphasising integrated soil fertility management, including biochar use, to optimise both soil physical and chemical conditions for improved crop productivity (Adekiya, Ojeniyi, & Adediran, 2017; Glaser, Lehmann, & Zech, 2002).

Conclusion

This study investigated the effects of groundnut bran biochar on the physical and chemical properties of soil, as well as the growth performance of watermelon (*Citrullus lanatus*) in Owerri, Nigeria. The incorporation of biochar significantly altered the soil's physical properties by decreasing bulk density, increasing total porosity, and enhancing water-holding capacity. These improvements indicate better soil structure and moisture retention, which are beneficial for plant growth. Concurrently, biochar influenced the soil's chemical properties by increasing pH with higher application rates, although the soil remained acidic due to its initial acidity and buffering capacity that moderated the biochar's alkaline effect. Despite this, base saturation increased, reflecting enhanced soil fertility through improved retention and exchange of essential base cations. Additionally, organic carbon, organic matter, total nitrogen, available phosphorus, and exchangeable bases all showed increases following biochar application.

The growth performance of watermelon was substantially improved in biochar-amended plots. By six and eight weeks after planting, the plots treated with 5, 10, and 15 t/ha biochar exhibited uniform growth parameters, including vine length, leaf area, and leaf number, with only slight differences in leaf area index. This uniformity suggests that the plants adapted to the biochar amendments and reached a similar growth plateau. In contrast, the control plots consistently showed lower values across all growth parameters.

Correlation analysis revealed that watermelon growth was significantly influenced by soil bulk density, hydraulic conductivity, total porosity, moisture content, base saturation, and effective cation exchange capacity (ECEC). These findings provide compelling evidence that groundnut bran biochar enhances soil fertility and supports improved watermelon growth. The superior performance of watermelon in biochar-amended soils underscores the potential of this amendment to improve soil quality and crop productivity.

Based on these results, the study recommends applying groundnut bran biochar at 5 t/ha as a cost-effective rate for watermelon production. It also suggests integrating biochar with organic fertilizers or compost to optimize soil fertility and promote sustainable crop production. Furthermore, long-term studies are advised to evaluate the sustained effects of biochar on soil properties and crop growth, particularly its potential to mitigate soil acidity over time. These recommendations aim to build on the current findings and advance sustainable watermelon production in Owerri and similar agro-ecological zones.

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Role of Dietary Crude Protein on Poultry Reproduction: A Review

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Abstract

Poultry production has been known as a very lucrative business all over the world but then, it has its own risk. Maximal productivity in poultry farming declines with declining health and general wellbeing which can be caused by poor nutrition and management practices hence, it is important to ensure that poultry are fed in such a way that their daily nutrient requirements are provided and protein has been recognized as one of the essential components of a balanced diet. The importance of protein in reproductive performance of poultry birds cannot be overemphasized; Proteins are metabolized to form hormones and immune antibodies. Proteins help to improve semen parameters, egg production and maintain body weight. Excessive body weight has been reported to be the major cause of poor ovulation and early ovarian regression in poultry breeders. Protein is also important for embryonic development and hatching of high quality chicks. It has been observed that low hatchability is associated with high protein levels in hen's diets. Thus, proteins need to be regulated in poultry nutrition to avoid negative impacts.

Keywords: Dietary Crude Protein; Protein; Poultry; Reproduction and Nigeria.

Introduction

Background of the Review

Protein is derived from a Greek word "proteios" which means "holding first place". Proteins are large complex molecules that consist of amino acids which play many critical roles in the body. It plays a major role in the building of organs and tissues and in the repair and development of strong muscles. Protein helps build and repair cells in the body and is used to make the hormones and enzymes that regulate growth, development, metabolism and reproduction. Proteins are species specific in action and different livestock species have different sources of protein supply. Sources of protein for poultry production are animal, plant, and insect. In general, animal-based protein sources are high-quality proteins due to their high digestibility, biological value, and rich amino acid profile than plant-based protein sources but through the use of exogenous enzymes and proper processing, plant-based proteins can be converted into more digestible proteins with a good amino acid profile. Insect proteins are good in essential amino acid content and protein digestibility. Many studies have established the concept that insect proteins are well accepted by animals and 25–100% of soy meal or fish meal can be easily replaced by insect protein. The expression of full genetic potential of an animal requires improved ration, health care and management but among all these factors, nutrition plays the most important function. Nutrition in poultry involves providing a balance of nutrients that best meets the animals' need for maintenance, reproduction and any other productive function. Hence, poultry require the presence of at least 38 dietary nutrients in appropriate concentrations and

balance Klasing (1995) to enhance its reproductive and productive performances. Earlier findings have reported the positive influences of minerals Ogbuewu et al. (2015), protein Alagawany et al. (2016), amino acids Todd (2008), energy Bramwell et al. (1996) and vitamins Yaun et al. (2014) in poultry reproduction. Protein is a very essential nutrient and micronutrient for animals including chickens. It is also the most costly component of poultry feed production. The quantity of protein in feed largely depends on both amino acids profile and its digestibility. Also, the protein requirement of an animal is dependent on its physiological status and level of production. High demand for protein derived from poultry products calls for increase in poultry production and increase in poultry production relies on fertility of the parent stocks which obviously involves fertility of both male and female brood stocks. According to McGary et al. (2002), Lagares et al. (2017) and Wu et al. (2017) one male is responsible for the production of huge number of fertilized eggs which can exceed more than 1000 fertilized eggs per year in some species. The protein level of a breeder diets is an important factor for hatching characteristics and embryonic mortality. Owing to its amino acid constituents, protein plays a significant role in growth, reproduction, egg production, immunity, adaptation to the environment, and in many other biological functions in poultry.

The role of protein on livestock reproduction cannot be over emphasized. Adequate protein ensures proper growth, development and increased reproductive efficiency while deficiency of crude protein supply can result to feather abnormalities, overeating (resulting to obesity), stunted growth, feather picking and decrease in reproductive efficiency. Shrestta et al. (2002) reported that low reproductive performance can be attributed to factors like heat stress, diseases, unbalanced nutrition. Generally, nutrition plays a significant impact on the overall reproductive performance of farm animals. There has been a number of research works on the role of protein on reproductive efficiency of farm animals. Fernanadez et al. (2005) reported that appropriate nutritional management is essential for successful mating and conception in sheep flocks. Protein and amino acid intake are important for libido, semen volume and semen output. Tyler and Bekker (2012) reported that male broiler breeder fed 12.6% CP produced sperm in a longer period after insemination than those fed 10.5% and 15% CP. However, Mohiti-Asli et al., (2012) observed that fertility, hatchability of total and fertile eggs, and embryonic mortality of hen with high protein (17.40%) were higher than those of hen with low CP protein (14.50%). However, Protein was reported to play a significant role in the development of seminiferous tubules in rats where protein deficiencies during development led to reduced seminiferous tubules in diameter, reduced epithelial cell height as well as reduction in testicular DNA and RNA Vawdaw and Mandiwana (1990). Moskovtseu et al. (2007) observed that protein helps in the maturation of sperm in human epididymis as well as prevention of spermatozoa defects in humans Zhao et al. (2004). Thus, it is very important to know the role of CP in poultry reproduction in order to enhance reproductive efficiency of poultry. This paper therefore reviews the role of crude protein in poultry reproduction

Effects of Crude Protein on Semen Quality of Poultry

Chicken is the most common member of the poultry family and wide spread domestic animals, with the total population of more than 19 billion as of 2011. The male chicken semen is composed of sperm and seminal plasma secreted by the epididymis and vas deferens. The sperm are produced in the testes while in the case of the avian species; the seminal fluid is also produced in the testes. All these secretions are controlled by

endocrine hormones carried to them via the blood stream. The Follicle stimulating hormone (FSH) and luteinizing hormone (LH) regulates the testes which in turn produce testosterone which controls the testicular development and secretions. Semen quality is the measure of male fertility. It is also the measure of the ability of the sperm to accomplish fertilization. It involves both sperm quality and quantity. Semen quality characteristics includes the following; semen color, volume of ejaculate, semen pH, sperm morphology, sperm motility and semen concentration. According to Hafez and Hafez (2013), semen is the secretion of the male reproductive organ containing the gametes (spermatozoa) and seminal fluid produced in the testis and the quality of this semen is of great important in determining the fertility and reproductive efficiency in farm animals. Semen quality is of great important in poultry production hence the need to know the factors that affects semen quality and crude protein has been shown to be among the factors. Tyler and Beeker (2012) reported that fertility may be negatively affected when crude protein levels below 12.6% are used to feed male broiler breeders or if rations higher in crude protein are fed. This contradicts the reports of Vaughter et al. (1987) that lower CP fed to males during cycling period had no negative effects on semen volume and spermatozoa concentration. Vaughter's report supports the findings of Zhang et al, (1999) that spermatozoa concentration, volume, number of spermatozoa per ejaculate and testes weight tested at 50 weeks of age (WOA) were not affected by CP levels at 9%, 12% and 15%. Also, Remero-Sanchez et al. (2007) reported that 12% CP diet was not deficient in rearing where male broiler breeders had significantly greater fertility throughout the production period and those fed higher protein in rear also required more energy later in production to sustain fertility. The male poultry plays a significant role in the overall reproductive performance of female poultry. They contribute to 50% of the genetic blueprint of chicks produced in the farm with their semen been used to fertilize several eggs either via natural mating or artificial insemination (AI). Since crude protein is one of the important components in poultry feed production and reproduction, it is therefore very important to know the levels of crude protein required for maximum male fertility.

Effects of Crude Protein on Sperm Motility and Morphology

Sperm motility is the ability of the sperm to move or swim efficiently through the female reproductive system in order to fertilize an egg. Sperm must be motile and survive the environment of the vagina to reach the sperm storage tubules (SST) which is a crypts that store sperm in the hen for extended periods of time. This "reservoir" of sperm within the SST insures that sperm are available between inseminations and ideally secures the sustained probability of fertilization. Upon release from the SST and transport to the infundibulum, the site of fertilization, Sperm are vehicles that carry DNA to the ovum and, therefore, their "movement or motility" is important. Characteristics of sperm motion or percentage of motile sperm are reasonable indicators of male breeder potential. Semen morphology refers to the shape, size and appearance of the sperm which when abnormal can decrease fertility by making it very difficult to fertilize the egg. Sperm can be misshaped based on the following conditions: size of the head or tail, having extra head or tail, not having head or tail at all, having bent or coiled tail, stump-tail and not having tail attached at the correct location. The head shape is important because it can affect the sperm ability to penetrate the outer surface of the egg for

fertilization. Semen motility and morphology are usually assessed through semen analysis that examines the sperm cells under a microscope. Semen motility and morphology in poultry birds has not been observed to be effected by protein nutrition as the phenotypic expression of semen motility genotype of a bird is thought not to be influenced by environmental factors however; Froman and Feltmann (1998) find out that breeder male with average or high sperm motility phenotype remained so over time. This finding is in support of Graafet et al. (2018) who reported no response in sperm motility to CP at any age during production of broiler breeder males while Siqueira et al. (2011) on his own findings observed an average sperm motility range of 82.8% to 90.6% on boar fed lower CP levels at 7% and 16% respectively. However, Tyler and Bekker (2012) observed no difference in the percentage of normal sperm morphology or the number of live sperm with normal motility from males on different treatments at any age although no differences were observed in the numbers of live sperm with normal motility or morphology from males fed different CP concentrations, males fed 12.6% CP produced sperm that resulted in a longer fertile period than those fed 10.5% or 15% CP, as predicted from the number of sperm trapped in the outer perivitelline membrane. The method of determining the number of sperm in the perivitelline membrane is preferable to the estimation of egg fertility, as it is more sensitive to estimate on a continuous scale compared to the binary measurement of fertile versus infertile sperm that hatchability would estimate. Tyler and Bekker's report was consistent with the reports of Hossain et al (2011), Kheradmand et al. (2006) and Jibril et al. (2016). But on the contrary, Siti (2017) observed that combination of diets containing metabolizable energy and crude protein had significant effect on sperm motility of Rambon drake ($P < 0.05$). The sperm motility of Rambon drake fed on G6 gave the best result compared to drake fed on other groups. Whilst, G1 containing a high energy and protein level had the lowest motility rate. This finding is inversely proportional with the findings in Cihateup drake which had a highest motility rate as a result of a combination of high energy and protein level administration. The difference in this findings might be due to the fact that both Cihateup and Rambon drake have a different body weight which lead to different physiological responses on their environment. Zemanet al. (1996) reported that smaller body weight of birds have better heat tolerance. From all these reports, it can be concluded that nutritional deficiencies can depress sperm quality.

Role of Dietary Crude Protein In Poultry Semen Concentration

Sperm concentration also known as sperm density is the number of sperm per millimeter of sperm. Sperm concentration has an important influence on fertility. Cockerel semen is highly concentrated ranging from 4-6 billion spermatozoa per millimeter. The assessment of poultry semen characteristics gives an excellent indicator of their reproductive potentials and has been reported to be the major determinant of fertility and subsequent hatchability of eggs. Some factors have been studied to influence semen concentration either negatively or positively and crude protein is one of the factors. According to Jibril (2011), increase in crude protein intake (up to 12%) above the minimum requirements resulted in improved sperm concentration and favors spermatogenesis. This report concurs with the report of Kabirulet al. (2022) that the required level of protein increased semen concentration in Bangladesh sheep which also was in line with the observation of Elmazet al (2007) and Azizunnezaet al. (2013). Sperm produced as well as the total

number of spermatozoa per milliliter can be affected by the nature of the diet Fernandez *et al* (2005) and extra protein lead to an increase in testicular size due to an increase in diameter of seminiferous tubule Hotzelet *et al* (1998). The increase in sperm concentrations with different CP levels could be an indication that sperm production is regulated by physiological mechanisms. Some authors have suggested that follicle stimulating hormone (FSH) secretion is regulated by active and inhibin. In males, FSH controls inhibin secretion through unknown mechanisms. This hypothesis of physiological regulation can be reinforced by the fact that increases in the number of Sertoli cells and spermatogonia were not associated with increases in the sperm concentration of birds. All these studies suggests that increase in dietary crude protein level can lead to an increase in semen concentration it is however important to note that excessive consumption of dietary crude may have detrimental effects on semen concentration.

Impacts of Dietary Crude Protein in Poultry Semen Volume

Semen volume is the amount of semen, the fluid that contains sperm produced during one ejaculation. The fluid that makes up the semen volume comes from several sexual glands and organs like the seminal vesicles and the epididymis. Sufficient semen volume is necessary to transport sperm and enable it to fertilize an egg as a result, semen volume is one quality of sperm that is necessary for fertilization. Different farm animals' produces different volume of ejaculate: the cockerel produces between 0.01-1ml per ejaculation with 0.6ml being the average ejaculate volume recorded Cole and Cupps (1977). Cockerels of the same specie often produce different volumes of semen at different times. Nutrition and diet has been shown to be among the factors of great impact on semen quality and protein as an important component of poultry feed (nutrition) has been reported to impact semen volume. Miller *et al.* (2007) reported that feeding Turkey with high protein source had significant effects on growth and semen quality at 20-30 WOA but no significant different in semen volume and semen concentration at 34 WOA. This report contradicts the report of Megel *et al* (1980) that male turkeys fed with higher dietary crude protein diets produced slightly greater volume of semen than males turkeys fed with lower dietary crude protein diets. Mengel's report was in harmony with that of Sotirovet *al* (2002) that Turkeys fed 17% CP produced higher ejaculate volume than their counter parts fed with 14% CP. Shafqat *et al* (2002) on his own account reported that absence of ungraded protein affected semen volume while Jibril *et al* (2011) reported that 11-12% CP significantly increased semen volume while 14.6% CP significantly increased semen concentration in ram. Also Yahaya *et al* (2014) observed a progressive increase in semen volume, concentration, motility, and morphology and live-dead proportions with increase in dietary CP (12%-20%). All reports support the report of Ghonim *et al* (2010) that higher crude protein level improved reproductive performance in animals than lower CP levels. The above reports are indication that dietary crude protein is very essential at for optimal reproductive performance of the male chicken or cockerel.

Effect of Crude Protein In Semen pH

The pH (potential of hydrogen) of a sperm is the measure of its acidity and alkalinity. The pH is important because it affects the ability of the sperm to reach and fertilize an egg hence a balanced pH is necessary for fertilization to occur. The pH of birds varies

slightly with breeds and species. Optimum pH for birds ranges from 7.0 to 7.4%. Sperm motility is high between 7.0-7.4 (slightly alkaline) with increased fertilization ability while 6.4 pH (acidic) does not favor sperm motility and as well not good for semen preservation. During ejaculation, the semen protects the sperm from acidic environment of the female reproductive track. If the pH of semen is too acidic, it may damage or kill the sperm cells thereby reducing the chances of fertilization and conception. In the other hand, if the semen pH is too alkaline, it can create a hostile environment for the sperm preventing them from reaching the egg. Therefore maintaining a balanced semen pH is the key to maximum reproductive efficiency. It is important to note that pH levels can be affected by various factors such as diet, lifestyle and medication the role of CP in poultry semen pH is sketchy. However, Yahata *et al* (2014) observed no significant effect on Turkey Tom semen pH and morphology fed with graded levels of crude protein while Kabirul *et al* (2022) observed significant different in groups of ram fed with different levels of CP although he attributed the differences to the dietary composition of the ration, management system, age and body configuration of the ram. Thus, increased protein intake leads to excessive nitrogen excretion with an increased uric acid rejection, which makes the cloacal environment acidic with the consequence of reducing the quality and motility of sperm in storage (De Beer, 2009).

Impacts of Dietary Crude Protein in Poultry Spermatogenesis

Spermatogenesis is the process of sperm cell development where rounded immature sperm cells undergo successive mitotic and meiotic divisions (spermatocytogenesis) and a metamorphic change (spermiogenesis) to produce spermatozoa. The process of spermatogenesis is complicated and it involves a multitude of cellular interactions including sequential gene transcription, expression and function of the translated gene products, and control of cell function and cell to cell interactions by endocrine, autocrine and paracrine hormones, cytokines, or growth factors. The process of spermatogenesis begins when the hypothalamus releases a pulse of gonadotrophin releasing hormone that induces the release of pituitary luteinizing hormone (LH) and follicle stimulating hormone. LH stimulates Leydig interstitial cells while FSH stimulates sertoli cells to synthesize and secrete testosterone. Several factors has been reported to affect spermatogenesis but among these factors, nutrition has been shown to play a key role in the production and quality of semen because nutrition affects the endocrine and the spermatogenic function of the testis according to reproduction in farm animal textbook by Hafez (1987) and MacDonald (1980). Ahmed *et al* (2020) concluded that Amino acids and their metabolites, oils rich in n-3 polyunsaturated fatty acids, vitamin E, selenium, phytochemicals, and components that regenerate natural antioxidants can maintain testicular evolution and enhance spermatogenesis, semen quality, and fertility. Crude protein as an aspect of nutrition has been reported to affect semen quality parameters although; proteins are not energetic substrates for sperm cells Piomboni *et al.* (2011) and Ferramosca *et al.* (2014). Moreover, a high protein diet has been reported to have no significant effect on glycemic control Urner and Sakkas(2013). However, a low protein diet has been considered a potential risk factor for male infertility causing a significant reduction in testis, epididymis, and seminal vesicle weights, as well as a decrease in serum testosterone Aitken *et al.* (1995). Pamela *et al* (2022) during the course of his experiment discovered that dietary CP levels affected body development, Sertoli cell

numbers, and the number of spermatogonia in male Japanese quails, but their reproductive efficiency during the production phase was unaffected. The increased Sertoli cell numbers and the number of spermatogonia in adult birds in response to increased dietary CP during the growth phase did not affect flock fertility. This could be due to the fact that male Japanese quails naturally present high fertility rates (higher than 90%), even with decreased levels of dietary amino acids. In the contrary, Pamela et al. (2022) also observed a reduction in Leydig cell concentration per testicular unit with increased CP which suggests that testicular enlargement is not related to the number of Leydig cells but only to the number of tubular cells (spermatogonia and testis). This hypothesis is reinforced by the increase in the tubule: intertubule ratio stimulated by the increase in dietary CP. Since male fertility is essential to one day old chick production systems and is directly related to spermatogenesis. Spermatozoid production, in turn, depends on the Sertoli cell number and activity and the number of proliferating spermatogonia Alves et al. (2013).

Influence of Dietary Crude Protein in Female Poultry Sex Hormones

Sex hormones are hormones that are secreted by gonads and is involved in the regulation of sexual functions, such as the regulation of reproductive cycle and development of accessory reproductive organs. Sex hormones also refer to certain types of chemical substances that prepare an animal's body for reproduction. They are secreted by a gland or an organ. Sex hormones determine both male and female sexual characteristics and can also influence an animal's behavior. Hormones are chemical messengers in both animals and plants. In animals, they are produced by glands. Hormones travel through the blood to target tissues where the hormones act as chemical regulators. Hormones influence reproduction, growth, and overall bodily balance, among other things. Sex hormones are important to all animals, but are especially so to vertebrates (animals with a backbone) and poultry is among the vertebrates. The female poultry reproductive system in the domestic fowl consists of the ovary and the accompanying oviduct. The ovary is well endowed with blood vessels to ensure there is no hindrance to the transport of nutrients to the developing yolk. The female reproductive system produces hormones that aid in the control of body functions. These hormones include androgen, estrogen and progesterone. Androgen causes comb growth and condition and has a function in the formation of albumen, estrogen causes the growth of the female plumage, mating and nesting behavior, oviduct development together with the nutrient supply to the ovary/oviduct for egg formation while progesterone with androgen is involved in the production of albumen and the carriage of the message to the pituitary gland to release luteinizing hormone.

Nutrition in poultry is integrally linked to the hypothalamic pituitary gonadal axis. The hypothalamic-pituitary-gonadal (HPG) axis governs egg production by regulating the cyclic production of gonadotropins follicle stimulating hormone (FSH), luteinizing hormone (LH), steroid hormones and the selection of a dominant follicle for ovulation (Mikhael et al., 2019). In the hypothalamus, gonadotropin releasing hormone (GnRH) and gonadotropin inhibitory hormone (GnIH) act on the pituitary gland to either stimulate or inhibit the production of gonadotropins, respectively (Tsutsui et al., 2000; Bédécarrats et al., 2009; Bain et al., 2016). GnRH stimulates the pituitary gland to synthesize FSH and LH, which stimulates the developed gonads to synthesize sex steroids hormones for initiating sexual maturity (Tsutsui et al., 2000; Bain et al., 2016). But, GnIH inhibits the synthesis of FSH and LH. A recent research has

shown that high energy diet activated the HPG axis and stimulated the secretion of reproductive hormones in broiler breeder pullets (Hadinia et al., 2020). However, little is known on the effect of dietary crude protein on sex or steroid hormones. Protein is a very important nutrient for poultry and other classes of animals. By virtue of its amino acid constituents, protein have been found to play a significant role in growth hormones development, egg production, immunity, adaptation to environment and in many other biological function.

Effects of Crude Protein in Poultry Egg Production

Egg production is the process by which hens or pullets drop egg. Laying hens are specialized breeds of chicken that have been selected for their high rates of egg production and are different to the breeds reared for meat. Several factors have been reported to play significant role in the egg productivity of a laying bird and among all these factors, nutrition has been reported to play major role in poultry egg production. A good knowledge of poultry nutrition and modern biotechnology can provides novel nutritional approaches to closely fit the requirement of pullets and laying hens, which will consequently decrease the nutrition excretion and maintain low cost of pullets feed. Nutritional concentration of feed is very important in the poultry industry as it affects both laying performance and profitability. Laying birds require a completely balanced ration to sustain maximum egg production over time. Inadequate nutrition can cause drop in egg production. Inadequate levels of protein have been reported to cause a drop in egg production. This is why it is important to supply laying birds with the required percentage of crude protein. The role of protein on laying birds performance cannot be overemphasized. Protein is the major source of amino acids needed for maximum egg productivity. According to NRC (1994), enough crude protein is essential in laying birds diet in order to provide nonessential amino acids needed for egg production. NRC (1994), recommends 18.8%, 15.0%, or 12.5% CP in the diet of Leghorn type laying hen for feed intakes of 80, 100, or 120 g/hen per day respectively while Some breeding companies have recommended 19% to 20%g of crude protein per day for young commercial laying hens Pullet and Layer Management Guide; DeKalb Poultry Research (2012). Technically, laying hens do not have a specific requirement for CP due to variations in breeds, age or climate etc. Hence, many producers are feeding dietary protein levels far in excess of the NRC (1994) recommended level of 16 g/hen per day which is in accordance with the findings of Leeson et al., (2001) that laying hen diets are generally formulated with excess protein which increases nitrogen loss due to excretion. The findings of Lesson et al (2001) is in agreement with that of Gunawardana et al. (2008) who documented that, when testing dietary protein levels over a 12 weeks trial, increasing dietary protein would increase feed intake to provide energy needed for increased egg production caused by increased protein Numerous investigations have focused on methods of influencing egg productivity through diet manipulation during various production phases. Thus, increasing levels of protein have resulted in improvements in egg production. Shim et al (2012) observed that hens fed with high protein series of diets gained more body weight, eat more feed with better feed conversion efficiency and had much higher hen day egg production (HDEP) especially in older age when compared with published breeders' guidelines by Centurion poultry (2012). Shim further stated that Hens fed with medium series of diets laid very well with HDEP exceeding Bovans (2012) guidelines by almost 9%. While hens fed with medium protein level consumed 45g less feed per dozen eggs. The only parameter measured that was below the guidelines (Bovans, 2012) was the smaller egg weight. Because egg weight increased by 3.21 g from feeding the medium vs. low series of diets and 2.84 g from feeding the high vs. medium series, the data suggest that feeding even higher levels of protein would be

necessary for the birds to achieve breeder guidelines. Mortality was less than 2.1% during the 55 weeks trial and was the same across treatment groups with was in accordance with the reports of Lesson (1989), Pesti (1993) and Nakajima (1995) that birds fed with low protein had reduced growth and increased mortality. Similarly, Novak et al. (2008), reported that the gain in body weight from 39 to 50 weeks of age was reduced ($P \leq 0.02$) by lowering CP by 3%. In addition, Eija (2007) reported that hens fed low protein diet laid smaller eggs than hens on the high protein diet ($p < 0.001$). In the contrary, Wang et al (2017) observed no significant differences on egg production (EP), egg weight(EW), daily feed intake (DFI), feed conversion ratio (FCR), or daily egg mass (DEM) among groups from week 1 to 6 ($P > 0.05$). In addition, from week 7 to 12, the different protein ingredients did not affect the EP, EW, DFI, or FCR but significantly affected the DEM ($P = 0.04$). The above reports are indications that dietary crude protein is very crucial in maintaining sustainable egg productivity.

Effects of Protein in Egg Quality Parameters

Egg qualities are those characteristics of an egg that affect consumer acceptability and preference. Egg quality is a general term which refers to several standards which define both internal and external quality. External quality is focused on shell cleanliness, texture and shape, whereas internal quality refers to egg white (albumen) cleanliness and viscosity, size of the air cell, yolk shape and yolk strength. Egg quality is a crucial criterion for layers production with important economic implications. Poor quality eggs can to downgrading while good quality eggs can as well lead to improved value of egg production. Egg quality has an important concern in the poultry industry which can be addressed to a large extent through balanced layers ration and good management practices. Egg quality has been proven to be related to nutrition and nutrition is of outmost important because what the hen eat goes a long way to determine the frequency and quality of its egg. Since egg quality has been known to be affected by nutrition and dietary composition, excess or insufficient nutrients in hen's feed can be accountable for poor quality and deformed eggs. The diet of the laying hen is crucial in the optimization of the excellent genetic potential of modern chickens for both production performance and egg quality and nutritional approaches aiming to minimize poor quality and deformed eggs have been established. Moreover, nutrients could successfully enrich the egg in some minor components of interest for human nutrition, and by this way the nutritional quality of eggs could be increased. Protein is an aspect of nutrition that is proven to have significant impact on egg quality. It has been reported that egg size increases as dietary protein increases but however, the level of protein intake that is needed for optimum egg size have not been clearly ascertained. Leeson (1989) reported that egg size was dramatically increased as daily protein intake increased from 13.1 to 20.7 g/bird per day and egg weight was still increasing linearly at the 20.7 g level of protein intake.

Effects of Protein in External Egg Quality

External qualities of poultry egg are all the parameters that are observable with the naked eye of the consumer which includes egg weight, shell color and thickness and egg shape. Nutritional factors have been proven to have the highest effects on external quality of the egg most especially in egg shell. Several nutrients have shown significant effects on the external qualities of egg and have as such, have to be adjusted to egg quality requirements of the different breeds of laying birds. For example, Calcium, phosphorus

and vitamin D have direct effect on eggshell quality. According to (Bar et al 2002) Calcium deficiency will lead to weaker eggshell with a decrease of eggshell weight and eggshell strength. On the other hand, Diets rich in fat, unsaturated fatty acid like linoleic acid with high levels of protein and amino acids have been reported to push up egg size Ancter (2004) while Wang (2017) found no differences in the external qualities of the egg like the egg shape index, egg shell breaking strength, egg shell thickness, and egg shell toughness of birds feed with different protein sources among all treatments from week 6 to 12 ($P > 0.05$). This report supports the reports of Kim and Kang (2022) that increase in CP level did not influence hen day egg production egg weight, floor eggs, broken and dirty eggs, egg mass, feed intake, and feed conversion ratio. However, there were no significant interactions between ambient metabolizable energy (AME) and CP in the diet affecting eggshell strength, eggshell thickness, egg yolk color, or Haugh unit of the laying hens which were also not influenced by the increase in AME and CP levels in the diets. Based on the above reports, the effects of dietary crude protein in external egg qualities have not been fully ascertained.

Effects of Dietary Crude Protein In Internal Egg Qualities

Egg internal quality is an important parameter to both layers and breeders poultry farmers because to a layers farmer, egg internal quality defines the egg nutritional quality and acceptance in the market while to the breeders farmer, egg internal quality means better hatchability and good chick's quality. Internal egg quality comprises of York quality, yolk color, and albumen quality. Internal egg quality involves functional, aesthetic and microbiological properties of the egg yolk and albumen. The proportions of components for fresh egg are 32% yolk, 58% albumen and 10% shell (Leeson, 2006). A good quality egg should be free from internal blemishes such as blood spots, pigment spots and meat spots. A number of nutritional factors have been reported to affect albumen quality although Williams (1992) concluded that albumen quality is not greatly influenced by layers nutrition. Nevertheless, there are reports of albumen quality decreasing with increasing dietary protein and amino acid content Hammershoj and Kjaer (1999). In the contrary, Wang (2017) observed significant increase in yolk weight from 27 to 74 weeks of age with increase in dietary crude protein. In addition, internal egg quality which includes albumen height, Haugh unit, and yolk color were not affected by the dietary protein sources at week 6 ($P > 0.05$). At week 12 of the feeding trial, there were distinct differences in albumen height ($P = 0.03$), HU ($P = 0.02$), and yolk color ($P = 0.02$) among dietary treatments. Wang's results were in agreement with that of Gunawardana et al. (2008) that from 70 to 81 weeks of age ($P = 0.0497$), Yolk percentage was indirectly proportional to CP only in younger hens from 23 to 26 weeks of age ($P = 0.001$) while there was no consistent differences at the other ages. However, Novak et al., (2008) reported that yolk percentage was directly proportional to dietary CP ($P \leq 0.004$) during each phase, suggesting that the amino acids required for albumen synthesis may have been limited at the lower CP levels. The increase in yolk percentage was probably associated with the reduction in albumen percentage and egg size.

Effects of Dietary Crude Protein in Poultry Egg Hatchability and Fertility

Fertility and hatchability are two major parameters that highly influence the supply of day-old chicks. Fertility refers to the percentage of incubated eggs that are fertile while

hatchability is the proportion of eggs that survive to the end of incubation to produce chicks. According to King'ori, (2011) hatchability and fertility are interrelated heritable traits that varies among breeds, variety and individuals that varies in a breed and variety and Hatchability is a trait of major economic importance in the poultry industry because it has an effect on chicks output Khalid et al. (2015). There are some factors that are known to influence egg fertility and hatchability and they include lethal genes, insufficient nutrients in the egg, exposure to conditions that do not meet the needs of the developing embryo, strain, health, nutrition and age of the flock, egg size, weight and quality, egg storage duration and conditions. Among all these factor, the impact of nutrition is well understood. Abiola et al. (2018) observed that egg size can be improved to increase hatchability rate by manipulating fat levels, protein and enzymes additive. Thus, the protein characteristics of feeds are a major nutritional factor in assessing the nutritional value of feeds Ding et al. (2016) and must be considered when formulating breeder diets (Nideou, 2018). The diet of breeder poultry should be adequate in both quantity and quality in order to meet the recommended nutrient levels of each group of birds. The breeders' diet should be regulated in order to prevent excessive body weight gain which is the major cause of poor quality ejaculate and ovulation and at the extremes, early ovarian and testicular regression (Brillard, 2007). Parental nutrition can significantly influence egg and meat quality (Anton et al., 2006). Besides these factors, nutrition can impact the fertility and hatchability of the eggs. Nutritional deficiency in breeder feed can directly result in the abnormal development of the embryo (Bourin et al., 2011). Breeders' female nutrition influences its egg characteristics and is therefore extremely important for the development of the embryo and the successful hatching of high quality chicks Brand et al 2003; Vieira 2007; Kenny and Kemp 2007. According to Ravindran (2011), energy and protein are essential for egg production, hatchability and chick productivity. Zeweil et al. (2011) reported that a high protein content of the diet during lay can result in decrease in fertility and hatchability of fertile eggs in breeders which agrees with the reports of Emous (2015) that the fertility of the High Protein group was significantly lower which may be due to the excessive supply of nutrients before and during the laying phase period, which increases the deposition of the fat in the reproductive system, thereby blocking the oviduct of the hen to prevent the movement and storage of sperm (Van Emous et al., 2015). Saleh et al. (2013) in his own account observed poorer fertility on high energy-low protein (HELP) diet groups and the best hatchability on the high energy-high protein (HEHP) diets of breeders' hen. In addition, Early and late embryonic mortality were not affected by diet but mid mortality was observed on the HELP compared to HEHP diets. This agrees with the report of Emous (2015) that poultry breeders fed medium crude protein diet showed a decreased hatchability of fertile eggs caused by an increased embryonic mortality between day 18 and 21 compared to breeders fed on high crude protein and low crude protein diets. It can be deduced that high dietary crude protein diet is crucial for increased fertility and hatchability, decreased embryonic mortality, and improved offspring performance in poultry breeders, whereas decreased dietary protein level have pronounced negative effects on these factors.

Impacts of Dietary Crude Protein in Poultry Embryonic Development

Embryo development in chicken is the development of the chicken inside of the egg. Fertilization of the germinal disc by the sperm takes place in the infundibulum about 15 minutes after its holding follicle has released the yolk. Cell division to create the new embryo starts about five hours after fertilization and continues while the egg passes along the oviduct and after the egg is laid. It is generally said that the hen's egg takes 21 days of favorable incubation conditions for the chicken to develop and hatch. However, this development takes 22 days one day in the oviduct and 21 days in the incubator or nest. Proper growth and development of chicken embryo requires some macro and micronutrients because nutrient deposits in the fertile egg affect broiler embryo development and hatchling quality. Although the fertile egg has a defined nutrient composition, the rate and mechanism of absorption of these nutrients by the yolk sac membrane (YSM) and by the embryonic intestine are largely unknown. Depending on the species of the bird, about 33-86% of the egg consists of albumen while the albumen contains about 10.5% protein and 88.5% of water in domestic fowl and may be regarded as the main water source for the developing embryo. Besides carbohydrates, lipids, and inorganic ions, over 90% of the solids in the albumen are proteins. The developing embryo is completely dependent on nutrients in the egg for its growth and development. Hence, the physiological status of the chick at hatch (chick size, vigor and immune status) is greatly influenced by maternal nutrition and the chicken egg yolk, which is abundant with lipids, proteins, and minerals, is the major nutrient resource for the embryonic development. According to Emous et al (2015), maternal nutrition influences chick body weight and hatching egg composition varies with maternal nutrition, body composition, age, and strain (Nonis&Gous, 2013) which in turn also influence embryonic development and offspring performance. Moran (2007) reported that adequate deposition of protein in the egg by the hen is particularly important because towards the end of incubation it is highly used for gluconeogenesis by the embryo. Hence, nutritional deficiencies of the hen during egg formation may affect embryonic development. Hens on low protein diets produced chicks with poor growth and higher mortality than hens on high protein diets Kenny and Kemp (2007). Saleh (2018) concluded that maternal dietary energy and protein levels influenced embryonic development of FUNAAB alpha chicken and the standard or high energy high protein diets will maintain good developmental trajectory of embryos. This is in agreement with the report of Lare et al., (2021) that dietary protein of breeder guinea fowl affected embryonic development and hatchability. The feed with high protein improved the egg weight, and hatchability but reduced the rate of fertility. The feed of guinea fowl breeders with low protein content improved fertility but had a negative effect on embryonic development. Thus, since both high and low dietary maternal protein affected embryonic development, more research should be carried out to know the optimum inclusion of crude protein that will favor poultry embryonic development.

Effects of Dietary Crude Protein in Reproductive Track of Laying Hen

The reproductive system of an organism, also known as the genital track, is the biological system that is made up of all the anatomical organs involved in sexual reproduction. Many non-living substances such as fluids, hormones, and pheromones are also important accessories to the reproductive system. The female chicken has two reproductive system

which include the ovary and oviduct. Unlike most female animals, the chicken usually has only one ovary. The right ovary stops developing when the female chick hatches, but the left one continues to maturity. Left ovary is placed in the abdominal left cavity and it is fastened by the broad ligament. The ovary is characterized for having a clustered form due to the presence of numerous follicles. It contains more than 4000 microscopic ovules and only a limited number will develop and form the yolk. The oviduct has a pale pink tubular structure that goes from the ovary up to the cloaca, and it is fastened by two ligaments (dorsal and ventral). The effect of dietary crude protein on the reproductive track of laying birds has not been proven as there is no much work done to that effect but according to Emous et al. (2015), high protein intake before and after layering causes fat deposition in the reproductive system which blocks the oviduct of the hen from movement or passage of sperm. Thus, high dietary crude protein intake could be detrimental to the hen's reproductive track.

Consequences of Cp Deficiency on Poultry Nutrition

Protein deficiency results in:

- i. Decline in egg production
- ii. Thin or soft-shelled eggs
- iii. Reduced semen volume and sperm abnormalities
- iv. Lower fertility and hatchability
- v. Increased embryonic mortality
- vi. Weak chicks with low survivability

However, chronic deficiency may also impair immunity and increase susceptibility to infections.

Recommendations

In order to maximize reproductive efficiency of the breeder poultry birds using CP,

- i. Balance crude protein with digestible amino acids (lysine, methionine, threonine).
- ii. Use high-quality protein sources** (soybean meal, fish meal, synthetic amino acids).
- iii. Implement phase-feeding programs** tailored to reproductive stages.
- iv. Monitor body weight and condition** to avoid protein excess or deficiency.
- v. Use feed formulation software** to optimize nutrient profiles.

These strategies help maintain productivity and reduce feed costs.

Conclusion

Although dietary crude protein is very essential in poultry birds production, but however, excessive protein inclusion has been known to cause reduced feed intake, increased ammonia level, kidney damage, reduced egg production and abnormal growth while insufficient dietary crude protein has been reported to cause decreases egg production, reduction in male fertility and negative impacts in health. Hence, protein like every other nutrients, should be fed in moderation based on the age and purpose as both excessive and insufficient amount are dangerous to poultry birds performance and more research should

be carried out in order to ascertain the optimal level of inclusion of dietary crude protein for sustainable poultry performance, production and reproduction,

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What Determines Arable Crop Farmers Mitigation Strategies to Flood Disaster? Empirical Evidence from Imo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

In Nigeria and mainly across Imo State, flooding has become an increasingly severe and frequent environmental hazard, posing a major threat to the livelihoods of arable crop farmers. These flood events result in significant crop losses, soil degradation, and reduced farm income, thereby exacerbating food insecurity and rural poverty. Despite the growing impact of floods, many farmers in the Imo State remain highly vulnerable due to limited adaptive capacity and inadequate support systems. Empirical studies on determinants of arable crop farmers' mitigation strategies to flood disasters are relatively scanty in the study area. Without this empirical study, policymakers may find it challenges to effectively design targeted interventions to improve arable crop farmers' resilience to flood disaster. It was against these backdrops that the study was rigorously undertaken in the study area. The study identified arable crop farmers' flood disaster mitigation strategies in the study area; determined arable crop farmers' mitigation strategies to flood disaster and identified barriers arable crop farmers face in the use of mitigation strategies to flood disaster. The study utilized of cross-sectional data elicited from one-hundred and eight (108) arable crop farmers' who were purposively selected from critical farming communities in Imo State. Structured questionnaire was the main tool for data collection. Multinomial logit regression and descriptive statistics were used to analyze the gathered data. Result shows that arable crop farmers employed varieties of mitigation strategies to manage the flood disaster including constructing floodways; constructing dams; land filling; raising beds and ridges and crop diversification. The study demonstrates that sex (X_1); age (X_2); marital status (X_3); household size (X_4); educational level (X_5); membership of cooperative (X_6); access to extension agents (X_7) and farming experience (X_8) influenced the mitigation strategies of arable crop farmers to flood disaster in the study area. Furthermore, high cost of flood disaster mitigation strategies (95.00%) and inadequate knowledge on mitigation strategies (84.00%) among others were the barriers facing arable crop farmers' mitigation decisions to flood disaster in the study area. The study recommends that the arable crop farmers should take advantage of

their various cooperative societies so as to jointly pool productive resources and adapt adequately to flood disaster in the area. Ultimately, it is important that the State government to strengthen the agricultural extension service system so as to provide up-to-date modern flood disaster information, training, and capacity building to arable crop farmers mitigate adequate to flood disaster for improved yield, income, and standard of living in the study area.

Keywords: Arable Crop, Flood, Flood Disaster, Mitigation Strategies, Multinomial Logistic Regression, Barriers, Imo State and Nigeria.

Introduction

Flooding is one of the most devastating environmental challenges affecting agricultural productivity and rural livelihoods globally (Uwayisenga et al., 2024; De Brito et al., 2024). Meanwhile, flooding is the temporary overflow of water onto land that is normally dry. It occurs when the volume of water in rivers, lakes, or drainage systems exceeds their capacity due to heavy rainfall, storm surges, blocked drainage, or the release of water from dams (Ibeabuchi, 2024). In agricultural areas, flooding disrupts planting and harvesting cycles, damages crops, and degrades soil fertility. Also, flood disasters refer to severe flood events that result in widespread damage to human life, property, infrastructure, and the environment. In rural farming communities, these disasters often lead to the destruction of crops, displacement of farmers, and long-term food insecurity (Buba et al., 2021). Flooding occurs in Nigeria in three main forms which are; river flooding, urban flooding and coastal flooding (Chen et al., 2024). The heavy rainfall coupled with bad human activities about the environment and lack of drainage infrastructure in most Nigerian cities has left hundreds of people distressed and homeless (Agboola et al., 2025). It should be mentioned that flooding in cities can contaminate water supplies and intensify the spread of epidemic diseases, diarrhoea, typhoid, scabies, cholera, malaria, dysentery and other water-borne diseases (Glago, 2021). However, flooding is not entirely natural and threatens the ecosystem. Furthermore, due to man's propensity towards coastal areas and flood plains, flooding frequently has an unfavourable impact on human activities and poses a risk when it does (Guo et al., 2025). Elaborated on the causes of flood disasters around the world, including the following: Human Interaction with his environment, As was already established, human contact with the environment through industrialization, technological advancement, urbanization, deforestation, fossil fuel burning, and agricultural activities significantly contribute to flooding (Abijith et al., 2025). This is closely followed by Bad Planning: which is also the product of poor design, the building of structures on natural waterways or canals, and when humans have tried to control the water resources available to them by damming and other water control structures leading to floods (Khan et al., 2025). The socio-economic impacts are particularly pronounced among smallholder farmers who lack access to adaptive technologies or insurance mechanisms. In Nigeria, and particularly in the southeastern region including Imo State, the frequency and intensity of flood events have increased significantly due to climate change, poor land use practices, deforestation, and inadequate drainage systems (Mfon et al., 2022). For arable crop farmers whose livelihoods depend heavily on stable climatic conditions flood disasters result in severe crop losses, destruction of farmland, and heightened food insecurity (Hong et al., 2018; Ibeabuchi, 2024). In Imo State, the vulnerability of smallholder farmers is compounded by limited access to flood early warning systems, poor infrastructure, and insufficient support from extension services. As a result, farmers adopt various indigenous and modern strategies to mitigate the effects of floods. These strategies range from altering planting dates and using flood-tolerant crop varieties, to

adopting raised ridges, diversifying crops, and seeking off-farm income sources (Shoyama et al., 2020). However, the choice and effectiveness of these mitigation strategies are influenced by multiple socio-economic, environmental, and institutional factors, including education level, farm size, access to credit, farming experience, and proximity to extension services (Esiobu et al., 2023; Esiobu et al., 2025). Mitigation strategies are proactive measures taken to reduce the impact of flooding on lives, livelihoods, and infrastructure (Erick et al., 2025). Among arable crop farmers, these strategies may include: agronomic adjustments (early planting, crop rotation, and use of flood-tolerant varieties), structural measures (construction of drainage channels, raised ridges, and embankments), land use practices: avoiding cultivation on flood-prone land and practicing soil conservation), livelihood diversification (engaging in off-farm income-generating activities to reduce risk exposure) and institutional support: (accessing weather forecasts, extension services, agricultural insurance, and credit facilities) (Esiobu et al., 2020; Olumba et al., 2025). Despite the importance of understanding these determinants for policy and program design, there remains a gap in localized, empirical research especially in Imo State. Without this empirical study, policymakers may find it challenges to effectively design targeted interventions to improve arable crop farmers' resilience to flood disaster. It was against these backdrops that the study was rigorously undertaken in the study area. From the specific objectives of the study, the study determined arable crop farmers mitigation strategies to flood disaster and identified barriers arable crop farmers face in the use of mitigation strategies to flood disaster The findings will contribute to the development of targeted interventions aimed at strengthening farmers' resilience to flooding and promoting sustainable agricultural development in vulnerable communities.

Materials and Method

From November, 2024 through May of 2025, the study was conducted in Imo State of Nigeria. Imo State is located in the South Eastern zone of Nigeria and lies between latitudes 5° 45' N and 6° 35' N of the equator and longitude 6° 35' E and 7° 28' E of the Greenwich Meridian [(Nigerian Meteorological Agency (NiMET), 2020)]. The State is bordered by Abia State on the East and Northeast, Rivers State on the South, Anambra State to the North and Rivers State to the South. Imo State is divided into three (3) agricultural zones of Owerri, Orlu and Okigwe and twenty-seven (27) Local Government Areas. With a total land area of 5,530km², the State has an estimated population of about 4.8 million persons and an annual growth rate of 3.35 percent [(Nigeria Populations Commission (NPC), 2006)]. The population of Imo State varies from 230 persons per kilometer square in Oguta/Egbema areas to about 1400 persons per kilometer square in Mbaise, Mbano, Orlu and Mbaitoli areas [(National Boundary Commission (NBC) of Nigeria, 2020)]. Purposive sampling procedure was used to identify farmers in the area who cultivate arable crops as their primary source of income. Areas with high arable crop farming intensity (growing, among other things, cassava, sweet potatoes, maize, rice, melon, pepper, ginger, and yam) were chosen through the use of purposive sampling. The aggregate sample size consisted of one hundred and eight (108) farmers who cultivates arable crops. The survey was administered by trained enumerators selected across the study area. Table 1 displays the sample proportion. The main tool utilized for data collection was a structured questionnaire. In addition, multinomial logistic regression was used to examine the collected data. When a nominal outcome variable has more than two categories without a defined rank or order, a multinomial logistic regression is used (Vera, 2022). This model can be used with any number of continuous or categorical independent variables. The multinomial logit model is an extension of the binary logit model used to model categorical dependent variables with more than two categories

(Esiobu et al., 2025). A significant number of research (Esiobu et al., 2020; Belachew & Ababu, 2021; Molla et al., 2023) have modelled farmers' decisions on climate change adaptation in conjunction with their socio-economic characteristics using the multinomial logit model. The following is the formula for the multinomial logit regression that was given for the study:

If p_{ij} is the probability of y_i falling in category $j, j = 1, 2, \dots, J$, then

$$\ln\left(\frac{P_{ij}}{P_{iJ}}\right) = \alpha_j + \beta_j X_i, \quad j = 1, 2, \dots, J-1 \dots\dots\dots(1) \text{ leading to}$$

$$P_{ij} = \frac{e^{\alpha_j + \beta_j X_i}}{1 + \sum_{k=1}^{J-1} e^{\alpha_k + \beta_k X_i}}, \quad j = 1, \dots, J-1 \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

and

$$P_{iJ} = \frac{1}{1 + \sum_{k=1}^{J-1} e^{\alpha_k + \beta_k X_i}} \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

Where P = Response Probability ($J=0,1,2,3,---5$)(4)

Y = Arable Crop Farmers **Flood Disaster Mitigation Strategies** category; $J = 1, 2, \dots, 5$;

Y= Flood Disaster Mitigation Strategies of the Arable Crop Farmers variables

Y₁= Constructing floodways (dummy variable; yes = 1, no = 0)

Y₂= Constructing dams (dummy variable; yes = 1, no = 0)

Y₃= Land filling (dummy variable; yes = 1, no = 0)

Y₄= Raised Beds and Ridges (dummy variable; yes = 1, no = 0)

Y₅= Crop Diversification (dummy variable; yes = 1, no = 0)

NFDMS = No Flood Disaster Mitigation Strategies

e_i = Error term

P_{ij} = Probability response jth observation of the ith arable crop farmer

k-1 = jth observation of the ith arable crop farmer

ln = Log likelihood

J = Response category

β₁ = Estimated regression coefficients (Esiobu et al., 2025)

The explanatory variables are defined as follows:

X₁ = Sex (dummy variable; Male = 1, Otherwise = 0)

X₂ = Age (years)

X₃ = Marital Status (dummy variable; Married = 1, Otherwise = 0)

X₄ = Household size (number of persons)

X₅ = Education (years spent in school)

X₆ = Membership of Cooperative (dummy variable; Member = 1, Otherwise = 0)

X₇ = Access to Extension agents (dummy variable; Access = 1, Otherwise = 0)

X₈ = Farming experience (years)

e_i = Error term

Table 1: Sampling proportion for the Arable Crop Farmers

Agricultural Zones in Imo State	Total number of Local Government Areas (LGAs)	Total Number of Communities Selected	Total Number of Villages	Total Number of Arable crop Farmers	Total Number of Arable crop Farmers per Zone
Owerri	4 (Owerri North; Ngor-okpala; Ikeduru and Oguta)	5 (Ihitte-Ogada; Eziamana; Akabo; Awa and Eguoma)	12	3	36
Orlu	4 (Orlu; Ideato-North; Ideato-South and Orsu)	5 (Umudioka; Osina; Dikenafai; Orsu-ihitte Ukwu and Ntueke)	12	3	36
Okigwe	4 (Okigwe; Onuimo; Ehime-Mbano and Ihitte/Uboma)	5 (Ihube; Umunumo; Amakohia; Umuezegwu and Okwe)	12	3	36
Total	12	15	36	9	108

Source: Field survey data, 2025

Results and Discussion

Flood Disaster Mitigation Strategies of the Arable Crop Farmers

Figure 2 shows the various flood disaster mitigation strategies of the arable crop farmers in the study area. It shows that 90.00% of the arable crop farmers identified crop diversification as one of their flood disaster mitigation strategies in the study area. Arable crop farmers increasingly adopt crop diversification as a flood mitigation strategy to enhance resilience against climate-induced risks. Diversifying crops allows farmers to spread risk across species with varying tolerance to water stress, reducing the likelihood of total crop failure during floods (Nandi et al., 2025). For instance, integrating flood-tolerant varieties like rice with short-duration legumes or root crops ensures continued productivity despite inundation. Moreover, diversification improves soil structure and drainage, which can mitigate flood impacts over time (Primov, 2025). Economically, it stabilizes income by providing alternative sources of revenue when staple crops fail. However, this strategy may require additional knowledge, labor, and inputs, which can strain resource-limited farmers (Gawdiya et al., 2025). Policy support in training, access to improved varieties, and market integration is essential for success. Ultimately, crop diversification offers a sustainable, ecosystem-based approach to managing flood risks under

changing climate conditions. Also, 84% of the arable farmers used construction of floodways as one of their various flood disaster mitigation strategies in the study area. Arable crop farmers use floodways to channel excess water away from farmlands, reducing the risk of waterlogging and crop destruction during floods. This proactive measure enhances field drainage, protects soil integrity, and maintains timely planting and harvesting schedules [(Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) (2025)]. Properly designed floodways also recharge groundwater and support nearby ecosystems by directing overflow to designated areas (Maharjan et al., 2025). Positively, they increase farm productivity and reduce flood-related losses, improving food security and income stability. When combined with community-based planning, floodways strengthen local resilience to climate variability, making them a sustainable solution for managing flood-prone agricultural landscapes. In addition, 77% of the arable crop farmers utilized land filling as one of their various flood disaster mitigation strategies in the study area. Arable crop farmers use land filling as a flood mitigation strategy to elevate farmland, reducing vulnerability to floodwaters. By raising the soil surface, land filling prevents prolonged water stagnation, enhances drainage, and protects crop roots from submersion (Mesele et al., 2024). This method is particularly effective in low-lying or flood-prone areas, enabling continued cultivation even during heavy rainfall. Positively, it ensures more stable yields, supports year-round farming, and reduces post-flood recovery time (Faruk & Maharjan, 2022). Additionally, land filling can improve soil fertility when combined with organic materials, promoting long-term productivity and resilience in the face of climate-related flood risks. Furthermore, 62% and 12% of the arable crop farmers utilized raised bed and ridges and construction of small dams as one of their various flood disaster mitigation strategies in the study area. Arable crop farmers use raised beds and ridges to elevate crops above flood levels, enhancing drainage and preventing root waterlogging during heavy rains. Similarly, constructing small dams helps control water flow, store excess runoff, and reduce downstream flooding (Zhao et al., 2024). These strategies improve soil aeration, reduce erosion, and allow for better water management across seasons (Ritter et al., 2024). Positively, they increase crop survival, stabilize yields, and support dry-season irrigation using stored water (Jat et al., 2025). Together, they enhance resilience to climate variability, promote sustainable farming, and improve food security in flood-prone regions. The result implies that the arable crop farmers have one or more flood disaster mitigation strategies in the study area.

Socio-economic Determinants of Arable Crop Farmers Decision to Practices Flood Disaster Mitigation Strategies

The Table 2 shows determinants of arable farmers flood disaster mitigation strategies in the study area. The estimation of the multinomial logit model for this study was undertaken by normalizing one category, which is normally referred to as the “reference or base category”. In this analysis, the last category (no mitigation Strategies) is the reference category. The model was run and tested for the validity of the independence of the irrelevant alternatives (IIA) assumption by using the Hausman test for IIA. The test accepted the null hypothesis of independence of the mitigation strategies to flood disaster, suggesting that the multinomial logit specification is appropriate and a good fit to model farmers Mitigation Strategies to Flood Disaster. Results reveals a likelihood ratio chi-square (χ^2) values of 0.8837 implying that 88.37% of variation in the model for the mitigation strategies was explained by the explanatory variables while the remaining 11.63% was accounted for due to stochastic error. The model was also statistically significant at 1% ($P < 0.00001$), suggesting that the models have strong explanatory power. This indicates that all the models had good fit to the model. The significance of this likelihood ratio statistics test indicates that farmers’ socio-economic characteristics significantly influence the use of mitigation strategies for flood disaster in the area. Consequently, the interpretation and discussion of the multinomial logit result indicates the following:

Sex (X_1): Sex of the arable farmers shows that female-headed households practice mitigation strategies to flood disaster that required less-labour and energy demand to flood disaster than their male their male counterpart. The female households practiced more of crop diversification.

This is expected as crop diversification may require less- energy demand than all the mitigation strategies identified. Similarly, male-headed households were more readily resilient to flood disaster than their female counterparts in practicing constructing floodways, constructing dams, land filling and raised ridges and bed. The finding shows that the probability of use of energy demanding mitigation strategies during flood disaster was higher for males than females. Sex plays a significant role in the use of flood disaster mitigation strategies, as men and women often have different access to resources, information, and decision-making power. These differences impact the effectiveness and inclusiveness of mitigation efforts. Promoting gender-sensitive approaches enhances community resilience, as women's involvement brings diverse knowledge and priorities into planning [(United Nation (UN) Women, 2022)].

This result agrees with the study of Rotimi et al. (2025) opined that there is higher rate of practice of mitigation strategies by male farmers than their female counterpart, this is due to labour and energy demand of some mitigation measures.

Age (X₂): Age of the arable farmers significantly affected mitigation strategies to flood disaster. Age of the farmers was negative across the constructing floodways, constructing dams, land filling, and raised beds and ridges and all of the above. This reason could be because the options is labour intensive and practices more by younger farmers than their older counterpart in the study area. The result implies that a unit increase in the age of the farmers increases the likelihood of using the constructing floodways by 1.830 (18.30%), constructing dams by 0.091 (9.10%), land filling by 0.073 (7.30%), raised beds and ridges by 0.049 (4.90%). This implies that the practice of labour intensive flood mitigation measures strategies decreases as the arable farmers gets older. In contrast, older farmers often rely on traditional knowledge and may be less inclined to change established practices. This generational gap can affect the overall effectiveness of flood response and adaptation efforts. Encouraging intergenerational knowledge exchange and training improves adoption rates and community resilience. Policies targeting youth involvement in climate-smart agriculture can strengthen long-term mitigation capacity (Nurrahman & Putri, 2024). This result corroborates that of Yusuf et al. (2023) who reported that for every unit increase in age of farmers there is probability of increase in coping strategies employed. However, the result is inconsistent with the findings of Musa et al. (2024) who noted that the older farmers becomes the more risk averse and practice less strategies over time.

Marital Status (X₃): Marital status of the arable crop farmers significantly affected mitigation strategies to flood disaster. Marital status of the farmers was positive across the constructing floodways, constructing dams, Land filling, raised beds and ridges and crop diversification. The result shows that marital status have likelihood of having household members who could help to carry-out several mitigation strategies to flood disaster than their single counterpart. The result implies that a unit increase in the marital status of the arable crop farmers increases the likelihood of using the constructing floodways by 4.040 (40.40%), constructing dams by 0.007 (0.70%), land filling by 0.008 (0.80%), raised beds and ridges by 0.012 (0.12%) and crop diversification. by 0.059 (0.59%). Married individuals may also prioritize long-term resilience strategies to protect family welfare, including crop diversification and food storage. In contrast, single or widowed farmers, especially women, may face labor and resource constraints, limiting their options (UN Women, 2022). These disparities highlight the need for inclusive policies that support vulnerable groups regardless of marital status to ensure equitable access to effective

flood mitigation strategies. This finding is supported by the result of Mohammed and Favretto (2025) who asserted that married farmers tend to have easy access to production variables such as land and large family size which are traditionally owned and provided by household heads (husbands) to compliment family labour to enhance farming and reduce the cost of hired labour. The result is in line with the study of Djanibekov et al. (2024) who opined that married farmers have likelihood of adapting to mitigation strategies easily than their unmarried counterpart since they have access to labour.

Educational level (X₄): Education of the arable crop farmers was positive across all the mitigation strategies to flood disaster. This result is line with the *a priori* expectation of the model. The finding is in line with the study of Faruk and Maharjan (2022) who asserted that exposure to higher education of the farmer increases the probability of choosing different mitigation strategies to flood disaster. The probable reason is due to the fact that educated farmers have more knowledge of flood disaster and are already aware of various techniques and management practices that could be employed to adapt easily and combat the negative impacts of flood disaster in the area. Education plays a crucial role in farmers' adoption of flood disaster mitigation strategies. Educated farmers are more likely to access, understand, and implement scientific and technical knowledge, such as improved drainage systems, early warning information, and climate-resilient practices (FAO, 2025). Higher education levels enhance awareness of climate risks and the benefits of proactive adaptation. Conversely, low literacy may hinder the adoption of effective strategies, increasing vulnerability (Esiobu et al., 2025). Promoting agricultural extension services and farmer training programs can bridge knowledge gaps, ensuring that both literate and non-literate farmers are equipped to manage flood risks effectively. Additionally, the study of Maharjan et al. (2025) also confirmed the importance of education on choice of mitigation strategies to flood disaster for farmers.

Household size (X₅): Household size of the farmers was negative with constructing floodways and constructing dams and was positive with land filling and Improved storage facilities respectively. This could be that farmers may demand for additional labour for the construction of floodways and dam and utilizes family labour for land filling and raised beds and ridges and crop diversification. The result was also significant at 1% level of probability. This indicates that household size increases the probability of uptake of the identified mitigation strategies to flood disaster for arable crop farmers because it requires additional labour from the farmer which is usually provided by his/her household members. The finding tallies with the study of Mfon et al. (2022). who reported that large household size is associated with a higher labour endowment which would enable household to accomplish various agricultural tasks especially at the peak seasons and ensures ease mitigation strategies to flood disaster. Larger households often have more available labour, enabling the implementation of labor-intensive measures such as constructing ridges, floodways, or small dams (FAO, 2025). They may also diversify income sources, allowing for better resource allocation to resilience efforts. Conversely, smaller households may struggle with labor shortages and limited capacity to adopt such strategies (Abijith et al., 2025). The finding is also supported by the result of Shoyama et al. (2020) who opined that large household size has shown to provide cheap and available source of labour for farmers in mitigating easily to flood disaster.

Membership of Cooperative (X₆): Membership of cooperative had a positive and significant influence across all the mitigation to flood disaster measures modeled. The finding shows that a being a member of cooperative society increases the likelihood of practicing constructing floodways by 3.710 (37.10%) constructing dams by 7.829 (78.29%), land filling by 7.317 (73.17%) by raised beds and ridges by 3.026 (30.26%) and crop diversification by 2.729 (27.29%). Cooperatives provide access to shared resources, credit, information, and training, enabling members to implement practices such as raised beds, floodways, and crop diversification (FAO, 2025). Members benefit from collective action and knowledge exchange, improving preparedness and resilience. Additionally, cooperatives can advocate for government or NGO support during and after flood events. Conversely, non-members may lack access to these benefits, increasing their vulnerability. Promoting cooperative membership strengthens community-wide adaptation and ensures more inclusive and effective flood risk management (Esiobu et al., 2020). The study is in line with the result of Olumba et al. (2025) reported that cooperatives can pool resources together and achieve great goals which are out of reach of each farmer working alone.

Access to Extension agents (X₇): Access to extension agents had a positive and significant influence across all the mitigation to flood disaster measures modeled. The finding shows that a unit increase in access to extension agents of the farmers increases the likelihood of practicing constructing floodways by 0.084 (8.4%) constructing dams by 0.006 (0.06%), land filling by 0.047 (0.47%) by raised beds and ridges by 0.962 (9.62%) and crop diversification by 0.824 (8.24%). Access with extension agents which denotes access to information had positive effect across all adaption measures indicating that extension contact increases the likelihood of mitigating to flood disaster easily. Extension services provide an important source of information on climate change as well as agricultural production and management practices. Farmers who have significant extension contacts have better chances to be aware of changing environmental conditions and also of the various management practices that they can use to adapt to changes in environmental and flood conditions. Extension agents provide critical information, training, and technical support on practices such as flood-tolerant crop varieties, proper drainage, and soil management (FAO, 2025). Farmers with regular access to these services are more likely to adopt effective and timely interventions, reducing flood-related losses. This access enhances knowledge, builds adaptive capacity, and encourages the use of climate-smart techniques (Esiobu et al., 2023). In contrast, limited extension access can lead to poor preparedness and ineffective responses. Strengthening extension services is vital for building resilience among smallholder farmers. The findings is in line with the study of Primov (2025) argued that extension contact enhance farmers production and promote their knowledge on modern farming methods.

Farming experience (X₈): Farming experience had a positive and significant relationship across all the mitigation to flood disaster measures modeled This implies that increase in years of farming experience increases the probability of uptake of practicing constructing floodways, constructing dams, land filling, raised beds and ridges, and crop diversification. Highly experienced farmers are likely to have more information and knowledge on changes in flood and environmental conditions than their counterpart with less years of experience. In addition, experience exposes farmers' to various flood management practices that they could employed in the face of anticipated environmental situation. Farming experience plays a vital role in the

adoption of flood disaster mitigation strategies. Experienced farmers often possess valuable indigenous knowledge and historical understanding of local flood patterns, enabling them to implement effective, context-specific strategies such as early planting, crop rotation, or raised beds (FAO, 2025). Their familiarity with past flood events enhances risk perception and preparedness. However, excessive reliance on traditional practices may limit openness to innovative, science-based solutions (Abijith et al., 2025). Integrating experiential knowledge with modern extension services can enhance adaptation effectiveness, improving resilience across generations and farming systems (Esiobu, 2021). The findings shares view with the study of Esiobu (2024) who opined that as the number of years a farmer has spent in the farming business may give an indication of the practical knowledge he has acquired on how he can overcome certain inherent farm production problems, which include the vagaries of weather and environmental situation.

Table 2: Estimated Multinomial Logit Regression of the Determinants of Arable Crop Farmers' Mitigation Strategies to Flood Disaster

Independent Variables	Constructing Floodways	Constructing Dams	Land Filling	Raised Beds and Ridges	Crop Diversification
Sex (X₁)	5.258 (-2.836)***	5.521 (-2.372)**	5.832 (-2.103)**	-5.111 (-2.021)*	5.023 (2.810)***
Age (X₂)	1.830 (-3.320)***	0.091 (-3.002)***	0.073 (-3.107)***	0.049 (-3.804)**	0.093 (3.094)***
Marital Status (X₃)	4.040 (2.092)**	0.007 (4.975)***	0.008 (3.964)***	0.012 (0.732)	0.059 (2.613)***
Household size (X₄)	-0.0724 (-2.861)***	-0.0035 (-2.011)*	0.927 (1.350)*	0.083 (0.728)	-0.039 (-2.592)***
Educational Level (X₅)	0.0085 (3.083)***	0.0059 (2.602)***	0.0852 (2.927)8***	0.038 (3.850)***	0.073 (3.742)***
Membership of Cooperative (X₆)	3.710 (2.016)**	7.829 (1.847)*	7.317 (1.729)	3.026 (2.763)***	2.729 (2.950)***
Access to Extension agents (X₇)	0.084 (3.842)***	0.006 (1.729)*	0.047 (1.918)*	0.962 (2.980)***	0.824 (3.820)***
Farming Experience (X₈)	0.930 (3.023)***	0.088 (5.830)***	0.939 (4.470)***	0.054 (3.600)***	0.069 (4.010)***

UAES FIRST INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS, 2025.

Pseudo R²	96.200*
Likelihood Chi square	88.37
Sample Size (n)	108
Reference / Base Category	No Flood Disaster Mitigation Strategies

Computer Printout of SPSS; Values in parenthesis are Z-Values; *** Significant at 1% level, ** Significant at 5% level, * Significant at 10% level;
Field Survey, 2025

Barriers of Arable Crop Farmers' in Use of Flood Mitigation Strategies to Flood Disaster

Figure 2 illustrates the barriers of arable crop farmers' in use of flood mitigation strategies to flood disaster in the study area. It demonstrates that 95.00% of the arable crop farmers identified high cost of flood disaster mitigation strategies as one of the barriers they face in use the use of flood mitigation strategies to flood disaster in the study area. The high cost of flood disaster mitigation strategies often limits adoption by arable crop farmers, especially smallholders with constrained financial resources. Measures such as constructing floodways, raised beds, or small dams require significant investment in labour, materials, and technology (Mfon et al., 2022). As a result, many farmers rely on low-cost, less effective strategies or do nothing, increasing their vulnerability to flood impacts. This financial barrier hampers resilience, leading to repeated crop losses and income instability. Enhancing access to subsidies, credit, and community-based funding mechanisms is essential to support widespread adoption of effective flood mitigation strategies (Maharjan et al., 2025). In the same way, inadequate knowledge on mitigation strategies (94.00%) were identified by the arable crop farmers as one of the barriers they face in use the use of flood mitigation strategies to flood disaster. Inadequate knowledge of flood disaster mitigation strategies significantly hinders arable crop farmers' ability to prepare for and respond to flood events. Many farmers lack awareness of effective techniques such as raised beds, early warning systems, and water diversion methods due to limited education or poor access to extension services (Erick et al., 2025). This knowledge gap leads to ineffective or delayed responses, increasing crop losses, soil degradation, and food insecurity. The absence of training also reduces farmers' willingness to adopt new technologies [(International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI), 2022)]. Strengthening farmer education and extension outreach is critical for building resilience and ensuring informed decision-making in flood-prone areas. More so, limited availability of farmland (75.00%) and high cost of labour (60.00%) were stated by the arable crop farmers' as the barriers they face in use of flood mitigation strategies to flood disaster. Limited availability of farmland and high labour costs significantly constrain arable crop farmers' ability to implement effective flood disaster mitigation strategies. Scarce land forces farmers to cultivate flood-prone areas, increasing exposure to crop damage (Djanibekov et al., 2025). Meanwhile, high labor costs deter the adoption of labour-intensive measures such as constructing floodways, ridges, or drainage systems (IFPRI, 2022). These constraints reduce farmers' capacity to adapt, leading to repeated crop losses, soil degradation, and reduced income. Promoting mechanization, community labour sharing, and land-use planning can help address these challenges and enhance resilience to flood risks in vulnerable farming communities. Ultimately, poor extension agents contact (46.00%) were stated by the arable crop farmers' as the barriers they face in use of flood mitigation strategies to flood disaster in the study area. Poor contact with extension agents limits arable crop farmers' access to timely and accurate information on flood disaster mitigation strategies. Without regular interaction, farmers may lack awareness of effective practices such as flood-tolerant crops, proper drainage systems, or early warning signs (Olorunfemi et al., 2021). This knowledge gap results in low adoption of adaptive measures, increasing vulnerability to flood-related crop failures and income loss. Poor extension

outreach also reduces trust in new technologies and slows behavioral change (Antwi-Agyei & Stringer, 2021). Strengthening extension services through increased staffing, mobile outreach, and farmer field schools is crucial to improving resilience in flood-prone farming communities. There is no denying that these barriers might be responsible for poor mitigation to flood disaster by arable crop farmers in the study area. Addressing these barriers will be key to improving adaptive capacity of arable crop farmers' and enhancing yield, income, standard of living of the arable crop farmers' in the study area.

Figure 2: Barriers of Arable Crop Farmers' in Use of Flood Mitigation Strategies to Flood Disaster

Conclusion

Flooding remains a major threat to arable crop production in Imo State. Farmers' responses to flood risks are shaped by both individual characteristics and institutional support systems. The study has empirically demonstrated that flood disaster is still evident in the study area and arable crop farmers' are observing this evidence and have started utilizing several flood disaster mitigation strategies to reduce the negative effect of flood disaster in their arable crop production. Some of the flood disaster mitigation strategies arable crop farmers' used were constructing floodways; constructing dams; land filling; raised beds and ridges and crop diversification. The study also found how different socioeconomic factors significantly influenced arable crop farmers' decisions to mitigate to flood disaster in the study area. The findings further indicate that the following socio-economic factors influenced the flood disaster mitigation strategies of

arable crop farmers' in the study area: sex (X_1), age (X_2), marital status (X_3), household size (X_4), educational level (X_5), membership of cooperative (X_6), access to extension agents (X_7) and farming experience (X_8). Therefore, these factors are crucial when formulating policies meant to increase the adaptive capacity of producers of arable crops. Additionally, the following flood disaster mitigation strategies constructing floodways; constructing dams; land filling; raised beds and ridges crop diversification were used by the arable crop farmers' to mitigate the flood risks. The study finds that socioeconomic factors significantly shape arable crop farmers' decisions to adopt strategies like crop diversification, raised beds, land filling, and the construction of small dams. Farmers of arable crops also had to deal with a number of obstacles that prevented them from implementing flood disasters mitigation strategies. These limitations include, but are not limited to, the high cost of adapting to flood disaster, the lack of understanding about these tactics, the high cost of labour, and the poor extension contact. The study concludes that enhancing education, extension services, and resource accessibility is crucial to increasing the adoption of effective flood mitigation strategies. Institutional and policy support play a pivotal role in shaping farmer resilience.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the major findings of the study.

- i. The finding found that there were poor contact between arable crop farmers and extension agents. Hence, the government should strengthen agricultural extension service so as to Increase the frequency and quality of farmer-agent interactions to improve knowledge transfer on flood mitigation strategies in the study area.
- ii. The government should support and promote farmer cooperatives as these would improve group-based approaches to enhance resource sharing, training access, and collective action toward flood management, yield, income and standard of living.
- iii. The arable crop farmers' identified the high cost of adapting to flood disaster as one of their barriers to flood disaster mitigation in the study area. Therefore, the government should reduce financial barriers by subsidizing or offering low-interest loans for implementing structural measures like floodways and raised beds.
- iv. The government should improve infrastructure and land access as the Support land-use planning and rural infrastructure will make arable crop farmers', flood-prone areas more resilient and accessible.

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Assessment of Soil Organic Carbon Spatial Patterns in Water-Stable Aggregate Fractions in Continuously Cultivated Croplands on Various Parent Materials

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Abstract

A study was carried out on soil geo-referenced and sampled at 0-100cm depth in continuously cultivated croplands to evaluate the potential of various aggregates size fractions (> 2.00, 0.50-1.00, 0.25-0.50, <0.25mm) to sequester carbon under different parent materials and croplands in southern Nigeria, using geospatial techniques. Soil samples were collected from continuously cultivated croplands with varying parent materials: Cassava/Maize/*Telferia* (CCC-CMTF) on Coastal Plain Sands, Cassava/Maize/*Telferia* (CCC-CMTIF) on Alluvium, Cassava/Maize/Okra (CCC-CMO) on Imo Clay Shale, Cassava/Maize/Yam (CCC-CMY) on Coastal Plain sands, Cassava/Maize/Melon (CCC-CMM) on Shale. Results revealed that SOC content had low ($p < 0.05$) concentration in fractions >0.50 mm whereas, higher ($p < 0.05$) concentration was observed in fractions <0.50 mm across the parent materials and croplands. Semi-variogram indicated that SOC in aggregate size fractions was variable. Nugget variance (C_0) range was (0.061- 0.942). Coefficient of determination (R^2) of predicted SOC content were >0.50, which showed a good fit. Low (0.31-0.572) root mean square error (RMSE) showed that theoretical model was adequate patterns of SOC content. It therefore implies that SOC were sequestered majorly in small-sized aggregate (0.25- 0.50 mm), and micro-aggregates (<0.25 mm) in CCC-CMTF, CCC-CMM, CCC-CMO, CCC-CMY, and CCC-CMTI. These emphasize significance of considering both parent materials and cultural practices in managing SOC in Croplands in Southern Nigeria. Sustainable soil management practices (crop rotation, Organic manure application etc.) should be encouraged in the study area. This will promote soil aggregation and C sequestration in aggregate size fractions, thereby enhancing soil health and productivity, leading to food security.

Keywords: SOC sequestration, Aggregate Sizes, Parent materials, Croplands, Geospatial techniques

Introduction

Soil organic carbon (SOC) is an important component of the soil ecosystem, playing a vital role in soil fertility, carbon sequestration, and overall soil health. It is well recognized that the spatial distribution of SOC within the soil profile is highly heterogeneous, influenced by a variety of biotic and abiotic factors such as soil texture, Land use practices, climate and topography (Ibe, 2021). In arable soils, the management practices adapted by farmers, including tillage, crop rotation, and application of organic amendments, can significantly impact the distribution and

storage of SOC (Amanzeet *al.*2025). Adequate understanding of SOC distribution in cultivated croplands is essential for implementing effective conservation practices and sustainable management strategies to enhance soil health and food security, while mitigating the effects of climate change (Amanzeet. *al.*, 2024a). According to Amanzeet. *al.*2024b), soil organic carbon plays a pivotal role in soil health, fertility and ecosystem functioning. It is an essential component of the soil that contribute to soil structure, water holding capacity, nutrient availability and overall soil health. Ibe (2025) agreed that spatial distribution and dynamics of SOC in soil aggregates is important for assessing soil quality, carbon sequestration potential, and sustainable land management practices.

In cultivated soils, SOC is often affected by land management practices such as tillage, cropping system, fertilization, and irrigation (Backlund, 2008; Bird, 2015). Continuous cultivation of Agricultural lands can lead to the depletion of SOC, which in turn can impact soil fertility, crop productivity, and ecosystem services. The distribution of SOC in different aggregate fractions is an important indicator of SOC in soil (FAO, 2002; Garage *et. al.*2003). Soil aggregates are formed through physical, chemical, and biological processes that result in the aggregation of soil particles into distinct size fractions. In particular, water-stable aggregates are aggregates that are resistant to breakdown when subjected to wetting and drying cycles, making them important for soil structure and carbon sequestration (Xieet. *al.* 2012; Olayeet. *al.*, 2016).

One of the key aspect of SOC distribution in Agricultural soils is it's association with soil aggregates, which are structurally defined units of soil particles held together by organic matter, clay minerals, and other binding agents. Soil aggregates play a crucial role in determining soil physical and chemical properties, including porosity, water retention, and nutrient availability (Igwe and Obalum, 2013). Among the various aggregate fractions present in the soil, water-stable aggregates are particularly important as they are resistant to mechanical breakdown and water erosion, this serving as reservoirs for SOC storage and protection against soil degradation (Ibeet. *al.* 2025; Lal, 2015).

Lal (2005) and Amanzeet *al.*(2024b) noted that size distribution and stability of soil aggregates are influenced by soil management practices, such as tillage intensity, crop residue management, and soil amendments. Intensive tillage practices, such as plowing and cultivation, can disrupt soil aggregates and accelerate the decomposition of organic matter, leading to a decline in SOC stocks and soil fertility. On the other hand, Ibeet *al.* (2025) reported that conservation tillage practices, such as minimum tillage or no-till, can enhance soil aggregation in stable aggregates. Therefore, characterizing the spatial distribution of SOC within different aggregate fractions can provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of various land management practices in enhancing SOC stocks and improving soil quality in cultivated croplands.

Lal (2004) stated that in addition to soil management practices, parent material of the soil also plays a significant role in determining the spatial pattern of SOC distribution in Agricultural soils. Different parent materials in the tropical rainforest, such as sandstone, Shale, Coastal plains and basement complex or limestone, etc. posses distinct mineralogical and chemical properties that influence soil formation processes, nutrient availability, and microbial activities. Igwe and Obalum (2013)reported that these different in parent material can result in variations in soil properties, including SOC content, aggregation dynamics, and water retention capacity. Therefore, assessing the spatial distribution of SOC in water-stable aggregate fractions on various parent materials can provide valuable insights into the interactions between soil mineralogy, land use practices, and SOC sequestration in cultivated croplands.

Improved water-stable aggregate fractions in soils are essential for C sequestration. Hence, improvement of water-stable aggregates is a useful strategy for mitigating increase in concentration of atmospheric CO₂ (Bird, 2015). Human activities related to soil management and cultural practices that leads to the breakdown of soil aggregates and/or inhibits aggregate formation, have contributed to the buildup of carbon dioxide (CO₂) to the atmosphere and various degrees of soil degradation (IPCC, 2001; Lal 2004, 2015; Okebalama, 2016 and World Bank, 2012). During the past 150 years, land use and soil ecosystem disturbance were responsible for one third of all human emissions of CO₂ (Shahmiret *et al.*, 2017; Meng-Yuh and Shoa, 2014). Land cover removal and inappropriate soil management are responsible for overall soil nutrient depletion and erosion (Olayeet *et al.*, 2016; Zachary and James, 2013). Over the next 100 years, global land use system, land cover removal and inappropriate soil management and cultural practices are likely to account for at least 10 percent of overall human caused CO₂ emission and environmental degradation (Baldyga, 2005; Backhund, 2008; EPA, 2008 and IPCC, 2000, 2007). The dominant drivers of current and past land use related emission of CO₂ are the conversion of forest and grassland to crop and pasture land and the depletion of soil carbon, through agricultural tillage system and longterm continuously cultivation of soil. (Ding *et al.*, 2016; Linsieret *et al.*, 2013; Onweremaduet *et al.*, 2011 and FAO, 2002).

Bhumiaet *et al.* (2016) and Lal (2005; 2007) demonstrated that land use and management practices can alter the distribution of organic C and N among labile and stable pools with kinetically different turnover rates. For example, intensive cultivation of grassland reduces the SOC and SON because of the destruction of soil macroaggregates by different levels of tillage (Wei *et al.*, 2013 and Liguanget *et al.*, 2016). According to Lugatoet *et al.*, (2009) biomass production which is an important determinant of C pool and fluxes depends on land use and management consequently, conversion of natural (TRF and TS) ecosystems to agricultural land use (plantation, pastoral and cropland) has a drastic impact on C pool and emissions of GHGs to the atmosphere. Tillage also results in partial aggregate destruction and concomitant OM loss (Chem, 2000, FAO, 2002 and Ayoubiet *et al.*, 2011). Furthermore, a general increase in C levels ($235 \pm 113 \text{Kg CGa}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$) was observed under minimum or no-till system (NT) compared with conventional tillage system (CT) in tropical and temperate soils (Lal, 2017).

Bianco-anquiet *et al.* (2007) found that SOC concentration explained 48% to 86% in aggregate wetting. Xueqiet *et al.* (2016) recognized the important role OM plays in soil particle aggregation and consequently reported that part of the aggregate size variation indices in tropical soils can be attributed to the variation in the OM content. They further observed that a soil that is low in OC will be poorly aggregated since the weight and the content of OC in the >2.00mm size class is lower than the weight and content of OC of other classes. Microaggregates have a lower OM concentration than macroaggregrate stability after cultivation and most pronounced in soil macroaggragtes, while the stability of soil microaggregates remains unchanged (Houghton, 2003; John *et al.*, 2004; Knopes and Tilman, 2000). Kutschet *et al.* (2009) reported that OC does not influence microaggregate stability greatly when the values of SOC are low and do not reach critical limits. Leifeld (2013) observed that the OM contents of microaggregates obtained by dry-sieving were closely related to their clay and silt contents. The findings by Li *et al.* (2013); Li *et al.* (2002) and Liu *et al.* (2014) and Christensen and Sorensen (1985) showed that C and N are associated with finer soil particles, and these particles may vary among different aggregate fractions. Martens et al (2004) reported a significant positive relationship ($r^2 = 0.79$) between WSA and fPOM/SOM. Motavalliet *et al.* (2000) and Osher *et al.*, (2003) reported that on some north central Italian soils, in terms of total content, C.N. and P were preferentially concentrated

in the macroaggregates. Parfiltet *al.* (2003) reported that aggregation was significantly greater at 0-5cm depth with no-tillage (NT) and ridge tillage, especially in the > 4750 and 500-212 μm size classes where aggregate C and N contents were as much as 60% and > 100% respectively, more C and N were retained in the > 4750 μm size fraction at the 10-15cm depth. Shrestha *et al.* (2007). Showed that macroaggregates in the surface layers of Nepal soil contained 14.9 to 24.8 and 5.5 to 20.7 gkg^{-1} SOC in cultivated and forest soils respectively, while microaggregates contained 12.5 to 30.8 and 11.9 to 25.4 gkg^{-1} SOC, respectively.

Quantification of the impacts of land use and soil cultural/management practices on carbon stocks, soil aggregation and aggregate stability in southern Nigeria is challenging because of the spatial heterogeneity of soil, climate, cultural/management conditions, and due to the lack of data on soil carbon pools of most common agro-ecosystems. Furthermore, the impact of C sequestration on greenhouse gases and agricultural sustainability has not been well elucidated at regional, national or global scales. Some available statistics are generally based on extrapolation. Improvement in the data base on the concentration of SOC needed to be validated with ground truth measurement/assessment as the use of reliable data is essential for developing techniques of soil management and identifying policy options needed for promoting appropriate measures.

Geospatial techniques, including remote sensing, geographic information systems, (GIS), and spatial analysis, offer powerful tools for mapping and analyzing the spatial distribution of SOC in Agricultural soils (Ibe, 2021; Bhunia *et al.* 2016). These techniques allow for the integration of soil data with environmental factors, such as topography, climate, and land use, to identify patterns and trends in SOC distribution. By combining field -based soil sampling with geospatial analysis, researchers can develop detailed maps of SOC content in soil aggregates and assess the factors influencing its spatial variability.

Quantification of SOC within aggregates size classes permits evaluation of aggregation under different soil management systems and its contribution to the accumulation and loss of SOM (Sotomayor-Ramirez *et al.*, 2006; Calero *et al.*, 2008). The relevance of this study is to generate reliable information which is essential for developing techniques of soil/land management systems and for recommendation sequestration for sustainable agriculture and erosion control leading to advancement in food security and consequently, mitigate global warming, using five (5) location in the southern agro-ecological zones of Nigeria. The general aim of the study was to assess the spatial pattern of soil organic carbon in water-stable aggregate fractions in continuously cultivated croplands on various parent materials in Southern Nigeria using ordinary kriging interpolation techniques. The general aim of this study is to carry out the assessment of soil organic carbon spatial pattern in water-stable aggregate fractions in continuously cultivated croplands on various parent materials, southern Nigeria. This aim will be achieved through the following specific objectives. To;

- i. determine the influence of parent materials and continuous cultivation on soil physico-chemical properties
- ii. assess soil organic carbon spatial pattern in water-stable aggregate fractions (>2.00 mm, 1.00- 2.00 mm, 0.50 -1.00 mm, 0.25 -0.50 mm, <0.25 mm)

Materials and Method

Description of the Study Area

Geographically, southern Nigeria refers to the area bounded within latitudes 10°28' North of the equator and longitude 5°25' and 8°51' East of the Greenwich Meridian, occupying a land area of about 282,672.48km² or about 30.6% of the total land area of Nigeria. It represents about 75.02million or 39.3% of the population of Nigeria (Monanu, 1975; and Ofomata, 1975) (Fig 1).

Figure 1: Georeferenced Map of the Study Area showing Sampling Locations

Table 1: Sample Sites Under Different Parent Materials and Arable Croplands at the Selected Research Institutions and River Basin Development Authorities across the study area

Parent material	Soil Unit No	Soil Sample Site	Land Utilization type	Latitude	Longitude	Elevation (M)
CPS-FRIN-Isieke	FRN-01	Arable Cropland	Cassava/Maize/telferia mixed crop	05°25'00"N	07°31'34"E	162
	FRN-02	Arable Cropland	Cassava/Maize/telferia mixed crop	05°25'31"N	07°31'15"E	162
	FRN-03	Arable Cropland	Cassava/Maize/telferia mixed crop	05°24'49"N	07°31'50"E	173
L-NIHORT-Okigwe	NIH-04	Arable Cropland	Cassava/Maize/Melon Mixed Crop	05°49'21"N	07°18'24"E	177
	NIH-05	Arable Cropland	Cassava/Maize/Melon Mixed Crop	05°42'36"N	07°18'40"E	172
	NIH-06	Arable Cropland	Cassava/Maize/Melon Mixed Crop	05°51'59"N	07°18'40"E	171
CS-AIRBDA Agbala	AIB-07	Arable Cropland	Cassava/maize/Okra mixed crop	05°17'40"N	07°05'42"E	110
	AIB-08	Arable Cropland	Cassava/maize/Okra mixed crop	05°18'01"N	07°05'50"E	98
	AIB-09	Arable Cropland	Cassava/maize/Okra mixed crop	05°18'12"N	07°05'28"E	10
CPS-NDBDA-Kpong	NDB-10	Arable Cropland	Cassava/maize/yam mixed crop	04°40'13"N	07°05'42"E	30
	NDB-11	Arable Cropland	Cassava/maize/yam mixed crop	04°40'08"N	07°05'50"E	30
	NDB-12	Arable Cropland	Cassava/maize/yam mixed crop	04°40'42"N	07°05'28"E	26
V-NDBDA-Isiokolo	NDB-13	Arable Cropland	Cassava/maize/Telferia mixed crop	05°28'17"N	06°00'10"E	25
	NDB-14	Arable Cropland	Cassava/maize/Telferia mixed crop	05°28'05"N	05°59'55"E	17
	NDB-15	Arable Cropland	Cassava/maize/Telferia mixed crop	05°28'00"N	05°59'40"E	22

There are six major geological materials from which the soils of southern Nigeria are derived from. Namely: alluvium, coastal plain sands of Benin formation; upper coal measures of Nsukka formation; sandstones of Ajali formation, lower coal measures of many formation; shale of Bende Ameki formation and Imo clay shale of Imo formation (Jungerius, 1964, Lekwa and Oparaugo, 1984; Ojanuga, 1977 and Igweet *al.*, 2005). The soil type of the study area are dominantly ultisols (USDA Classification) or Acrisols (FAO/UNESCO Classification) (Lekwa and Whiteside, 1986; Igweet *al.*, 1995; Okpamenet. *al.*, 2013; Nuga, 2009 and Ahaiweet *al.*, 2010).

The freshwater swamp and the tropical rainforest area have bimodal rainfall distribution pattern but with less intensity and clear distribution between wet and dry seasons in the tropical rainforest (Imo and Abia States). The fresh water swamp and tropical rainforest have average rainfall of 2500mm and 2350mm respectively (NIMET, 2018 and NDBDA, 2019). Air temperatures in southern Nigeria are generally high all year round. The mean maximum temperature of the area is 32°C while the mean minimum is 21°C, given an annual range of about 11°C. February and March are usually the hottest months, while July and September records the

lowest temperature (Enwezoret *al.*, 1990; NIMET, 2017 and Ofomata, 1975). The study area is endowed with an annual average daily sunshine of 6.25 hours ranging from 3.5 hours at the coastal area and 9.0 hours at the far northern boundary. Their minimum and maximum hours of sunshine amount to 0.1 and 9.9 hours respectively (Uguru *et al.*, 2011, NIMET, 2008 and Odurukweet *al.*, 1995). Similarly, it has annual daily solar radiation of about 2.25Kwh/m²/day varying between 3.5Kwh/m²/day at the coastal area and 7.0Kwh/m²/day at the northern boundary (NIMET, 2008 and Abia State official Gazette, 1992). Relative humidity over southern Nigeria ranges from 65% to 92% at the coastal area (Rivers and Delta States) through 82% at the central area (Abia and Imo States) to 95% toward the north (Enugu and Ogoja) areas (NIMET, 2008 and 2017). Evaporation is generally high in southern Nigeria because of the relatively high value of isolation and temperature (NIMET, 2008 and 2017).

The vegetation of the experimental area is typical of tropical rainforest vegetation. The secondary bush which dominates the area are the remnant of the typical rainforests which are fast disappearing in the area, some of the forest species found in the area especially in the alley crop portion include, oil bean (*Pentaclethramarcophyllum*), oil palm (*Elaeisguinensis*), plantain/banana (*Musaspp*), raffia palm (*Raphiaspp*). Grasses and brown leaf weeds that dominate the entire area include *Panicummaximum*, *Pennisetumpurperium*, *Aspilliaafricana* etc. The major tuber and root crops mostly grown on ridges and mounds in the area include cassava (*Manihotesculanta*), yam (*Discoreaspp*), sweet potato (*Ipomoeabatatas*) and cocoyam (*Xanthosomanassagottofolium*), maize (*Zea mays L*) melon (*Citrullusvulgaris*) and vegetables such as okra (*Hisbiscusesculentus*) and *Fluttedpumpkin (Telferiaspp)*. There were longer stand rotation in the horticultural and managed forest tree plantations. There were also mulching in the horticultural plants and prunings in the managed forestry tree plantations.

Field Studies and Sample Collection

Stratified random sampling as modified by Smith (1976), was used in the field. Soil samples were collected at 5 sites within 5 locations under four (4) LUTs. Soil samples were collected at the following locations: Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria (FRIN), Isieke; National Horticultural Research Institute (NIHORT), Okigwe and Niger Delta Basin Development Authority (NDBDA), Isiokolo; Niger Delta Basin Development Authority (NDBDA), Kpong and Anambra-Imo River Basin Development Authority (AIRBDA), Agbala. The LUTs are shown in (Table1).

A global positioning system (GPS) was used to locate each sampling point to generate their area and coordinates for further geostatistical soil spatial analysis(ordinary kriging). Three mini-pits (0.5m x 0.5m x 1m) were dug in each of the sample sites. A total of 15 soil samples were collected from geo-referenced point of 0-100cm sampling depth from each sample point for chemical analysis. Additional 15samples were collected at each depth for the determination of bulk density. In general, 30 soil samples were collected.

Physical properties

Particles size analysis of <2mm fine earth fractions were carried out to determine the soil texture by the hydrometer method as described by Gee and Bander (1986), using sodium hydroxide as the dispersing agent, and with deionized water alone for the determination of water dispersible clay and silt. Bulk density measurement was obtained by the cylindrical core method as described by Blacke and Hantge (1986), which was used to calculate soil organic carbon (SOC) on an area basis.

$$\text{Bulk density} = \frac{\text{Mass of oven dry soil (g)}}{\text{Volume of bulk soil (cm}^3\text{)}} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

Saturated hydraulic conductivity (Ksat) of the soils was calculated using Darcy’s equation provided by Young (2001):

$$K_{\text{sat}} = \frac{QL}{AT\Delta H} \dots\dots\dots(2)$$

Where Q, L, A, ΔH, and T in the equation represent quantity of water discharged (cm³), length of soil column (cm), Interior cross-sectional area of the soil column (cm), head pressure different causing the flow or hydraulic gradient, and time of water flow (s), respectively.

Chemical properties

Soil pH was determined in distilled water and potassium chloride solution at ratio 1:1 and 1:2.5 soil/water suspension using pH meter (Mclean, 1982). Soil organic carbon content of the whole soil and that associated with the various water-stable aggregate fractions were quantified by Walkley and Black wet oxidation method as described by Nelson and Sommers (1982).

Total nitrogen content of the bulk soil and that associated with the three soil depth were determined by the macro kjeldahl digestion method using CuSO₄ and Na₂SO₄ catalyst mixture (Bremmer and Mulvaney, 1982). Electrical conductivity (EC) was determined by Jackson (1958). Exchangeable potassium (K) was determined by Muhret. *al*(1965). Available Phosphorus was determined by Bray and Kurtz (1945). Cation exchange capacity (CEC) was determined by the NH₄OAC (Ammonium acetate) at pH 7 methods (Thomas, 1982).

Statistical and Spatial Analyses

Data collected from the study were subjected to the Analyses of variance. Separation of means for significant difference was performed using the F-LSD procedure as stated by Obi (1986).

More detailed spatial analysis using GIS analysis was carried out in the Cartographic/GIS laboratory of the Department of geography and environmental management, university of Port-Harcourt, Rivers state, Nigeria. Ordinary kriging (OK) method was used in ArcGIS10.1 environment to describe the spatial structures of the spatial maps of the SOC concentration in WSA (Bhunia*et. al.* 2016; Ibe, 2021). Five (5) predictive spatial maps were generated using best fit semi-variogram with ordinary kriging. The generated predictive maps were used to describe the spatial variability of soil organic carbon content for the continuously cultivated croplands at 0-100cm depth. The OK interpolation method was used for prediction of the values of the un-sampled locations X₀ by assuming the Z* (X₀) equals the sum of the known measured value (field measured value). Kriging process was calculated by the following equation (Wang, 1999).

$$Z^*(X_0) = \sum_{i=1}^n \lambda_{iz}(x_i) \dots\dots\dots(3)$$

Where: Z* (X₀) = predicted value at position X₀, Z (x_i) = known value at sampling site X_i

λ_i= weighting coefficient of the measured site

n = The number of sites within the neighbourhood searched for interpolation.

Semivariograms were used as the basic tool to examined the spatial distribution structure of the soil organic carbon content. Based on the regionalized variable theory and it intrinsic hypotheses (Neslen and Wendroh, 2003), a semivariogram is expressed as:

$$Y(h) = \frac{1}{2N(h)} \sum_{i=1}^n [Z(x_i) - Z(x_i + h)]^2 \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

Where: $Y(h)$ = Semivariance, h = Lag distance, Z = parameter of the soil property; $N(h)$ = number of pairs of locations separated by a lag distance h ; $Z(x_i)$ and $Z(x_i + h)$ = values of Z at position X_i and $X_i + h$ (Wang and Shao, 2013).

The empirical semivariograms obtained from the data were fitted by theoretical semivariogram models to produce geostatistical parameters, including nugget variance (C_0), structure variance (C_i), sill variance ($C_0 + C_i$), and distance parameter (λ). The nugget/sill ratio, $C_0/(C_0 + C_i)$, was calculated to characterize the spatial dependency of the values. In general, a nugget/sill ratio <25% indicates strong spatial dependency and >75% indicates weak spatial dependency; otherwise, the spatial dependency is moderate (Cambardella *et al.*, 1994).

Results and Discussion

Mean Value of Soil Physico-Chemical Properties

Mean data on soil Physico-Chemical properties of the study area are presented in Table 2. Alluvial soils of Niger Delta Basin Development Authority at Isiokolo (ALV-NDBDA-Isiokolo) under continuously cultivated croplands of Cassava/Maize/Melon (CCC-CMM) had significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher sand (80.31 %) and silt (9.50 %) fraction. Soils derived from Shale at the National Horticultural Research Institute, Okigwe (SHL-NIHORT-Okigwe) under continuously cultivated croplands of Cassava/Maize/Melon intercrop (CCC-CMM) had significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher clay (27.27 %) and bulk density value (1.88 g/cm³). Igwe and Obalum (2013) attributed the high values sand to the nature of the parent materials and mineralogy of the soils. The clay content of the soils is moderately low relative to the total sand fraction. The highest (9.50 %) mean silt observed at ALV-NDBDA-Isiokolo may be due to the movement of sediments by the river in the area. The textural class generally ranged from loamy sand to sandy loam at the surface and sandy clay loam at the subsurface horizons. The highest bulk density observed at SHL-NIHORT-Okigwe support the findings of Knopes and Tilman (2000), who noted that periodical farm tractorization, high soil clay Content, as seen in the location, could result in soil compaction, high bulk density and poor hydraulic Conductivity, leading to high runoff volume, erosion and nutrient loss. Soils derived from coastal plain sands of Niger Delta Basin Development Authority at Kpong (CPS-NDBDA-Kpong) under continuously cultivated croplands of Cassava/Maize/Yam intercrop had significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher Ksat (0.63 ds/m), which is rated moderately slow. Onweremadue *et al.* (2011) affirmed that slow Ksat, soil surface sealing and crusting are common in continuously tilled soils that are subjected to rainfall or sprinkler irrigation with water low in electrolytes. Bala *et al.* (2016) reported that soil surface sealing leads to low infiltrations and consequently causing increased runoff, erosion and transport of sediments, nutrients and pollutants from the land, even at low slope gradients.

Soils derived from coastal plain sands of Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria at Isieke (CPS-FRIN-Isieke) under continuously cultivated croplands of Cassava/Maize/ Telferia intercrop had significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher pH(5.2), followed by SHL-NIHORT-Okigwe with CCC-CMM pH(4.9) and ALV- NDBDA-Isiokolo with CCC-CMTI pH(4.9). While soils formed on Imo clay Shale of Anambra-Imo River Basin Development Authority, Agbala(ICS-AIRBDA-Agbala) under continuously cultivated croplands of Cassava/Maize/Okra intercrop (CCC-CMO) and coastal plain sands of Niger Delta Basin Development Authority, Kpong (CPS-NDBDA-Kpong) under continuously cultivated croplands with Cassava/Maize/ Yam intercrop (CCC-CMY) had least pH(4.8) value each. It therefore implies that coastal plain sands with Cassava/Maize/Telferia intercrop improved soil pH. Whereas, ICS-AIRBDA-Agbala under CCC-CMO, SHL-NIHORT-

Okigwe under CCC-CMM, and ALV-NDBDA-Isiokolo under CCC-CMTI, depleted soil pH. Across the study area, soil reaction ranged from strongly to very strongly acid pH (4.8-5.2). This implies that acid nature of the soils contribute significantly to the low DOM content of the soils. This is in line with the findings of Ikeorguet *al.* (2006), which indicated that acid condition incapacitates soil organisms from producing different kinds of SOM which enhance the aggregate stability of the soils. Soils formed on CPS-NDBDA-Kpong with CCC-CMY had significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher electrical conductivity (EC) 0.26 ds/m. The least EC (0.06 ds/m) was recorded at SHL-NIHORT-Okigwe under CCC-CMM. The mean values of EC across the study area were below the threshold (> 0.26 ms/cm) as provided by Reynoldset *al.* (2009) for characterizing the soil as saline, except CPS-NDBDA-Kpong under CCC-CMY. This may be due to the proximity of the area to the tidal marshes of the Atlantic Ocean. While Azeezet *al.* (2013) reported that EC is influenced by land use, Igwe (2000) noted that management and cultural practices that lead to low organic matter, poor infiltration, poor drainage, or compaction results in salt accumulation in the root zone, increasing EC and the soil ability to buffer EC. There was Higher (1.73 %) significantly ($p < 0.05$) influence of alluvial soils of ALV-NDBDA-Isiokolo with CCC-CMTI on SOC. This implies that Alluvium parent material of Niger Delta Basin Development Authority, Isiokolo, under CCC-CMTI improved SOC sequestration. While CCC-CMTF, CCC-CMM, CCC-CMO and CCC-CMY depleted SOC, their lithological differences notwithstanding. Soils of CPS-NDBDA-Kpong under CCC-CMY had significantly higher TN (0.19 %), followed by ICS-AIRBDA-Agbala under CCC-CMO (0.14 %). TN across the study area ranged low to moderate (0.08 - 0.19 %). The low TN recorded in the area could be a result of losses through liquid leaching. This is in agreement with Pal *et al.* (2013), who reported that loss of N by NO_3 leaching is aggravated by heavy rainfall especially in drained soils. Soils of ALV-NDBDA-Isiokolo under CCC-CMTI had significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher exchangeable K (0.14 cmol/Kg). Exchangeable K was depleted in soils across the study area, irrespective of varying parent materials and crop combinations. This is in line with Igwe (2003), who observed that exchangeable cation K is usually leached down the profile, away from the soil rooting zone in the rainforest agroecological regions of Nigeria due to intensive rainstorms and varying parent materials. Soils formed on ALV-NDBDA-Isiokolo with CCC-CMTI had significantly higher cation exchange capacity (CEC) 18.00 cmol/Kg¹. Across the study area, CEC was rated moderate (12.27- 26.67 cmol/Kg¹). Agbede (2009) stated that the higher the CEC values of a soil, the greater the potential fertility of the soil. Ibeet. *al* (2025) observed that where the Cation exchange capacity of the soil is < 5 cmol/Kg¹, the soils are considered inherently infertile. Soils of CPS-FRIN-Isieke with CCC-CMTF had significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher available P (26.67 Mg/Kg¹), followed by SHL-NIHORT-Okigwe with CCC-CMM P (26.63 Mg/Kg¹). While the least available P was observed in ALV-NDBDA-Isiokolo with CCC-CMTI. This implies that CPS-FRIN-Isieke under CCC-CMTF and SHL-NIHORT-Okigwe with CCC-CMM improved available Phosphorus. This is in line with the earlier findings of other researchers such as Opeke (2006) and Osodeke (2017), who reported that Phosphorus is the most limiting nutrient element in the soil, due to its high disposition to fixation by several soil constituents.

Table 2: Analysis of variance (ANOVA) Comparing Soil Physico-Chemical Properties Under Different Parent Materials and Continuously cultivated Croplands in the Study Area

Soil Property	CPS-FRW-Isieke/ CCC-CMTF	SHL-NIHORF-Okigwe/ CCC-CMM	ICS-AIRBDA-Agbala/ CCC-CMO	CPS-NDBDA-Kpong/ CCC-CMY	ALV-NDBDA-Isiokolo/ CCC-CMTT	LSD	Significant
Sand (%)	75.00 ^c	65.10 ^c	70.00 ^d	77.00 ^b	80.31 ^a	312	*
Silt (%)	7.86 ^b	7.63 ^c	5.22 ^c	6.99 ^d	9.50 ^a	1.52	*
Clay (%)	17.14 ^c	27.27 ^a	24.78 ^b	16.01 ^d	10.19 ^c	0.22	**
BD (g/cm ³)	1.56 ^c	1.88 ^a	1.62 ^d	1.66 ^c	1.72 ^b	1.92	**
Ksat (ds/m)	0.48 ^d	0.56 ^b	0.48 ^d	0.63 ^a	0.52 ^c	4.15	*
EC (MSCM ⁻¹)	0.13 ^c	0.006 ^c	0.08 ^d	0.26 ^a	0.20 ^b	1.20	*
PH (H ₂ O)	5.2 ^a	4.9 ^b	4.8 ^c	4.8 ^c	4.9 ^b	0.56	*
Soc %	1.15 ^c	0.86 ^d	1.18 ^b	0.73 ^c	1.73 ^a	0.08	*
TN (%)	0.14 ^b	0.13 ^c	0.14 ^b	0.19 ^a	0.08 ^d	0.21	*
K (cmolkg ⁻¹)	0.05 ^c	0.06 ^d	0.10 ^c	0.12 ^b	0.14 ^a	0.14	*
CEC (Cmolkg ⁻¹)	12.15 ^c	16.00 ^d	18.60 ^a	16.12 ^c	18.00 ^b	0.25	*
P (Mgkg ⁻¹)	26.67 ^a	26.63 ^b	23.83 ^c	13.27 ^c	22.00 ^d	0.42	*

Key: *, ** = Significant at 0.01 and 0.05 alpha levels, respectively. Values in the same row followed by the same letter are not significant at 0.01 and 0.05 alpha levels respectively

BD = Bulk density, BC = Electrical conductivity, Soc =Soil Organic Carbon,TN = Total Nitrogen, K= Exchangeable Potassium, CEC =Centrifuge Exchange Capacity, P = Phosphorous

Mean values of SOC content (g/Kg) in water-stable aggregate size fractions

Mean values of SOC content in water-stable aggregate size fractions across the study area are presented in Table 3: In > 2.00 mm WSA, soils of ALV-NDBDA-Isiokolowith CCC-CMTI had significantly ($p < 0.005$) higher SOC content (40.16 g/Kg), followed by CPS-NDBDA-Kpong under CCC-CMY (38.62 g/Kg). Whereas, SHL-NIHORT-Okigwe under CCC-CMM had the least (34.04 g/Kg). For 1.00- 2.00 mm WSA, there was significant influence of parent material and crop combination on SOC content with ALV-NDBDA-Isiokolo having highest value (45.18 g/Kg), followed by ICS-AIRBDA-Agbala under CCC-CMO (37.44 g/Kg) and CPS-NDBDA-Kpong under CCC-CMY sequestered the least (33.60 g/Kg). In 0.50 -1.00 mm WSA, soils of ALV-NDBDA-Isiokolo under CCC-CMTI had significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher SOC content (46.10 g/Kg), followed by ICS-AIRBDA-Agbala under CCC-CMO (43.03 g/Kg), the least being CPS-NDBDA-Kpong under CCC-CMY (40.28 g/Kg). It therefore implies that ALV-NDBDA-Isiokolo under CCC-CMTI improved sequestration of SOC in macroaggregates (>2.00 mm, 1.00-2.00 mm, and 0.50- 1.00 mm). This is in agreement with Okebalama (2016), who observed high soil organic carbon content in tropical Humid fresh water swamps.

For 0.25- 0.50 mm WSA, soils of SHL-NIHORT-Okigwe under CCC-CMM significantly ($p < 0.05$) sequestered higher SOC content (66.10 g/Kg). Whereas, the least (43.48 g/Kg) was CPS-NDBDA-Kpong with CCC-CMY. This revealed that SHL-NIHORT-Okigwe under CCC-CMM improved the sequestered SOC in small-sized WSA. In <0.25 mm WSA, soils of ICS-AIRBDA-Agbala under CCC-CMO had significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher SOC content (63.06 g/Kg) and CPS-FRIN-Isieke under CCC-CMTF had the least (41.80 g/Kg). It therefore implies that SHL-NIHORT-Okigwe under CCC-CMM improved SOC in small-sized water-stable. Whereas, ICS-AIRBDA-Agbala under CCC-CMO enhanced the storage of SOC in microaggregates. Researchers in confirmation to this inference about in literature (Lal, 2009b; Onweremadue *et al.*, 2011; Igwe and Obalum, 2013). Generally, SOC sequestration in the water-stable aggregate size fractions increased from >2.00 mm to <0.25 mm lithological differences and variation in crop combination notwithstanding. This affirms the findings of Mbagwu and Schwartzman (2006) and Ogunwole *et al.* (2014) that observed the reduction of SOC in macroaggregates of water-stable aggregate size fractions.

Table 3: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) Comparing SOC Content (gkg⁻¹) in Water-Stable Aggregate Size Fractions Under Different Parent materials and Continuously Cultivated Croplands in the Study Area

Water-Stable Aggregate Fraction(mmm)	CPS-FRW-Isieke	SHL-NIHORT-Okigwe	ICS-AIRBDA-AGBAK	CPS-NDBDA-Kpong	ALV-NDBDA-Isiacolo	LSD	Significance
	CCC-CMTF	CCC-CMM	CCC-CMO	CCC-CMY	CCC-CMTT		
72.00	30.53 ^c	34.04 ^d	35.99 ^c	38.62 ^b	40.16 ^a	0.39	*
1.00 -2.00	36.80 ^c	34.99 ^d	37.44 ^b	33.60 ^c	45.18 ^a	0.74	*
0.50 – 1.00	42.77 ^c	41.88 ^d	43.03 ^b	40.28 ^c	46.10 ^a	3.15	**
0.25 -0.50	48.35 ^d	66.10 ^a	50.22 ^c	43.48 ^c	58.90 ^b	6.99	**
<0.25	41.80 ^c	46.30 ^c	63.06 ^a	45.71 ^d	47.66 ^b	12.33	**

Key= *, **= significant at 0.01 and 0.05 alpha levels respectively. Values in the same row followed by the same letter are not significant at 0.01 and 0.05 alpha.

CPS-FRW-Isieke = Coastal plain sands of Forestry Research Institute of Nigeria, Isieke

CCC-CMTF = continuously cultivated cropland of Cassava/Maize/Telferia in inter crop MFRW

SHL-NIHORT-Okigwe = shale of National Horticultural Research Institute, Okigwe

CCC-CMM = continuously cultivated cropland of Cassava/Maize/Melon intercrop

ICS-AIRBDA = Agbala = Imo clay shale of Anambra-Imo-River basin Development Authority, Agbala

CCC-CMO = continuously cultivated cropland of Cassava/Maize/Okra intercrop

CPS-NDBDA-Kpong = Coastal plain sands of Niger Delta Basin Development Authority, Kpong

CCC-CMY= Continuously cultivated cropland of Cassava/Maize/Yam Intercrop

ALU-NDBDA – Isiokolo = Alluvial of Niger Delta Basin Development Authority, Isiokolo

CCC-CMTI = Continuously cultivated cropland of Cassava/Maize/ Feljanai intercrop in Isiokolo

Geostatistical Parameters of the Fitted Semi Variogram for SOC Content in Soils of the Study Area

Geostatistical parameters of the fitted semi-variogram exponential model for SOC content are shown in Table 4. Maps showing the spatial distribution of the estimated SOC content in water-stable aggregate fractions in soils under different parent materials and varying crop combinations were the main output of the spatial analysis (Figs 2-6). The shaded different grey tone was according to the value estimated at that locations. The maps are shaded proportionally to the kriging results.

The semi-variogram parameters of SOC content explained the semi variance in the best way with the nugget values range 0.061-0.409. The nugget-sill ratio (N:S) ranged from 0.685-0.1135. This hinted a strong spatial dependence of SOC content in WSA fractions and suggest that structural factors such as parent materials, climate, mineralogy, texture and slope are the primary cause of spatial patterns of SOC content in WSA. This is in agreement with Liu *et al.* (2004) and ECOS (2008), who noted that carbon sequestration is dependent on mineralogy, climate and slope. The fitted model occurs at a very short range, indicating localized dependency of SOC under different parent materials and arable croplands. The different ranges of the spatial dependence among the water-stable aggregate size fractions may be attributed to differences in response to the varying parent materials and crop combinations. Research findings in confirmation to this abound in literature (Schulin, 2013 and Bhunia *et al.*, 2016; Saygnet. *al.* 2017; Ibe, 2021).

Table 4: Geostatistical Parameters of the Fitted Semivariogram Exponential Model for SOC Content in WSA Fractions in the Study Area

Soil Property	Depth (Cm)	Nugget (Co)	Sill (Co + C)	Range (M)	(N:S)	R²	ME	RMSE
SOC (gkg ⁻¹) in WSA fraction								
> 2.00mm	0-100	0.399	4.830	19.3	0.0825	0.663	0.0232	0.341
1.00-2.00mm	0-100	0.349	4.561	20.5	0.0765	0.633	0.00481	0.427
0.50-1.00mm	0-100	0.409	3.612	20.2	0.1135	0.661	0.00387	0.338
0.25-0.050mm	0-100	0.061	0.886	19.6	0.0685	0.701	0.00327	0.449
< 0.25mm	0-100	0.076	1.067	19.8	0.0715	0.684	0.024114	0.372

Key: R² = Coefficient of determination, RMSE = Root mean square error, , N:S= nugget-sill ratio, ME = Mean error.

Spatial pattern of SOC content in water-stable aggregate size fractions at varying parent materials

The predictive maps showing spatial pattern of SOC content in the WSA fractions(> 2.00, 0-100-2.00, 0.50-1.00; 0.25-0.50, and <0.25mm) under varying parent materials and arable croplands is shown in Fig 2-6. In the >2.00mm WSA fraction, the results showed highest concentration of SOC in the northwest region of the study area. This corresponds to soils developed under alluvium, cultivated with cassava/maize/teff. Extreme southeast region dominated by coastal plain sands and shale with cassava/maize/okra and cassava/maize/yam croplands had minimum values of SOC concentration. The central southeast region had medium values of SOC content with mean error and RMSE of 0.232 and 0.341 respectively.

Figure 2: Predictive Map Showing the Spatial Pattern of SOC Content (gkg⁻¹) under Varying Parent Materials and Cropland in >2.00 mm WSA Fraction Interpolated by Ordinary Kriging Model

The predictive map of SOC content for 1.00-2.00mm WSA fraction across the study area (Fig.3), showed highest concentration of SOC in extreme and central western zones of the study area. These represent the soils formed under alluvium and cultivated with cassava/maize/teff crop combination. The extreme southeast region had minimum values. This area corresponds to soils formed under coastal plain sands, with cassava/maize/yam cropland. The central region and the northeastern corner of the study area had medium values of SOC with mean error and RMSE of 0.00481 and 0.427, respectively. These areas correspond to soils developed under shale, Imo clay shale and alluvium cultivated with crop combination of cassava/maize/melon, cassava/maize/okra and cassava/maize/teff respectively.

Figure 3: Predictive Map Showing the Spatial Pattern of SOC (gkg^{-1}) under Varying Parent Materials and Croplands in 1.00-2.00mm WSA Fraction Interpolated by Ordinary Kriging Model

The predictive spatial map of SOC in 0.5-1.00mm WSA fraction across the study area (Fig. 4), showed pockets of highest concentration of SOC in WSA fraction 0.50-1.00mm, in the central southeast and western regions of the study area. These area represent soils developed under Imo clay shale, coastal plain sands and alluvium, cultivated with cassava/maize/okra, cassava/maize/yam and cassava/maize/tefleria cropping combinations. The central southeast and northeast had medium values of SOC content. These area correspond to soils developed under shale, coastal plain sands and alluvium cultivated with cassava/maize/melon, cassava/maize/yam and cassava/maize/tefleria with mean error and RMSE of 0.00387 and 0.338, respectively.

Figure 4: Predictive Map Showing Spatial Pattern of SOC (gkg^{-1}) Under Varying Parent Materials and Croplands in 0.50-1.00mm WSA Fraction Interpolated by Ordinary Kriging Model.

The predictive spatial map of SOC in 0.25-0.50mm WSA fraction (Fig.3), showed pockets of highest values of SOC content in the Western Zone. There were also pockets of highest concentration of SOC in central southeastern corner of the study area. That corresponds to soils formed under coastal plain sands and alluvium cropped with cassava/maize/telferia and cassava/maize/yam. There were pockets of minimum values of SOC in the northeastern region and extreme southern part of the study area. These areas represent soils developed under shale, coastal plain sands and alluvium, cropped with cassava/maize/yam, cassava/maize/melon and cassava/maize/telferia. Northern, central and southern regions had medium values of SOC concentration with mean error and RMSE values of 0.00327 and 0.449, respectively.

Figure 5: Predictive Map Showing Spatial Pattern of SOC Content (gkg^{-1}) Under Varying Parent Materials and Croplands in 0.25-0.50mm WSA Fraction Interpolated by Ordinary Kriging Model.

The predictive spatial map of SOC in <0.25mm WSA fraction (Fig.3), showed highest concentration of SOC in the central and extreme western region of the study area. These corresponds to soils formed under alluvium and cassava/maize/telferia crop combination. Northeast and southern zones had minimum values of SOC content. These represent soils developed under shale and coastal plain sands, cultivated with cassava/maize/melon and cassava/maize/yam. There were pockets of medium values of SOC concentration observed in the western and eastern zones. The area correspond to soils developed under coastal plain sands and alluvium, cultivated with cassava/maize/telferia crop combination with mean error and RMSE of 0.0124 and 0.436, respectively.

Figure 6: Predictive Map Showing the Spatial Pattern of SOC Content (gkg^{-1}) in $<0.25\text{mm}$ WSA Fraction under Varying Parent Materials and Croplands Interpolated by Ordinary Kriging Model.

Generally, coefficient of determination (R^2) of SOC content in the various WSA fractions across the study are arranged from 0.851-0.701. The R^2 were >0.5 , which indicate a good fit. The RMSE were approximately near to zero (0). This shows that the theoretical model was adequate representation of the spatial patterns of SOC content. This is in agreement with Bhunia *et al.* (2016) who reported very low RMSE in soils of similar climatic region.

The assessment suggests that the geographical allocation patterns of SOC content in the WSA fractions at 0-100cm soil depths were extremely variable. The results suggest that both structural and stochastic factors (parent material, crop combinations and cultural practices) influenced SOC content in the aggregate size fractions. Research findings in confirmation to this abound in literature (Xie *et al.*, 2011; Wei *et al.*, 2013; USDA-NRCS, 2019). According to Hall *et al.* (1997), Idowu (2003) and Jia *et al.* (2004), carbon sequestration in soil was mainly influenced by structural factors (climate, parent material, topography, soil properties) and natural factors.

Conclusion

Assessment of soil organic carbon patterns in WSA in continuously cultivated croplands in varying Parent materials was conducted in southern Nigeria, to determine the potential for C sequestration in water-stable aggregate size fractions under varying Parent materials and crop combinations. The assessment suggest that ALV-NDBDA-Isiokolo under CCC-CMTI had significantly ($p<0.05$) higher sand (80.31%) and silt (9.50 %) fraction. SHL-NIHORT-Okigwe

under CCC-CMM had significantly ($p < 0.05$) had higher Clay (27.27 %) and bulk density value (1.88 g/cm^3) Soils formed from CPS-NDBDA-Kpong under CCC-CMY had significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher K_{sat} (0.63 ds/m). Soils derived from CPS-NDBDA-Isieke under CCC-CMTF had significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher pH (5.2), followed by SHL-NIHORT-Okigwe under CCC-CMM and ALV-NDBDA-Isiokolo under CCC-CMTI had pH (4.9) Soils formed on CPS-NDBDA-Kpong under CCC-CMY had significantly higher EC (0.26 ds/m). The main values of EC across the study area were within the threshold ($> 0.26 \text{ ms/cm}$) for characterizing the soil as saline. There was significantly higher influence of alluvial soils of ALV-NDBDA-Isiokolo with CCC-CMTI on SOC, while CCC-CMTF, CCC-CMM, CCC-CMO and CCC-CMY depleted SOC, the varying lithology notwithstanding.

ALV-NDBDA-Isiokolo under CCC-CMTI improved sequestration of SOC in macro-aggregate fractions ($> 2.00 \text{ mm}$, $1.00 - 2.00 \text{ mm}$ and $0.50 - 1.00 \text{ mm}$). While SHL-NIHORT-Okigwe under CCC-CMM improved C sequestration in small-sized aggregate fraction ($0.25 - 0.50 \text{ mm}$). Whereas, ICS-AIRBDA-Agbala under CCC-CMO enhanced SOC content in micro-aggregate fractions ($< 0.25 \text{ mm}$). However, SOC content increased with decreasing water-stable aggregate fractions $> 2.00 \text{ mm}$ to $< 0.25 \text{ mm}$, irrespective of the crop combinations and lithological differences. It therefore implies that SOC sequestered majorly in small-sized aggregate ($0.25 - 0.50 \text{ mm}$), and micro-aggregate ($< 0.26 \text{ mm}$) in CCC-CMTF, CCC-CMM, CCC-CMO, CCC-CMY and CCC-CMTI. The geographical allocation pattern of SOC content in the WSA fractions at 0-100cm soil depth were extremely variable.

The semi-variogram model suggested that Spatial patterns of SOC content in Water-stable aggregate size fractions revealed varied spatial pattern. Nugget variance (C_0) ranged from 0.61-0.09. Coefficient of determination (R^2) were > 0.50 . Low ($0.338 - 0.449$) root mean square error (RMSE) showed that the theoretical model was an adequate representation of the spatial pattern of SOC. The semi-variogram parameters of SOC content explained the semi-variance in the best way with the nugget values range 0.061- 0.409. The nugget-sill ratio ranged from 0.685 to 0.1135. This hinted a strong spatial dependence of SOC content in WSA fractions and suggest that structural factors (parent materials, climate, mineralogy, texture, and slope) are the primary cause of spatial patterns of SOC content in WSA fractions. These emphasize the significance of considering both parent materials and cultural practices (crop rotation, cropping combination, application of fertilizer and organic manure etc.) for sustainable soil management in the area. Application of organic manure should be encouraged in the study area. This will promote soil aggregation and C sequestration in macro- and micro- aggregate size fractions as this will enhance soil health and productivity, leading to sustainable ecosystem services and food security.

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SUB-THEME 2:

**INNOVATIONS IN CLIMATE-SMART FARMING
PRACTICES**

Utilization of Bamboo in Construction of Sustainable Structures to Mitigate Coastal Erosion in Nigeria

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Abstract

Nigeria's vast coastline is facing an increasingly serious environmental threat: coastal erosion, which poses a high risk to infrastructure, coastal residents, and the entire ecosystem units. Conventional erosion control techniques, such as rock revetments and concrete seawalls are very expensive and unsustainable. This paper investigates the use of bamboo as an economical, locally accessible, and sustainable material for building an eco-friendly coastline protection structure in Nigeria. Bamboo has great potential for use in constructing erosion control structures because of its quick growth and good engineering properties. The engineering qualities of treated bamboo and the applications of bamboo in the construction of coastal erosion control structures are also highlighted. Important issues including challenges, longevity, and a lack of design standards are discussed along with preservative treatments. The study concludes that, with the right design and upkeep, bamboo-based structures can reduce coastal erosion in Nigeria in an environmentally responsible manner while also encouraging sustainable growth and local empowerment.

Keywords: Bamboo, sustainable structures, coastal erosion, eco-friendly, infrastructure.

Introduction.

Coastal regions of the world are traditionally among the densely populated regions of the world due to the economic benefits they provide such as;recreational activities, aquatic animals, naturally refreshing air, tourism, navigation, coastal industries, etc. However, these regions are increasingly challenged by coastal erosions, seasonal rise in sea level, hurricanes, intense storm surges and tsunamis(Mai Van et al., 2021). Coastal erosion is a major threat to communities, infrastructuresand the ecosystem units around the various water bodies in Nigeria(Ankrah et al., 2023). Coastal erosion which is the gradual washing away of soils close to the water bodies is mainlycaused by the activities of man and natural forces such as; waves, rise in sea levels and storm surges (Williams et al., 2018).The continuous changes in the global climate have several consequences on both man and the natural ecosystem. Coastal regions are important socio-ecological regions as they are among the densely populated regions of the world due to the economic and ecological potential they possess. They are also among the regions largely affected by the negative impacts of climate change such as continuous rise in global temperature which causes melting of polar ices leading to rise in sea levels, a major cause of coastal erosion (Ankrah et al., 2023).Over the years, certain infrastructures around coastal and marine environment like;erosion mitigation structures, piers, coastal huts, boardwalks, floating platforms, etc. have been constructed using traditional building materials like timber, steel and

concrete. Due to the environmental issues arising from the use of these materials and the current high cost of these materials in Nigeria, researchers and Engineers have shifted focus on search for cheaper and eco-friendly materials for construction of coastal infrastructures (Das et al., 2024) (Harihar & Verhagen, 2017). Among several options to remedy coastal erosions, bamboo has offered a more favorable, cheaper, eco-friendly and sustainable solution to coastal erosion. Unlike other coastal erosion solutions that are based on the use of reinforced concrete structures such as dikes, retaining walls etc which are very expensive and whose construction processes involve burning fossil fuels with its attendant environmental hazards and disrupt the natural eco system balance in the coastal regions, bamboo provides a healthier, less costly and sustainable approach to the protection of coastal regions ("How Bamboo Is Nature's Answer to Coastal Erosion," 2024).

Physical and Mechanical Properties of Bamboo Culms/Stems.

As a result of the high cost and adverse environmental issues associated with traditional building materials like; steel and concrete, researchers and engineers have resorted to the use of sustainable, low-cost, eco-friendly and readily available materials in the construction of civil infrastructures (Onyechere et al., 2023). This is made possible because, bamboo culms possess appreciable engineering properties.

(a) Physical Properties.

Bamboo is the fastest growing grass on earth with a growth rate of about 1.2m per day and reaches maturity within 3 to 5 years which is the shortest maturity age recorded for any woody plant (Onyechere et al., 2023). Physical properties such as length, weight, diameter and number of nodes is unique for each bamboo, the physical properties is not the same for two bamboos. Due to the fact that bamboo is a natural product, its physical properties differ from one another depending on the soil and climatic factors (Shuvo et al., 2022). Each bamboo culm contains several nodes with transverse diaphragms in between the nodes, the nodal length of each bamboo culm depends on the height and diameter. The range of the diameter and height of each mature bamboo culm depends on the specie. Bamboo just like other woody plants has a high moisture content which varies depending on the age of the bamboo.

(b) Mechanical Properties.

Mechanical properties are characteristics of a material which determines its behavior and response when the material is subjected to load.

(i) Compressive Strength: This is the capacity of the bamboo culm to withstand crushing when axial compressive load is applied to it. In the works Bantie et al., (2025) on the physical and mechanical properties of bamboo, it was observed that the compressive strength (parallel to grain) of most species of bamboo full culms ranges from 40 – 65 N/mm² depending on the specie and section of the culm. This value is 2 – 4 times higher than the compressive strength of most timber species. Compressive strength decreases from the top section to the bottom section of the culm for most species of bamboo with top section possessing the highest compressive strength due to the fact it contains fewer vascular bundles which results in more fibers at the top section leading to higher compressive strength. Rahim et al., (2020) in their work on bamboo as reinforcement in concrete carried out compressive strength test on two specimens of bamboo culm; one with node at the center and one without node and obtained their compressive strength to be 34.86 N/mm² and 44.93 N/mm² respectively. This shows that presence of node reduces the compressive strength of the bamboo culm.

(ii) Tensile Strength: This is the ability of bamboo to resist stretching or pulling forces. Tensile strength parallel to grain of the bamboo's culm is its capacity to resist forces trying to split it. Bamboo has a high tensile strength as a result of its high vascular bundles and axial membrane fibers (Onyechere et al., 2023).

In the works of Sutharsan et al., (2020) on the study on bamboo as reinforcement in concrete, they obtained the average tensile strength of bamboo to be around 109.86 N/mm². Rahim et al., (2020) conducted tensile test on whole culms of several species of bamboo, the specimens tested have no nodes, in their work and obtained an average tensile strength of 169.27N/mm², this value is 68% of the tensile strength of mild steel. In general, bamboo has more tensile resistance than compressive resistance. Using proper connections to ensure adequate bamboo-concrete bonding, bamboo culms can be effectively used in concrete construction to replace steel as reinforcement.

(iii) Modulus of Elasticity: This is a measure of stiffness of the material, it defines the materials capacity to withstand deformation when subjected to stress. Liese & Köhl, (2015), in their work investigated the modulus of elasticity of several species of bamboo and observed that it ranges from 6,000 to 30,000N/mm².

(iv) Modulus of Rupture: This explains the maximum bending stress that bamboo culm can resist before it can fail. Liese & Köhl, (2015) conducted bending stress test on several specimens of Guadua bamboo specie and obtain the modulus of rupture to range from 54 to 113.9N/mm².

3. Applications of Bamboo in Sustainable Coastal Erosion Control

Bamboo being the fastest growing grass, readily available in large quantity, resilient to adverse climatic factors and possessing good mechanical properties is a sustainable material for coastal erosion control via the use of bioengineering techniques (Isukuru et al., 2023). Leveraging bioengineering techniques, its special fibrous root system enhances soil stabilization while the excellent mechanical properties and natural flexibility of bamboo culms makes it capable of absorbing and dissipating wave energy and resisting coastal dynamics thus, keeping the coastal soils safe and stable (Tardio et al., 2017). For maximum performance in coastal applications, bamboo culms are treated to withstand harsh coastal environments and protect them from decay and attacks from marine borers. Some of the techniques adopted in coastal erosion control applications using bamboo include;

(a) Living Root System of Bamboo for Soil Stabilization.

Bamboo has fast-growing, deep and extensive root system interwoven with rhizomes that is resilient to harsh environmental factors such as wildfire, helps to hold soil particles together, improves the stiffness of the soil and reduces soil erodibility (Mai Van et al., 2021).

(b) Construction of Wave-Dissipating Barriers.

Bamboo culms are used in the construction of structural wave-dissipating barriers such as; Bamboo breakwaters, Bamboo Pile walls, Bamboo T-Fences, etc.

(i) Bamboo Breakwaters: These are permeable structures made with bamboo culms, they are constructed at the seashores to reduce flood and wave velocity and hence, promotes deposition of sediments, prevents soil erosion, protects existing vegetation and mangrove and promotes creation of new vegetation as shown in Plate 1. Also, bamboo culms can be used in combination with other materials such as pre-cast concrete to create breakwaters at the seashore which is cheaper and more eco-friendly than using traditional boulders.

Plate 1: Bamboo breakwaters.

(ii) Bamboo Pile Walls: This is a structural wall constructed with bamboo culms as vertical posts and horizontal elements and usually reinforced with soil or mud and joint together with bamboo strips and other fasteners. They are used as retaining walls to protect coastal soils and in slope stabilization as shown in Plate 2.

Plate 2: Bamboo Pile Walls

(iii) Bamboo T-Fences: These are permeable walls constructed using bamboo culms arranged in a T-shape. This reduces flood velocity, wave energy and hence encourages deposition of sediments which reduces soil erosion, encourages soil stabilization and promotes mangrove growth (Cole, 2025).

(c) Bamboo in Bio-Engineering: Soil bioengineering implies a group of land management techniques employed by man using natural systems and factors to ensure sustainable, safe and functional land use (Tardio et al., 2018).

When combined with vegetation like vetiver grass or mangroves, bamboo matting or lattices enhance soil stabilization, reducing coastal and riverbank erosion effectively.

4. Advantages of Using Bamboo

(i) Mangroove Rehabilitation: Bamboo structures helps in stabilizing coastal environment, reduces wave energy and promotes deposition of sediments which encourages mangrove growth. Due to its flexibility, bamboo structures can be integrated with the growing mangrove habitat and can be removed or be left in place after the mangrove has been fully established.

(ii) Eco-friendly: Bamboo reduces reliance on concrete and steel, minimizing carbon footprint.

(iii) Cost-effective: Readily available and inexpensive in many tropical regions.

(iv) Community-based construction: Local communities can engage in harvesting, treating, and building with bamboo.

(v) Flexibility and resilience: Bamboo structures deform under pressure rather than break, providing durability in storm-prone areas.

5. Challenges and Solutions in the Application of Bamboo in Coastal Erosion Control

- **Durability Issues:** Untreated bamboo is prone to rot and insect attack. Proper chemical treatment (e.g., boron-based preservatives) and coating techniques can significantly improve lifespan.
- **Engineering Standardization:** Lack of standardized design guidelines can hinder wider adoption. Continued research and pilot projects are essential for mainstream implementation.

Conclusion.

Bamboo is an eco-friendly, low-cost sustainable material for the construction of coastal erosion mitigation structures. Bamboo has fast-growing, deep and extensive root system interwoven with rhizomes that is resilient to harsh environmental factors such as wildfire, helps to hold soil particles together, improves the stiffness of the soil and reduces soil erodibility.

The excellent mechanical properties and natural flexibility of bamboo culms makes it capable of absorbing and dissipating wave energy and resisting coastal dynamics thus, keeping the coastal soils safe and stable. Using bamboo in coastal protection structures helps to promote mangrove growth, protects vulnerable shorelines and encourages sustainable development and community resilience. For maximum performance in coastal applications, bamboo culms are treated to withstand harsh coastal environments and protect them from decay and attacks from marine borers

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Green Manufacturing: A Tool for Sustainable Development and Antedote to Climate Change

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Abstract

This paper examines green manufacturing as a strategic pathway for sustainable development and a practical antidote to climate change within Nigeria and the wider African industrial landscape. Drawing on secondary data from government reports, international environmental agencies, and peer-reviewed studies published between 2018 and 2025, the study synthesizes how clean production technologies, energy-efficient systems, circular-economy models, and eco-design collectively reshape manufacturing performance across economic, environmental, and social dimensions. The findings demonstrate that Nigeria has recorded measurable progress in industrial decarbonization, including a 12.7% reduction in CO₂ emissions between 2018 and 2024, driven largely by solar-assisted processing, waste-heat recovery, and improved machinery efficiency. Resource productivity has also increased significantly, with circular-economy practices yielding 25–40% savings in raw material usage, particularly in plastics, packaging, and metal-fabrication sectors. Additionally, green manufacturing has contributed to inclusive socio-economic development, generating substantial employment in renewable energy, recycling, and eco-design industries. Despite these gains, the study identifies major barriers—including high initial investment costs, weak policy enforcement, limited technical expertise, and inadequate access to green financing—that constrain broader adoption. The paper argues that scaling green manufacturing requires stronger regulatory mechanisms, targeted incentives, capacity-building, and coordinated policy implementation. It concludes that embedding green manufacturing into Nigeria's industrial strategy is essential for achieving long-term climate resilience, economic competitiveness, and alignment with global sustainability commitments.

Keywords: Green Manufacturing; Sustainable Development; Climate Change Mitigation; Circular Economy; Industrial Decarbonization

Introduction

Manufacturing has been a cornerstone of economic development for two centuries, raising living standards through mass production, employment and technological progress. At the same time, conventional manufacturing practices are a significant and persistent source of environmental harm: energy-intensive processes, material inefficiencies, hazardous wastes and supply-chain emissions all contribute to the global greenhouse-gas burden and local pollution. Tackling these effects without undermining industrial competitiveness has given rise to the field of green manufacturing—an integrated set of principles and practices that seek to minimise environmental impact across product life cycles while maintaining productivity and profitability. Recent systematic reviews and frameworks show that green manufacturing is no longer peripheral but central to strategies for decarbonisation, circularity and resilient industry.

The world is currently facing an unprecedented ecological crisis marked by rising global temperatures, declining biodiversity, and increasing pollution levels. Industrial activities, particularly in the manufacturing sector, have been identified as the primary contributors to greenhouse gas emissions and unsustainable energy consumption (UNEP, 2023). In Africa, and especially in Nigeria, manufacturing processes often rely heavily on fossil fuels, outdated technologies, and resource-intensive methods, resulting in severe environmental consequences. Green manufacturing—defined as the integration of environmentally friendly technologies, materials, and processes throughout the product life cycle—offers a transformative solution to these challenges (Chukwuma and Nwachukwu, 2022).

Green manufacturing is not merely an environmental intervention; it is a holistic economic and social development strategy that aligns industrial productivity with ecological responsibility. It emphasizes the optimization of energy and material use, the minimization of waste, and the promotion of circular economy practices that keep resources in use for as long as possible. The concept serves as an *antidote to climate change* by mitigating emissions, fostering clean energy transitions, and enhancing adaptive industrial resilience (World Bank, 2024).

In Nigeria, where industrialization remains a cornerstone of economic development, the need for sustainable manufacturing approaches cannot be overstated. Recent studies by the Federal Ministry of Environment (2023) highlight that over 65% of industrial emissions originate from manufacturing activities, particularly in cement, petrochemical, textile, and food processing sectors. Despite this, the integration of green manufacturing principles has been slow due to inadequate policy enforcement, limited awareness, and financial constraints.

However, the global shift toward sustainability fuelled by commitments under the Paris Climate Agreement and the African Union's Agenda 2063 presents a compelling opportunity for Nigeria to reorient its industrial strategies toward green practices. The implications extend beyond climate mitigation to include innovation, employment, and competitive advantage in emerging green markets.

Notably energy use in factories and emissions from process-intensive sectors such as cement, steel, chemicals and basic metals remains a major contributor to global greenhouse-gas emissions. Energy-related CO₂ and process emissions from industry together account for a substantial share of global emissions, and recent global assessments highlight that without concerted industrial transformation the emissions gap to the Paris targets will persist. Moreover,

some manufacturing processes release potent, long-lived fluorinated gases and other industrial greenhouse gases that require targeted mitigation. These facts establish manufacturing as both a core driver of anthropogenic climate change and a critical leverage point for mitigation through technological, managerial and policy interventions.

Sustainability in manufacturing means moving beyond single-factor improvements (e.g., energy savings) toward systemic change across design, production, supply chains and end-of-life management. Approaches such as Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), circular economy strategies (reuse, remanufacture, recycling), adoption of low-carbon energy sources, and digital optimisation via Industry 4.0 technologies have demonstrated measurable reductions in resource intensity and carbon footprints. Importantly, sustainability delivers co-benefits — reduced operating costs, improved regulatory compliance, enhanced brand value and job creation in green sectors — making the business case for green manufacturing increasingly compelling. Recent reviews emphasize that digitalisation (IoT, AI, big data) can accelerate sustainability goals when paired with sound environmental metrics and policy support.

Despite clear technical pathways and demonstrated pilot successes, many manufacturers — particularly small and medium enterprises and firms in emerging economies — face substantial obstacles to adopting green manufacturing: high up-front capital costs, fragmented supply chains, limited technical capacity, and weak policy incentives. Additionally, gaps exist in translating lifecycle-based evidence (for example, LCA) into routine managerial decisions, and in integrating digital tools with environmental objectives in a way that is affordable and scalable. This paper is motivated by the urgent need to (a) synthesize the contemporary evidence linking green manufacturing actions to climate and sustainable development outcomes, (b) identify the main implementation barriers in diverse contexts, and (c) propose focused strategies that accelerate adoption without sacrificing competitiveness. Filling these gaps will help policymakers, industry leaders and researchers prioritise interventions that yield the largest sustainability returns.

This study has three primary objectives:

1. To provide a concise synthesis of the conceptual foundations and recent empirical evidence that link green manufacturing practices to reductions in greenhouse-gas emissions and broader sustainable development goals.
2. To analyse technological, economic and institutional barriers that limit the diffusion of green manufacturing, with attention to industry heterogeneity and the specific constraints faced in developing regions.
3. To provide pragmatic, evidence-based policy and managerial strategies

Conceptual and Theoretical Framework

Green manufacturing is rooted in the broader theoretical constructs of sustainable development and ecological modernization theory. Sustainable development, as defined by the Brundtland Commission (1987), advocates for meeting present needs without compromising future generations' ability to meet theirs. Within this framework, manufacturing becomes sustainable when it simultaneously promotes economic growth, social welfare, and environmental integrity (Adeleke, 2021).

Ecological modernization theory (EMT) further underpins this research by asserting that technological innovation and institutional reform can decouple economic progress from environmental harm. EMT posits that industrial transformation is not only possible but necessary for achieving sustainability (Mol and Spaargaren, 2019). This theory provides a strong analytical

lens for understanding how Nigeria’s manufacturing sector can evolve from pollution-intensive processes to innovation-driven green production systems.

Conceptual Framework of Green Manufacturing as a Tool for Sustainable Development

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of Green Manufacturing as a Tool for Sustainable Development(Source: adapted from UNEP, 2023 and FMEnv, 2024).

In the context of Africa, where manufacturing accounts for nearly 12% of total GDP (AfDB, 2022), green manufacturing represents a critical pivot for industrial diversification and resilience. The diffusion of green technologies—such as biomass conversion, energy-efficient machinery, and renewable energy integration—has demonstrated measurable benefits in reducing emissions and resource consumption (Eneh, 2023).

Table 1: Comparative Overview of Conventional vs Green Manufacturing Approaches

Parameter	Conventional Manufacturing	Green Manufacturing
Energy Source	Fossil fuels	Renewable/clean energy
Waste Management	Linear (produce–use–dispose)	Circular (reuse–recycle–recover)
Material Use	Resource-intensive	Resource-efficient
Production Process	Emission-heavy	Low-carbon and optimized
Economic Model	Profit-driven	Sustainability-driven

(Source: Author, 2025, compiled from UNEP and AfDB data)

Methodology

This study adopted a qualitative-descriptive research design complemented by secondary quantitative data to explore the role of green manufacturing in promoting sustainable development and mitigating climate change in Nigeria and Africa. The choice of design was

informed by the study’s aim to synthesize patterns, policy trends, and case-based evidence from multiple sources to construct a holistic understanding of green manufacturing dynamics within the regional context.

Data Sources and Collection

Data were drawn from reputable secondary sources including the Federal Ministry of Environment (FMEnv, 2024), National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2023), African Development Bank (AfDB, 2022), United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP, 2023), and peer-reviewed academic journals (2018–2025). Reports on energy consumption, industrial emissions, manufacturing performance, and sustainability policies were systematically reviewed.

A total of 62 documents were analyzed, comprising government reports, journal articles, and conference papers. Data triangulation was applied to ensure validity and reliability.

Analytical Framework

The analytical approach combined thematic content analysis and comparative trend evaluation. Thematic analysis was used to identify recurring themes such as “policy gaps,” “technological innovation,” “economic incentives,” and “environmental performance.” Comparative evaluation was employed to contrast conventional and green manufacturing outcomes, focusing on energy efficiency, emission intensity, and economic returns.

To structure the interpretation of findings, the study used the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) model — emphasizing the integration of economic, environmental, and social sustainability dimensions.

Table 2: Analytical Framework Based on the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) Model

Sustainability Pillar	Focus Area	Indicators Used	Expected Impact
Economic	Industrial competitiveness and productivity	Cost efficiency, profitability, innovation rate	Increased firm competitiveness
Environmental	Resource and emission management	Carbon reduction, waste recycling rate	Improved ecological balance
Social	Employment and welfare outcomes	Job creation, occupational health	Inclusive and equitable growth

(Source: Author, 2025; adapted from Elkington, 1998; UNEP, 2023).

Scope and Limitations

The study focuses on Nigeria as the primary case, with comparative insights from South Africa, Kenya, and Egypt, representing Africa’s leading industrial economies. While the study relies on secondary data, it ensures accuracy through triangulation across verified institutional sources. Limitations include unavailability of disaggregated sectoral data for small-scale industries and possible underreporting of informal manufacturing emissions.

Results and Discussion

The results of this study confirm that green manufacturing has begun to gain measurable traction in Nigeria’s industrial landscape and demonstrates that green manufacturing practices have a measurable and positive impact on environmental performance, economic productivity, and social welfare in Nigeria and Africa. When interpreted through the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) framework, the findings demonstrate that cleaner production technologies, circular economy practices, and eco-innovations significantly improve industrial sustainability outcomes. Key findings are grouped under five thematic areas: Emission Reduction and Climate Mitigation; Resource Efficiency and Circular Economy Transition; Policy Evolution and Institutional Support; Socio-Economic Impact; and Technological Adoption and Innovation Diffusion.

Emission Reduction and Climate Mitigation

Analysis of data from FMEnv (2024) and UNEP (2023) shows that industrial CO₂ emissions in Nigeria decreased by approximately 12.7% between 2018 and 2024 due to improved energy efficiency measures and cleaner production technologies. The cement and beverage industries recorded the most significant declines following the adoption of solar-assisted production systems and process heat recovery methods.

Comparatively, Adeleke (2021) reported that green manufacturing interventions in West Africa led to 10–15% emission cuts within 5 years, closely matching the reductions recorded in this study. The sharper reductions in Nigeria’s cement sector also mirror findings by the International Energy Agency (2022), which highlighted cement as one of the fastest-adopting industries of alternative fuels globally. However, unlike the South African case, where carbon-pricing accelerated adoption (AfDB, 2022), Nigeria’s progress appears driven mainly by firm-level efficiency gains rather than regulatory pressures suggesting that policy mechanisms remain underutilized.

Table 3: Trends in Industrial CO₂ Emission Reduction in Nigeria (2018–2024)

Sector	2018 Emission (MtCO ₂ e)	2024 Emission (MtCO ₂ e)	Reduction (%)	Key Green Initiative
Cement	17.5	14.1	19.4	Alternative fuels, waste heat recovery
Food and Beverage	9.8	8.1	17.3	Solar-assisted processing

Textile	5.2	4.6	11.5	Energy-efficient machinery
Petrochemical	12.4	11.0	11.3	Cleaner production process
Metal Fabrication	6.3	5.9	6.3	Emission filtration technology

(Source: *FME*nv, 2024; Author’s compilation).

These reductions underscore that even partial transitions to green manufacturing technologies yield substantial climate benefits.

Resource Efficiency and Circular Economy Transition

Green manufacturing has also improved resource productivity, particularly in energy and material usage. According to NBS (2023), firms adopting circular economy models recorded 25–40% savings in raw material inputs. Sectors such as packaging, plastics, and metal fabrication demonstrated significant reuse and recycling practices, reducing landfill waste and conserving virgin resources. These findings corroborate previous studies by Chukwuma and Nwachukwu (2022), who observed that Nigerian firms using closed-loop recycling improved material efficiency by roughly one-third. Similarly, Ogedengbe (2023) argued that resource savings in African green manufacturing rarely fall below 20%, typically clustering around 30–45% efficiency gains.

One notable insight from the current study is that the packaging and plastics sectors recorded the highest savings (35–40%), which exceeds figures reported in Kenya and Egypt (20–30% savings; AfDB, 2022). This suggests that Nigeria’s recycling and material-reuse subsector may be evolving more rapidly due to strong private-sector involvement in plastics repurposing, a trend less visible in earlier comparative studies.

Figure 2: Circular Economy Gains from Green Manufacturing in Selected Nigerian Sectors

This trend indicates growing industrial awareness of the economic benefits of green efficiency, which extends beyond compliance to profitability.

Policy Evolution and Institutional Support

The evolution of Nigeria’s green industrial policy has been gradual but promising. The National Policy on Climate Change (2021) and the Energy Transition Plan (2022) provide frameworks for integrating sustainability into industrial processes. However, implementation gaps remain due to limited inter-agency coordination and funding constraints. Prior studies (Mol and Spaargaren, 2019) have long argued that policy inconsistencies hinder the ecological modernization of developing economies; the present results reinforce this standpoint.

A comparative policy review reveals that South Africa leads Africa in green manufacturing incentives, offering tax rebates and carbon credit trading, while Kenya leverages renewable energy investments to enhance industrial sustainability. Nigeria’s current momentum, if consolidated through the establishment of a Green Manufacturing Development Fund (GMDF), could fast-track industrial decarbonization and sustainable growth. However, South Africa’s Green Economy Accord and Egypt’s Vision 2030 have resulted in more structured incentives such as carbon tax rebates and renewable-energy subsidies. UNEP (2023) also documented that Kenya’s climate-policy enforcement outpaces Nigeria’s due to stronger cross-ministry coordination. Thus, while Nigeria’s policy direction aligns with global best practices, its limited implementation capacity continues to slow down meaningful industrial decarbonization.

Socio-Economic Impact

The social dimension of green manufacturing is equally compelling. Transitioning to low-carbon industries has stimulated job creation in renewable energy, waste management, and green design. Between 2018 and 2024, the International Labour Organization (ILO, 2024) estimated that green sectors created over 620,000 jobs in Sub-Saharan Africa, with Nigeria contributing roughly 27% of this figure.

The finding that renewable-energy and recycling sectors dominate green job expansion also mirrors patterns observed in South Africa and Egypt (AfDB, 2023). However, the Nigerian context displays greater job concentration in SMEs, unlike Egypt where large industries drive green employment. This difference emphasizes the role of Nigeria’s expanding informal and semi-formal sector in absorbing new green labour opportunities, a nuance not extensively highlighted in previous studies.

Table 4: Employment Growth in Green Manufacturing Sectors (2018–2024)

Country	Green Jobs Created	Key Growth Sectors	Policy Drivers
Nigeria	167,000	Renewable energy, recycling, eco-design	Energy Transition Plan
South	195,000	Carbon trading, waste-	Green Economy Accord

Africa		to-energy	
Kenya	112,000	Clean energy, bio-industries	National Climate Change Action Plan
Egypt	146,000	Green construction, eco-industries	Egypt Vision 2030

(Source: ILO, 2024; AfDB, 2023).

These findings confirm that the green manufacturing shift not only mitigates climate risks but also advances inclusive economic growth and sustainable livelihoods.

Technological Adoption and Innovation Diffusion

This study found notable strides in deploying solar-assisted systems, waste-heat recovery, filtration technologies, and energy-efficient machinery. These findings match the conclusions of Jamwal et al. (2021), who stressed that Industry 4.0 technologies strengthen sustainability by reducing energy intensity and automating waste minimization.

However, unlike earlier studies that emphasize high-tech adoption in Asia and Europe, the present study shows that Nigeria’s adoption pattern is moderate but rising, driven largely by cost-saving motives rather than environmental compliance. This reinforces Bendig (2023), who noted that in emerging economies, green manufacturing is primarily adopted for economic competitiveness before environmental goals. Thus, the Nigerian trajectory reflects a typical developmental progression documented in global literature.

Comparison With Earlier Empirical Evidence

Overall, the results of this study are consistent with existing literature, but they also highlight new dynamics:

Table 5: Comparison with Earlier Empirical Evidence

Key Variable	Findings from Current Study	Findings from Previous Studies	Comparison
Emission Reduction	12.7% decrease (2018–2024)	10–15% reduction over similar timelines (Adeleke, 2021; UNEP, 2023)	Strong alignment
Circular Efficiency	25–40% resource savings	20–35% (Chukwuma and Nwachukwu, 2022)	Slightly higher in Nigeria’s plastics/packaging sectors
Policy Impact	Weak	Similar challenges	Reinforces earlier

	enforcement; strong frameworks	across developing countries (Mol and Spaargaren, 2019)	findings
Job Creation	167,000 green jobs	Strong growth across Africa (ILO, 2024)	Directionally consistent
Technology Adoption	Moderate but rising	Slow but incremental (Bendig, 2023)	Confirmatory

The consistency between the present study and earlier empirical evidence confirms that Nigeria is experiencing the typical transitional pathway noted in global ecological modernization, where industry-led initiatives precede comprehensive government-driven frameworks.

Challenges and Policy Implications of Green Manufacturing

Despite its potential, green manufacturing in Nigeria and Africa faces systemic challenges:

1. **High Initial Investment Costs:** Many manufacturers cite high costs of energy-efficient machinery and renewable installations as a key deterrent (AfDB, 2022).
2. **Weak Institutional Frameworks:** Environmental policies often lack enforcement mechanisms, leading to partial compliance.
3. **Limited Technical Expertise:** The scarcity of engineers and technicians skilled in clean technologies hinders adoption.
4. **Inadequate Financing Mechanisms:** There is limited access to green credit facilities and sustainability-linked bonds.
5. **Cultural and Informal Sector Barriers:** Many SMEs operate informally, outside regulatory oversight, and are resistant to green transitions.

Addressing these constraints requires integrated policies that link environmental governance with industrial competitiveness.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study demonstrates that green manufacturing is both a tool for sustainable development and a potent antidote to climate change in Nigeria and across Africa. By combining technological innovation, efficient resource use, and strong policy support, nations can achieve industrial growth without ecological degradation.

Green manufacturing transforms the production landscape from pollution-intensive industries to low-carbon, resource-efficient systems that align with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs 7, 9, 12, and 13). The study concludes that Nigeria’s pathway to climate resilience lies in fully embedding green manufacturing within national development frameworks. Future gains, however, depend heavily on policy enforcement, financing mechanisms, and technological capacity-building.

- i. Institutionalize Green Industrial Policies: Nigeria should establish a dedicated National Green Manufacturing Council to coordinate multi-sectoral efforts.
- ii. Expand Green Financing Instruments: Introduce tax incentives, carbon credits, and soft loans for industries investing in renewable technologies.
- iii. Build Technical Capacity: Universities and polytechnics should integrate Green Engineering and Manufacturing into curricula.
- iv. Promote Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs): Collaborative research between academia, government, and industry can fast-track innovation diffusion.
- v. Strengthen Regulatory Oversight: Enforcement of emission standards through digital monitoring systems is essential.

This paper makes the following contributions to knowledge:

- i. The study provides updated, sector-specific evidence showing a 12.7% decline in industrial CO₂ emissions (2018–2024), demonstrating how targeted green technologies significantly reduce emissions in Nigeria’s major manufacturing sectors.
- ii. It reveals 25–40% raw material savings across key industries, offering one of the clearest Nigerian datasets showing how recycling, reuse, and material recovery drive resource efficiency.
- iii. The findings show that Nigeria’s transition to green manufacturing is driven more by cost-saving motives than regulatory pressure, adding new context-specific insight to ecological modernization theory.

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Effect of Climate Smart Agricultural (CSA) Practices on Increase in Food Production in Imo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The goal to achieve self sufficient in food production has still not been achieved by agricultural stakeholders in Nigeria due to challenges that emanate from adverse climatic changes which has become prominent this days. To close this gap the researchers carried out an investigates on the impact of CSA on increase in food production in Imo States, Nigeria. The study Specifically describe farmers awareness, level of adoption of CSA, impact of the adoption of CSA on food production and constraints faced by farmers in adoption of CSA. We adopted multistage sampling technique for the selection of 120 farmers. The data were collected through the use of structured questionnaire and oral interview. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics, rank order and mean score of Likert-type rating scale. The results reveal that majority of the respondents representing 64% claimed unaware of CSA, while only 36% are aware of it. Secondly, mixed cropping ($\bar{x}= 3.408333$) is highly adopted as CSA practice by the farmers and the none adopted were agro-forestry (1.65) and artificial intelligent technology ($\bar{x}= 1.55$). The test on impact, farmers generally commended that CSA increasing productivity ($\bar{x}= 3.5$). The study revealed inadequate extension services (13.63%) as the main constraint. The study concluded that majority of the farmers are not aware of CSA which they are already practicing. Therefore the study recommended that proper orientation on CSA should be extended to farmers through adequate extension services to encourage them increase production through adoption of CSA farming.

Keywords: Agricultural Practices, Climate, Climate Smart Agricultural, Food Production and Increase

Introduction

Nigeria is an agric dependent country (70% of its population depend on agriculture for their livelihood) with a largely subsistence-based agricultural sector (88.4% are small holders) and a very rapidly growing population (Cervigni *et al.*, 2013, UN 2022). It is assumed that agriculture is the backbone of Nigeria economy. Agricultural production in most developing countries particularly Nigeria is weather dependants, most times adverse climatic situation emanate which becomes a threat to increase food production when it occur. In most adverse countries the challenges imposed by this adverse climate has been over come through the use of CSA. Recently, developing countries like Nigeria try to join suit by going into CSA in other to boast food production in the country.

Climate is an important factor for agricultural productivity and any variation in these factors is bound to result in a larger impact on crop yield (Ashalatha *et al.*, 2012). Symptoms of climate change include global warming, prolonged drought leading to crop losses, erratic rainfall patterns, glacier melting, displacement of populations due to floods, and devastation caused by cyclones and hurricanes.

Smallholder farmers are heterogeneous in nature and they will prefer to adopt combinations of practices in order to address varying constraints they encountered. Considering economic rationality assumption, smallholder farmers who depend on food production for livelihood sustenance would adopt technologies that reduce costs of production with increasing benefits from greater incomes through improved yields Oyewole *et al* (2022).

As a response for the need to increase food security without compromising environmental quality and in support of the Paris Agreement on climate change, FAO developed the concept of Climate Smart Agriculture (CSA) (FAO, 2018, IPCC, 2019). Climate smart agriculture (CSA) is an approach to transform farming that aims to deliver positive outcomes on three impact pillars, namely, intensification, adaptation, and mitigation to support food security under the new realities of climate change (Lipper *et al.*, 2014, Taylor 2018). Climate-smart agriculture (CSA) practices seek to mitigate agriculture's contribution to climate change while building resilience and adaptation to the impacts of climate change and increasing the production of food crops. CSA is an approach to identify production systems that can best respond to the impacts of climate change and to adjust these systems to suit local conditions (Gabriel *et al.* (2023).

The climate-smart agriculture (CSA) concept reflects an ambition to improve the integration of agriculture development and climate responsiveness. It aims to achieve food security and broader development goals under a changing climate and increasing food demand. CSA initiatives sustainably increase productivity, enhance resilience, and reduce greenhouse gases (GHGs), and require planning to address tradeoffs and synergies between these three pillars: productivity, adaptation, and mitigation. (FAO, 2010). While the concept is new, and still evolving, many of the practices that make up CSA already exist worldwide and are used by farmers to cope with various production risks (FAO, 2013). Some CSA practices (e.g. intercropping/multiple cropping, agro forestry, conservation agriculture etc.) are quite widespread and their proliferation has been facilitated by ease of adoption, and multiple benefits such as food, income diversification and improved resilience.

Climate-smart agriculture (CSA) is climate change adaption technique that encourages development of agricultural systems with a set of practice and approach capable of achieving multiple objectives such as improved food security, increased resilience in food production and low-emissions development (FAO, 2010). CSA focused on the strategic effort of integrating climate change and agriculture in development planning with a view of aggregating opportunities to link adaptation and mitigation efforts. The approach aims to ensure planning around climate change and agriculture is holistic, maximizing multiple outcomes and minimizing tradeoffs in management of food systems that generates significant quantity of green house gas (World Bank, 2011).

Climate smart agricultural practices remains an adaptive strategies that must be promoted to address climate change problem and declining agricultural productivity with poor resource use among smallholder farmers in Nigeria Oyewole *et al* (2022). Climate smart agriculture include proven practical techniques like; mulching, intercropping, conservation of agriculture, crop rotation, integrated cop-livestock management, agro-forestry, improved grazing, and improved water management.

According to FAO (2010), CSA practices are seen as the means to achieve resilience at the same time reducing environmental degradation. Climate-smart agriculture (CSA) helps promote sustainable and resilient agricultural practices in the face of climate change. It encompasses three pillars: increasing productivity and income, enhancing adaptation to climate change and reducing greenhouse gas emissions. CSA integrates traditional knowledge with modern technologies to optimize resource use, conserve biodiversity, and foster climate resilience in farming systems Kuku and Okonkwo (2023).

Agriculture in Nigeria must undergo a major transformation in the coming decades in order to meet the intertwined challenges of achieving food security, reducing poverty and responding to climate change without depletion of the natural resource base. Although there has been a rapid uptake of CSA by national organizations and the international community, implementation of the approach is still in its infancy and equally challenging partly due to lack of tools, capacity and experience in developing countries. CSA is still evolving and faces a number of challenges related to awareness, adoption, practice, conceptual understanding, policy, environment, social and economic issues Opeyemi, *et al* (2021). This study therefore, evaluates the impact of climate smart agricultural (CSA) practices on food production in Imo States, Nigeria

Despite substantial efforts to mainstream climate change adaptation into its developmental agenda and policies, Nigeria is still grappling with challenges in achieving the desired results. Some of these challenges include funding, capacity building, and poor technical skills. Other challenges include lack of synergy, coordination and collaboration by stakeholders, and a lack of target-setting, monitoring, and evaluation, which gave room to overlaps, duplication of efforts and a greater cost burden. Poor communication is another problem reducing the effectiveness of adaptation efforts in the country. The lack of active involvement of the sub-national governments (especially the local governments) and indigenous people constitutes a major barrier to effective and inclusive National Adaptation Plan (NAP) implementation in the country Kuku and Okonkwo (2023).

Climate change has caused significant impacts on resources that are useful for agricultural production and food security (FAO, 2013). Persistent increase in temperature and irregular rainfall pattern affects food production with attendant decline in crop and livestock output. Addressing the menace caused by climate change has proved challenging. Low returns from agricultural production has been attributed to varying weather condition with great effect on many ecosystem services such as nutrient cycling, nitrogen fixation, soil regeneration and pest and disease control through biological method. Hence, these have impacted adversely on sustainable food production among smallholder farmers (Lee, 2005; Teklewold *et al.*, 2013).

The specific objectives of this study include to;

i. identify farmers awareness of climate smart agricultural practices;

- ii. ascertain level of adoption of climate smart agricultural practices by farmers in the study area;
- iii. examine the impact of the adoption of climate smart agricultural practices on food production;
- iv. identify the constraints faced by farmers in climate smart agricultural practices adoption.

Methodology

This study was conducted in Imo state, Nigeria. Imo State lies within Latitudes 4°45'N and 7°15' N, and between Longitude 6°50'E and 7°02'5'E of the Greenwich meridian with an area of around 5,100sqkm (Vanguard, Nigeria, 2015). The State has a population of about 4.13 million people (NPC, 2013). It is bounded on the East by Abia state, on the North by Anambra and Abia State, and on the West by Rivers State. The State is divided into 27 administrative units called Local Government Areas which are grouped into 3 agricultural zones viz Owerri, Okigwe and Orlu. Agriculture is the predominant occupation of the people. The ecological zone favours the growing of tree crops, roots and tubers, cereals, vegetables and nuts. These crops are grown in small holder plots usually in mixtures of at least two simultaneous crops. Major animals reared include chicken, turkey, goats, sheep and pigs (Onyenwaku and Nwachukwu, 2010).

Figure 1: Map of Imo State Showing the Agricultural Zones. (Department of Geography, Imo State University, Owerri, Nigeria).

This study used multistage sampling procedure for the selection of 120 registered crop farmers in Imo State. The first stage involved purposive selection of three Agricultural zones in Imo State due to changes in their few climatic factors and different in their soil formation and geomorphology. In the second stage, two Local Government Areas (LGAs) were randomly selected from each agricultural zone. In the third stage, five communities were randomly selected from each of the selected LGAs. In the fourth stage, one village was randomly selected from each community. Finally, four crop farmers were randomly selected from each of the villages to give a sample size of 120 respondents for the study as sample size. Random sampling was employed in this study to ensure equal chances of the element to be selected. Primary data were

used for the study. The data were collected through the use of structured questionnaire and oral interview. These questionnaires were administered to the respondents by the trained enumerators. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics, rank order and mean score. Objectives i and iv were achieved using descriptive statistics (pie chart, percentage and standard deviation) while objectives ii and iii were achieved using mean score to be computed on a Likert-type rating scale of highly adopted, moderately adopted, partially adopted and no adoption and strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed respectively, assigned weight of 4, 3, 2, and 1. The score was added to give 10 divided by 4 to give 2.50 which is the discriminating index. So any value (≥ 2.5 and $< 2.5 - \geq 1$) was taken as adoption of CSA while any value that falls within (≤ 1) was taken as non adoption of CSA. For impact of adoption on CSA decision rule: mean ≥ 2.25 indicates positive impact; mean < 2.25 indicates negative impact.

Table 1: Population of the Study

S/N	Agricultural Zones in Imo State	LGAs	Communities	Village	N0 of Farmers (sample size)
1	Owerri	Ikeduru Ngor Okpala	5	1*5=10	4 *5 =20
			5	1*5=10	4 *5 =20
2	Okigwe	Ehime Mbanu Onuimo	5	1*5=10	4 *5 =20
			5	1*5=10	4 *5 =20
3	Orlu	Nwangele Oguta	5	1*5=10	4 *5 =20
			5	1*5=10	4 *5 =20
Total	3	6	30	60	120

Table 1: Sampling and Sample Proportion for the Study. Source: Author’s own construct, (2025).

Results and Discussion

Farmers Awareness of Climate Smart Agricultural Practices

Figure 2: Distribution of farmers on Awareness of Climate Smart Agricultural Practices

(Source: Field survey, 2025).

From the responses gathered majority of the respondents representing 64% are not aware of any climate smart agriculture in the study, while 36% claimed awareness of CSA and they are practicing it. The survey draw reference from utilization were majority of the farmers has adopted most of the CSA without knowing based on their traditional practice. This implies that CSA is a mixture of cultural and modern agriculture. The study is in line with FAO report that many of the practices that make up CSA already exist worldwide and are used by farmers to cope with various production risks. Some CSA practices (e.g. intercropping/multiple cropping, agro forestry, conservation agriculture etc.) are quite widespread and their proliferation has been facilitated by ease of adoption, and multiple benefits such as food, income diversification and improved resilience (FAO, 2013).

Farmers Level of Adoption of Climate Smart Agricultural Practices

Table 2: Distribution of farmers based on Level of Adoption of Climate Smart Agricultural Practices

CSA Practices adopt	Highly Adopted	Moderately adopted	Partially adopted	Not adopted	Total Score	Mean Score	Remark
	4	3	2	1			
	F Score	F Score	F Score	F Score			
Agro-forestry	13 (52)	12 (36)	15 (30)	80 (80)	198	1.65	Not adopted
Crop rotation	60 (240)	23 (69)	12 (24)	25 (25)	358	2.983333	Highly adopted
Mixed cropping	80 (320)	20 (60)	9 (18)	11 (11)	409	3.408333	Highly adopted
Improved crop varieties	70 (280)	30 (90)	8 (16)	12 (12)	398	3.316667	Highly adopted
Intercropping	30 (120)	56 (168)	24 (48)	10 (10)	346	2.883333	Highly adopted
Compost making	25 (100)	25 (75)	28 (48)	42 (42)	265	2.208333	Partially adopted
Fallowing	30 (120)	49 (147)	20 (40)	21 (21)	328	2.733333	Highly adopted
Organic manure	40 (160)	30 (60)	28 (56)	22 (22)	298	2.483333	Highly adopted
Mulching	22 (88)	35 (105)	33 (66)	30 (30)	289	2.408333	Moderately adopted
Cover crops	30 (120)	42 (126)	30 (60)	18 (18)	324	2.7	Highly adopted
Mixed farming	18 (72)	25 (75)	40 (80)	37 (37)	264	2.2	Partially adopted
Soil conservation practices	40 (160)	45 (135)	25 (50)	10 (10)	355	2.958333	Highly adopted
Bag cropping	35 (140)	40 (120)	32 (64)	13 (13)	337	2.808333	Highly adopted
Artificial Intelligent technology (using drone, using robots for task)	8 (32)	12 (36)	18 (36)	82 (82)	186	1.55	Not adopted
improved water management	18 (72)	30 (90)	38 (76)	34 (34)	272	2.266667	Partially adopted

(irrigation, rain water harvesting)							
Grand Total					4627		

Source: Field survey, 2025.

Multiple responses were recorded

The level of adaptation was measured using a 4 point likert-type scale, the study shows that the major climatic smart agriculture adaptation measures farmers practiced were mixed cropping (\bar{x} = 3.408333), improved crop varieties (\bar{x} = 3.316667), crop rotation (\bar{x} = 2.983333), soil conservation practices (\bar{x} = 2.958333), intercropping (\bar{x} = 2.883333), bag cropping (\bar{x} = 2.808333), fallowing (\bar{x} = 2.733333), cover crops (\bar{x} = 2.7) and organic manure (\bar{x} = 2.5) the farmers accepted that they highly adopted. Mulching (\bar{x} = 2.408333) was moderately adopted, improved water management (\bar{x} = 2.266667), mixed farming (\bar{x} = 2.2) were partially adopted while agro-forestry (1.65) and artificial intelligent technology (\bar{x} = 1.55) were not adopted by farmers as the strategies they used in mitigating adverse weather effect.

The mean value of each attribute equal (≥ 2.5 and $< 2.5 - \geq 1$) was taken as adoption of CSP and were regarded as being an accepted decision while any value that falls within (≤ 1) was taken as not adopted and were regarded as a rejected decision. This implies that farmers in Imo State have various adaptation strategies in adapting to climate change to improve their output, sales, and standard of living through climatic smart agriculture. This finding is not in with the literature that adoption of CSA is low among smallholder farmers in sub-Sahara Africa (Giller *et al.*, 2009; Usman *et al.*, 2021). The reasons for high adoption in Imo State could be that farmers in the study area are practicing CSA by culture which has existed over decades.

Impact of the Adoption of Climate Smart Agricultural Practices on Food Production in Study Area

Table 3: Distribution of Farmers Based on Impact of the Adoption of Climate Smart Agricultural Practices on Food Production

Impact of Adoption	SA	A	SDA	DA	Total	Mean	Remark
	4	3	2	1	Score	Score	
	F Score	F Score	F Score	F Score			
Increasing productivity	83 (332)	20 (60)	11 (22)	6 (6)	420	3.5	Acceptance
Increasing income	62 (248)	30 (90)	16 (32)	12 (12)	382	3.18333	Acceptance
Enhancing adaptation to climate change	51 (204)	48 (144)	7 (14)	14 (14)	376	3.13333	Acceptance
Improves soil water conservation	40 (160)	9 (27)	50 (100)	21 (21)	308	2.56667	Acceptance
Improve biodiversity	48 (192)	47 (141)	14 (28)	11 (11)	372	3.1	Acceptance
Reduces the effect of harsh weather impact	67 (268)	40 (120)	8 (16)	5 (5)	409	3.40833	Acceptance
Increased Food Security	9 (36)	32 (96)	71 (142)	8 (8)	282	2.35	Rejected
Improved Soil usage or management	44 (176)	40 (120)	22 (44)	14 (14)	354	2.95	Acceptance
Reduces land waste	55 (220)	50 (150)	10 (20)	5 (5)	395	3.29167	Acceptance
TOTAL					3298	27.4833	

Source: Field Survey, 2025. AS = Strongly agree, A = Agree, D = Disagree and SD = Strongly disagree.

The impact of adoption was measured using a 4 point Likert-type scale of strongly agree, agree, disagree and strongly disagree. The result shows that increasing productivity ($\bar{x}= 3.5$), reduces the effect of harsh weather impact ($\bar{x}= 3.40833$), reduces land waste ($\bar{x}= 3.29167$), increasing income ($\bar{x}= 3.18333$), enhancing adaptation to climate change ($\bar{x}= 3.13333$), improve biodiversity ($\bar{x}= 3.1$), improved soil usage or management ($\bar{x}= 2.95$), improves soil water conservation ($\bar{x}= 2.56667$), ‘ with their mean scores were agreed as the major impact of the adoption of climate smart agricultural practices on food production in study area while the farmer disagreed that the adoption leads to increased in food security ($\bar{x}= 2.35$). Any mean value of each attribute equal to 2.50 and above was taken to be accepted decision by the farmers as impact of CSA adoption in the study area. While attributes with mean value less than ($\bar{x}\geq 2.50$) was regarded as a rejected decision because the discriminatory index produced was 2.50. This implies that adoption of CSA have a positive impact on food production in Imo State.

Constraints Faced by Farmers in Climate Smart Agricultural Practices Adoption in the Study Area.

Table 4: Distribution of Farmers Based on Constraints

Variables	Frequency	Percentage	Mean	Standard Deviation	Rank Order
Poor capital and limited funding	50	8.52		19.63	7
Poor technical know how	62	10.56			5
Social-cultural issues.	55	9.37			6
Lack of synergy coordination ,	40	6.81	53.36		9
Poor target-setting	18	3.07			11
Poor incentives	63	10.73			4
Inadequate information	78	13.29			2
Inadequate extension services.	80	13.63			1
Limited availability of farmland	45	7.67			8
Low adoption rate	28	4.77			10
High cost of improve crop variety	68	11.58			3

Source: Field survey, 2025.

Multiple responses were recorded

The result on constraints confronting the ability of the farmers to adopt Climate Smart Agricultural practices in the study area revealed inadequate extension services which ranked first with (13.63%) followed by inadequate information (13.29%), high cost of improve crop variety (11.58%), poor incentives (10.73%), poor technical knowhow (10.56%) and social-cultural issues (9.37%) as the major barriers they faced in adapting climate smart agriculture change in the area. Improved and steady contact of farmers with extension agents is critical in improving farmers' information, access to input, innovation resulting to high yield and income and standard of living. Short coming on information poses threat to the farmers’ adoption to CSA and this mainly centered on effective agricultural extension services packages. The finding is in line with the studies of Esiobu *et al.* (2021) who reported that extension contact improves farmers' access to recent information and expertise of contemporary farming techniques to raise their yield, income and standard of living. Among others are poor capital and limited funding (8.52%),

limited availability of farmland (7.67%), lack of synergy coordination (6.81%), low adoption rate (4.77%) and poor target-setting (3.07%). With mean and standard deviation of (\bar{x} = 53.36; σ = 19.63), the values of standard deviation (σ) denote the degree of variation in the responses of the farmers perceived on their challenges on adoption of CSA in the area. The standard deviation value indicates low variances in farmers' response regarding their adoption challenges in CSA. This indicates that the challenges faced by farmers in the study area are closely related.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Despite the potential roles of agriculture in Nigeria economic growth and achievement of food security objective, food is produced less than required by most households creating wide food demand gap due to low productivity caused by adverse climatic factors. Unusual climate condition is recognized as major threats to agricultural productivity in several regions of the world. Because of this, most farmers tend to sort solution using climatic smart agriculture (CSA) in other to increase food production.

Agriculture in Nigeria must undergo a major transformation in the coming decades in order to meet the intertwined challenges of achieving food security, reducing poverty and responding to climate change without depletion of the natural resource base. This research on impact of CSA on food production increase becomes in disposable if Nigeria must achieve self sufficient and reliability in food production. The study recommended that the existing method of our agricultural extension services should be re-strategies to update the services of agricultural extension agents, information on modern technologies like AI use of improve varieties, resent agronomic practice etc should be disseminate to farmers at easy.

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Strategic Thinking Competences As Correlates of Okobi-Spirited Farming In Owerri Communities

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Abstract

The One Kindred One Business Initiative (OKOBI) which is an innovative business philosophy of the Hope Uzodimma-led Imo State Government has unarguably created a lot of research gaps which call for sustainability and goal-oriented research. This study investigates strategic thinking competences and OKOBI-spirited farming in Owerri communities. The objectives of the study are to investigate the level of correlation between creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming; assess the level of correlation between creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming; evaluate the level of correlation between relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming; and ascertain the level of correlation between relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities. Four research questions and four hypotheses guide the study. It adopts the survey research design. A structured questionnaire was the major instrument for data collection. It employs the Cronbach Alpha statistic to obtain the value of 0.83 as the instrument reliability ratio. The research commits data analysis to descriptive and inferential statistics for data analysis. It finds a positive and significant level of correlation between creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming; creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming; relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming; relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities. The study concludes that strategic thinking competences are correlates of OKOBI-spirited farming in Owerri communities. It recommends that management of OKOBI-spirited farms in Owerri communities should always think outside the box in sustainably managing their farms.

Keywords: Strategic thinking, Creative thinking, Relational thinking, OKOBI, Farming.

Introduction

Over the years, enterprises that yearn for survival and sustainability strive to articulate and develop competences that may enable them achieve their corporate outcomes. Top among the contemporary competences sought by 21st Century businesses include strategic thinking competences. Wilson (2025) sees strategic thinking as a very keystone for intentional as well as rational thought processes which are vital for handling the complexities of enterprises, team dynamics and individual endeavours. This implies that strategic thinking entails the proactive and creative as well as system-oriented process that is cognitive in nature but available to both managers and other leaders for analyzing complex situations; for anticipating future outcomes and for making informed decisions for the achievement of long-term corporate goals and for securing competitive advantage. This accounts for the reason why Njoku (2025) opines that strategic thinking is the process in which various factors and variables are considered in line with one's core objectives so as to develop action plans that are crystal clear.

There are various strategic thinking competences including creative thinking, practical thinking, relational thinking (Njoku, 2025), strategic leadership, leadership innovation (Olasehinde, Onibon, Adarabierin, Weya-Ajayi and Adewale, 2025). Others are strategic intelligence, innovative thinking (Ovivi and Ayasal, 2025), foresight, system thinking (Ogaji and Goni, 2025), focused intent, intelligent opportunism, thinking in time (Dahiru, 2025). All these show that strategic thinking competences are various indices of strategic thinking.

In the context of this study however, the term strategic thinking competences is the use of creative thinking and relational thinking to enhance One Kindred One Business Initiative-spirited (OKOBI-spirited) farming in Owerri communities. Creative thinking focuses on solving problems by developing innovative solutions. Usoro and Brownson (2024) believe that creative thinking involves solving problems through the force of imagination and the force of reasoning. It entails coming up with original solutions, solutions that are unique and innovative. Creative thinking is so essential that it is very relevant for business decision making (Wegwu, 2024).

Another strategic thinking competence which this study examines is relational thinking. Njoku (2025) maintains that relational thinking anchors on the need for collaboration and relationship building with stakeholders. It emphasizes paying attention to others' perspectives so as to work together to meet targets. Interpersonal relationships are important for making strategic choices hence people while interacting with each other must influence each other. In relational thinking, synergy is enhanced and sound human relations is made manifest. This is why Thornton and Hill (2023) describe human relations as the interactions which exist in corporate settings. Also, they are essential for the success of the organization (Gunthner, 2023). Relational thinking encompasses emotional intelligence – the ability one has to understand and manage one's emotions as well as the emotions of others (Keiling, 2025). In emotional intelligence, one recognizes, understands and manages one's own emotions and influence those of others. It has dimensions like self-awareness, motivation, self-regulation, social skills and empathy.

Strategic thinking competences may influence OKOBI-spirited farming in Owerri communities. Ikiebey (2025) describes OKOBI as a socio-economic philosophy for the sustainable development of Imo State. It epitomizes the Government's Kindred Economic Empowerment Paradigm (KEEP) of grassroot development, rooted in 'umunnamics' philosophy. The OKOBI programme fosters sustainable entrepreneurship by incentivizing each extended family unit or 'kindred' to establish one communally-owned enterprise aligned with their indigenous interests, passions, capabilities and resources. The kindred wholly lead and controls the business and OKOBI furnishes wider socioeconomic benefits aside the transformation of lives within local communities. Okiebey (2025) states that OKOBI mobilizes these tight-knit 'umunna' relationships through inclusive financing, training and a platform to jointly own and run micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) on a sustainable training and capacity building programmes in areas like entrepreneurship, agriculture and environmental sustainability. Historically, the Imo State Government started the OKOBI programme in the year 2022 and the Initiative formally kicked off as an economic philosophy early 2023. Around August 2024, the programme became mandatory for all 655 autonomous communities in the State, it is spearheaded by Professor Kenneth Amaeshi, the Chief Economic Adviser to the Imo State Government and who doubles as Chair in Sustainable Finance and Governance at European University Institute (Florence, 2024).

In the context of this study, OKOBI-spirited farming is the ability Owerri-based fish and pig farmers have to inculcate the philosophy and principles of OKOBI in their agro practices. Kindred in this context is not necessarily traditional kindreds but any enterprising group of people that come up with

a particular business interest and make it come to fruition. That is the OKOBI spirit. Such enterprising groups are kindreds and they can be clubs, colleagues, family members, traditional kinsmen, church groups, etc.

This study focuses on fish farming and pig farming. Fish farming otherwise called aquaculture, is an agro practice in which certain selected fish species are reared in enclosed water bodies like streams, ponds as well as rivers based on scientifically-controlled conditions and the fishes are fed, grown, bred and/or consumed. This agrees with the views of Adamu and Kawugana (2025) who posit that fish farming entails raising fish in commercial quantities in tanks or other enclosures. They reveal that fish farming boosts household income; it increases food security and it is a creator of direct as well as indirect job opportunities. There are technologies or innovations useful for fish farming including recirculating aquaculture systems (RAS) which can reuse as high as 99% of water, sophisticated biological and mechanical filtration systems for waste removal as well as advanced monitoring technologies that track water quality parameters continuously. There are also precision feeding technologies for waste reduction, water treatment solutions for maintaining optimal conditions and energy-efficient pumps and systems which are powered by renewable sources. The innovations are sound for creating farming environments which reduce ecological footprints and maximize fish health and fish growth (Finnforel, 2025).

Also, pig farming entails the agro practice of commercially raising domestic pigs for pork, for fats and indeed for other by-products. Onyekuru, Ukwuaba and Aka (2020) opine that the animal, pig, is monogastric and it has enormous potentials which makes the piggery ventures highly profitable and lucrative with capabilities to deal with hunger and poverty in the land. Edo, Ihejirika, Okoli and Okoli (2021) assert that in Imo State, pig farming breeds bad odour and it is associated with inappropriate dung disposal, animal noise and loss of friends by families. Strategic thinking may give room for use of technologies that could be helpful for pig farming including AI-powered monitoring for health and behavior, feeding and watering systems that are automated plus environmental controls that are advanced. Others include the use of sensors and the use of cameras for the purpose of weight and activity training, automated cleaning robots, systems for waste management and production of energy from manure. Indeed, applying artificial insemination in swine breeding activities is a major priority to the producers who seek to boost reproductive breeding as well as reproductive efficiency (Pokharel and Sharma, 2025).

This study on strategic thinking competences as correlates of OKOBI-spirited farming in Owerri communities is geared towards investigating how farmers employ creative thinking and relational thinking in their fish farming and pig farming activities. This is with a view to bridging research gaps and contributing to knowledge.

Statement of the Problem

The researchers have observed that many farms in Owerri communities are yet to employ strategic thinking competences for sound OKOBI-spirited fish farming and OKOBI-spirited piggery farming – a situation that has the capacity to adversely influence these kinds of farming with a view to weakening the OKOBI spirit and ideology in Owerri. It is ideal that any agro-based endeavour that desires to have resounding outcomes in a fiercely competitive business environment does everything within its powers to inculcate strategic thinking competences in its operations for the purposes of survival and sustainability. However, it is worrisome that many agro enterprises especially OKOBI-spirited fish and piggery farms in Owerri communities seem to find it difficult to embrace strategic thinking competences of creative thinking and relational thinking hence some of them have been

observed by the researchers to have taken no serious and significant steps to turn over new leaves. This has the capacity to weaken the ability of the enterprises to have sustainable farms that may continue to exist in the spirit of the One Kindred One Business Initiative (OKOBI) of the Distinguished Senator Hope Uzodimma-led Imo State Government. This situation exposes the farms to sudden collapse.

Indeed, the researchers also discovered wide research gaps in the area of strategic thinking hence the empirical studies accessed by the researchers did not assess how creative thinking influenced OKOBI-spirited fish farming and OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities. The accessed studies did not also assess the correlation between relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming and OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities. This study bridges these research gaps with a view to contributing to knowledge.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to investigate strategic thinking competences as correlates of OKOBI-spirited farming in Owerri communities. The study specifically intends to:

- i. investigate the level of correlation between creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming.
- ii. assess the level of correlation between creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming.
- iii. evaluate the level of correlation between relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming.
- iv. ascertain the level of correlation between relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities.

Research Questions

Based on the objectives of the study, the researchers developed the following research questions:

- i. What is the level of correlation between creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming in Owerri communities?
- ii. To what extent does creative thinking correlate with OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities?
- iii. How does relational thinking correlate with OKOBI-spirited fish farming in Owerri communities?
- iv. What is the level of correlation between relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities?

Hypotheses

In alignment with the research questions, the researchers developed the following null hypotheses:

H₀₁: There is no significant level of correlation between creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming in Owerri communities.

H₀₂: There is no significant extent to which creative thinking correlates with OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities.

H₀₃: There is no significant level of correlation between relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming in Owerri communities.

H₀₄: There is no significant level of correlation between relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities.

Scope of the Study

Geographically, the study focuses on Owerri Senatorial Zone, Imo State. The content scope shows the relationship between creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming, creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming, relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming, relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri Senatorial Zone. The unit scope comprises of the Chief Executives of the study enterprises. This is in agreement with the objectives of the study.

Theoretical Underpinning

Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory (1986)

Ogaji and Goni (2025) opine that the RBV is the work of Barney who developed it in the year 1986. It emphasizes the importance of an organization's internal resources and the firm's capabilities in the aspect of having competitive advantage. The theory supposes that enterprises have the capacity to gain such advantage if they develop and leverage on resources that are valuable, that are rare and inimitable and even non-substitutable.

The RBV insists that firms ought to internally assess themselves over uncommon strengths instead of relying on those market conditions that are external. Since organizations are seen as the collection of physical and both human and corporate resources, the theory posits that valuable resources, rare resources, resources that are imperfectly imitable and resources that are imperfectly substitutable constitute the core sources of advantages that are sustainably competitive thereby contributing to superior and high-level performance.

Indeed, the theory pays attention to the relevance of difficult-to-imitate corporate attributes as such is the source of superior performance. Such attributes remain typically unique for an organization; they are not easily transferred. In addition, they may require significant learning if not cultural changes should one attempt to replicate them. This suggests that variations in corporate performance among enterprises can be a function of the possession of such unique inputs as well as unique capabilities. Ogaji and Goni (2025) therefore maintain that Barney's RBV emphasizes that it is with valuable resources that enterprises can implement those strategies which beef efficiency and corporate effectiveness thereby positively influencing sales, cost reduction and margin increases.

The theory becomes relevant to this present study as creative strategic thinking requires internal innovative abilities of corporate human resources. Also, the relational strategic thinking competences showcase the abilities of the human resources to demonstrate their human relations skills in effectively navigating hurdles and human factors that may affect business performance.

Empirical Review

Njoku (2025) investigates 'strategic thinking and the formation of future leaders in Nigerian Naval institutions with a focus on Accounts, Budget and allied naval offices'. The objectives of the research include to determine the link between analytical strategic thinking and future leadership in Nigerian naval institutions; and to investigate the connection between creative strategic thinking and future

leadership in Nigerian naval institutions in Nigerian naval institutions. The study employs the extant literature method. It finds that analytical strategic thinking is essential for future leadership in Nigerian naval institutions; and there is a formidable connection between creative strategic thinking and future leadership in Nigerian naval institutions. The paper concludes that any naval institution that relegates strategic thinking to the background risks weak leadership in the future. It recommends among others that the Nigerian Navy needs to ensure that future leaders in its institutions demonstrate analytical thinking by being evidential and logical in their financial and allied dealings in the organizations.

Kamau, Ngina and Kyule (2025) investigate how strategic thinking impacts on the performance of quoted agribusiness companies in Nairobi, Kenya. Their study employs the survey research method. It commits data analysis to Cronbach's Alpha, Karl Pearson's correlation coefficient, regression analysis, mean and standard deviation. The study finds that the firms practice strategic thinking to a large extent; strategic thinking is mainly practiced in the agribusiness companies listed at the NSE. It recommends that policy makers should create clear regulatory frameworks that promote fair competition, support integration in the value chain and address sectoral challenges like resource constraints and market volatility.

Dhahi (2025) evaluated the effect of strategic thinking patterns on levels of organizational conflict by mediating employee job satisfaction: an analytical study of the opinions of a sample of employees at ThiQar University. The objectives of the study include to determine the nexus between strategic thinking patterns and levels of organizational conflict as well as the link between strategic thinking patterns and job satisfaction. It was a survey research. Descriptive statistical analytical method was employed as data analysis was committed to arithmetic mean, standard deviation and correlation. The study finds a positive and significant relationship between strategic thinking patterns and levels of organizational conflict; and a significant level of correlation between strategic thinking patterns and job satisfaction. The paper concludes that strategic thinking patterns and job satisfaction positively influence levels of organizational conflict. It recommends the need to train employees on strategic thinking patterns so as to improve their abilities to deal with conflicts in more effective ways.

Olasehinde, Onibon, Adarabierin, Weya-Ajayi and Adewale (2025) assessed strategic leadership and its effect on innovation and performance in Nigerian industries. The objectives of the study include to examine the relationship between strategic thinking and leadership innovation for enhanced organizational performance; and to evaluate the effect of leadership innovation on performance. The survey research design was adopted in the study. Data analysis was committed to descriptive statistics. The findings show a positive and significant relationship between strategic thinking and leadership innovation for enhanced organizational performance; a positive and significant relationship between leadership innovation and performance. The study concludes that fostering strategic thinking, promoting innovation, ensuring adequate resource allocation are important for optimizing leadership impact. It recommends that organizations should focus on innovation-driven culture.

Ovivi and Ayasal (2025) investigate strategic thinking and the implementation of business intelligence system of Coca-Cola Plc, Abuja, Nigeria. the study objectives include to find the relationship between system thinking and strategic intelligence; assess the relationship between critical thinking and competitive intelligence; and evaluate the nexus between innovative thinking and technological intelligence. The survey research method was used in the study. Data were analyzed with descriptive statistics and Partial Least Square-Structural Equation Model (PLS-SEM). The findings show a significant and positive relationship between system thinking and strategic

intelligence; critical thinking and competitive intelligence; innovative thinking and technological intelligence in Coca-Cola Nigeria Plc., Abuja. It concludes that strategic thinking drives the implementation of business intelligence system in the enterprise. The study recommends that management needs to strengthen strategic thinking practices to achieve organizational objectives.

Aribatise, Oladipo, Ahmodu, Yankey and Ibeka (2025) assessed strategic thinking, monetary policy rate and corporate performance of Deposit Money Banks in Nigeria. The objectives of the study include to ascertain how strategic thinking influences profitability and how monetary policy rate influences return on assets. It was an ex-post-facto research. Data analysis was done with Generalized Method of Moments (GMM). The study finds that strategic thinking positively drives profitability and that monetary policy rate negatively affects return on assets of bank profitability. The paper concludes that strategic thinking and monetary policy rate were drivers of corporate performance. It recommends that Nigerian banks need to strengthen strategic thinking capabilities to sustain profitability under volatile monetary conditions.

Ogaji and Goni (2025) examines the effect of strategic intelligence on performance of selected manufacturing firms in North East, Nigeria. The objectives of the study include to determine the relationship between foresight and performance as well as to investigate the nexus between system thinking and performance of the manufacturing firms. It was a survey research. The PLS-SEM statistic was used in handling data analysis. It was found that a positive and significant relationship exists between foresight and business performance. Also, there exists a positive and significant relationship between system thinking and business performance. The study concludes that strategic intelligence is necessary for corporate performance. It recommends training for employees on foresight methodologies and tools.

Dahiru (2025) evaluates strategic thinking and organizational performance of selected Pension Fund Administrators in Nigeria. The objectives include to determine how each of focused intent, intelligent opportunism, thinking in time, system perspective and hypothesis driven influence organizational performance. It was a survey research. Multiple regressions and Ordinary Least Square (OLS) were used for data analysis. While intelligent opportunism and hypothesis driven have positive and significant relationship with organizational performance, indices like focused intent, thinking in time, and system perspective showed negative relationship with organizational performance. The paper recommends for management to focus on long term market and competitors.

Iwuoha, Uzodimma and Njoku (2025) explored 'combating unemployment and youth criminality in Ala Igbo using akuruoulo principle: A focus on Imo State OKOBI'. The objectives of the study were to examine the relationship between OKOBI-akuruoulo principle and reduction of unemployment in Ala Igbo as well as determine the relationship between OKOBI-akuruoulo principle and youth criminality in Ala Igbo. It was a survey research. Data analysis was committed to descriptive statistics. The findings show a positive and significant relationship between OKOBI-akuruoulo principle and reduction of unemployment in Ala Igbo as well as a positive and significant link between OKOBI-akuruoulo principle and youth criminality in Ala Igbo. The study concludes that OKOBI-akuruoulo principle effectively addresses unemployment and youth criminality in Ala Igbo. It recommends addressing limited access to capital and business training.

Gap Identified in Literature

The literatures accessed by the researcher failed to assess the nexus between creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming; creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming; relational thinking

and OKOBI-spirited fish farming as well as relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities. This study bridges these gaps.

Methodology

The work adopts the survey research method. The population of the study comprises of the Chief Executives of four (4) OKOBI-spirited farms in each of the nine (9) Local Government Areas in Owerri Senatorial Zone. The companies were purposively chosen in consideration of convenience and security. The total population of the study is thirty-six (36). The study samples the whole population size because it is small. It is a census. Therefore, thirty-six copies of the research instrument (structured questionnaire) were administered to the respondents in the study farms. The data sources are the primary and secondary sources. Though the questionnaire instrument was the major instrument for data collection in the study, the researchers used journals, texts and internet sources for secondary data. The researchers determined the validity of the instrument by showing the research instrument to various research experts for their useful inputs (face validity). They also ensured that the research concentrated on the study objectives (content validity). Uzodimma, Iwuoha and Njoku (2025) believe that it is germane and appropriate that a study questionnaire agrees with study objectives. The reliability ratio of the instrument was done with the use of pilot study whose results were committed to Cronbach alpha statistic. A ratio of 0.83 was obtained. The instrument was therefore 83% reliable. The study employs the descriptive statistics of mean scores and standard deviation for data analysis. It uses Spearman rank correlation coefficient to test hypotheses. A study by Iwuoha, Uzodimma and Njoku (2025) showcases the relevance of mean score and correlations to survey research. Also, in this study, the rejection of null hypothesis is based on $P < 0.05$.

Data Presentation & Analysis/Discussion of Results

Out of the thirty-six (36) questionnaire copies distributed to the respondents, only 28 copies were properly filled and returned. This means 77.8% return.

Research Question 1:

What is the level of correlation between creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming in Owerri communities?

Table 1: Respondents’ responses on the level of correlation between creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming in Owerri communities

Q/No	Item	SA	A	UN	D	SD	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
1	Creative thinking enables OKOBI-spirited fish farmers to embrace green innovations for quality outputs.	12	10	3	1	2	28	4.04	0.804
2	With creative thinking OKOBI-spirited fish farmers plan effectively for the inculcation of Artificial Intelligence in their operations.	11	10	4	2	1	28	4.00	0.738

Field Survey (2025).

The Table 1 above presents data from responses by the respondents under study. The result also disclosed a strong agreement by the respondents on their opinion on the level of correlation between creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming in Owerri communities. The results further show that the respondents agreed to the facts that creative thinking enables OKOBI-spirited fish farmers to embrace green innovations for quality outputs ($\bar{x} \pm S.D$ of 4.04 ± 0.804); with creative thinking OKOBI-spirited fish farmers plan effectively for the inculcation of Artificial Intelligence in their operations (with a $\bar{x} \pm S.D$ of 4.00 ± 0.738).

Research Question 2:

To what extent does creative thinking correlate with OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities?

Table 2: Respondents’ responses on the level of correlation between creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited piggery farming in Owerri communities

Q/No.	Item	SA	A	UN	D	SD	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
3	Creative thinking enables OKOBI-spirited pig farmers to introduce technologies to guarantee sanitation in the farms so as to avoid environmental pollution.	15	7	2	1	3	28	4.07	0.914
4	Creative thinking is the tool for effective ranching arrangements among OKOBI-spirited pig farmers in Owerri communities.	14	9	2	1	2	28	4.14	0.907

Field Survey (2025).

The Table 2 above presents data from responses by respondents on the level of correlation between creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities. The results show that majority of the respondents affirmed to the statements. There is a high level agreement by the respondents on the opinion that creative thinking enables OKOBI-spirited pig farmers to introduce technologies to guarantee sanitation in the farms so as to avoid environmental pollution as the result accounted for a mean of 4.07 and a standard deviation of 0.914. The result has indicated that the majority of the respondents agreed to the item statement that creative thinking is the tool for effective ranching arrangements among OKOBI-spirited pig farmers in Owerri communities (with a $\bar{x} \pm S.D$ of 4.14 ± 0.907).

Research Question 3:

How does relational thinking correlate with OKOBI-spirited fish farming in Owerri communities?

Table 3: Respondents’ responses on the level of correlation between relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming in Owerri communities

Q/No.	Item	SA	A	UN	D	SD	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
5	With relational thinking, OKOBI-spirited fish farmers develop sound human relations for effective business performance.	13	9	3	1	2	28	4.07	0.827
6	It is with the instrument of relational thinking that fish farmers offer after-sales services to their clients.	14	7	5	1	1	28	4.14	0.857

Field Survey (2025).

The Table 3 above presents data from responses by respondents on the level of correlation between relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming in Owerri communities. The results show that majority of the respondents affirmed to the statements. There is a high level agreement by the respondents on the opinion that with relational thinking, OKOBI-spirited fish farmers develop sound human relations for effective business performance as the result accounted for a mean of 4.07 and a standard deviation of 0.882. The result has indicated that the majority of the respondents agreed to the item statement that it is with the instrument of relational thinking that fish farmers offer after-sales services to their clients (with a $\bar{x} \pm S.D$ of 4.14 ± 0.769).

Research Question 4:

What is the level of correlation between relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities?

Table 4: Respondents’ responses on the level of correlation between relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities

Q/No.	Item	SA	A	UN	D	SD	N	Mean	Std. Dev.
7	Relational thinking drives a strong cooperation between pig farmers and host communities over security of the farms.	13	8	2	1	4	28	3.89	0.788
8.	It is with the tool of relational thinking that pig farmers work together with veterinary doctors for the sound health of pigs in the farm.	9	14	3	1	1	28	4.04	0.914

Field Survey (2025).

The Table 4 above presents data from responses by respondents on the level of correlation between relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities. The results show that majority of the respondents affirmed to the statements. There is a high level agreement by the respondents on the opinion that relational thinking drives a strong cooperation between pig farmers and host communities over security of the farms as the result accounted for a mean of 3.89 and a standard deviation of 0.788. The result has also indicated that the majority of the respondents agreed to the item statement that it is with the tool of relational thinking that pig farmers work together with veterinary doctors for the sound health of pigs in the farm (with a $\bar{x} \pm$ S.D of 4.04 ± 0.914).

Testing of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant level of correlation between creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming in Owerri communities.

Table 5: Correlation analysis between creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming in Owerri communities

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	Correlation Coefficient	P-value
Creative thinking	4.04	0.804	0.982	0.001
OKOBI-spirited fish farming	4.00	0.738		

SPSS Correlation Analysis Output (2025).

The above table shows the correlation analysis between creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming in Owerri communities. The result shows a p-value of 0.001. It also shows a correlation coefficient of 0.982. The result shows a p-value less than 0.05 being the level of significance. This implies the rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis. Accordingly, the correlation coefficient between creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming in Owerri communities is statistically significant. And so, there is a significant level of correlation between creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming in Owerri communities.

H₀₂: There is no significant extent to which creative thinking correlates with OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities.

Table 6: Correlation analysis between creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	Correlation Coefficient	P-value
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Creative thinking	4.07	0.914	0.977	0.001
OKOBI-spirited pig farming	4.14	0.907		

SPSS Correlation Analysis Output (2025).

The above table shows the correlation analysis between creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities. The result shows a p-value of 0.001. It also shows a correlation coefficient of 0.977. The result shows a p-value less than 0.05 being the level of significance. This implies the rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis. Accordingly, the correlation coefficient between creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities is statistically significant. And so, there is a significant extent to which creative thinking correlates with OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities.

H₀₃: There is no significant level of correlation between relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming in Owerri communities.

Table 7: Correlation analysis between relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming in Owerri communities

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	Correlation Coefficient	P-value
Relational thinking	4.07	0.827	0.956	0.001
OKOBI-spirited fish farming	4.14	0.857		

SPSS Correlation Analysis Output (2025).

The above table shows the correlation analysis between relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming in Owerri communities. The result shows a p-value of 0.001. It also shows a correlation coefficient of 0.956. The result shows a p-value less than 0.05 being the level of significance. This implies the rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis. Accordingly, the correlation coefficient between relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming in Owerri communities is statistically significant. And so, there is a significant level of correlation between relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming in Owerri communities.

H₀₄: There is no significant level of correlation between relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities.

Table 8: Correlation analysis between relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities

Item	Mean	Standard Deviation	Correlation Coefficient	P-value
Relational thinking	3.89	0.788	0.737	0.001
OKOBI-spirited pig farming	4.04	0.914		

SPSS Correlation Analysis Output (2025).

The above table shows the correlation analysis between relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities. The result shows a p-value of 0.001. It also shows a correlation coefficient of 0.737. The result shows a p-value less than 0.05 being the level of significance. This implies the rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis. Accordingly, the correlation coefficient between relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities is statistically significant. And so, there is a significant level of correlation between relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities.

Findings

After the data analysis, the study found that:

1. There is a significant level of correlation between creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming in Owerri communities.
2. There is a significant extent to which creative thinking correlates with OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities.
3. There is a significant level of correlation between relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming in Owerri communities.
4. There is a significant level of correlation between relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities.

Discussion of Findings

The findings made in this study are discussed as follows:

The fact that creative thinking enables OKOBI-spirited fish farmers to embrace green innovations for quality outputs as shown on table 1 underscores the opportunities created by strategic thinking over inclusion of innovation-based farming in recent times. Creative thinking is the brain behind applications of innovations including the use of solar energy and other sustainable innovations as well as technological innovations in the management of fish farms. The same table reveals further that with creative thinking OKOBI-spirited fish farmers plan effectively for the inculcation of Artificial Intelligence in their operations. Edewhor and Okoh (2024) investigated ‘analysis of the impact of strategic thinking on organizational performance of manufacturing firms in Delta State,

Nigeria'. The objectives of the study include to assess the impact of strategic thinking on corporate performance. Their study adopts a survey research design. It uses linear regression and correlation analysis to handle data analysis. The findings show that strategic thinking has a significant relationship with each of corporate performance. Also, Wegwu (2024) investigates 'strategic thinking and effective decision-making of the telecommunication industry in Rivers State, Nigeria'. It was found that a positive and significant relationship exists between creative thinking and effective decision making. These studies agree with the findings in this present study.

Given that creative thinking enables OKOBI-spirited pig farmers to introduce technologies to guarantee sanitation in the farms so as to avoid environmental pollution as shown in table 2, it indicates that creative thinking gives the farmers the opportunity to design effective innovation-aided waste management systems. The table 2 also shows that creative thinking is the tool for effective ranching arrangements among OKOBI-spirited pig farmers in Owerri communities. All these underscore the strategic place of employee creativity and knowledge in farm management. Alzghoul, Algraibeh, Khawaldeh. Khaddam, Al-Kasasbeh (2023) did a study to investigate the 'nexus of strategic thinking, knowledge-oriented leadership and employee creativity in higher education institutes'. It finds that strategic thinking promotes and increases employee creativity. This agrees with the findings in this study. This breeds competitive abilities in firms. Indeed, Ibodo and Nzewi (2023) investigated 'strategic thinking and competitive advantage: evidence from the Nigerian Pharmaceutical industry'. The study was carried out to find how creative thinking impact the competitive advantage of pharmaceutical firms. The study finds that creative thinking has significant effects on the competitive advantage of pharmaceutical firms in Nigeria. Also, Olotu, Ayoola and Balogun (2021) assesses the 'impact of strategic thinking on organizational performance in a Nigerian mega-supermarket'. The study objectives include to assess the relationship between creative thinking and employee productivity. The outcomes indicate a positive and significant relationship between creative thinking and employee productivity. Indeed, Obalemo (2021) assesses the 'nexus between strategic thinking and entrepreneurship development: A conceptual framework'. The paper finds that strategic thinking helps entrepreneurs discover new business opportunities and take advantage of such opportunities to maximize profit in the society. These studies are in alignment with the findings in this present research.

The fact that with relational thinking, OKOBI-spirited fish farmers develop sound human relations for effective business performance as shown on table 3 reveal that cordial relationships drive both sustainability and pleasant business outcomes in OKOBI-spirited fish farming. The table three also shows that it is with the instrument of relational thinking that fish farmers offer after-sales services to their clients. This is a sure route to achieving customer retention in the business. Njoku (2025) examines 'strategic thinking and the formation of future leaders in Nigerian Naval institutions with a focus on Accounts, Budget and allied naval offices'. The objectives of the study include to analyze how relational strategic thinking may influence future leadership in Nigerian naval institutions. It finds that relational strategic thinking is a strategic tool for sustainable future leadership in Nigerian naval institutions. This agrees with the findings in this present study.

Given that relational thinking drives a strong cooperation between pig farmers and host communities over security of the farms as shown on table 4, it implies that relational strategic thinking competence remains a formidable tool for business-host community peaceful co-existence. The table further indicates that it is with the tool of relational thinking that pig farmers work together with veterinary doctors for the sound health of pigs in the farm. The finding in the study by Njoku (2025) who examines ‘strategic thinking and the formation of future leaders in Nigerian Naval institutions with a focus on Accounts, Budget and allied naval offices’ as shown above, still agrees with this finding in this present study.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

The study concludes that strategic thinking competences are correlates of OKOBI-spirited agro farming in Owerri communities. In fact, creative thinking greatly influences OKOBI-spirited fish farming in the area. It is a driver of OKOBI-spirited pig farming in the communities.

The study submits that relational thinking positively affects OKOBI-spirited fish farming in the communities and it predicts OKOBI-spirited pig farming in the area. The study therefore infers that any OKOBI-spirited agro farmer that relegates strategic thinking to the background risks business collapse and other undesirable farming outcomes because farming in this context remains a serious business.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study makes the following recommendations:

1. Management of OKOBI-spirited fish farms in Owerri communities should always embrace creative thinking for sound business outcomes.
2. OKOBI-spirited pig farms should always strive to inculcate innovativeness in the conduct of their farming business.
3. Fish farming enterprises that are OKOBI-spirited should not relegate human relations to the background so as to seamlessly achieve their business goals.
4. OKOBI-spirited pig farmers need to show tolerance and accommodation in their dealings with host communities so as to avoid destructive conflicts that may destroy their businesses.
- 5.

Contribution to Knowledge

This study contributes to knowledge by providing empirical literature and by bridging research gaps on the relationships between creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming in Owerri communities; creative thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming; relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited fish farming as well as relational thinking and OKOBI-spirited pig farming in Owerri communities. The study adds to the body of existing knowledge in the area of strategic thinking.

Implications for Further Research

Given that this present study focuses only on Owerri communities, further research ought to be done with a wider geographical scope to investigate areas outside Owerri. The present study also concentrates on creative thinking and relational thinking indicators of strategic thinking. Future researchers need to work on other indices of strategic thinking. This study anchors only on OKOBI-spirited agro farming. This indicates that future researchers should investigate OKOBI-based endeavors in other industries outside agriculture. In this research, the survey research design was employed to evaluate strategic thinking and OKOBI-spirited agro farming in Owerri communities. Future researchers need to vary the methodology over the same relationships to determine if there may be consistency or reliability in the results obtained. They may employ ex post facto approach or even desk research among others.

Again, this paper assesses only the Chief Executives in the study farms. Future researchers need to expand their survey scope to accommodate other stakeholders over the proxies and linkages evaluated in this research. Given that this study examines the correlation between creative thinking and fish farming as well as creative thinking and pig farming in Owerri communities as well as relational thinking and both fish farming and piggery farming in Owerri communities, future researchers should ascertain the correlation between strategic thinking as correlates of OKOBI-spirited transport enterprises in Okigwe and Orlu Senatorial Zones of Imo State.

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Geochemical Assessment of Impact of Umusedeli Dumpsite on the Environment of Kwale Town, South-South Nigeria

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Abstract:

A waste dumpsite is a selected site for disposal of municipal solid waste. Open dumpsites are the oldest method of disposing solid wastes. This study is design to evaluate the extent of leachate and pollution in Umusedeli open refuse dumpsites in the environment of Kwale, Delta State, South-South Nigeria. A total of fifteen samples consisting of ten soil samples, four groundwater and one leachate' samples were collected and analyzed for different parameters using Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometer (AAS). The results revealed the presence of TDS, COD, and EC were widely distributed in the water samples studied. pH values were found significantly elevated when compared by the standard set by WHO in all the samples and ranges between 5.5 – 6.5. Also, Mg, Fe, and Pb concentrations significantly exceeded WHO permissible limits. The results of soil samples revealed high leaching potentials (86.7 -89.9%) for sand fraction. Ph result for soils which is in the range of 6.2 -8.2 showed slightly acidic to alkaline. The average values for Mn, Zn, Cu, Cr, Cd, Pb and Ni are lower than the WHO permissible standards limit except Fe that has the high value (21.4mg/kg) which exceeded WHO permissible limits. However, risk assessment and pollution load index analysis were carried out on heavy metals for both water and soil samples. Fe showed high concentration above other heavy metals for both samples. In conclusion both soils and groundwater in the investigated dump sites vicinity had been impacted by the dumpsite. However, government should make plans to remove this refuse dump in this area.

Keywords Hydrochemistry, Soil chemistry, Dumpsite, Leachate, Risk Assessment.

Introduction

Dumpsite is a common phenomenon for disposing municipal solid waste (MSW). Population and industrial growth are major contributing factors in the ever increasing amount of waste produced worldwide, and dumpsites are still the most common method of solid waste disposal (Scott *et al.*, 2005; El-Fadel *et al.*, 1997). Worldwide, up to 95% of solid waste is deposited in landfills (EPA, 2012, Scott *et al.*, 2005; Gendebien *et al.*, 1992; Bingemer and Crutzen, 1987; Cossu, 1989). However, pollution of the environment (groundwater resources / soils) can occur directly from municipal waste water, industrial discharges, agricultural waste, urban runoff, landfills or waste dump and indirectly from air pollution.

The waste dump materials are expected to biodegrade and generate effluent. The generated effluent may have found its way into the groundwater through percolation. There is the possibility that the groundwater within the premises of the dump site could have been contaminated. Therefore, there is need to carry out a geochemical evaluation of the area around the Umusedeli Kwale waste dump site, evaluate the quality of the soil and groundwater by carrying out chemical analysis of sampled borehole, hand dug wells, leachate and soil samples; and use it to assess the degree and extent of impact of the waste dump site on the quality of the groundwater and soil in the study area.

A vast literature exists showing the applications of geochemical methods in environmental problems associated with groundwater and soils contamination due to leachate percolation. This study used physicochemical methods to map the contamination at the subsurface and investigate the contamination level of the various hand dug wells, boreholes and soils situated in the study area.

The Study Area

The study area (fig.1) is located within geographical co-ordinates of latitudes 5°40'32" N and 5°43'5" N and longitude 6°25'20" E and 6°24'39" E in Kwale Ndokwa-west Local Government area of Delta State, South-south Nigeria.

The refuse dumps at Umusedeli Kwale consists of heterogeneous refuse materials. Geologically, the study area lies entirely within the Niger Delta Basin of Southern Nigeria. The geology of Niger Delta Basin has been discussed extensively by several authors including (Short and Stauble, 1965), Akpokodje and, Etu-Efetobor (1987), (Short and Stauble, 1967; Doust and Omatsola, 1990). The Niger Delta Basin has three distinct formations which includes; Akata Formation, Agbada Formation and Benin Formation. The study area Kwale is underlain by continental sand of upper Benin Formation. The lithological units of this area are generally composed of sands and clayey sand. The area has a flat topography and is situated by the bank of river Niger. It is thickly populated and of high economic importance.

Figure 1: Map of study area showing sampling locations

Materials and Method

During the period of field exercise, a total of four (4) water samples and one leachate samples were collected from boreholes, hand-dug wells and leachate at different locations of the waste dump using plastic container while a total of ten (10) soil samples were collected at five auger points both within and outside the two dumpsite. The plastic containers were properly rinsed and dried to remove any form of impurities before the samples were taken and GPS reading was taken at each point to determine the co-ordinate points. Samples were stored in a cool dry place before commencement of laboratory analysis.

The collection of soil samples was done using soil auger boring. The soil samples were collected with the hand auger boring at various depths and the collected samples were sealed in a nylon before taken to the laboratory for analysis. The depth interval at which the samples were collected at 0.5m- interval. Physiochemical analysis of soil and water samples were carried out in the laboratory using Atomic Absorption Spectrometer (AAS) MODEL SOLAAR 969 UNICAM SERIES. Data generated were subjected to mean, standard deviation and coefficient of variation analyses using Genstat Statistical Package Version 18. The coefficient of variation (CV) was ranked according to the procedure of (Wilding *et al.*, 1994) where $CV < 15\%$ = least variation, $CV > 15 < 35\%$ = moderate variation, $CV > 35\%$ = high variation.

Results and Discussion

Physiochemical analysis Results of water and leachates.

The physiochemical results of water and leachate samples were presented in table 1. It was shown that water color differed among the sampled water with the variation ranging from colorless to 0.8 with a mean value of 0.4 (Pt.Co), indicating that the water collected from borehole 2 of Umusedeli dumpsite (D) had darker platinum-cobalt colour than others. World Health Organization (WHO) suggested that good drinking water should be colourless. Differences in waste composition between both water sources lead to the differences in the leachate colour. Emenike, *et al.*,2011).

Similarly, total suspended solids (TSS) were highest (1.1) in sample(D) and in general it ranged from 1.1 mg/l to not detected with average value of 0.7 mg/l. The high total suspended solids (1.1 mg/L) of the borehole sample (D). will make it possible for microorganisms to adsorb to solid particle surfaces, thereby enhancing biodegradation of organic pollutants (Mohod and Dhote 2013). Similar to colour, TSS was not detected in leachate sample (A) and borehole sample (C). Results of Table 1 also displayed variation in total dissolved solids (TDS) with the highest (201 mg/l) and lowest (6 mg/l) value occurring in sample A and D. Concentrations of TDS in leachate, borehole and hand-dug well were greater in A (201mg/l), C (55 mg/l) and hand-dug well E (12.8 mg/l) respectively. High concentration of dissolved organic matters lead from the deposition of waste in the landfills reflected the high concentration of TDS and turbidity value (Emenike, *etal.*,2011). Umar, *et al.*,2010) also stated that the main source of high TDS was from inorganic salts and dissolved organics in the landfill. According to the rating of Wilding *et al.* (1994), there was high (CV=132.6%) variation of TDS across the sampling points.

In this study, chemical oxygen demand (COD) ranged from 60.9-7.2 mg/l (mean=16.9 mg/l). It was highest (60.9mg/l) in leachate sample (A), borehole sample (C) (13.6 mg/l), hand-dug well sample (E) (12.8 mg/l). This indicated that concentration of COD was highest in Leachate than other water source. Concentrations of COD in the present study were far lower than mean of concentration of 2926 ± 15.65 mg/l to 4062.04 ± 32.81 mg/l recorded by Olarewaju, *et al.*, 2012) in Kabawa and Lokongoma phase II dumpsites respectively. The variations in values may possibly be attributed to the fact that different decomposition stages are taking place simultaneously at various locations within an open dumps waste management system.

Table 1 also show the results of the physiochemical properties of the water samples studied where results of coefficient of variation (CV) demonstrated that all the parameters apart from pH(CV=7.48) were widely distributed. pH of the water samples ranged from 6.6–5.5 (mean=5.9) with highest (6.6) occurring at point A while the lowest was found in point D (5.5), suggesting that almost all the water samples were acidic especially in borehole 2 (sample D) of Umusedeli dumpsite. All the samples had pH value below 7.0 (acidic) and this showed presence of pollutants especially metals (Badmus, *et al.*, 2014). Moreover, it was only sample A and C that fall within WHO acceptable standard range of 6.5–8.5 (WHO, 2010).

Electrical conductivity (EC) highly (CV=133.7) varied from 404–12 μ S/cm with mean value of 92.3 μ S/cm. Its highest and lowest concentration was obtained in sample A and D respectively. Amongst the leachate, borehole and hand-dug well samples, EC was highest in A, C and E respectively. These values were low considering average value of 229 μ S/cm recorded by (George, *et al.*, 2014) in Leachate on Groundwater around the Ikot Ekpene Dumpsite in Akwa Ibom State, Southern Nigeria.

Hydrogen carbonate (HCO_3) of the water samples ranged from 195.2–12.2 mg/l (mean=42.7 mg/l). Results of coefficient of variability (CV) showed that it was widely distributed with CV being high (CV=119.6%). Considering samples from leachate, hand-dug well and borehole, sample A (195.2 mg/l), E (24.4 mg/l) and C (36.4 mg/l) were shown to have highest concentrations of HCO_3 . The slightly acidic nature of the leachate indicates the presence of carbonate, bicarbonate, and hydroxide compound of calcium, sodium, and potassium (Jorstad, *et al.*, 2004; Niloufer, *et al.*, 2013). Moreover, the primary source of HCO_3^- in groundwater is the dissolved carbon dioxide in the rain water that enters the soil to dissolve more carbon dioxide

Mg was in a range of 8.8–7.8 mg/l, 2.13–0.77 mg/l and 3.33–0.6 mg/l respectively, indicating that leachate had greater concentration of Mg followed by hand-dug well and borehole samples. Values recorded for Mg were slightly higher than recorded by (Olagunju, *et al.*, 2018) in Ilokun Waste Dumpsite, Ado - Ekiti, Southern Nigeria. Besides, these values exceed maximum permissible levels (0.20ppm) for potable ground water recommended by NSDWQ (2007). This high value of magnesium in the water samples may indicate that water in these wells has been infiltrated by toxic materials from the waste dumpsite.

A range of 212.7–12.7 mg/l with an average of 82.3 mg/l was recorded for Cl. Maximum (212.7 mg/l) and minimum (12.7 mg/l) values were shown to occur in sample A and D respectively. These values were somewhat higher than a range of 17 to 106 mg/L recorded by (Badmus, *et al.*, 2014). However, the values recorded in the present study were

still below the permissible level of 250mg/L for WHO and NSDWQ levels. Furthermore, its presence in water connotes pollution hence requires pre-treatment before u

Table 1; Physiochemical Properties of the Water Samples Compared with WHO Standards

Code	Units	A	B	C	D	E	Range (Mean ± SD)	CV%	WHO recommended level(2017)
Col.	Pt.Co	ND	0.6	ND	0.8	0.2	0.8–ND (0.4±)		Colorless
TSS	mg/l	ND	1	ND	1.1	0.4	1.1–ND (0.7±)		NA
TDS	mg/l	201	9	55	6	28	234–6(70±92.8)	132.6	600
COD	mg/l	60.9	8	13.6	7.2	12.8	127.2–7.2(16.9±43)	140	10
pH		6.6	6	6.5	5.5	5.6	6.6–5.5(5.9±0.4)	7.48	6.5 -8.5
EC	µS/cm	404	18	102	12	56	468–12(92.3±186.2)	133.7	1500
HCO ₃	mg/l	164.7	12.2	36.4	12.2	24.4	195.2–12.2(42.7±73.8)	134.2	1000
Na	mg/l	3.7	0.22	1.8	0.21	1.62	4.3–0.2(1.2±1.7)	119.6	
Mg	mg/l	7.8	0.77	0.33	0.6	2,13	8.8–0.6(2.3±3.3)	105.5	0.05
Cl	mg/l	212.7	24.1	94.9	12.7	94.9	230.4–12.7(82.3±80.4)	105.9	250
NO ₃	mg/l	0.435	0.02	0.145	0.015	0.12	0.6–0.015 (0.1±0.2)	79.79	50
SO ₄	mg/l	0.67	0.18	0.345	0.095	0.235	0.7–0.1(0.3±0.2)	124.1	100
Sal	g/l	0.183	0.008	0.046	0.005	0.025	0.2–0.009 (0.04±0.1)	69.33	

Key: Col. =colour, Pt.Co=Platinum-Cobalt, Turb. turbidity=, TSS=total suspended solids, TDS= total dissolved solids, COD=chemical oxygen demand, ND=not detected, EC=electrical conductivity, Sal. =salinity

Table 2: Heavy Metal Concentrations of the Water Samples Compared with WHO Standards.

Code	Units	A	B	C	D	E	Range (Mean ± SD)	CV	WHO Recommended Level(2017)
Fe	mg/l	0.125	0.62	0.15	0.48	0.263	0.62–0.111 (0.3±0.2)	60.9	0.3
Mn	mg/l	0.033	0.142	0.041	0.187	0.052	0.187–0.021(0.1±0.1)	71.57	0.4
Zn	mg/l	0.074	0.28	0.08	0.311	0.093	0.28–0.07(0.2±0.1)	65.75	0.311
Cd	mg/l	0.003	0.02	0.005	0.025	0.009	0.025–0.001(0.01±0.01)	75.54	0.003
Ni	mg/l	0.001	0.018	0.003	0.018	0.006	0.018–0.001(0.01±0.01)	83.92	0.07
Pb	mg/l	0.006	0.038	0.007	0.041	0.01	.038–0.002(0.02±0.01)	85.41	0.01
THC	mg/l	ND	ND	ND	ND	ND	-		

Heavy metal concentrations of the water samples

Displayed in Table 2 are the results of the heavy metal concentrations of the water samples studied where results of coefficient of variation (CV) demonstrated that all the parameters varied widely. Iron concentrations of the water samples varied from 0.6–0.111 mg/l (mean= 0.3 mg/l) with maximum (0.62 mg/l) obtained in sample B while the lowest was obtained in point A (0.125 mg/l). Moreover, variation of Iron concentration displayed the least value of CV of 60.9%. In similar study (Olla *et al.*, 2015), iron concentration ranged from 0.01-0.2 mg/L in distances within municipal dumpsite in Ibadan. Higher values of Fe especially in sample E is possible indication that they are reflections of the direct impact of the dumpsite within areas where they are situated. It was also observed from the Table 2 that concentrations of Fe was higher than other metals studied. This was in line with the findings of (Beinabaj, *et al.*,2023) in Tehran’s landfill.

Manganese (Mn) is relatively abundant in the Earth's crust with an average upper crustal abundance of 600 ppm and a bulk continental crust average of 1400 ppm (McLennan and Taylor,1999). It is a common lithophile element. Concentrations of Mn in the water samples ranged from 0.187–0.02 mg/l (mean=0.1 mg/l). Results of coefficient of variability (CV) showed that it was widely distributed with CV being high (CV=71.57%). Considering samples from leachate,hand-dug well and borehole, sample A (0.033mg/l), E (0.142mg/l) and G (0.187mg/l) were shown to have highest concentrations ofMn. Similarly, in the study of (Olagunju, *et al.*,2018) Mn in water was in a range 0.128 to 0.313ppm.

Zinc also highly (CV=65.75%) varied from 0.28–0.07 mg/lwith mean value of 0.2 mg/l. Its highest and lowest concentration were obtained in sample B(0.28 mg/l) and A(0.07 mg/l) respectively. Amongst the leachate, hand-dug well and borehole samples,Zn was highest in

A(0.074 mg/l), B(0.28 mg/l) and D(0.311 mg/l) respectively. According to the ratings of WHO (2010), critical level of Zn is 3 mg/l, indicating that all the water samples had tolerable values. Zinc toxic effects in humans are most obvious from accidental or occupational inhalation exposure to high concentrations of zinc compounds, such as from smoke bombs, or metal-fume fever (El-Sayed, 2016).

In general, cadmium concentrations varied widely (CV=75.54%) with a range of 0.025–0.001 mg/l (mean= 0.01 mg/l). Considering samples from leachate, hand-dug well and borehole water, Cd was in a range of 0.003–0.001, 0.02–0.009 mg/l and 0.025–0.005 mg/l respectively, indicating that hand-dug well had greater concentration of Cd followed by leachate and borehole samples. This range of concentrations in leachate samples were quite lower than those reported by (Thomas, *et al.*, 2008) as 1.28 – 21.31 mg/l and (Okorokwo, *et al.*, 2006) as 1.64 – 2.50 mg/l.

Furthermore, these concentrations are also lower than the allowable limit of 1.00 mg/l by FEPA, (1991) and WHO, (1997). Generally, these values were within the acceptable level (0.03 mg/l) of WHO with the exception of sample C(0.005 mg/l) and E(0.009 mg/l).

Nickel in the studied water samples was greater in both sample E and G (0.018 mg/l) followed by B (0.011), C(0.008), H (0.006), F(0.003) and both A and D that had same value of 0.001. Besides, variation of Ni across the samples was also high (CV=83.92%) with the mean being 0.01 mg/l. These values in leachates (0.001 mg/l) were far lower than 11ml that was reported by (Torkashvand *et al.* 2016) in landfill leachate. In general however, all the water samples had concentrations of Ni lower than 0.07 and 0.02 stated as critical by WHO and NSDWQ respectively. According to Kadirvelu (2000), higher concentrations of nickel cause cancer of lungs, nose and bone. Dermatitis (Ni itch) is the most frequent effect of exposure to Ni, such as coins and jewellery. Acute poisoning of Ni (II) causes headache, dizziness, nausea and vomiting, chest pain, tightness of the chest, dry cough and shortness of breath, rapid respiration, cyanosis and extreme weakness.

Furthermore, similar to Ni, lead concentrations of the water samples showed high variation (CV=85.41%) amongst the soils and had the same mean value of 0.01. Its variation was in a range of 0.038–0.002 mg/l. It was greater (0.038 mg/l) and least (0.002 mg/l) in sample E and A respectively. These concentrations in leachates (0.038 mg/l) were far below the concentrations reported by (Agyarko, and Berlinger, 2010) as 8.59 – 9.20 mg/l. The concentration of lead obtained in this study indicate that the water sources around these dumpsites apart from sample A(0.002 mg/l), D(0.006 mg/l), F(0.007 mg/l) and H(0.01 mg/l) exceeded the allowable limit of 0.01 mg/l by WHO (2010). Increased lead concentration is usually attributed to industrial activities (Eddy, *et al.*, 2006). Also, lead is mostly found in automobile battery in sufficient amount.

Soils Analytical Results

Heavy metal concentrations of the Soil Samples.

Depicted in Table 3 are the results of heavy metal concentrations of the studied soils where Fe dominated the heavy metals. From the results, coefficient variation for iron concentration was low (CV=12.84%), indicating uniform distribution across the sampling points. Overall, Fe ranged from 26.04–13.31(mean=21.4 mg/kg). Irrespective of locations and depths, Fe was highest (23.51 mg/kg) in S2P3 (0.0m) and least (13.31 mg/kg) in S2P2 (2.0m) respectively.. Within the sampling points, it was observed that higher concentration of Fe was in S2P5(23.3

mg/kg) whereas the least was in S2P2 (17.6 mg/kg). Equally, on mean basis, Fe concentration was slightly higher at surface (21.71 mg/kg) than subsurface (21.1 mg/kg). The observed values obtained for the various study locations is not any different from that observed by Shaibu *et al.* (2015) for dumpsites in Ilorin. They stated that the high content of Fe within the dumpsites was linked to the nature and size of the waste and also regular burning of the waste at the dumpsite that impacts on the metal concentration at the dumpsite.

Zinc concentration also varied moderately ($CV > 15 \leq 35\%$) across the entire soils studied with a range of 18.11–8.11 mg/kg and mean value of 13.4 mg/kg. Considering the depths, it was in a range of 17.04–8.88 mg/kg and 18.11–8.11 mg/kg at the surface and subsurface, indicating that surface (13.57 mg/kg) had higher concentration than subsurface soils (13.19 mg/kg). Such pattern of Zn distribution was also observed in some dumpsite soils studied by Ojegu (2016). Amusan *et al.* (2005) reported concentration of Zn ranging from 63.2 to 102.11 mg/kg⁻¹ in soils of dumpsites in Ile-Ife, Nigeria while Amadi (2011) reported Zn concentration ranging from 68.3 to 290 mg/kg⁻¹ in soil at Aladinma dumpsite. Also, Adefemi and Awokunmi (2009) reported Zn concentration of 72.47 to 201.6 mg/kg⁻¹ in dumpsites of Ado-Ekiti, indicating that values recorded in the present study was lower than that reported by previous workers. Thus, values in this present study were generally lower than 50 stipulated as critical level (WHO, 2010).

Depth-wise, copper also increased slightly with soil depth as 4.91 and 4.67 mg/kg in surface and subsurface depths respectively. Amongst the locations, Cu higher (6.64 mg/kg) in S2P3 and lower in S2P2 (1.88 mg/kg). As regards the sampling points, it was highest (6.64 mg/kg) in S2P3 and least (3.33 mg/kg) in soils from S2P1 with coefficient of variation being high ($CV = 43.61\%$). These values were far lower than 318 mg/kg within the dumpsite of Iyara Area Warri Nigeria (Ofomola *et al.*, 2021) but lower than the WHO and DPR of Nigeria permissible limit of 36 mg/kg. Copper is an essential trace element for all organisms, and humans can tolerate levels up to 12 mg per day (WHO, 1996), although the element can be toxic at extremely high levels. For example, Reimann and de Caritat (1998) reported examples of kidney failure in small children resulting from drinking water from new copper pipes in low pH environments containing high concentrations of Cu up to about 1 ppm.

Distribution of cadmium (Cd) across the locations was 0.845 and 0.727 mg/kg at S2P3 and S2P5 respectively, suggesting Cd to be better in S2P3. Lower concentrations (0.0001 ± 0.01 mg/kg) of these metal was recorded by Ige *et al.* (2022) in Igando waste dumpsite, southwestern Nigeria. Between the surface and subsurface depths, Cd was in a range of 1.8 - 0.17 (mean = 0.80 mg/kg) and 1.8 - 0.15 (mean = 0.77 mg/kg) respectively, suggesting insignificant effects of dumpsites at both depths. However, across the various sampling points, variation was high ($CV = 73.86\%$), indicating erratic distribution pattern. The values of the Cd concentrations obtained for the sampled sites are all lower than the natural limits of 0.01-3.0 mg/kg in soil as given by MAFF (1992) and EC (1986). This is in agreement with the findings of Asawalam and Eke (2006) and Njoku and Ayoka (2007) who investigated the trace metal concentrations and heavy metal pollutants from dump soils in Owerri, Nigeria. Even though these heavy metal concentrations fell below the critical permissible concentration level, it seems that their persistence in the soils of the dump site may lead to increased uptake of these heavy metals by plants.

Similar to most of the heavy metals, lead (Pb) contents of the soils differed widely (CV=63.89) with overall range of 2.43–0.27 mg/kg and grand mean of 1.1 mg/kg. Across the surface and subsurface soil depths, it varied from 2.2- 0.3 (mean=1.20 mg/kg) and 2.43- 0.27 (mean=1.08 mg/kg) respectively, showing that higher concentration of Pb was at the surface and subsurface soil depths of S2P1 and S2P5 respectively. Moreover, on average, it was observed that Pb decreased slightly with soil depths probably due to higher concentration of organic matter at top soils. Higher levels were reported by Ige *et al.* (2022) in similar research in Igando wastedumpsite (14.75±0.04 to16.14±0.05 mg/kg) and Ewu-Elepe dumpsite (33.74 mg/kg) respectively. These values in the present study were also lower than (EC, 1986) upper limit of 300 mg/kg and the maximum tolerable levels proposed for agricultural soil, 85 mg/kg set by WHO (2010). This is in agreement with the results obtained from similar study by Umoh and Etim (2013) for soils from dumpsites within Ikot-Ekpene in Akwa-Ibom State, Nigeria. Concentration of lead in the soils from both areas could be as a result of its sources from automobile exhaust fumes as well as dry cell batteries, sewage effluents, runoff of wastes and atmospheric depositions owing to the close proximity of the sites to high vehicular traffic along the dumpsites.

Nickel is a siderophile metallic element with chalcophilic and lithophilic affinities (Kabata-and Pendias, 2001). In general, nickel ranged from 1.11–0.08 (mean=0.4 mg/kg). Concentration of Ni varied slightly within the locations studied with greater (0.77 mg/kg) value obtained in S2P3 compared to S2P1(0.18 mg/kg). Across the sampling points, highest mean value of 0.7 was obtained in S2P1, compared to equal value of 0.6 mg/kg obtained in S2P2, S2P5 andS2P3, equal value of 0.4 mg/kgobtained in S2P1,S2P4 and S2P5 and 0.2 mg/kg obtained in S2P2. In similar study, higher mean value of 12.00 ppm was obtained for Ni in the study of Olorunfemi *et al.* (2020) in Ewu-Elepe dumpsite, Lagos State, Nigeria. Besides, Ni at the surface soils (0.45 mg/kg) of this present studywas slightly higher than subsurface (0.44 mg/kg) could probably be due to higher concentration of organic matter that always form complexes with heavy metals at the top soils.

Table 4: Heavy metal concentrations of the Soil Samples

Code	Units	S2P1 (0m)	S2P1 (2.0m)	S2P2 (0m)	S2P2 (2.0m)	S2P3 (0m)	S2P3 (2.0m)	S2P4 (0m)	S2P4 (2.0m)	S2P5 (0m)	S2P5 (2.0m)	Range (Mean ± SD)	
Fe	mg/kg	22.32	19.54	21.84	13.31	23.54	20.8	19.51	23.51	20.35	23.33	26.04–13.31(21.4±2.7)	12.84
	mg/kg											11.76–3.6	34.42
Mn		9.87	5.51	8.73	3.61	10.78	6.51	4.98	10.57	5.54	9.98	1(.8±2.7)	
Zn	mg/kg	15.88	10.37	15.3	8.11	16.55	11.74	8.97	16.45	10.39	16.18	18.11–8.11(137.4±3.2)	23.77
Cu	mg/kg	5.11	3.33	4.73	1.88	6.64	3.88	2.71	6.33	3.48	5.1	9.54–1.88(4.8±2.1)	43.61
Cr	mg/kg	2.1	0.85	1.73	0.48	2.53	1.25	0.6	2.48	0.9	2.28	4.51–0.48(1.7±1)	57.92
Cd	mg/kg	0.75	0.29	0.66	0.15	1.55	0.43	0.21	1.5	0.38	1.35	1.8–0.15(0.8±0.6)	73.86
Pb	mg/kg	1.5	0.41	1.3	0.27	2.08	0.66	0.34	1.88	0.44	1.55	2.43–0.27(1.1±0.7)	63.89
Ni	mg/kg	0.55	0.18	0.38	0.08	0.77	0.33	0.15	0.73	0.21	0.61	1.11–0.08(0.4±0.3)	64.79
V	mg/kg	0.37	0.07	0.2	0.03	0.54	0.17	0.07	0.47	0.09	0.41	0.75–0.03(0.3±0.2)	76.75

Key:S1= sample location 1, S2= sample location 2, P= sampling point.

Risk Assessment of The Heavy Metals.

Single pollution index of water samples

Results of Table 5 summarized single pollution index (SPI) and pollution load index (PLI) of water samples studied. Single pollution index and Nemerow comprehensive pollution index are used to evaluate the degree of heavy metal pollution (Hu *et al.*, 2019). Single pollution index can effectively combine the ecological, environmental and toxicological effects, and consider the biological toxicity of heavy metals (Hakanson, 1980; Chen *et al.*, 2017). It is a widely used and reliable method in heavy metal pollution assessment. Mean single pollution index of Fe was highest compared to other heavy metals. It ranged from 0.19–0.025 with the highest (0.12) and lowest (0.025) value occurring in hand-dug well of (sample B) and borehole 1 of Umusedelikwale dumpsite (sample C) respectively. According to the criteria postulated by Wilding *et al.* (1994), coefficient of variation (CV) of ratings $\leq 15\%$, $>15\leq 35\%$ and $>35\%$ are rated low, moderate and high respectively. Thus, there was high (CV=132.6%) variation of Fe SPI across the sampling points.

Single pollution index of manganese in water ranged from 0.028–0.007 (mean=0.022). It was highest (0.028) in hand-dug well of (sample B) followed by borehole sample D (0.027), borehole 2 of Umusedelikwale dumpsite (G) (0.027), leachate of Umusedelikwale dumpsite (A) (0.008), borehole sample (C) and hand-dug well sample (E) with equal value of 0.007. This indicated that concentration of COD was highest in borehole than other water source. Likewise Fe, coefficient of variation was also high for Mn SPI (CV=70.11%) which indicated wide distribution pattern of Mn SPI.

Zinc SPI like most like other heavy metals displayed high variation (CV=64.81%) with a range of 0.063-0.019, 0.056-0.012 and 0.088-0.012 in leachate, hand-dug well and borehole respectively, suggesting that amongst various water sample sources, it was highest in sample A, E and B respectively. On average basis however, Zn SPI value of 0.041 was obtained for the samples. Furthermore, Cu single pollution index of the water samples showed high variation (CV=68.8%) amongst the soils. It varied from 0.012–0.013 with a mean of 0.013. It was highest and lowest in sample C and E respectively.

Nickel single pollution index ranged from 0.006–0.0003 (mean=0.002). Results of coefficient of variability (CV) showed that it was widely distributed with CV being high (CV=86.81%). Considering samples from leachate, hand-dug well and borehole, sample A (0.001), E (0.004) and B (0.006) were shown to have highest Ni SPI.

Furthermore, displayed in Table 5 also are the results of the pollution load index (PLI) of water samples studied. Pollution load index (PLI) ranged from 2.4×10^{-7} – 1.66×10^{-11} with mean value of 2.4×10^{-7} – 1.66×10^{-11} . It was higher in sample D (8.7×10^{-9}), followed by B (2.7×10^{-9}), E (3.12×10^{-11}), C (2×10^{-11}) and A (1.66×10^{-11}). This indicated that water from hand-dug well sample (D) had highest PLI whereas sample (A) from leachate of Umusedelikwale dumpsite had the least PLI. Besides, results of CV indicated that its variation across the sampled water was high.

Table 5: Single pollution index (SPI) and pollution load index (PLI) of water samples

Code	A	B	C	D	E	Range (Mean ± SD)	CV
Fe	0.031	0.12	0.025	0.07	0.033	0.19–0.025(0.084±0.06)	68.43
Mn	0.008	0.028	0.007	0.027	0.007	0.052–0.007(0.022±0.02)	70.11
Zn	0.019	0.056	0.013	0.044	0.012	0.088–0.012(0.041±0.03)	64.81
Cu	0.005	0.02	0.005	0.016	0.004	0.031–0.004(0.013±0.01)	68.8
Cr	0.002	0.01	0.002	0.009	0.002	0.016–0.002(0.006±0)	74.81
Cd	0.0008	0.004	0.001	0.004	0.001	0.008–0.0008(0.003±0)	87.31
Ni	0.0003	0.004	0.001	0.003	0.001	0.006–0.0003(0.002±0)	86.81
						2.4 X10⁻⁷-1.66 X10⁻¹¹	
PLI	1.66 X10⁻¹¹	2.7 X10⁻⁹	2 X10⁻¹¹	8.7 X10⁻⁹	3.12 X10⁻¹¹	(1.66 X10⁻¹¹±0)	257.8

Single pollution index and pollution load index (PLI) of soil

Results of the single pollution index and pollution load index (PLI) of soil are presented in Table 6 where Fe single pollution index (SPI) was shown to be higher than other metals studied. It was also shown that amongst the locations, SPI of Fe ranged from 23.27–17.58 (mean=21.4). SPI of Fe was highest (22.17) in S2P3 and least (17.58) in S2P2. Across the locations, SPI of Mn was maximum (8.65) and minimum (6.17) in soils from S2P3 and S2P2 respectively. However, CV (7.54%) results indicated low variation of SPI of Fe. Also, single pollution index of Mn was higher in S2P3 (8.65) compared to S2P2 (6.17). Across the sampling points its variation (CV=15.05%) was moderate with decreasing values of 8.65, 7.78, 7.76, 7.69 and 6.17 obtained in S2P1, S2P2, S2P3, S2P4 and S2P5 respectively.

Similar to Fe, distribution pattern of SPI of zinc was low (CV=10.09%) across the sampling points with a range of 15.07–10.91 (mean=13.38). It was highest in S2P3 (14.17) and lowest in S2P2 (11.17), it was also comparatively higher in S2P4 (13.77) compared to S2P5 (12.99). In Table 6, it was observed that the metals studied, SPI of Cd was the least. However, cadmium single pollution index of the soil samples showed high variation (CV=37.93%) amongst the soils. It varied from 0.04–0.01 with a mean of 0.03. It was highest (0.04) and lowest (0.01) in sample S2P2 and S2P3 respectively. Furthermore, Pb SPI like most other heavy metals displayed moderate variation (CV=30.67%) with a range of 0.32–0.09 and 0.27–0.16 in location 1 and 2 respectively, suggesting that amongst various soil sampling points, it was highest in S2P1. On average basis however, Pb SPI value of 0.23 was obtained for the entire soil samples. In general, Ni SPI varied moderately (CV=34.37%) with a range of 0.13–0.04 (mean=0.09). Considering samples from the dumpsite, Ni SPI was in a range of 0.13–0.04 (mean=0.01) and 0.11–0.05 (mean=0.08) respectively, indicating that on average, Ni SPI was highest in soil samples from S2P4 than S2P5.

This results were in disagreement with findings by Okeke *et al.* (2022) in Ebonyi state that the values obtained from various sampled locations for heavy metals have SPI <1, suggesting various degrees of contamination. However, the low SPI obtained for these metals are not static, there is a tendency for an increase as a result of increased human input and activities and hence there is a need for regular check.

The use of contamination factor (Cf), degree of contamination, index of geoaccumulation, (Igeo), pollution load index (PLI), etc. are some of the conventional methods which had been developed and employed to evaluate the pollution status of heavy metals in the soil. The

ecological risks assessment is part of the contemporary research in soil pollution studies and environmental management, it indicates the tendency of the adverse effects of heavy metals on the ecological health (Ogundele *et al.*, 2020). Pollution load index (PLI) greater than 1 shows a significant contamination of the soil of interest with metal (Zango *et al.*, 2013). Shown in Table 6 are the results of the pollution load index (PLI) of soil samples studied. It ranged from 34.27-0.27 with mean value of 10.49. It was higher in S2P3 (11.7) compared to S2P4 (9.20), S2P5 (5.71), S2P1 (3.49) and S2P2 (1.46). This indicated that soil sample from sampling point 3 and sampling point 4 of the dumpsite respectively had highest least PLI. Similarly, across the locations, it was higher in location point 3 (11.7) than location point 2 (1.46). Besides, results of CV indicated that its variation across the sampled soils was high (CV=99.49%). Based on ratings of PLI, all the sampled sites had PLI> 1 which indicated serious pollution of the assessed heavy metals.

Table 6: Single pollution index and pollution load index (PLI) of soils

Soil Samples	S2P1	S2P2	S2P3	S2P4	S2P5	Range (Mean ± SD)	CV%
Fe	20.93	17.58	22.17	21.51	21.84	23.27–17.58(21.42±1.62)	7.54
Mn	7.69	6.17	8.65	7.78	7.76	9.3–5.59(7.81±1.18)	15.05
Zn	13.13	11.71	14.15	12.71	13.29	15.07–10.91(13.38±1.35)	10.09
Cu	0.84	0.66	1.05	0.9	0.86	1.31–0.64(0.96±0.23)	23.51
Cr	0.74	0.55	0.95	0.77	0.8	1.26–0.46(0.85±0.24)	28.03
Cd	0.02	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.03	0.04–0.01(0.03±0.01)	37.93
Pb	0.19	0.16	0.27	0.22	0.2	0.32–0.09(0.23±0.07)	30.67
Ni	0.07	0.05	0.11	0.09	0.08	0.13–0.04(0.09±0.03)	34.37
V	0.11	0.06	0.18	0.14	0.13	0.23–0.05(0.14±0.06)	42.44
PLI	3.49	1.46	11.7	9.20	5.71	34.27–0.27(10.49±17.5)	99.49

Conclusion

The geochemical study of the dumpsite has revealed the presence of some of the physical, chemical and heavy metal concentrations at various degrees in the study area. The result of physical properties generally shows pH value to be above the WHO permissible limit in the water samples analyzed indicating that the groundwater in the study area is acidic. Total suspended solid, color, chemical oxygen demand, total dissolved solids were also detected in most of the samples analyzed. In the chemical properties, the result shows the presence of chloride ion, electrical conductivity, hydrogen carbonate, sodium, potassium, calcium, magnesium, ammonium nitrogen, in all the samples analyses and their coefficient of variation determined. Heavy metals like Iron(Fe), Manganese(Mn), Chromium(Cr), , Zinc (Zn), Cadmium (Cd), Nickel were detected and their coefficient of variation were determined.

The results of soil physiochemical samples analyzed reveal low coefficient variation in pH value, indicating that pH is uniformly distributed across the soils. The coefficient of variation of other metals which is also significant are iron, lead, zinc, chloride, magnesium, nickel and manganese. The single pollution index (SPI) of the water samples analyzed for heavy metal shows SPI <1 indicating low contamination. Based on rating for pollution load index (PLI), all the sample locations had PLI>1 which indicated serious pollution for all the heavy metals

analyzed. It can be concluded that the result of water samples and soil samples analyzed indicates that the water and soils in the vicinity of the dumpsite studied are polluted.

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Developing Coping Strategies for Smallholder Farmers in Nigeria

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Abstract

Smallholder farmers in Nigeria are increasingly exposed to climate-induced flooding which threatens livelihoods, food security and rural resilience. This study examined coping strategies adopted by smallholder farmers against flooding, identified socioeconomic factors influencing strategy choice, and assessed constraints limiting effective adaptation. A multistage sampling technique was used to select 180 smallholder farmers from flood-prone communities in Imo, Anambra, Delta and Abia States, Nigeria. Primary data were collected using structured questionnaires and analysed using descriptive statistics and multinomial logit regression. Results showed that farmers adopted multiple coping strategies including crop diversification, adjustment of planting dates, use of improved crop varieties, construction of drainage channels and livelihood diversification. Education level, farm size, farming experience, access to extension services and access to credit significantly influenced farmers' choice of coping strategies ($p < 0.05$). Major constraints included inadequate financial resources, limited access to timely climate information, weak institutional support and poor rural infrastructure. The study concludes that although smallholder farmers actively respond to flooding risks, their coping capacity remains constrained. Strengthening extension delivery, improving access to affordable credit, enhancing climate information dissemination and integrating indigenous knowledge into climate adaptation policies are recommended to build resilient smallholder farming systems in Nigeria.

Keywords: Coping strategies; Flooding; Smallholder farmers; Climate change; Nigeria

Introduction

Climate change poses a major threat to agricultural production systems worldwide, with developing countries being disproportionately affected due to their high dependence on climate-sensitive livelihoods (IPCC, 2022). In Nigeria, flooding has become the most recurrent and destructive climate-related hazard, causing widespread damage to farmlands, crops, livestock and rural infrastructure (Nwafor, 2019; World Bank, 2023). Increasing rainfall variability, poor land-use planning and inadequate drainage systems have intensified flood occurrences across many farming communities (FAO, 2021).

Smallholder farmers dominate Nigeria's agricultural sector, contributing over 80% of national food production (NBS, 2020). These farmers typically operate on small landholdings and rely heavily on rain-fed agriculture, making them particularly vulnerable to flooding impacts (Ozor and Madukwe, 2019). Flood events often result in crop failure, income loss, food insecurity and deepening rural poverty.

Coping strategies refer to short-term and long-term actions adopted by households to manage, reduce or offset the adverse effects of environmental shocks (Deressa et al., 2019). In flood-prone areas, farmers adopt a range of agronomic, economic and social measures to mitigate losses. However, the choice and effectiveness of these strategies are strongly influenced by socioeconomic characteristics, access to climate information and institutional support (Ajani et al., 2020; Akintola and Yusuf, 2021).

Despite the increasing frequency of flood events in Nigeria, empirical evidence on coping strategies adopted by smallholder farmers and the factors influencing their choices remains limited, particularly across multiple flood-prone states. This study therefore analysed coping strategies employed by smallholder farmers against flooding, identified determinants of strategy choice, and examined constraints to effective coping in Imo, Anambra, Delta and Abia States, Nigeria.

Materials and Method

Study Area

The study was conducted in selected flood-prone farming communities across Imo, Anambra, Delta and Abia States, Nigeria, located within the South-East and South-South geopolitical zones. The area is characterised by a tropical humid climate with distinct wet and dry seasons. Annual rainfall is high, often exceeding 2,000 mm, predisposing the region to recurrent flooding, particularly during the peak rainy season.

Agriculture is the dominant livelihood activity in the study area, with smallholder farmers cultivating crops such as cassava, maize, rice, yam and vegetables. The states are intersected by major rivers and low-lying floodplains, which increase exposure to seasonal flooding. Poor drainage infrastructure and increasing rainfall variability further exacerbate flood risks, making the area suitable for analysing farmers' coping strategies against flooding.

Sampling Technique and Data Collection

A multistage sampling technique was employed. In the first stage, Imo, Anambra, Delta and Abia States were purposively selected based on their vulnerability to flooding. In the second stage, flood-prone communities were selected from each state, followed by random selection of villages within the communities. In the final stage, smallholder farmers were randomly selected from village farmer lists to obtain a total sample size of 180 respondents.

Primary data were collected using structured questionnaires administered through face-to-face interviews. Information collected included farmers' socioeconomic characteristics, flooding experience, coping strategies adopted and constraints faced.

Analytical Techniques

Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages and means were used to summarise the data. A multinomial logit regression model was employed to analyse the socioeconomic factors influencing farmers' choice of coping strategies, consistent with climate adaptation studies in sub-Saharan Africa (Okonya et al., 2018; Akintola and Yusuf, 2021).

Results and Discussion

Results indicated that the majority of respondents were within the economically active age group and had considerable farming experience. Although many farmers had some level of formal education, access to credit and extension services remained limited, corroborating findings by Ajani et al. (2020).

Farmers across Imo, Anambra, Delta and Abia States adopted a combination of on-farm and off-farm coping strategies. Common strategies included crop diversification, adjustment of planting dates, use of improved and early-maturing crop varieties, construction of drainage channels, mixed cropping and livelihood diversification into non-farm activities. The use of multiple strategies suggests a risk-spreading approach, similar to observations by Ozor and Madukwe (2019) and FAO (2021).

Multinomial logit results revealed that education level, farm size, farming experience, access to extension services and access to credit significantly influenced farmers' choice of coping strategies ($p < 0.05$). Educated farmers were more likely to adopt improved technologies, while access to extension services enhanced awareness and uptake of climate-smart practices (Akintola and Yusuf, 2021; World Bank, 2023).

Major constraints identified included inadequate financial resources, limited access to climate and weather information, weak institutional support, high cost of improved inputs and poor rural infrastructure. These constraints significantly reduce farmers' adaptive capacity in flood-prone areas (IPCC, 2022).

Conclusion

Smallholder farmers in Imo, Anambra, Delta and Abia States, Nigeria, actively adopt diverse coping strategies to mitigate the impacts of flooding. However, their coping capacity remains constrained by financial, informational and institutional challenges. Addressing these constraints is essential for enhancing agricultural resilience and ensuring sustainable food production.

Recommendations

1. Strengthen agricultural extension services to improve farmers' access to climate information and adaptation technologies.
2. Improve access to affordable credit facilities for smallholder farmers.
3. Integrate indigenous coping practices into national and sub-national climate adaptation policies.
4. Invest in rural infrastructure, particularly drainage systems, to reduce flood impacts.

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SUB-THEME 3:

**ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTION AND
AGRICULTURAL, ARTIFICIAL
INTELLIGENCE AND BIG DATA IN
AGRICULTURE AND ENVIRONMENTAL
MONITORING; ENVIRONMENT AND
SUSTAINABLE HEALTH.**

**In - Vitro Assessment of Antioxidant Potentials and Phytochemical Profile of Ethanol,
Methanol Leaf Extracts of *Euphorbia Serrata*.**

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Abstract

The eminent use of medicinal plants in disease treatment and oxidative stress related illness cannot be over-emphasized. *Euphorbia serrata* suggested from its ethno-medicinal uses to possess antimicrobial, and antioxidant activities was assessed for its antioxidant and phytochemical constituents. The antioxidant potentials of the extracts was determined by their abilities to scavenge 2, 2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl radical, nitric oxide radical, hydrogen peroxide. The antioxidant potentials were further determined by the reducing power using standard methods. Phytochemical analysis was carried out using standard qualitative and quantitative analytical methods. Scavenging of DPPH, nitric oxide, H₂O₂ radicals and reducing power ability were concentration dependent. Ethanol extracts had a significant ($p < 0.05$) antioxidant scavenging activities for H₂O₂ and reducing power. *E. serrata* exhibited a strong reducing power (R.P 0.5_{AU} = 15.01 µg/ml and R.P 0.5_{AU} = 34.09 µg/ml) for ethanol and methanol extracts respectively and effectively scavenged DPPH, nitric oxide and H₂O₂ radicals. Threshold inhibitory concentrations (IC₅₀) of *E. serrate* and ascorbic acid against DPPH radicals were (28.74 µg/ml and 15.62 µg/ml) for ethanol extracts and (2.92 µg/ml and 15.62 µg/ml) for methanol extracts. IC₅₀ of *E. serrate* and ascorbic acid for nitric oxide radicals were (22.67µg/ml and 15.46 µg/ml) for ethanol extracts and (16.55µg/ml and 15.46 µg/ml) for methanol extracts. IC₅₀ of *E. serrata*, and ascorbic acid against H₂O₂ radicalswas (15.31 µg/ml and 15.15 µg/ml) for ethanol extracts and (15.48 µg/ml and 15.15 µg/ml) for methanol extracts. Results of phytochemical analysis revealed the presence of Alkaloids (6.85%), Tannins (35.2%), Saponnins (5.77%), Flavonoids (9.80%) and Cardiac glycosides (5.31%). This study suggested that *Euphorbia serrate* have strong antioxidant potentials, which can be used to treat various illness related to oxidative stress

Keywords: Euphorbia Serrata Phytochemicals, Antioxidant, IC₅₀, Free Radicals, Extracts, Scavenging.

Introduction

The investigation of antioxidant potentials and phytochemical profiles in plant extracts has garnered substantial attention in recent years, driven by the increasing recognition of natural compounds as sources of therapeutic agents (Uddin et al., 2018). Plants belonging to the Euphorbia genus have a rich history of use in traditional medicine for their antiseptic properties and in the treatment of various ailments, including upper respiratory tract infections like sinus congestion, common cold, and influenza (Gullón et al., 2020). The growing demand for plant-derived products in therapeutic applications has fueled research into the composition of plants and how it influences their applications (Vecchio et al., 2016). Investigating the phytochemical composition of Euphorbia serrata can reveal a wide array of bioactive compounds, such as alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, and phenolic acids, each contributing uniquely to the plant's therapeutic potential (Carrera et al., 2021). The antioxidant activity of these compounds is of particular interest, as it offers a defense against oxidative stress, a major contributor to numerous chronic diseases. (Chandorkar et al., 2021). Exploring the antioxidant potential and phytochemical composition of Euphorbia serrata not only contributes to the validation of its traditional medicinal uses but also paves the way for the discovery of novel therapeutic agents and applications in the pharmaceutical and nutraceutical industries (Khlifi et al., 2013). By identifying the specific compounds responsible for the plant's bioactivity, researchers can better understand the mechanisms of action and optimize extraction and formulation processes for maximum efficacy.

Materials and Method

Preparation of plant materials

Fresh leaves of *E. serrata* were collected from Eziudo in Ezinihitte L.G.A in Imo state. The identification and verification of the plant species were conducted at the Biology Department of University of Agriculture and Environmental Sciences, Imo State with voucher number UAES/BDH/0038 by a botanist. The leaves were washed with distilled water and air dried at room temperature for about 2-3 weeks until totally dried. The samples were crushed with electronic blender and sieved using 2 mm mesh size to uniform particle. The fine powder was then stored in a cool dry place until use.

Extraction

The powdered leaves of *E. serrata* was extracted with ethanol and methanol for a period of 72 h. The extracts were concentrated *in-vacuo* at 40° C, evaporated to dryness and the residues obtained were stored in a freezer at -20° C until needed for further study.

Phytochemical Screening

The qualitative and quantitative phytochemical screening of the plant samples for major bioactive constituent like tannins, flavonoids, alkaloids, saponins, phenols, terpenoids, carotenoids, cardiac glycosides, steroids etc was carried out using standard analytical methods.

Free Radical 2, 2-Diphenyl-1-Picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) Scavenging Activity.

The free radical scavenging activity testing was determined using 2, 2 - diphenyl-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) based on the method described by Lim and Quah (2007).

Concentrations of 20, 40, 60, 80 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of *Eurphorbia serrata* extract was mixed vigorously in 5 ml of DPPH solution (0.1 mM in methanol) and incubated for 30 minutes in the dark at room temperature. Decolourization of DPPH was measured against blank at 517 nm. The percentage inhibition was calculated using the formular and represented as

$$\% \text{inhibition} = \frac{(\text{Abs Blank} - \text{Abs sample}) \times 100}{\text{Abs Blank}}$$

Nitric Oxide Radical Scavenging Activity

The activity was measured based on the method described by Panda, Raj, Shrivastava and Prathani, (2009). To 4ml of the extract, having different concentration (20, 40, 60, 80 $\mu\text{g/ml}$), 1 ml of sodium nitroprusside (SNP) solution (5 mM) was added and incubated at 27°C for 2 h. An aliquot (2ml) of the incubation solution was removed and diluted with 1.2 ml of Griess reagent (1% sulphanilamide in 5% H_3PO_4 and 0.1% naphthylethylene diamine dihydrochloride). Absorbance of the chromophore was read immediately at 550 nm and compared with standard ascorbic acid.

$$\text{Nitric oxide scavenging activity (\%)} = \frac{\text{abs}(\text{control}) - \text{Abs}(\text{sample})}{\text{Abs}(\text{control})} \times 100$$

Where Abs (control): Absorbance of the control and

Abs (sample): absorbance of the extract.

Hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) Radical Scavenging Activity

The ability of the extract to scavenge hydrogen peroxide was determined based on the method adopted by Ngonda (2013). Two mMol/l solution of hydrogen peroxide was prepared in phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). Different concentrations of the extracts (20, 40, 60, 80 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) were added to (0.6 ml) hydrogen peroxide solution. After 10 min the absorbance of hydrogen peroxide at 230 nm was determined against a blank solution (containing phosphate buffer without hydrogen peroxide) and compared with the standard (ascorbic acid).

$$\text{H}_2\text{O}_2 \text{ activity (\%)} = \frac{\text{Abs}(\text{control}) - \text{Abs}(\text{sample})}{\text{Abs}(\text{control})} \times 100$$

Where, Abs (control): absorbance of the control and

Abs (sample): Absorbance of the extracts/standard

Total Reducing Power

The antioxidant activities were determined using the ferric reducing antioxidant power (FRAP) assay according to the method described by Sofidiya, Odukayo, Familoni and Inya-Agha, (2006).

Concentrations of the extracts (20, 40, 60, 80 $\mu\text{g/ml}$) in 1.0 ml deionized water was mixed with 2.5 ml of 0.2 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.6) and 2.5 ml of 1 % potassium ferrocyanide. Then mixture was incubated at 50°C for 20 minutes, latter 2.5 ml of 10% trichloroacetic acid

was added and centrifuged for 10 minutes at 3000 rpm. Then upper layer of the solution (2.5 ml) was mixed with 0.5 ml of 0.1% FeCl₃. The absorbance measured at 700 nm. All the tests were performed in duplicate and average plotted and compared with a standard vitamin C.

Qualitative Analysis

The method used in determination of phytochemical in this research as described by Ejikeme, Ezeonu, and Eboatu (2014) and Harbourne, Boulter and Turner, (1998) were used to carry out the qualitative analysis to ascertain the presence of different phytochemical constituents of the plant samples.

Test for Saponins

Frothing test

Powdered plant samples, 2.0 g of each was boiled in 20 ml of distilled water in a water bath and filtered. The filtrate (10 ml) was mixed with 5 ml of distilled water and shaken energetically for a stable persistent froth to occur. Three drops of olive oil was mixed with the frothing and shaken energetically and observed for the emulsion formation, confirmed the presence of Saponin.

Test for Alkaloids I

Two ml of HCl was added to 5 ml of each extracts, and then 1 ml of Dregendroff's reagent was added. The presence of alkaloid was indicated by the production of a red or orange precipitate.

Test for Alkaloids II

Into a test tube, 1.0 ml of each extract was pipetted, 5.0 ml of 2% HCl was also pipetted and was heated in a water bath for 10 minutes, filtered using filter paper (Whatman No1) and the filtrate was used for Wagner's Reagent Test.

Wagner's Reagent Test

Pipetted into test tube was 10 ml of filtrate and 1.0 ml of Wagner's reagent was pipetted, mixed properly, and observed for colour change. A reddish brown precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids. (Ejikeme, *et al.*, (2014).

Test for Cardiac Glycosides

Added into a test tube was 10 cm³ of 50% H₂SO₄, and 1.0 ml of each extract was also added, heated in boiling water for 5 minutes, and 10 cm³ of Fehling's solution (5 cm³ of each solution A and B) was added and boiled. It was observed for brick red precipitate indicating the presence of cardiac glycosides.

Test for Terpenoids

Into 2 ml of chloroform was added 5 ml of each extract, also 1.0 ml concentrated H₂SO₄ was carefully added which formed a layer. Reddish brown colouration of the inner interface was formed, showing the presence of terpenoid.

Test for Steroids

Into 2 ml chloroform was added 0.5 ml of each extract in a test tube, and 1.0 ml concentrated hydrogen sulphide (H₂SO₄) added which formed lower layer. Greenish brown interface colour was observed.

Test for Tannins

Acid Test

To 2.0 ml of 1% HCl was added 3.0 ml of extract and observed for the presence of red precipitate. Red precipitate indicated the presence of phlobotannins.

Test for Flavonoids

Sodium Hydroxide Test

Pipetted into the test was 1 ml of extract, 1.0 ml of dilute sodium hydroxide solution was also pipetted and the mixture was observed for colour change. Formation of precipitate indicated presence of flavonoids (Ejikeme *et al.*, (2014).

Test for Phenol

Ferric Chloride Test

Pipetted into the test tube was 1.0 ml of extract, 1.0 ml of 10 % FeCl was also pipetted and mixed properly and observed for colour change. Greenish brown or black coloration indicated the presence of phenolic nucleus.

Quantitative Analysis

Estimation of Saponin

From each plant sample, 5.0 g was measured into 20% acetic acid ethanol and allowed to stand in a water bath for 24 hours at 50°C. This solution was filtered and the extract was concentrated to one-quarter of the original volume using a water bath. Concentrated Ammonium hydroxide (NH₄OH) was added to the extract drop-wise until the precipitate was complete. The solution was allowed to settle, precipitate collected by filtration and weighed. The content of saponin was weighed and calculated in percentage using this formular (Harbourne *et al*, 1998).

Calculation:

$$\% \text{ saponin content} = \frac{(\text{weight of filter paper} + \text{residue}) - (\text{weight of filter paper}) \times 100}{\text{Weight of sample analysed}}$$

Estimation of Flavonoids

Five grams (5.0 g) of each plant samples was extracted with 100ml of 80% aqueous methanol at room temperature. The solution was then filtered and the filtrate evaporated to dryness using a water bath. The sample was then weighed (Harbourne *et al*, 1998). The percentage flavonoid was calculated using this formula.

Calculation:

$$\% \text{ flavonoids} = \frac{(\text{weight of beaker} + \text{Residue}) - (\text{weight of beaker}) \times 100}{\text{Weight of sample analysed.}}$$

Estimation of Alkaloids

From each plant samples, 5.0 g of the sample was transferred into a 250 ml beaker and 200 ml of 20% acetic acid in ethanol was added, covered and allowed to stand for 4 hours at 25°C. This solution was filtered using Whatman No.1, filtrate was concentrated to one - quarter of the original volume using a water bath. Concentrated NH₄OH was added to the extract drop-wise, the precipitate was collected and washed with dilute NH₄OH (1% ammonia solution). Pre-weighed filter paper was used to filter the solution. The residue on the filter paper is the alkaloid, and was dried in the oven at 80°C. The percentage alkaloid content was calculated (Harbourne *et al*, 1998).

Calculation:

$$\% \text{ weight of alkaloid} = \frac{(\text{Weight of filter paper} + \text{residue}) - (\text{weight of filter paper}) \times 100}{\text{Weight of sample analyzed}}$$

Estimation of Tannin by Titration

Follins-Dennis titrating method as described by Uyotismita and Arindan (2015) was used to estimate tannin. Five grams of ground plant sample in a conical flask was added 100ml of petroleum ether and covered for 24 hours. The solution was filtered and allowed to stand for 15 minutes, so that the petroleum ether will evaporate. It was soaked for 4 hours in 100 ml of acetic acid in ethanol for re-extraction. It was filtered and the filtrate collected.

To the filtrate, 25 ml of NH₄OH was added to precipitate the alkaloids. The alkaloid was heated with hot plate to remove some of the NH₄OH still in solution, the volume was measured, 5 ml was taken and 20 ml of ethanol was added to it. This was titrated with 0.1 M of Sodium hydroxide (NaOH) using an indicator (phenolphthalein) until pink end point was observed.

Tannin content was calculated in %

$$(C_1V_1 = C_2 V_2) \text{ molarity}$$

Calculation:

$$\text{Tannic acid } C_1V_1 = C_2 V_2$$

Where C₁=concentrated of Tannic acid

$$C_2 = \text{concentrated of Base} = 0.1 \text{ M}$$

$$V_1 = \text{volume of Tannic} = 5 \text{ ml}$$

$$V_2 = \text{Titre value of sample} = \text{titre} = 56.20$$

$$\text{Tannic acid } \underline{C_1} = \frac{C_2 V_2}{V_1}$$

$$V_1$$

$$\% \text{ of tannic acid content} = C_1 \times 100$$

Weight of sample analyzed

Estimation of Cardiac Glycosides

Cardiac glycosides estimation method as described by Osagie (1998) was adopted. A millilitre (1ml) of 2% solution of 3, 5 dinitrosalicylic acid (DNS) in methanol was added to 1 ml of the extract and 1 ml of 5% aqueous sodium hydroxide. It was boiled for 2 minutes until a precipitate (brick- red) was observed. The sample was filtered; the filter paper was weighed before filtration. The filter paper with the absorbed residue was dried in an oven at 50^o C. The weight of the filter paper with residue was recorded. The cardiac glycoside was calculated in percentage.

Calculation:

$$\% \text{ cardiac glycoside} = \frac{(\text{weight of filter paper} + \text{residue}) - (\text{weight of filter paper}) \times 100}{\text{Weight of sample analyzed}}$$

Estimation of Phytate

The phytate content in the samples was estimated using the method as described by Unuofin, Otunola and Afulayan, (2017). Each of the processed samples 2 g was weighed into three 250 ml conical flasks. Then each sample was soaked for hours in 100 ml of 2% concentrated hydrochloric acid (HCl). The samples were filtered and 50 ml of each filtrate placed in 250 ml beaker and 100 ml (distilled water) was added to each sample. About 10 ml solution of 0.3% ammonium thiocyanate (indicator) was added and titrated with standard Fe₃Cl solution which contained 0.00195 g (Fe) per ml. The phytic acid percentage was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Phytic acid \%} = \frac{\text{Titre value} \times 0.00195 \times 1.19 \times 100}{2}$$

2

Estimation of Terpenoid

Into 2.0 ml of chloroform was added 5.0 ml of each extract and was transferred from assay tube to colorimetric cuvette containing methanol 95% (V/V), used as blank to read the absorbance at 538 nm. Measured 200 ml of previously prepared linalool solution in methanol was added to 1.5ml chloroform for the standard curve and serial dilution was done (dilution level 100 mg/200 µl to 1 mg/ 200 µl linalool concentrations). For the serial dilution, total volume of 200 µl was made up by dilution of 95% (V/V) methanol.

Estimation of Phenol

The estimation of phenols was done using spectrophotometric method. The plant sample (2 g) was heated with 50 ml ethanol for 50 minutes. From the boiled sample, 5 ml was pipetted into 50 ml volumetric flask and 10 ml (distilled water) added. Also 2 ml of (NH₄OH) solution and concentrated pentanol (5 ml) were added to the mixture. The sample was made up to the mark and left for 30 minutes for colour development and the wavelength measured at 505 nm.

Estimation of Steroids

The steroid content was estimated spectrophotometrically using the method adopted by Owiredu, Teye and Quaye, (2013). Chloroform was added to 1.0 ml of extract to make the volume up to 5.0 ml. Liberman-Burchard reagent (concentrated Sulphuric acid (0.5 ml) in 10 ml of acetic anhydride) was added and mixed. The tubes were covered with black paper and kept under dark for 15 minutes. A green colour complex formed was measured spectrophotometrically at 640 nm. To construct a calibration curve, cholesterol was used as standard.

Data Analysis

Data was analysed using appropriate software (Microsoft Excel was used for calculating means and standard deviations. The software Table curve 2D systat, USA and Sigma plot 10.0 Systat USA was used for mathematical modelling of data from free radical scavenging activities. The percentage inhibition was calculated relative to control using equation 1. The inhibition data generated were fitted into appropriate non-linear equations (Alisi, Ojiako, Osugwu and Onyeze, 2011). The models used in this study are Logistic dose response abc (Equation 2), Logistic dose response abcd (Equation 3), Weibull cumulative abcd (Equation 4), Sigmoid models abc (Equation 5), and Sigmoid model abcd (Equation 6) respectively. The parameters were estimated by iterative minimization of least squares using Levenberg-Marquardt algorithm. The data of % inhibition or scavenging ability, fitted into the equation was used to evaluate the thresholds inhibitory concentrations (IC_{50}) which are the concentrations of the extracts that inhibited or scavenged 50% of the respective radicals. Equation with the highest Pearson correlation (R^2) and appropriateness to data was selected (Alisi *et al.*, 2011). Lower fit standard error was also considered as a criterion for acceptance of an equation as an appropriate model.

Equations

$$\% \text{ Inhibition} = \left[\frac{\text{Control}_{ABS} - \text{Test}_{ABS}}{\text{Control}_{ABS}} \right] \times 100 \quad 1$$

Logistic dose response model

$$y = \frac{a}{1 + \left(\frac{x}{b}\right)^c} \quad 2$$

Where: x is the concentration of the extract, a is the maximum response (of untreated control), b is the IC_{50} , c is parameter determining the relative slope at IC_{50} .

$$y = a + \frac{b}{1 + \left(\frac{x}{c}\right)^d} \quad 3$$

Where: x is the concentration of the extract, b is the maximum response (of untreated control), c is the IC_{50} , d is parameter determining the relative slope at IC_{50} .

$$y = a \left[1 - \exp \left[- \left[\frac{x + c(\ln 2)^{1/d} - b}{c} \right]^d \right] \right] \quad 4$$

Where: x is the concentration of the extract, a is the maximum response (of untreated control), b is the IC₅₀, c is parameter determining the relative slope at IC₅₀.

$$y = \frac{a}{1 + \exp - \frac{x - b}{c}} \quad 5$$

Where: x is the concentration of the extract, a is the maximum response (of untreated control), b is the IC₅₀, c is parameter determining the relative slope at IC₅₀.

$$y = y_0 + \frac{a}{1 + \exp - \frac{x - b}{c}} \quad 6$$

Where: x is the concentration of the extract, a is the maximum response (of untreated control), b is the IC₅₀, c is parameter determining the relative slope at IC₅₀, y₀ is a correction term

Results and Discussion

Ethanol and Methanol Extracts of *E.serrata* and Ascorbic acid on Scavenging of

2, 2-Diphenyl-1-Picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) Radical.

The antioxidant activity of plant extracts is often attributed to their rich content of phenolic compounds, which act as potent scavengers of free radicals and inhibitors of oxidative processes (Mondal et al., 2008). Figure 1 shows that the ethanol and methanol extracts of *E. serrata* exhibited high DPPH scavenging activities within the tested doses (20 µg/ml- 80 µg/ml). The scavenging activity was concentration dependent, with increasing concentration of extracts. *E. serrata* extracts scavenging activity was comparable with ascorbic acid. Threshold inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) obtained for the ethanol and methanol extracts of *E.serrata* and ascorbic acid were 28.74µg/ml, 2.92 µg/ml, and 15.62µg/ml respectively. Methanol extracts exhibited a high DPPH scavenging better than ascorbic acid. The result of the antioxidant potentials of Ethanol and methanol extracts of *E. serrata* exhibited high DPPH scavenging activities within the tested doses, showing its potential as a natural antioxidant (Cho et al., 2007). The scavenging activity activity observed in the ethanol and methanol extracts of *E. serrata* was concentration dependent, which aligns with previous research indicating that higher concentrations of plant extracts generally lead to increased antioxidant activity (Cho et al., 2007) and also suggests the presence of compounds capable of donating electrons or hydrogen atoms to neutralize DPPH radicals (Raj et al., 2017). The comparable scavenging activity of the extracts with ascorbic acid, a well-known antioxidant, indicates their potential as natural sources of antioxidants. High phenol and flavonoid contents frequently correlate with enhanced antioxidant activity in plant extracts (Subedi et al., 2014).

Comparative analysis of ethanol and methanol extracts of *E.serrata* and ascorbic acid on DPPH radical scavengingshowed that the DPPH scavenging abilities of ethanol extracts followed a Sigmoid abc model while the methanol extracts followed a Welbull abcd model. Methanol extracts scavenged DPPH radicals better than ethanol extracts as seen in the inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) values in Table 1.

Figure 1: Ethanol and methanol extracts of *E.serrata* and ascorbic acid on scavenging of 2, 2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) radical.

Table 1: Comparative analyses of ethanol and methanol extracts of *E.serrata* and ascorbic acid on DPPH radical scavenging.

Threshold Inhibitory concentration (IC_{50}) of DPPH radical scavenging activity of *Ethanol* and Methanol Extracts of *E. serrata* and Ascorbic acid standard

Extraction Solvent	Extracts	Model	R ²	IC ₅₀ *
	Ascorbic Acid	Sigmoid abc	0.991	15.62
Ethanol	<i>E. serrata</i>	Sigmoid abc	0.959	28.74
Methanol	<i>E. serrata</i>	Webull abcd	0.999	2.92

* IC_{50} is the concentration of the extract or standard that scavenged 50% of the generated free radicals.

Ethanol and Methanol Extracts of *E.serrata* and Ascorbic acid on Scavenging Nitric Oxide Radical.

Nitric oxide is a free radical involved in various physiological and pathological processes. The results obtained showed that ethanol and methanol extracts of *E. serrata* inhibitions of nitric oxide by the extracts were comparable to that observed for ascorbic acid. *E. serrata* exerted a good nitric oxide scavenging activity with inhibitory concentration (IC_{50}) value of 22.67 $\mu\text{g/ml}$, 16.55 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for ethanol and methanol respectively while ascorbic acid was more effective against nitric oxide radical with inhibitory concentration (IC_{50}) value of 15.46 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ as evaluated from the inhibition graph in fig 2. The methanol extracts have better nitric oxide scavenging properties than ethanol extracts. The nitric oxide radical scavenging was concentration dependent. The ability of the *E. serrata* extracts to scavenge nitric oxide suggests their potential in modulating nitric oxide-related pathways, which could have implications for inflammation and cardiovascular health.

Comparative analysis of ethanol and methanol extracts of *E.serrata* and ascorbic acid on nitric oxide radical scavenging showed that both ethanol and methanol extracts abilities to scavenge nitric oxide generated *in vitro* by sodium nitroprusside followed a Sigmoid abc

model. Methanol extracts scavenged nitric oxide radical better than ethanol extracts indicated by their IC₅₀ values as seen in Table 2.

Figure 2: Ethanol and Methanol extracts of *E. serrata* and ascorbic acid on scavenging nitric oxide radical.

Table 2: Comparative analyses of ethanol and methanol extracts of *E. serrata* and ascorbic acid on scavenging nitric oxide radical

Threshold Inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) of Nitric oxide radical Scavenging activity of ethanol and Methanol extracts *E. serrata* and Ascorbic acid

Extraction Solvent	Extracts	Model	R ²	IC ₅₀ *
	Ascorbic Acid	Sigmoid abc	0.998	15.46
Ethanol	<i>E. serrata</i>	Sigmoid abc	0.996	22.67
Methanol	<i>E. serrata</i>	Sigmoid abc	0.996	16.55

* IC₅₀ is the concentration of the extract or standard that scavenged 50% of the generated radical

Ethanol and Methanol Extracts of *E. serrata* and Ascorbic acid on Scavenging Hydrogen Peroxide (H₂O₂) Radical.

Figure 3 represents the hydrogen peroxide scavenging abilities of *E. serrata* ethanol and methanol extracts with ascorbic acid. The extract inhibited H₂O₂ compared with ascorbic acid. The inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) values of ethanol, methanol extract *E. serrata* were 15.31 µg/ml, 15.48 µg/ml and 15.15 µg/ml for ascorbic acid as evaluated from the inhibition graph. The ethanol extract scavenging abilities was better than methanol extracts. (Ignat et al., 2010). Flavonoids, a ubiquitous class of polyphenolic compounds in plants, are known for their antioxidant properties stemming from their capacity to scavenge free radicals via hydrogen donation or single electron transfer (Csepregi et al., 2016). The number of hydroxyl groups

and their positions on the aromatic ring significantly influence the antioxidant activity of phenolic acids (Ceramella et al., 2024).

Comparative analysis of ethanol and methanol extracts of *E. serrata* and ascorbic acid on hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) radical scavenging showed that ethanol extracts of *E. serrata* scavenged radicals better than methanol extracts as seen by their IC₅₀ values in Table 3. Ethanol and Methanol extracts of *E. serrata* and ascorbic acid followed a Sigmoid abc model.

Figure 3: Ethanol and methanol extracts of *E. serrata* and ascorbic acid on scavenging hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) radical

Table 3: Comparative analyses of ethanol and methanol extracts of *E. serrata* and ascorbic acid on scavenging hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) radical.

Threshold Inhibitory concentration (IC₅₀) of Hydrogen peroxide scavenging activity of Ethanol and Methanol extracts of *E. serrata* and Ascorbic acid standard

Extraction Solvent	Extracts	Model	R ²	IC ₅₀ *
	Ascorbic Acid	Sigmoid abc	0.996	15.15
Ethanol	<i>E. serrata</i>	Sigmoid abc	0.998	15.31
Methanol	<i>E. serrata</i>	Sigmoid abc	0.966	15.48

* IC₅₀ is the concentration of the extract or standard that scavenged 50% of the generated radicals

Reducing Power of Ascorbic acid, Ethanol and Methanol Extracts of *E. serrata*.

The absorbance of the plant extracts was in a dose dependent manner as increase in concentration increases the absorbance. The RP_{0.5UA} of Ascorbic acid, and ethanol, methanol extracts of *E. serrata* were 12.32 µg/ml, 15.01 µg/ml and 34.09 µg/ml respectively (Figure 4). The R² values for ascorbic acid, ethanol and methanol extracts of *E. serrata* were 0.980 and 0.995 and 0.999 respectively (Table 4). The result shows that ascorbic acid had a better reducing power ability compared to the extract of *E. serrata*, but ethanol extracts was better than methanol extracts. The comparative analysis followed a Sigmoid abcd model.

Figure 4: Reducing power of Ascorbic acid, Ethanol and Methanol extracts of *E. serrata* at 700 nm (RP_{0.5AU} of ascorbic acid, Ethanol and Methanol extracts of *E. serrata* were 12.32 µg/ml, 15.01 µg/ml and 34.09 µg/ml respectively)

Table 4: Comparative analysis of reducing power of Ascorbic acid, Ethanol and Methanol extracts of *E. serrata*.

Extracts	Mathematical Model		Pearson Correlation (R ²)		Reducing power RP _{0.5UA} (µg/ml)	
	Ethanol	Methanol	Ethanol	Methanol	Ethanol	Methanol
Ascorbic acid	Sigmoid abcd		0.980	0.980	12.32	12.32
<i>E. serrata</i>			0.995	0.999	15.01	34.09
						21.77

RP_{0.5UA} is the concentration of extract able to give 0.5 absorbance reading.

RP_{0.5UA} was evaluated from sigmoid abcd models.

Qualitative and Quantitative Phytochemical Result

Phytochemical analysis serves as a cornerstone in the exploration of medicinal plants, offering insights into the diverse array of bioactive compounds responsible for their therapeutic properties (Moussaoui et al., 2019). The presence of diverse phytochemicals in plant extracts is greatly influenced by the choice of extraction solvent, with different solvents exhibiting varying affinities for specific compounds (Antia et al., 2015). The selection of appropriate solvents, such as methanol, ethanol, and ethyl acetate, is crucial for maximizing the yield and diversity of extracted phytochemicals from plant materials (Iurckevicz et al., 2021; Jain et al., 2019). The result of this study shows that the ethanol and methanol extracts of *E. serrata* demonstrated different levels of phytochemicals extracted such as alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, phenols, saponins, cardiac glycosides, phytates, oxalates and steroids in variable amounts. The percentage quantitative constituents of each phytochemical extracted from *E. serrata* recorded Alkaloids (6.85%), Tannins (35.2%), Saponins (5.77%), Flavonoids (9.80%), Cardiac glycosides (5.31%) and Phytate (2.77%). The detection of alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids, saponins, and phenols underscores the plant's potential as a source of bioactive compounds with diverse pharmacological properties (Ajuru, 2017). These compounds have been extensively studied for their antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and anticancer activities. The observed variations in phytochemical profiles between ethanol and methanol extracts of *E. serrata* could be attributed to the differences in solvent polarities and their respective affinities for different classes of compounds (Sharma & Mishra, 2019). Ethanol is a widely used solvent in herbal medicine due to its ability to extract a broad range of compounds and its safety for internal consumption (Agarwal et al., 2016). Methanol, on the other hand, is a more polar solvent and may be more effective in extracting certain polar compounds (Sibero et al., 2019).

Conclusion

Plant extracts exhibit considerable promise as sources of natural antioxidants, providing a diverse array of bioactive compounds that can mitigate oxidative stress and promote health. The comprehensive assessment of antioxidant potentials and phytochemical profiles, as exemplified by studies on plant extracts, underscores the importance of further exploration and utilization of natural resources for the discovery of novel therapeutic agents and health-promoting compounds. This study suggests that the extracts of *Euphorbia serrata* have strong antioxidant potentials, which can be used to treat various illness related to oxidative stress.

Recommendation

Investigating the synergistic interactions among different phytochemicals within the plant extracts could provide insights into their enhanced bioactivity and potential health benefits.

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Enhancing Methane Yield through Wood Ash Biochar Addition in Anaerobic Digestion of Oily Food Waste.

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of wood ash-derived biochar on methane yield during the anaerobic digestion of oily food waste. Batch experiments were conducted over a 21-day retention period with biochar dosages of 0%, 1%, 3%, and 5% (w/w). The digestion setup was monitored daily for methane production, and cumulative yields were modeled using the Modified Gompertz equation to describe the kinetics of biogas generation. Results showed progressive increases in methane yield with increasing biochar dosage, with peak cumulative yields of 22.0, 21.4, 26.7, and 31.7 L for 0%, 1%, 3%, and 5% biochar additions, respectively. Kinetic modeling using the Gompertz equation provided high goodness of fit ($R^2 > 0.95$), indicating strong agreement between experimental and predicted data. The maximum methane production rate and potential yield increased with biochar addition, suggesting enhanced microbial activity and reduced lag phase. Analysis of variance (ANOVA) confirmed a significant treatment effect on methane yield ($F = 3.56$, $p < 0.05$). Post-hoc Tukey's HSD test ($HSD_{0.05} = 17.23$) revealed that the 5% biochar treatment ($M = 39.66$ L) differed significantly from the control ($M = 20.69$ L; $p = 0.025$), while other pairwise differences were statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$). In conclusion, biochar enhanced methane production, improved kinetic parameters, and stabilized digestion performance. These findings highlight the potential of wood ash biochar as a cost-effective additive for optimizing biogas yield from oily organic wastes, contributing to sustainable waste-to-energy conversion systems.

Keywords: Biochar, Methane yield, anaerobic digestion, Oily food waste

Introduction

Oily waste are mostly produced from biological, mechanical and domestic sources. Food related oily wastes are mainly used cooking oil unfit for consumption due to loss of nutritive value, discolored and odorous oil (Aditya *et al.*,2023), palm oil residues from oil mills, meat processing from abattoir, waste oily food waste from restaurants and households and kitchen waste oil. They are waste contaminated with oil, lubricants like grease, hydraulic oil or fats. It is usually rich in lipid content, triglycerides, free fatty acids that affects its physical, chemical, and biodegradation properties (Alghashm, et al 2023). Management of waste is an environmental concern especially going by World Bank estimates that solid waste might increase from 2.24 billion tons in 2020 to 3.88 billion tons by 2050 (Manga et al , 2023) whereas about 75% of the waste generated are landfilled. Chao et al., (2022) The United

Nations Food and Agriculture Organization estimated food waste annual production at about 13.8% of total waste.

Although oily wastes is dense and has high energy potential, the high oil content hydrophobic nature, poor biodegradability and scum forming tendency during biological digestion is detrimental to many waste treatment processes (Ogumba and Burka 2023). Food waste putrefy when improperly handle. The use for biogas production is an efficient waste-to-energy approach. Oily waste is pretreated to make it feat for anaerobic digestion also addition of biochar has been reported to improve methane production (Aditya *et al.*, 2023).

Biochar is produced from biomaterials remains by heating under limited or no oxygen (a process known as pyrolysis). Recent findings shows that biochar additive serves as microbial support medium, potent pH stabilizer, and good adsorbent conditions that increase biogas yield during anaerobic digestion (Capone et al., 2024). Manonmani et al., (2017) reported the increase in concentration of volatile solids of the input, the density of the effluent with biochar additive were advantageous for process stabilization in methane production. Increase in methane yield with biochar dosage was observed in waste feedstock anaerobic digestion (Vijay et al., (2024). Inoculum is an essential microbial seed that activate anaerobic digestion. Manga et al (2023) described it as methanogenic source of active anaerobic microorganisms used to start or accelerate biogas digestion. It catalysis rapid methane formation and sustain digestion stability. Slurry, sewage and cow dung are potent source of inoculum (Li et al., 2023). Nwaigwe et al., (2018) used that of an active biogas digester. This work is a further study on the yield of methane of using oily waste at different dosages of biochar. It will increase the prospect of oily waste usage for methane production as well present how effective wood ash (biochar additive) alleviate challenges in biogas production.

Materials and Method

Characterization of oily food waste

The characterization of each sample was undertaken in the institution's Chemical Engineering laboratory. About 2.0g of each oily waste samples was weighed with a digital balance and standard laboratory procedures was followed to determine the volatile solid, total solid, moisture content, pH value, and temperature of reaction. The characteristics were calculated using Equations 1 to 3.

The volatile matter of waste was calculated using the Equation 1.

$$\text{Volatile matter} = \frac{\text{weight of sample from oven} - \text{weight of sample from furnace}}{\text{weight of sample}} \quad 1$$

The moisture content was calculated

$$\begin{aligned} \text{\% moisture (wb)} &= \frac{\text{wet weight} - \text{Dry weight}}{\text{Wet weight}} \times 100 \quad 2 \\ &= \frac{(W_1 - W_2)}{W_1} \times 100 \end{aligned}$$

Where

W_1 = weight of wet sample + crucible

W_2 = weight of oven dried sample + crucible.

$$\text{Total Solids (TS) (\%)} = \frac{\text{Dry weight}}{\text{Wet weight}} \times 100 \quad 3$$

The temperature was measure using a thermocouple

Methane production

The experiment was carried out using the digester Fig (1) at the Agricultural and Bioenvironmental Engineering of Imo State Polytechnic .The cylindrical metallic mill steel tank is 50cm in diameter, and 76cm in height, volume is 150 liters. The inlet (input) chamber is at angle of 60 degrees to the tank for substrate flow by gravity to the digester whereas the outlet (discharge) 4.5cm in diameter.

Figure 1: Plate of Biogas digester

The oily waste was collated from Umuagwo palm oil mill. Wood ash biochar was procured from Etche Charcoal firm whereas the inoculum was collected from previous test with the digester. Batch experiments were conducted with 40 liters (24kg) of waste oily over a 21-day retention period with biochar dosages of 0%, 1%, 3%, and 5% (w/w) of the oily waste and 2 liter of inoculum was used for each batch. The 0% biochar was used as control. The equations for the processes are stated in Equation 4 to 6.

Other gasses found in trace levels from the reaction are H₂S, CO, NH₃, N₂ and water vapour.

Data Analysis

One way ANOVA of the experimental data was done and Tukey's HSD procedure was used for pairwise comparisons between and within the means to determine the significant difference at $p < .05$. Kinetic modeling using the Gompertz equation (Equation 7) to provide the goodness of fit to the experimental data. The Gompertz model was employed to quantitatively simulate the cumulative biogas produced. The model is widely used in kinetic

modelling of biogas production during AD especially when production follows a pattern similar to microbial growth (Daniel et al. 2025).

$$\gamma_t = P_m * \exp \left\{ - \exp \left[\frac{R_m * e}{P_m} * (\lambda - t) \right] \right\} \quad 7$$

Where γ_t is the cumulative biogas generated (mL), t is the time (days), P_m = the highest achievable biogas potential (L/g VS), R_m = the peak daily biogas generation (L/g VS/d), λ =delay period (days), e = Euler's number (≈ 2.71828)

Results and Discussion

Methane Production Profile for Biochar-Amended Digesters

The trend of methane production with 0% biochar (control), 1 % biochar, 3% biochar and 5% biochar is shown in Figure 2. Figure 2 shows the variation in methane yield with 0%, 1%, 3%, and 5% biochar additions. It can be seen that all treatments displayed a characteristic methane production trend consisting of four stages: lag phase, exponential rise, peak phase, and decline.

Figure 2: Cumulative methane yield with time (days).

This behavior is typical for anaerobic digestion of lipid-rich substrates (Alghashm et al 2023).

a. Lag Phase (Days 1–5)

Methane generation remained very low (<5 L) for all treatments. During this period, hydrolytic and acidogenic microorganisms were adapting to the oily substrate and converting long-chain fatty acids (LCFAs) into simpler intermediates as reported by (Nwaigwe et al. (2018). At this stage Biochar did not influence this initial acclimatization, resulting in identical trends across treatments.

b. Exponential Growth Phase (Days 6–12)

Between Days 6 and 12, there was rapid methane formation as methanogens became fully active. The methane production for 5% biochar was 60 L by Day 12, that of 3% and 1% biochar were 55.L and 38–40 L respectively whereas 0% biochar, the control, exhibited the slowest increase (30–33 L).The result agree with the assertion that Biochar's porous structure improved microbial colonization, pH buffering, and adsorption of inhibitory LCFAs (Cruz et al. 2017), which accelerated methanogenesis compared to the control.

c. Peak Methane Production (Days 12–16)

All treatments reached their peak methane yields between Days 13 and 16. For 5% biochar, highest peak yield was at 70 L, 3% biochar was second highest at 65 L while 1% and 0% biochar had 43 L and 35 L. Although the magnitude of methane yield varied, the peak occurred at approximately the same period, indicating that the underlying biochemical pathways reported by Maet *al* (2023) (hydrolysis → acidogenesis → acetogenesis → methanogenesis) progressed at similar rates.

d. Decline Phase (Days 16–22)

After Day 16, methane production declined across all treatments, same observation was reported by (Cruz et al. 2017). The decline coincided with the depletion of readily biodegradable fractions of the oily waste. The similarity of the downward trends demonstrates that substrate availability, rather than biochar dose, controlled digester performance at this stage, this is in agreement with Singhalet al (2023).

Although biochar improved methane yield, the general shape of the curves remained similar because of the same oily substrate, so the breakdown process followed the same hydrolysis–acidogenesis–methanogenesis sequence. Biochar enhances performance but does not change the fundamental kinetics of anaerobic digestion. It mainly improves microbial attachment, electron transfer, and buffering, which increases magnitude, not timing, of methane peaks as reported in Qiu et al (2019). Environmental conditions were identical, causing synchronized microbial activity across treatments. Substrate exhaustion occurred at the same time, so all treatments declined together after Day 16.

Effects of treatments on methane yield

Analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to evaluate the effect of treatment on methane yield. The results indicated a significant difference among the treatments, with an F-ratio of 3.56 and a corresponding p-value of 0.0178 ($p < 0.05$) as showed in Table 2. This suggests that at least one treatment group differed significantly from the others in terms of methane production.

Table 2: Analysis of variance (ANOVA) for methane production with biochar				
<i>Source</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>MS</i>	F.ratio
Between-treatments	4837.9968	3	1612.6656	$F = 3.56062$
Within-treatments	36233.4143	80	452.9177	
Total	41071.411	83		

The *f*-ratio value is 3.56062. The *p*-value is .017832. The result is significant at $p < .05$.

ANOVA results revealed a significant effect of treatment on methane yield ($F_{3,80} = 3.56$, $p = 0.018$), indicating that methane production varied across the treatments. Post-hoc Tukey HSD analysis showed that T₄ (39.66L) produced significantly more methane than T₁ (20.69 L, $Q = 4.09$, $p = 0.025$), while differences between other

treatment pairs were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). These findings suggest that increasing the treatment level positively influenced methane yield, with T₄ achieving the highest production, highlighting the potential for treatment optimization in enhancing anaerobic digestion performance which confirm Dai et al (2023) observation

Post-hoc pairwise comparisons using the Tukey HSD test in Table 3 revealed that the difference between 0% biochar or T₁ (20.69 L CH₄) and 5% biochar or T₄ (39.66 L CH₄) was statistically significant ($Q = 4.09$, $p = 0.025$), indicating that the T₄ treatment produced a higher methane yield compared to T₁. Differences between other treatment pairs (T₁:T₂, T₁:T₃, T₂:T₃, T₂:T₄, and T₃:T₄) were not statistically significant at the 5% level ($p > 0.05$). The mean differences and corresponding Q-values for these comparisons suggest trends toward increased methane production with higher treatment levels, although these were not statistically significant.

Table 3: Post-hoc pairwise comparisons using Tukey's HSD (honestly significant difference)

<i>Pairwise Comparisons</i>		HSD_{.05} = 17.2328 HSD_{.01} = 21.1088	Q_{.05} = 3.7107 Q_{.01} = 4.5453
T₁: T₂	M ₁ = 20.69 M ₂ = 24.62	3.93	Q = 0.85 ($p = .93222$)
T₁: T₃	M ₁ = 20.69 M ₃ = 34.62	13.93	Q = 3.00 ($p = .15513$)
T₁:T₄	M ₁ = 20.69 M ₄ = 39.66	18.98	<u>Q = 4.09 ($p = .02510$)</u>
T₂:T₃	M ₂ = 24.62 M ₃ = 34.62	10.00	Q = 2.15 ($p = .42874$)
T₂:T₄	M ₂ = 24.62 M ₄ = 39.66	15.05	Q = 3.24 ($p = .10878$)
T₃:T₄	M ₃ = 34.62 M ₄ = 39.66	5.04	Q = 1.09 ($p = .86869$)

T = treatments: T₁ = 0% biochar, T₂ = 1% biochar T₃ = 3% biochar, T₄ = 5% biochar. M = Means: M₁, M₂, M₃, M₄ are for 0%, 1% ,3% and 5% biochar respectively. Q = mean difference at 0.0 and 0.5 respectively

Overall, the results demonstrate that the applied treatments significantly influenced methane yield, the assertion is confirmed in Yang et al (2023), with the highest yield observed in T₄. This highlights the potential for optimized treatment strategies to enhance anaerobic digestion performance.

Relationship between temperature of process and Methane yield

Figures 3 to 6 showed the relationship between methane yield and temperature of digester. Pearson correlation analysis between methane yield and temperature for the 0% biochar digester showed a negative R^2 of -0.0058 , indicating no significant linear association between the two variables (Fig 3). Although methane yield increased over time, this trend was not statistically explained by temperature variations. The weak correlation is attributed to the narrow mesophilic temperature range ($26\text{--}30.5^\circ\text{C}$), within which methanogenic archaea remain metabolically stable. Thus, methane production was primarily influenced by substrate biodegradation dynamics rather than temperature fluctuations which was observed by Trisakti et al (2021)

Figure 3: Methane yield with temperature of digester of control.

Correlation analysis for the 1% biochar addition shown in Figure 4 indicated a moderate positive association between methane yield and temperature ($r = 0.3955$, $R^2 = 0.156$). This indicates that approximately 15.6% of the variation in methane production can be attributed to temperature changes. The positive direction of the correlation suggests that methane yield tended to increase with higher mesophilic temperatures also observed in Li and Shimizu (2023); however, the relationship was not strong enough to conclude that temperature was the primary driver of methane generation.

Figure 4: Methane yield with temperature of digester for 1% biochar and temperature

The moderate association reflects the stabilizing effect of biochar, which enhances microbial activity, buffering capacity, and syntrophic interactions, thereby reducing the system's sensitivity to daily temperature fluctuations.

From Figure 5 below, the temperature profile of the 3% biochar (T_3) treatment exhibited a relatively stable mesophilic regime throughout the digestion period, with recorded values fluctuating narrowly between 27°C and 30°C. An initial baseline of 28–29°C was observed, followed by a modest rise coinciding with early microbial activity (0.9–9.9 days). The system displayed intermittent temperature elevations to 29.5–30°C during peak metabolic phases (days 30.4–67.2), suggesting enhanced microbial oxidation associated with the biochar-amended substrate as obtained in Salado et al (2023).

Figure 5: Methane yield with temperature of digester for 3% biochar and temperature

Notably, no thermophilic shift occurred, indicating that the digestion process remained fully mesophilic. This stability is consistent with the buffering and thermal moderation properties of biochar, which improve heat retention and support a conducive environment for methanogenic consortia. The slight decline toward the end of the cycle (28–29°C) reflects reduced substrate availability and attenuation of microbial activity. Overall, the 3% biochar treatment demonstrated temperature stability optimal for mesophilic anaerobic digestion, reinforcing the role of biochar in maintaining thermal equilibrium and supporting sustained biogas production as observed in Cheong et al (2020).

The temperature dynamics of the 5% biochar treatment (T_5) displayed in Figure 6 below showed broader fluctuations compared to lower biochar dosages, ranging from 26.5°C to 31.5°C, yet remaining within the mesophilic domain.

Figure 6: Methane yield with temperature of digester for 5% biochar and temperature

The digestion process initiated at 27–28.5°C, followed by a notable early rise to 30–31.5°C within the first 2.4 days, indicating intensified microbial activity stimulated by the higher biochar content. Mid-phase temperatures showed periodic declines to 26.5–28.5°C (days 28.6–40.4), suggesting temporary reductions in metabolic heat generation likely due to substrate degradation variability. Subsequent rebounds to 29.5–31.5°C (days 49.8–72.2) reflect renewed microbial turnover and improved thermochemical stability as biochar enhanced buffering and electron transfer pathways. The late-phase stabilization around 29–30.5°C demonstrates the system’s return to mesophilic equilibrium despite earlier fluctuations. Overall, the 5% biochar amendment induced pronounced but controlled thermal variability, supporting active microbial consortia while maintaining temperatures conducive to mesophilic anaerobic digestion, which is reported in Cui et al (2023). This behavior underscores biochar’s capacity to influence thermal responses at higher dosages without compromising digester stability.

Across all biochar dosages (1%, 3%, and 5%), the temperature profiles remained within the mesophilic range, demonstrating stable operational conditions throughout the digestion period. The 1% biochar treatment maintained a narrow thermal band between 26.5°C and 31.5°C, with minor fluctuations indicative of moderate microbial heat generation and steady-state digestion. The 3% biochar treatment similarly exhibited a stable range (27–30°C), reflecting a balanced metabolic response in which increased biochar availability enhanced buffering but did not significantly alter thermal behavior. In contrast, the 5% biochar treatment showed slightly wider temperature variations (26.5–31.5°C), characterized by early increases associated with heightened microbial activity and mid-phase dips linked to transitional substrate utilization as reported in Li et al., (2022). Despite these fluctuations, the system consistently returned to mesophilic equilibrium. Overall, the combined temperature response across treatments demonstrates that biochar amendment, even at elevated levels, does not disrupt mesophilic stability, but rather supports a controlled thermodynamic environment favorable for efficient anaerobic digestion, similar observation was made in Cavali et al., (2023).

Kinetic Parameters and Model Goodness Fit

The modified Gompertz model was applied to describe cumulative methane production from oily food waste with varying biochar additions (0%, 1%, 3%, and 5%). The model fitting variables included maximum methane potential (P), maximum methane production rate (R_m), lag phase (λ), along with sum of squares (SS) and R² to assess goodness-of-fit the result is shown in Table 4. Maximum Methane Potential (P) increased with biochar concentration from 30.12 L/g VS in control to 35.25 L/g VS in 1% Biochar, 54.23 L/g VS in 3% Biochar and 62.54 L/g VS in 5% Biochar. Table 4 shows the parameters acquired with Excel during the optimization process using the Gompertz model whereas the curve is showed as Figure 6.

Table 4: Gompertz model goodness fitting parameters

Conditions	P_m(L/g VSd)	R_m(L/g VS)	λ	SS	R²
0% (Control)	30.12	10.6	6.5	22709	0.8694
1% biochar	35.25	13.97	6.36	610.54	0.8961
3% biochar	54.23	13.83	6.97	2594.31	0.9172
5% biochar	62.54	14.54	6.79	1076.46	0.9280

Maximum Methane Production Rate (R_m) in control was 10.6 L/g VS/day, 1% Biochar was 13.97 L/g VS/day, 3% Biochar was 13.83 L/g VS/day and 14.54 L/g VS/day in 5% Biochar. Obviously addition of biochar clearly improved the rate of methane formation as observed in Li et al., (2023), especially at 1% and 5%. Notably, R_m for 3% is slightly lower than 1% and 5%, suggesting that while 3% biochar maximizes cumulative methane, the peak rate is influenced by microbial dynamics and substrate availability.

Lag Phase (λ) were fairly unchanged. It was in the Control 6.5 days, 6.36 days in 1% Biochar, and 6.97 days in 3% Biochar while 5% Biochar was 6.79 days. Biochar slightly reduced or maintained the lag phase, indicating faster microbial adaptation and earlier initiation of methane production compared to control. The minor variations reflect the influence of microbial community structure and substrate accessibility.

Table 4 showed that checking the Model Goodness-of-Fit, Sum of Squares (SS) increased with higher biochar concentrations, reflecting larger methane volumes and variance. That of Control was 227.09, 1% Biochar was 610.54, whereas 3% Biochar and 5% biochar were 2594.31 and 1076.46. the R² (Coefficient of Determination) values ranged from 0.8694 to 0.928, indicating good fit of the Gompertz model to the experimental data. The highest R² was observed for 5% biochar (0.928), confirming the model captured the cumulative methane kinetics accurately.

The trend in Figure 6 below demonstrate a clear enhancement in methane yield with biochar as reported in Shanmugam et al., (2023). The increase is attributed to improved microbial colonization on biochar surfaces, enhanced direct interspecies electron transfer (DIET) between syntrophic bacteria and methanogens and buffering of inhibitory long-chain fatty acids (LCFAs) in oily waste. The plateau reached its highest value at 5% biochar, indicating a dose-dependent positive effect although the rate of increase from 3% to 5% is smaller than from 1% to 3%, suggesting diminishing returns at higher loadings.

Figure 6: Modified Gompertz curve for biochar additions (0%, 1%, 3%, and 5%).

The Gompertz model reliably described the sigmoidal kinetics of methane production for all treatments Cui et al., (2023). Higher biochar concentrations increased cumulative methane (P) and peak production rate (R_m), demonstrating its stimulatory effect on anaerobic digestion. The lag phase was slightly reduced or stable, highlighting biochar's role in accelerating microbial adaptation.

Conclusion

The results of this study clearly demonstrate that biochar addition significantly enhanced the daily methane production from oily food waste digestion compared to the control (0% biochar). The methane profiles reveal a consistent trend where higher biochar dosages produced higher methane yields, with 5% biochar achieving the greatest improvement. While the control treatment exhibited a slow and modest rise in methane production, peaking at 37.5 L/g VS/d on day 16, the biochar-amended digesters showed markedly superior performance. The 1% and 3% biochar treatments produced substantially higher peak methane values of 43.4 L/g VS/d and 67.2 L/g VS/d respectively, indicating enhanced microbial activity and improved process stability. Notably, the 5% biochar treatment achieved the highest peak methane production of 72.2 L/g VS/d, representing the most effective dose for stimulating methanogenesis in this study.

Across all treatments, biochar accelerated the onset of active methane production, increased the maximum methane generation rate, and prolonged the period of stable gas output before decline. The improved performance can be attributed to the well-documented roles of biochar in anaerobic digestion, including enhanced buffering capacity, increased surface area for

microbial colonisation, improved mass transfer, and facilitation of direct interspecies electron transfer.

Overall, the findings confirm that biochar addition—especially at 3–5% w/w—substantially improves methane generation from oily food waste. These results highlight the potential of biochar-augmented anaerobic digestion as a robust strategy for valorizing lipid-rich organic waste, increasing renewable energy yield, and enhancing digester stability. Future work should focus on kinetic modelling, optimisation of biochar properties, and long-term operational performance to fully integrate biochar-assisted digestion into sustainable waste-to-energy systems.

The kinetic parameters of methane production from oily food waste amended with 0%, 1%, 3%, and 5% biochar, as estimated by the modified Gompertz model. The plateau methane potential (P) increased progressively with biochar addition, from 30.12 L/g VS for the control to 62.54 L/g VS for 5% biochar, demonstrating enhanced substrate conversion. The maximum methane production rate (R_m) similarly increased, indicating faster microbial activity, while the lag phase (λ) remained relatively short across treatments, reflecting rapid microbial adaptation. Goodness-of-fit indicators, including the sum of squares (SS) and R² values (0.869–0.928), confirm that the Gompertz model reliably described the sigmoidal kinetics of methane formation. These results collectively suggest that biochar addition improves both the rate and extent of methane production in batch anaerobic digestion of oily food waste. The Gompertz fitting clearly illustrates that biochar enhances both the magnitude and kinetics of methane production from oily food waste. The combination of P, R_m, λ , SS, and R² confirms both process improvement and model reliability. Among the treatments, 5% biochar produced the highest methane yield, while 3% achieved nearly the same yield but with slightly lower rate dynamics, indicating an optimal biochar range of 3–5% for this substrate.

From the study biochar significantly enhanced methane yield; however, the biochemical conversion pathway remained the same across treatments, resulting in similar trend shapes with different methane peak magnitudes. Biochar enhances microbial attachment, adsorbs toxic compounds, stabilizes pH, improves methane yield. Inoculum Supplies methanogenic bacteria that initiate and sustain anaerobic digestion.

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Morphological Characterization and Potential Applications of Graphene Oxide Synthesized from Sawdust Waste: A SEM-Based Approach

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Abstract

The development of sustainable, green synthesis routes for graphene oxide (GO) has gained considerable attention as conventional methods often involve hazardous chemicals and costly precursors. Despite this, limited studies have explored the direct conversion of lignocellulosic biomass waste into GO with controlled morphology. In this work, sawdust an abundant and underutilized agricultural byproduct was employed as a low-cost, renewable precursor for GO synthesis. The Modified Hummers Method was adapted to optimize yield and reduce environmental impact. GO, a multifunctional nanomaterial, is valued for its high surface area, tunable surface chemistry, and outstanding physicochemical properties, enabling applications in electronics, energy storage, water purification, and biomedicine. Morphological characterization via scanning electron microscopy (SEM) under high vacuum (5.0 kV, Everhart–Thornley Detector) at magnifications of $\times 100$ to $\times 1000$ revealed wrinkled sheet-like structures, porous networks, and agglomerated particles, a hallmark features of GO. The successful synthesis from sawdust not only demonstrates a viable waste-to-nanomaterial pathway but also reinforces the role of biomass economic importance in sustainable nanotechnology.

Keywords: Graphene Oxide, Sawdust waste, Green Synthesis, Morphology, Biochar

Introduction

Agricultural byproducts are referred as critical challenges which need to be addressed as they are becoming unfriendly to the environment (Rizket *et al.*, 2024). Conventional approaches should not be the only avenue of disposal, rather they should be converted to valuable resources. Graphene as family is addressed as a valuable agricultural residues. Graphene oxide (GO) has emerged as a promising nanomaterial owing to its unique physicochemical properties and functional versatility. This novel material has an outstanding features as reported by Rizket *et al.*, 2024; Moses *et al.*, 2023; Mendez-Lozano *et al.*, 2022; Tohamy *et al.*, 2020 & Aro-Modiu *et al.*, 2019).

Due to their abundant oxygen functional groups and high surface area, these two-dimensional materials are suitable for further modification (Renet *et al.*, 2014). These properties enable the GO structure to have broad application prospects in various domains such as photovoltaic (Widianto *et al.*, 2021), energy storage, catalysis (Doustkhah & Rostamnia, 2016), biosensors (Kang *et al.*, 2023), and so on. GO provides a variety of chemical techniques for attaching various functional groups to its surface, allowing it to adjust its electrical, optical transparency, and thermal conductance (Didekin & Vul, 2019). Furthermore, by entirely adjusting its functional groups, it can modify its band gap to obtain zero band gap graphene. Because of the existence of oxygenated groups, the GO structure has attractive characteristics. Recent approaches to GO synthesis have explored sustainable precursors such as lignocellulosic biomass (Civaset *et al.*, 2023; Ghosh *et al.*, 2020). Sawdust, an abundant agricultural waste product, offers a rich carbon source for GO production. This paper

explores the morphological attributes of GO derived from sawdust using SEM analysis, aiming to confirm synthesis and propose practical applications.

Materials and Methods

Materials: Sawdust waste, Potassium Hydroxide (KOH), Hydrochloric Acid (HCL), Sulfuric Acid (H_2SO_4), Potassium Permanganate ($KMnO_4$), Beakers, Conical flasks Measuring cylinders, Glass stir rods, furnace, magnetic stirrer, oven, Buchner funnel, filter paper, Analytical balance, mortar and pestle sieves and safety equipment. This paper was the continuation of the work published by (Sahabi *et al.*, 2024).

Preparation of Raw Materials

Pre-treatment: Clean and dry the sawdust waste. Grind them into fine powder.

Chemical Activation: Mix the powdered sawdust with KOH in a 1:1 ratio. Heat the mixture from $200^{\circ}C$ to $700^{\circ}C$ for 1 hour in a furnace to activate the carbon, to enhance porosity and surface area, treat the biochar with activating agent. After activation, the activated carbon was washed thoroughly with distilled water to remove any residual activating agent. The solution was neutralized using the dilute hydrochloric acid (HCL) before washing.

Reduction to GO

At the oxidation process, which convert activated carbon into GO, mix it with concentrated sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) and 2M of potassium permanganate ($KMnO_4$) in a ratio of 1:4 ($KMnO_4:H_2SO_4$). While stirring continuously to maintain the temperature below $50^{\circ}C$ to control the reaction. Gradually increase the temperature to $35^{\circ}C$ and stir for 2 hours to ensure complete oxidation. This step introduces oxygen-containing functional groups. By diluting the oxidized mixture with distilled water and then add hydrogen peroxide (3-6% (w/w) or 0.88-1.76 M). This will yield GO flakes.

Reduce graphene oxide (rGO) using reducing agents like hydrazine hydrate or sodium borohydride (typical concentration: 1-5% (w/w) or 0.1-1.0 M) at reaction conditions of $80-100^{\circ}C$ for 24 hours. This step converts GO into rGO. Figure 1, is the schematic representation of the transformation process from sawdust to GO vi chemical oxidation and exfoliation.

GO was synthesized from sawdust via a modified Hummers method involving chemical oxidation. SEM imaging was conducted using a JEOL model equipped with an ETD under high vacuum. Imaging conditions included:

1. Accelerating Voltage: 5.0 kV
2. Working Distance (WD): $\sim 14.0-14.2$ mm
3. Magnification: $\times 100$, $\times 150$, $\times 250$, $\times 500$, and $\times 1000$
4. Scale Bars: Ranging from $500\ \mu m$ to $50\ \mu m$

Figure 1: Sawdust Waste to GO Process Flow

Images were evaluated for topographical and morphological features using reference standards

Results

Figure 2, presents the SEM morphological features of GO derived from sawdust, highlighting the surface characteristics at varying magnifications and corresponding working distances.

Figure 2: SEM of GO Synthesized from Sawdust Waste at Different Magnification and Working Distance

Figure 2(a) revealed large-scale surface features such as fiber bundles, macro pores, and agglomeration zones, this proves that GO consist of a few layers that stack together which is in agreement with the work reported by (Smith *et al.*, 2019). While Figure2(b)showed finer textures including wrinkled sheets, interlinked flakes, and delamination patterns that are consistent with oxidized graphite derivatives.The extended focus due to ~14 mm working distance (WD) facilitated imaging of uneven porous surfaces. On the surface topology, the ETD-enhanced secondary electron (SE) imaging revealed sponge-like morphology typical of GO.The morphology of the synthesized GO samples is sheets randomly aggregated with

rounded folds. Additionally, all the images consist of layers with different transparencies which may be attributed to the number of layers as reported by (Shalaby *et al.*, 2015).

The images further showed that the GO consists of randomly aggregated crumpled nanosheets closely associated with each other by strong interaction and the morphology is distinctly different from that of graphite (Moses *et al.*, 2023). The crumpling in the morphology was due to exfoliation and restacking of GO sheet.

Discussion

The presence of wrinkled sheet-like structures at higher magnifications aligns with known SEM characteristics of GO. Lower magnifications confirmed the integrity of macro networks derived from sawdust precursors. The uniformity and porosity visible across SEM scans suggest high potential for pollutant adsorption, composite reinforcement, and energy electrode integration.

Figure 2(a), Reveals microstructural features like surface texture, cracks, and particle shapes at low voltage which enhances surface sensitivity and minimizes sample damage. Figure 2(b), is in agreement with the revealed features in Figure 2(a), which further confirms the macro-scale surface features like fiber networks, pores, and large particles. All the results were observed at high vacuum to ensure minimal scattering and high-resolution imaging for conductive samples.

Figure 2(c), shows macro-scale features like fiber networks, large pores, and surface irregularities. Both Figures 2(d) and 2(e) respectively revealed the features of surface morphology in the hundreds of microns range.

The morphological structure revealed from the SEM images of the GO shows wrinkled, crumpled sheets or layered structures, porous, sponge-like networks with interlinked nanosheets, and these features are consistent with oxidized graphite exfoliated into GO layers.

Applications of GO from Sawdust Waste

Using agricultural waste derived GO is not just ecofriendly, rather it is incredibly versatile material. GO can be used in many applications as summarized in Table 1. Also presented in figure 3.

Table 1: Summary of GO Applications

Field	Application
Environmental Remediation	Adsorption of heavy metals like cadmium (Cd^{2+}), lead (Pb^{2+}), and copper (Cu^{2+}) from waste water
Energy Storage	Used in super capacitors and battery electrodes due to high surface area and conductivity
Sensors	Functionalized GO can detect gases, biomolecules, or pollutants with high sensitivity
Composites	Reinforcement in polymers for lightweight, strong materials in aerospace

	and automotive
Biomedical	Potential use in drug delivery and antibacterial coatings (pending biocompatibility studies)

The nature of GO which has a high surface area and is rich in oxygen functional groups has been utilized in the manufacture of lithium sulfur battery cathodes and supercapacitor (Uzhviyuket *et al.*, 2023; Ramli&Hidayat, 2022; Zhang *et al.*, 2010). The varied oxidation degree or absorbing molecules which affect the electrical behavior of GO allows it to be applied as electrical sensor (Ramli&Hidayat, 2022).

Figure 3: GO Synthesized from Sawdust Waste and its Potential Applications in Environmental Remediation, Agriculture, Energy Storage, drugs Delivery, and Composite Materials

Several advantages associated with the applications of GO have been reported including applications in electronics, environmental and biomedical sectors (Singh *et al.*, 2023). The success associated with the broad application of GO is linked to its properties such as planar shape, high aspect ratio, good optical properties, electrical conductivity, mechanical and thermal stability (Affraid, 2023; Baragañoet *al.*, 2020; Rhazouaniet *al.*, 2021).

Comparative Overview of SEM Parameters and Outcomes

The comparative summary of SEM parameters observed from the images are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Comparative Overview of Images Observed from SEM

SEM Parameters	×100 (500 μm)	×150 (500 μm)	×250 (300 μm)	×500 (100 μm)	×1000 (50 μm)
Magnification	Very Low	Low	Low	Medium	Medium-High
Resolution	Macro	Macro	Macro	Micro	Micro
Field of View	Very broad	Broad	Broad	Moderate	Narrow
Clarity	Pores, cracks, fiber bundles	Pores, cracks, fiber networks	Fiber agglomerates, large particles	Grain boundaries, voids	Fine cracks, particles
Charging Sensitivity	High (non-conductive risks)	Moderate	Moderate	Lower	Lower
Best for Observing	Large-scale morphology	Surface roughness & agglomerate	Structural layering & pores	Microstructure texture	Fine topography & coatings
Potential Applications	Agriculture, biochar, pollutant adsorption	Composite coatings, carbon fertilizers	Ceramics, biomedical scaffolds	Supercapacitor electrodes, sensors	Biomedical nanomaterials, wear resistance studies

Conclusion

The successful synthesis of GO from sawdust using a Modified Hummers Method was confirmed through detailed SEM characterization. The observed morphological features such as wrinkled sheets, porous networks, and agglomerated particles are consistent with established GO profiles, indicating effective oxidation and exfoliation of the biomass precursor. The use of high-vacuum conditions, low accelerating voltage (5.0 kV), and an Everhart–Thornley Detector enabled high-contrast, surface-sensitive imaging, ensuring accurate morphological assessment. This study demonstrates that sawdust, an abundant agricultural byproduct, can be effectively converted into high-quality GO via an environmentally friendly synthesis route. The approach not only addresses waste management challenges but also offers a sustainable pathway for producing GO suitable for diverse applications in environmental remediation, energy storage, and advanced material systems. These findings significantly affirm the potential of biomass-derived GO as a viable alternative to conventionally produced nanomaterials in green nanotechnology.

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Empirical Determination of Jet Impingement Cooling Rate of Steel Using Temperature-Time Profile for Automatic Transmission Fluid (ATF)

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Abstract

A stationary rectangular hot steel plate, for a top surface single jet automatic transmission fluid accelerated controlled cooling process, was studied empirically and analyzed with lumped thermal mass. The assessment was with pipe diameters ranging from 10mm to 40mm, impingement gaps ranging from 115mm to 155mm, initial surface temperatures ranging from 450 °C to 410°C and at sub-cooled temperatures ranging from 150 °C to 110°C. Upon analysis, it shows cooling rate increases with the pipe diameter D decreasing and corresponds also to the impingement gaps H decreasing. Upon analysis, the results inferred that jet diameter increases with a decrease in cooling rate and an increase in impingement gaps. At the lowest diameter D 10mm, the highest heat removal rate was at an impingement gap of 115mm with $-1.11^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{s}$, and at the highest diameter D 40mm, the heat removal rate was highest at 145mm with $-1.09^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{s}$, which is the highest transfer rate in the entire study. The Leidenfrost phenomenon decreased here because of the higher heat removal at a lower impingement gap, which increases in water at a lower impingement gap. With this result, a new microstructure of a medium carbon steel is possible for designers' application to numerous engineering problems.

Keywords: Cooling rate, Temperature-Time profile, lumped thermal-mass analysis, Modified ROT, Automatic Transmission Fluid

Introduction

Impingement jet cooling has several processes, configurations, and fluids. Each of these gives steel depending on other variables: impingement gaps, pipe diameter, fluid velocity, etc, a different micro-structure when used for cooling. Any time cooling is mentioned, water as the fluid to be used is immediately thought of. However, recent events have shown that there is a drift from water to other fluids like palm kernel, extracted tiger-nut-juice oil, mist, etc. Because there is a growing need for cost reduction in steel production with improvement in its function for better application, there is composite formation in steel which gives better micro-structure of steel by dropping some alloying element and introduction of newer streamline processes: the thermo-mechanical control process (TMCP) has become increasingly important, as discoursed by [1][2][3].

Steel is a no do material in engineering application under very many circumstances; this requires steel to have many properties to withstand these numerous engineering applications. As revealed by, as revealed by [4] [5]. At various point in time of engineers designing one project or the other, this engineering material – steel is subjected to many postures: bending, twisting, in hot environment or cold, even as tooling material that will cut others etc., they with stand shock and tresses at various other times, to be able to service these conditions they are specific property or properties they must possess to serve well the designers purpose in

each application, as agreed by [6] [7]. Prior to this age, steel lacking these property specifics are upgraded through heat treatment process – this not cost effective. Hence there is need for better process of property upgrade that provides for heating and control cooling, as suggested and agreed by [8] [1] respectively. Medium carbon steel plates with known varying chemical compositions and mechanical properties were obtained from Ajaokuta Nigerian Steel Company as shown in Table 1

Table 1: Mechanical Properties of the sampled steel

Grade of Steel (%C)	UTS (MPa)	Brinell Hardness BHN	Impact of Strength (J)
0.56	957.1	252.98	34.11

The runout table ROT designed and discussed by [9] [10]. This was for top surface stationary configuration only, and its discussion was done using mechanistic modeling of pool boiling – time consuming and weighty to analyze, however, the need to save time and cost and better result – lumped thermal mass (LTMA) was employed for this study of determination of cooling rate of automatic transmission fluid (ATF). The process of heat treatment had over the years used water as impingement fluid, but with the use of thermo-mechanical controlled process – accelerated controlled cooling for the emergence of many more fluids as impingement fluid is made possible, discussed by [11]. In furtherance to the new jet impingement fluids, [7] introduced new cooling fluid – automatic transmission fluid. Hence the need for this study to determine its cooling rate of automatic transmission fluid (ATF) under rotating liquid jet impingement for its performance using numerical simulation. The target is a cylindrical ring, which contains curved target surfaces. They showed the effect of pipe rotation on heat transfer performance and compared existing literature regarding jet impingement cooling systems.

[12] Studied the cooling system of boiling heat transfer on a hot steel plate cooled by an inclined circular bottom surface using water. They focused on the inclined angle at the bottom of the steel hot plate, and the flow rate effect on heat extraction. He varied the flow rate, ROT speed, and inclined angles from 35 -55l/min, 0 -1 m/s, and 10-30oC respectively. With these variables, he employed the inverse heat conduction model and his measurements and calculated the boiling curve or heat fluxes as a function of plate surface temperature. Though cumbersome to analysis hence the use of lumped thermal analysis for the study.

[13] noted that accelerated controlled cooling is superior to other methods of improving steel properties, because it removes more heat and faster. Again, using new fluid other water, he introduced mist jet on rewetting of a horizontal downward facing hot surface. This is mainly applicable in electronic industry and steel. This fluid offers an alternative method to uncontrolled rapid cooling. The scattering of water dewdrops into an airflow can be categorized as either spray cooling or mist jet cooling. In spray cooling, compressed water is atomized by pressure at the nozzle, while in mist cooling, dewdrops are atomized by compressed air. Mist jets consequently permit smaller dewdrops.

Figure 1: Schematic of free surface impingement for a Single Jet Profile,[14]

While analyzing the pool boiling mechanism, in their air jet impingement cooling process of food industry, they acknowledged that convective heat transfer coefficient be subject to on many impingement parameters like - nozzle design, the geometry of the object being cooled, jet exit to object distance, the velocity of the air jet, and jet confinement by [15] [16] . Furthermore, they affirmed that the effects of the parameter can be studied in steady and unsteady state. Numerical model solution solved using CFD and authenticated by experiments (using PIV) to optimize these parameters. Heat transfer maximum found at H/D of 3. They concluded that data from their work can be used to design and optimize an impingement system for a given set of conditions.

Hence, used to determine the power requirement [5] [17] .experimented with quenching stainless steel using a single jet oil impingement cooling process on the bottom surface of the plate. They heated the sample specimen from 100oC to 900oC and their objective was to know the effect of oil as an impingement fluid on the bottom surface. Their changeable parameters were 113 to 381 ml/min, oil pressure 3.1 to 12 psi, and impingement height of 0.6 to 1 cm. Test results also display that oil heat transfer coefficient and heat flux keep increasing as plate temperature increases.

Having review all these literatures, water, before now has been the main stay for cooling of steel. However, recently, other fluids as mentioned in the literature are been used as impingement fluid. There is an effect water creates as an impingement fluid that slows down the cooling rate at the beginning of the cooling process which has affect the overall cooling rate – Leidenfrost phenomenon studied by [4] [18] ,hence the need for another fluid with varying physical property from water. Analytically, pool boiling has been dominant in jet impingement cooling, this has been so bulky and engineers find it difficult to use studied by [19] [20] . Therefore, the introduction of lumped thermal mass in this present study for the determination of the cooling rate of automatic transmission fluid. We expect ATF to show a faster cooling rate at the initial stage of the process- at the stagnation point.

Methodology

Fig. 2 below reveals the modified runout table used for the empirical run of the study. A schematic of the pilot scale of the industrial runout table. The modified is capable of having an empirical run for both top and bottom surface process simultaneously. This is installed at Enugu state university of science and technology ESUT, Mechanical and production Engineering department laboratory

Figure 2: Schematics of the Modified ROT set-up plant

1. Water tank, 2. Electric pump, 3.Heater, 4. Thermocouple wires, 5.The workpiece and its carrier, 6.Thermocouple control panel, Workpiece bed, 7. Bottom Impingement nozzle, 8. Motorized screw conveyor, 9. Furnace, 10. Electric motor, 11. Flow valve, 12. Flow meter, 13. Ladder, 14. Furnace support, 15. PVC Pipes, 16. Pressure gauge

The plant houses the blend of numerous parts abovementioned. The experiment features the cooling system – a closed loop where 1.6m³, volume of used water circulated throughout the system. Pipe diameter, Preliminary temperature, water temperature, impingement gap, and flow rate etc. were varied and controlled. The sample hot plate was placed under the headers after the system had stabilized. Average value of the attached four thermocouples wastaken after reading it out using the mounted control panel for the temperature. Already obtained 30litersof automatic transmission fluid from Coal camp automobile spare shop in Enugu Nigeria, and was used as automatic transmission fluid jet impingement cooling for the experiment.

Intensity of cooling employed in TMCP affects the microstructural evolution process such as austenite decomposition and precipitation [21], unlike cooling paths of the steel on ROT lead to different phase transformation such as ferrite, pearlite, bainite, and/or martensite as shown in Fig. 3. In order to proficiently apply novel cooling technologies to achieve desired microstructures as well as proper flatness, it is crucial to develop accurate heat transfer models to predict the temperature profiles through cooling of steel, in plate mills, controlled cooling is classified as ACC (Accelerated controlled cooling), [22].

Fig. 3: Run-out Table temperature-time and phase transformation of austenite decomposition. A: austenite, F: ferrite, P: pearlite B: bainite, M: martensite. [21]

Table 2: Properties of Sampled Fluid [23]

Fluids	Density (kg/m ³)	Viscosity (kg/M-S)	Thermal Conduct W/MK	Specific Heat J/KGK	Temp.°C
ATF-JIC	792	3.92x10 ⁻¹	0.135	2237	50 - 60

Experimental Design

The experimental design was done using (eq. 1) as:

$$n_i \times m_i = E_T \tag{1}$$

Where n_i is number of experiments per fluid and m_i is number of processes and E_T is total experiments. Since the degree of freedom is 10, subsequent upon 1 fluid, 10 experiments were done as shown on the Table 3 Experimental matrix formation.

Where H= impingement gap, D=diameter of nozzle, V=velocity of nozzle, t = time, Q=flow rate, T_i = initial temperature and T_f = final temperature

Table 3: Experimental Matrix Formation

S/N	D (mm)	H (mm)	V (m/s)	t _s (sec)	Q (m ³ /s)	T _i (°C)	T _f (°C)
1	D1	H1	V1	t 1	Q1	Ti 1	Tf 1
2	D2	H2	V2	t 2	Q2	Ti 2	Tf 2
3	D3	H3	V3	t 3	Q3	Ti 3	Tf 3
4	D4	H4	V4	t 4	Q4	Ti 4	Tf 4
5	D5	H5	V5	t 5	Q5	Ti 5	Tf 5

The principle of lumped thermal mass analysis for heat transfer coefficient h is that inside temperature of a body is maintained constant during the process of heat transfer. This constant temperature is a function of time,

$$T = T(t) \tag{2}$$

With this statement, there is no temperature gradient – plainly means that the conduction – inside resistance of the body is negligible when compared with the external resistance convection of the body. When a conducting solid (mass) or a well-blended fluid is subjected to heating or cooling by contact to an environment with which it exchanges heat. It is assumed that the temperature change with the well-blended fluid or mass can be neglected when compared with the temperature change of well-mixed or mass and the surrounding fluid by[24].

Lumped thermal mass model is presented in figure 3 which simplifies the complicated modeling process of impingement cooling involving conduction and convection. The following assumptions were made on this model

- (i) Heat transferred from the hot steel plate is seen as a lumped mass.
- (ii) The mass resistance to the heat transfer is negligible when compared with the resistant from impinging fluid.
- (iii) The volume of the mass remains unaffected.

Below is the model of the 2-D surface cooling heat transfer deals with a thickness of 12mm and a length of 230mm with a width of 120mm.

Figure 4: Control volume of lumped thermal mass model Analysis of impingement process

Experimental Model

By the lumped mass method based on control volume of the steel plate, Fig.4, mass behaves as a single lump of temperature, T. Thus, equating conduction heat transfer at the bottom to that conducted at the top by convection, since boiling heat is infinitesimal and was collapsed into convection, in equation (3) as;

$$MC \frac{d}{dt}(T_S - T_\infty) = -hA(T_S - T_\infty) \tag{3}$$

$$\frac{\partial(T_S - T_\infty)}{(T_S - T_\infty)} = \frac{-hAdt}{mcp} \tag{4}$$

Using integration for the above equations, we have

$$\int_{t=0}^t \frac{d(T - T_\infty)}{T - T_\infty} = \text{Log}_e \left(\frac{T - T_\infty}{T_S - T_\infty} \right) t = 0, = \frac{-hAt}{mcp} \tag{5}$$

$$\text{Thus, } \text{Log}_\theta = \frac{-hAt}{mcp} \tag{6}$$

The gradient is given as in equation 7, as,

$$\text{gradient is } -\alpha = \frac{-hAt}{mcp} \tag{7}$$

$$\text{From which, } h = \alpha \rho wcp \tag{8}$$

Where:

h is convective heat transfer coefficient (**W/m²k**); **t** is the time in seconds, (**s**)

T is the initial temperature, (**°C**); **m** is the mass of the sample in (**kg**)

A is the area of the specimen in (**m²**); **T_s** is the surface temperature (**°C**)

T_∞ is the infinite temperature. (**°C**)

for steel, density $\rho=7900\text{kg/m}^3$, specific heat $C_p=500\text{J/kgk}$; sampled thickness $w=0.012\text{m}$, α , is a gradient from equation (7) studied by [25]

Validity of Model

From our initial assumptions in the lumped thermal mass model, we assumed that temperature variation within mass is very small as compared to the surroundings. This variation can be neglected and assuming whole mass to a single lump of temperature. This will be correct when

$$\frac{\text{internal resistance}}{\text{external resistance}} \ll 1 \tag{9}$$

Where internal resistance is $\frac{L}{K_s A}$ (10)

Where: L is length of path of heat conduction within the mass, K_s is thermal conductivity of solid and A is area.

The external resistance is $\frac{1}{hA}$ (11)

Where: equ. 11 is the convective resistance.

Therefore, validity of the model lies within the equation below

$$\frac{\frac{L}{KA}}{\frac{1}{hA}} \ll 1 \tag{12}$$

$$\frac{hL}{Ks} \ll 1 \tag{13}$$

Equation 13 is dimensionless number called Biot number, validates the lumped thermal mass model.

Cooling Rate

To find the average cooling rate in degrees per second, using the basic formular for rate of change. We solved for each constant pipe diameter D for five different impingement gaps H. using the formular in equation 14 ass stated above.

$$\text{cooling rate} = \frac{\Delta T}{\Delta t} = \frac{T_{final} - T_{initial}}{t_{final} - t_{initial}} \tag{14}$$

There will be a minus sign in the result, which shows that the temperature is decreasing.

Results and Discussion

The results below are the experimental values of constant pipe diameters D with variant impingement gaps H with corresponding initial surface temperatures T_s control cooled at constant sub cooled temperatures T_{sub}.

Table 4, shows the initial surface temperature T_s of 450°C, 440°C, 430°C, 420°C, and 410°C on sampled steel and the time t(s), variant impingement gaps H of 115mm, 125mm, 135mm, 145mm, and 155mm at constant pipe diameter D=10mm. Controlled sub-cooled temperature T_{sub} of 150°C

Table 4: 150°C @D=10mm Variant T and H for ATF-JIC Top Surface

T=450 @D=10mm(H=115)		T=440 @D=10mm(H=125)		T=430 @D=10mm(H=135)		T=420 @D=10mm(H=145)		T=410 @D=10mm(H=155)	
T(s)	Ts	T(s)	Ts	T(s)	Ts	T(s)	Ts	T(s)	Ts
0	450	0	440	0	430	0	420	0	410
45	400	42	391.67	41.5	383.34	40	375	37.09	366.67
90	350	84	343.34	83	336.68	80	330	74.18	323.34
135	300	126	295.01	124.5	290.02	120	285	111.27	280.01
180	250	168	246.68	166	243.36	160	240	148.36	236.68
225	200	210	198.35	207.5	196.7	200	195	185.45	193.35
270	150	252	150	249	150	240	150	222.54	150

Figure 5: Temperature-Time @150°C D=10mm for ATF-JIC with Variant T and H (T)

Fig. 5, represents the temperature-time controlled cooling profile for diameter 10mm with wide-ranging impingement gaps H of 115mm, 125mm, 135mm, 145mm, and 155mm. From the straightness of the plot, the cooling rate was highest at opening top surface that has the highest temperature, followed by the middle and down to the bottom surface. This pattern of straight-line graph from top to bottom was maintained in all the plots.

The plot is for the diameter D=10mm and the same controlled sub-cooled temperature T_{sub} of 150°C, but with wide-ranging impingement gap H of 115mm, 125mm, 135mm, 14mm, and 155mm. At diameter 10m it revealed that heat is removed at the rate of -1.11°C/s with impingement gap of 115mm, and at 155mm impingement gap -1.16°C/s of heat is removed for second.

Therefore, for a smaller impingement jet diameter a lower impingement gap is recommended for cooling of steel with automatic transmission fluid. This result is still in the range for water as studied by [26] [27]. Table 5, shows the initial surface temperature T_s of 450°C, 440°C, 430°C, 420°C, and 410°C on sampled steel and the time t(s), variant impingement gaps H of 115mm, 125mm, 135mm, 145mm, and 155mm at constant pipe diameter D=15mm. Controlled sub-cooled temperature T_{sub} of 140°C.

Table 5: 140°C @D=15mm Variant T and H for ATF-JIC Top Surface

T=450 @D=15mm(H=115)		T=440 @D=15mm(H=125)		T=430 @D=15mm(H=135)		T=420 @D=15mm(H=145)		T=410 @D=15mm(H=155)	
T(s)	Ts	T(s)	Ts	T(s)	Ts	T(s)	Ts	T(s)	Ts
0	450	0	440	0	430	0	420	0	410
46	398.34	44	390	42	381.67	40.3	373.34	37.09	365
92	346.68	88	340	84	333.34	80.6	326.68	74.18	320
138	295.02	132	290	126	285.01	120.9	280.02	111.27	275
184	243.36	176	240	168	236.68	161.2	233.36	148.36	230
230	191.7	220	190	210	188.35	201.5	186.7	185.45	185
276	140	264	140	252	140	241.8	140	222.54	140

Figure 6: Temperature-Time @140°C D=15mm for ATF-JIC with Variant T and H Top

Fig. 6: Denotes the temperature-time controlled cooling profile for diameter 15mm with the same wide-ranging impingement gaps H of 115mm, 125mm, 135mm, 145mm, and 155mm. From the straightness of the plot, the cooling rate was highest at opening top surface that has the highest temperature, followed by the middle and down to the bottom surface.

In the same pattern jet impingement diameter 15mm shows that heat is dissipated from the surface of the hot steel plate at the rate of -1.12°C/s for impingement gap of 115mm and -1.21°C/s for impingement gap of 155mm. Consequent upon this, is that higher heat removal is achieved with lower impingement gap at diameter 15mm.

Table 6, shows the initial surface temperature Ts of 450°C, 440°C, 430°C, 420°C, and 410°C on sampled steel and the time t(s), variant impingement gaps H of 115mm, 125mm, 135mm, 145mm, and 155mm at constant pipe diameter D=30mm. Controlled sub-cooled temperature Tsub of 130°C.

Table 6: 130°C @D=30mm Variant T and H for ATF-JIC Top surface

T=450 @D=30mm(H=115)		T=440 @D=30mm(H=125)		T=430 @D=30mm(H=135)		T=420 @D=30mm(H=145)		T=410 @D=30mm(H=155)	
T(s)	Ts	T(s)	Ts	T(s)	Ts	T(s)	Ts	T(s)	Ts
0	450	0	440	0	430	0	420	0	410
47	396.67	44.77	388.34	42	380	41.5	371.67	40.3	363.34
94	343.34	89.54	336.68	84	330	83	323.34	80.6	316.68

141	290.01	134.42	285.02	126	280	124.5	275.01	120.9	270.02
188	236.68	179.19	233.36	168	230	166	226.68	161.2	223.36
235	183.35	223.96	181.7	210	180	207.5	178.35	201.5	176.7
282	130	268.73	130	252	130	249	130	241.8	130

Figure 7: Temperature-Time @130°C D=30mm for ATF-JIC with Variant T and H Top

Fig. 7: Designates the temperature-time controlled cooling profile for diameter 30mm with the same inclusive impingement gaps H of 115mm, 125mm, 135mm, 145mm, and 155mm. the plot shows that the cooling rate was highest at opening top surface that has the highest temperature, followed by the middle and down to the bottom surface.

The heat removal rate in seconds for impingement diameter 30mm revealed that -1.14°C/s is removed from the hot surface of the medium carbon steel sample. For impingement gap of 115mm. Meanwhile, at impingement gap of 155mm heat of further removed at -1.16°C/s . Again, it further strengthens the earlier result – that at smaller diameter lower impingement gap is recommended for cooling of steel. This agrees to the studies of [28], and [17]

Table 7, shows the initial surface temperature T_s of 450°C , 440°C , 430°C , 420°C , and 410°C on sampled steel and the time $t(s)$, variant impingement gaps H of 115mm, 125mm, 135mm, 145mm, and 155mm at constant pipe diameter $D=35\text{mm}$. Controlled sub-cooled temperature T_{sub} of 120°C .

Table 7: 120°C @ $D=35\text{mm}$ Variant T and H for ATF-JIC Top surface

T=450 @D=35mm(H=115)		T=440 @D=35mm(H=125)		T=430 @D=35mm(H=135)		T=420 @D=35mm(H=145)		T=410 @D=35mm(H=155)	
T(s)	Ts	T(s)	Ts	T(s)	Ts	T(s)	Ts	T(s)	Ts
0	450	0	440	0	430	0	420	0	410
49	395	47	386.67	44.63	378.34	42.67	370	41.5	361.67
98	340	94	333.34	89.26	326.68	85.34	320	83	313.34
147	285	141	280.01	133.89	275.02	128.01	270	124.5	265.01
196	230	188	226.68	178.52	223.36	170.68	220	166	216.68
245	175	235	173.35	223.15	171.7	213.35	170	207.5	168.35
294	120	282	120	267.78	120	256.02	120	249	120

Figure 8: Temperature-Time @120°C D=35mm for ATF-JIC with Variant T and H Top surface

Fig. 8: Represents the temperature-time controlled cooling profile for diameter 35mm with the same wide-ranging impingement gaps H of 115mm, 125mm, 135mm, 145mm, and 155mm. From the straightness of the plot, the cooling rate was highest at opening top surface that has the highest temperature, followed by the middle and down to the bottom surface.

From the plot and use of equation 14 the rate of cooling at diameter 35mm for automatic transmission fluid also shows that highest heat removal from a hot surface of steel is achieved better with lower impingement gap. At impingement gap H of 115mm heat is removed at the rate of -1.12°C/s and for 155mm it is removed at -1.17°C/s. Therefore, when using ATF as impinging fluid for steel cooling it is recommended to use lower impingement gap.[28]

Table 8, shows the initial surface temperature T_s of 450°C, 440°C, 430°C, 420°C, and 410°C on sampled steel and the time $t(s)$, variant impingement gaps H of 115mm, 125mm, 135mm, 145mm, and 155mm at constant pipe diameter $D=40mm$. Controlled sub-cooled temperature T_{sub} of 110°C

Table 8: 110°C @D=40mm Variant T and H for ATF-JIC Top surface

T=450 @D=40mm(H=115)		T=440 @D=40mm(H=125)		T=430 @D=40mm(H=135)		T=420 @D=40mm(H=145)		T=410 @D=40mm(H=155)	
T(s)	Ts	T(s)	Ts	T(s)	Ts	T(s)	Ts	T(s)	Ts
0	450	0	440	0	430	0	420	0	410
51	393.34	50	385	48	376.67	47	368.34	44.63	360
102	336.68	100	330	96	323.34	94	316.68	89.26	310
153	280.02	150	275	144	270.01	141	265.02	133.89	260
204	223.36	200	220	192	216.68	188	213.36	178.52	210
255	166.7	250	165	240	163.35	235	161.7	223.15	160
306	110	300	110	288	110	282	110	267.78	110

Figure 9: Temperature-Time @110°C D=40mm for ATF-JIC with Variant T and H Top surface

Fig. 9: Represents the temperature-time controlled cooling profile for diameter 40mm with the same wide-ranging impingement gaps H of 115mm, 125mm, 135mm, 145mm, and 155mm. The plot followed the same temperature-time pattern of straightness decreasing from the top to the bottom.

Just like the rest of the diameters, diameter 40mm showed the same pattern of having the lower impingement gap removing heat faster than the higher gaps. For impingement gap 115mm of diameter 40mm heat removed at the rate of -1.11°C/s and for the 155mm gap heat is dissipated at the rate of -1.12°C/s . It further confirmed that lower impingement gap gives better heat transfer from a hot surface of a steel.[28]

Generally, the result showed that with smaller jet diameters D lower impingement gap H is recommended and with bigger jet diameters D higher impingement gap H is recommended for heat transfer from a steel surface. At lowest diameter D 10mm the highest heat removal rate was at impingement gap 115mm with -1.11°C/s and at the highest diameter D 40mm the heat removal rate was highest at 145mm with -1.09°C/s , which is the highest transfer rate in the entire study.

Conclusions

The study of temperature-time profile of automatic transmission fluid as a jet impingement fluid to obtain its cooling rate at various jet diameters and impingement gaps, using an empirical analytical model – lumped thermal mass analysis model in place of pool boiling mechanism analysis of heat transfer, was completed in a modified runout table capable of simultaneously handling top and bottom surface impingement process. Variant jet diameters of 10mm, 15mm, 30mm, 35mm and 40mm, and impingement gaps of 115mm, 125mm, 135mm, 145mm, and 155mm, on rectangular steel plate with surface temperatures of 450°C/s , 440°C/s , 430°C/s , 420°C/s , and 410°C/s which was sub cooled to temperatures of 150°C/s , 140°C/s , 130°C/s , 120°C/s , and 110°C/s respectively

Upon, analysis with lumped thermal model, the plot of the temperature-time maintained the same pattern with that of water as shown in their works [28]

[29][30]

Generally, the result showed that with smaller jet diameters D lower impingement gap H is recommended and with bigger jet diameters D higher impingement gap H is recommended for heat transfer from a steel surface. At lowest diameter D 10mm the highest heat removal rate was at impingement gap 115mm with -1.11°C/s and at the highest diameter D 40mm the

heat removal rate was highest at 145mm with -1.09°C/s , which is the highest transfer rate in the entire study.

These results confirm that Automatic transmission fluid (ATF) can be used in place of water and the Leidenfrost phenomenon is far reduced.

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Development of a Low Cost Waste Tyre Pyrolysis Oil Reactor: a Sustainable Approach to Energy and Waste Management

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Abstract

The global accumulation of waste tyres poses significant environmental challenges, necessitating innovative waste-to-energy conversion approaches. This study focuses on the design, fabrication, and experimental evaluation of a pyrolysis plant developed to convert waste tyres into valuable oil suitable for use as an energy sources. The system was engineered with optimized reactor geometry, heating rate, and condensation unit to enhance process efficiency and energy recovery. Operating at 240 V and 650 °C, the plant processed 30 kg of waste tyre material per batch, requiring 42MJ of heat over a 5.83 hour duration. The waste tyre feedstock exhibited high volatile matter of 68.24 %, ash content of 2.87% and a calorific value of 36.82MJ/kg indicating superior combustibility and energy potential. Ultimate analysis showed high carbon of 83% and moderate oxygen of 4% with minimal sulphur of 1.54% signifying reduced emission potential. Physicochemical evaluations of the oil confirmed density of 840 kg/m³, viscosity of 3.95 mPa·s, and flash point of 28.7 °C values comparable to diesel fuels. GC–MS analysis results revealed significant quantities of valuable light hydrocarbon such as benzene, toluene, xylene and limonene. Some proportions of polycyclic aromatics such as fluorenes and naphthalene derivatives were also identified. These findings demonstrate that pyrolyzed tyre oil possesses esirable thermal, chemical, and combustion characteristics suitable for automotive fuel blending or as feedstock for chemical production. In the short term, this research provides a sustainable route for tyre waste valorization and localized bioenergy production. In the long term, its adoption could significantly reduce fossil fuel dependency, minimize landfill pollution, and support a circular economy within the automotive and environmental sectors.

Keywords: Alternative Fuels; Pyrolysis Oil; Sustainable Energy; Thermochemical Conversion; Waste Tyre Recycling.

Introduction

The global energy crisis, rising environmental concerns, and the rapid accumulation of wastes such as end-of-life tires have intensified the search for sustainable waste-to-energy technologies. Each year, millions of tons of used tires are discarded requiring waste management, treatment and disposal (Zerin et al. 2025, Gao et al. 2022). Conventional methods for the disposal of waste tires include landfilling, stockpiling, material and energy recovery. Waste tires are not degradable in landfills and when stockpiled the accumulation of water in the tires provide an ideal breeding ground for mosquitoes and vermin. Also, landfill dumping of tires is a potential danger because of the possibility of accidental fires with high emission of toxic compounds which contaminate soil, groundwater and air (Kieran 2023 and Han et al. 2023). According to Rusmi and Atiqah (2020), it is estimated that waste tires in landfills can survive between 80 to 100 years without any noticeable degradation. This is due to the tire properties that are designed to withstand harsh weather conditions such as exposure

to ozone, light and bacteria. Material recovery options for waste tires include recycling through the production of rubber particles for use as rubberized flooring in sport fields, playgrounds, under road surface filling and asphalt modification (Canon et al. 2018, Oboirien and North 2017). The combustion of tyres to provide energy in cement kilns is an important route for the disposal of waste tyres. However, due to the emission of mutagenic and carcinogenic chemicals such as polyaromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), NO_x, SO_x and heavy metals, expensive gas cleaning systems have to be installed to perform this process in an environmentally responsible fashion (Cheng et al. 2021, Alkhatib 2015, Quek et al. 2012)

On the other hand, the emissions of greenhouse gases from the combustion of fossil fuels have been identified as the major causes of climate change and global warming. The numerous and varied effects of climate change on the environment, human life and the economy are becoming obvious. Global warming is the increase in the average temperature of the earth surface as a result of emission of heat by greenhouse gases such as carbon dioxide, methane and nitrogen oxide. This increase in global temperature has caused changes in the global climate patterns described as climate change (Offoh, 2009; Lu et al. 2007). Both the U.S Energy Departmental report of 2008 and the 2007 report of the intergovernmental panel on climate change associated global warming with rise in sea level, flooding and changes in rainfall pattern. On human health, global warming has been linked with increase in cardiovascular diseases, asthma and other lung diseases (McMichael et al. 2003). These growing challenges underscores the urgent need for innovative conversion pathways that not only mitigate tire pollution but also generate alternative energy sources to reduce overdependence on fossil resources. Pyrolysis technology has emerged as an innovative approach for addressing critical global issues such as waste management, renewable energy generation and environmental conservation (Dusso et al. 2022 and Anand et al. 2023). Unlike combustion or gasification, pyrolysis offers the dual benefits of energy recovery and material recycling aligning with the principles of circular economy and sustainable development (Wang et al. 2024, Rasul et al. 2024 and Pahnla et al. 2023). The disposal challenges, environmental and human health hazard poised by used tires is shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Waste tyres

Materials and Method

Materials

- (a) Software Tools for Conceptual Design of the Pyrolysis plant
- (b) Carbon Steel Materials for the fabrication of the plant
- (c) Pyrolysis Reactor for the conversion of waste tyres into oil
- (d) Nitrogen gas to purge the system of oxidative gases
- (e) Waste tyres for the preparation of feedstocks

- (f) Drying oven for the removal of moisture from feedstock
- (g) Crucible to weigh and hold samples for ash content analysis
- (h) Analytical balance to measure sample before and after pyrolysis.
- (i) Elemental analyzer for the determination of the elemental composition of the feedstock.

Methods

Design Concepts

The design of the pyrolysis reactor was guided by the following;

Design Considerations

- (a) Material availability.
- (b) Functional requirement.
- (c) Fabrication simplicity.
- (d) Cost effectiveness.

System Components

Figure 2 is a schematic model of the developed pyrolysis plant with the main components identified with numbers:

Figure 2: Schematic Model of a Developed Pyrolysis Plant

1. Nitrogen Cylinder

Nitrogen cylinder supplies an inert gas to purge the reactor of oxidative gases.

2. Furnace

The furnace houses both the reactor and the electrical heater. It was insulated with bricks to shield the environment from high heat.

3. Reactor

The reactor is the vessel where the tyre chips are decomposed. It was designed to optimize heat transfer, product recovery and to operate within a temperature range of 300-650°C under inert nitrogen atmosphere. The charging system incorporated a 12cm diameter cap which can be opened for efficient feedstock loading and char removal at the end of the experiment. The exit pipe at the side carries away the evolved gases during pyrolysis. The temperature inside the reactor is measured by a thermocouple.

4. Vapour Exit Pipe

The exit pipe carries gaseous products from the reactor to the condenser where they are condensed into oil.

5. Controller

This is a digital instrument that regulates and controls the process temperature and heating rate to ensure safe and efficient thermal decomposition of the waste tyre. The controller supplies electrical energy to the furnace and ensures that the temperature in the reactor does not exceed the set temperature. The controller measures the temperature inside the reactor through a sensor which is in contact with the electrical heater. It was set at 650°C for the purpose of this experiment.

6. Condenser

This is the heat exchanger where condensation occurs. The hot vapors from the reactor pass through the tube and are condensed with the aid of circulation of cold water surrounding the tube. The condenser was designed to maximize cooling efficiency and ensure rapid condensation of vapors at the controlled condenser temperature of 4°C. To facilitate smooth operation, the oil outlet pipe was specified at 3.5cm while the vapor inlet was 6.35cm allowing adequate vapor flow without blockage.

7. Oil Collector

The Oil collector is the reservoir for the condensed liquid products.

8. Support

The support provides structural integrity to the entire system

Experimentation

Feedstock Material Sourcing

The waste tyres used as feedstock for this study were sourced from an automobile mechanic workshop. The collected tyres were representative of commonly used passenger car tyre composed primarily of natural rubber, synthetic rubber, carbon black, steel wire and textile reinforcements (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Image of the Workshop where the waste tyres were collected

Feedstock Preparation

The sourced waste tyres were manually cut into smaller fragments using a mechanical cutting tool to facilitate easy handling and uniform thermal decomposition within the pyrolysis reactor. The sidewall of the tyre was sectioned into pieces of approximately 3-5cm as smaller particle sizes has been shown to improve heat penetration and enhance the efficiency of pyrolysis reaction. To eliminate contaminants that might influence the yield or purity of the products, the tyre fragments were subjected to a pre-cleaning process involving high-pressure water rinsing followed by oven drying at 105°C for 2 hours to remove surface moisture and volatile residues.

Figure 4: Collected Waste Tyres Cut into Pieces using Knife

Characterization of Feedstock

The Proximate and ultimate test methods were used to examine the suitability of the feedstock for pyrolysis. Following ASTM standards, important parameters such as volatile matter, moisture, fixed carbon and ash contents were determined. Ultimate analysis in terms of carbon, hydrogen and sulfur (CHNOS) were also determined.

Pyrolysis Procedure

The pyrolysis process was carried out in a laboratory-scale batch-type pyrolysis reactor designed and developed as shown in figure 2. The pre-processed tyre feedstock was loaded into the reactor chamber and sealed tightly to prevent the ingress of atmospheric air. Nitrogen gas was flowed into the reactor for 10 minutes to eliminate oxidative gases (O_2 and H_2O). The reactor was externally heated by means of a 2kW electric heater starting at room temperature at a heating rate of $10^\circ C/minute$. The temperature of the reactor was controlled by a thermocouple. The maximum amount of liquid was obtained at $600^\circ C$. Figure 5 is the flow chart of the pyrolysis procedure.

Figure 5: Schematic Flowchart of the Pyrolysis Process

Heating Rate

The heating rate was determined by recording the temperature at each 3-min interval up to a final temperature of 600°C when maximum oil was obtained. The rate was calculated from the slope of the graph in figure 9.

Product Yields

The recovered products were quantified to determine the yield percentage of each product using the relationship between the mass of feedstock and that of each recovered product. These values provided insights into the pyrolysis process and serve as baseline data for evaluating future process optimisation.

Characterization of Pyrolytic Oil

The characterization of the pyrolyzed tyre oil was carried out to determine its compositional, elemental, physicochemical, and molecular properties, which are essential for understanding its fuel potential and quality relative to conventional petroleum fuels. The analyses were systematically performed to obtain complementary data that collectively describe the oil’s behaviour, stability, and usability. Physicochemical tests evaluated its performance-related attributes such as density, viscosity, and flash point (Zerin *et al.*, 2025). Furthermore, chemical composition analysis using chromatographic spectroscopic (Gas Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry) techniques enabled the identification of specific hydrocarbon compounds and functional groups present in the pyrolysis oil (Chen *et al.*, 2025).

Results and Discussion

Developed Prototype of the Pyrolysis Plant

Figure 6 presents the image of the developed prototyped pyrolysis plant, designed and fabricated for the thermal decomposition of industrial bio-wastes.

Figure 6: The Developed Prototype Pyrolysis Plant

The system demonstrated reliable performance at a standard operating voltage of 240V, achieving a maximum reactor temperature of 600°C, which is suitable for tyre material thermal degradation. The plant processed 30kg of tyre material per cycle, requiring approximately 41,943kJ of heat energy, with an efficient operational duration of 5.83 hours using a 2kW heating element. These outcomes reflect strong engineering applicability in sustainable waste conversion and bio-char production for rural or small-scale industrial setups.

Proximate Analysis Results

The results of the proximate analysis of the waste tyre feedstock are presented graphically in figure 7.

Figure 7: Proximate Analysis Result of the Pyrolyzed Tyre.

The proximate analysis of the tyre pyrolytic oil, as illustrated in figure 7, reveal volatile matter (68.24%) as the dominant component, indicating the presence of a high proportion of light hydrocarbons, which enhances its combustibility and fuel quality. The fixed carbon (28.76%) represents the solid residue contributing to the oil's heating value and stability, while the low ash content (2.87%) reflects minimal inorganic impurities, promoting cleaner combustion. The moisture content (0.13%) being low signifies reduced water interference during ignition and improved thermal efficiency. The results align well with the research by Ore & Adebisi (2025); Song *et al.*, (2025), achieving relative values of the proximity analysis of their research. Collectively, these results demonstrate that the pyrolytic oil possesses desirable characteristics comparable to conventional diesel fuels. Its high volatile and low ash fractions make it suitable for energy recovery and blending in automotive fuel applications, reducing reliance on fossil diesel.

Ultimate Analysis Results

Figure 8 presents the ultimate analysis of the feedstock sample, highlighting the relative proportions of its elemental components. This composition provides insight into the fuel's combustion characteristics and potential performance efficiency.

Figure 8: Ultimate Analysis Result of the Pyrolyzed Tyre

The ultimate analysis presented in figure 8 reveal that carbon constitutes the major component (83.10 wt. %), followed by hydrogen (7.7 wt. %), oxygen (4.0 wt. %), sulphur(1.54 wt.%). The high carbon concentration signifies the strong energy potential of the pyrolyzed tyre oil, indicating its suitability as a substitute for conventional hydrocarbon fuels. The moderate oxygen content enhances combustion

efficiency and promotes cleaner burning, while the low sulfur value is desirable for reducing harmful SO_x emissions.

Heating Rate

Table 1 is the heating values obtained while figure 9 is the graphical presentation of the heating rate.

Time (mins)	3	6	9	12	15	18	21	24	27	30	33	36	39	42	45	48	51	54	57	60
Temperature (°C)	55	76	98	133	165	203	240	269	295	329	355	390	410	435	457	467	482	500	550	600

Figure 9: Heating rate

The graph shows the temperature in °C versus residence time in pyrolysing tyre feedstock. The heating rate was determined theoretically from the slope of the graph:

$$\text{Heating Rate (°C)} = \frac{435 - 98}{42 - 9} = 10.21 \text{ °C min}^{-1}$$

Product Yields

The products obtained from the pyrolysis of waste tyres are oil 44 wt. %, char 39 wt. % and gas 17 wt. % (calculated by difference). The oil is a dark viscous liquid of pungent smell.

Figure 10: Product Yields

Physicochemical Tests Results

Figure 11 presents the physicochemical properties of the pyrolyzed tyre oil, highlighting key parameters that define its fuel quality and suitability for industrial and automotive applications.

Figure 11: Physicochemical Analysis Result of the Pyrolyzed Tyre

The physicochemical characterization of the pyrolyzed tyre oil, as shown in Graph 4, reveal properties comparable to conventional diesel fuels. The density (840 kg/m³) and specific gravity (0.9238 g/cm³) indicate a moderate energy concentration suitable for combustion engines. A calorific value of 36.82 MJ/kg demonstrates high energy potential, supporting its viability as an alternative fuel. The flash point of 28.7°C suggests the need for careful handling due to moderate volatility. The viscosity (3.95 mPa.s) falls within the acceptable range for efficient fuel atomization and engine lubrication. The acid and free fatty acid values reflect moderate oxidation stability, while the saponification and iodine values confirm a balanced composition of saturated and unsaturated hydrocarbons. The high peroxide value (360 mgKOH/g) suggests oxidative reactivity typical of pyrolytic oils. This result aligns well with that of physicochemical waste tyre values gotten by Aliş & Mohd Rafee (2020); Ramani et al., (2024). Overall, these properties indicate that tyre-derived oil can serve as a renewable, cost-effective substitute for fossil fuels, reducing waste tyre accumulation and promoting environmental sustainability in the automotive industry.

Chemical Composition Analysis Results

Figure 12 presents the Gas Chromatography–Mass Spectrometry (GC–MS) of the pyrolyzed tyre oil, showing the distribution of various hydrocarbon compounds formed during the thermal decomposition process.

Figure 12: The GC–MS Chromatogram Analysis of Pyrolyzed Tyre Oil

The GC–MS analysis of the pyrolyzed tyre oil, as presented in Figure 12, reveal a diverse composition of hydrocarbon compounds typically found in fuel-like materials. The chromatogram indicates that D-Limonene dominates the profile with the highest peak area of 21.40% at a retention time (RT) of 3.934 min, confirming its significant presence as a monoterpene hydrocarbon. Other notable compounds include p-Cresol (4.77%), 4-Methyl-2H-benzopyrane (7.33%), Benzene, 2-butenyl- (7.04%), and Naphthalene derivatives (2.63–5.62%), all contributing to the aromatic and aliphatic complexity of the pyrolytic oil.

The presence of phenolic compounds such as Phenol, 3-methyl- and p-Cresol indicates partial oxidation reactions, which enhance the oil's solvency and stability. Similarly, the detection of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) like Naphthalene and Fluorene demonstrates the advanced cracking of rubber polymer chains during pyrolysis, producing compounds with high calorific potential. The appearance of nitrile and acid derivatives such as Hexadecanenitrile (1.08%) and Octadecanoic acid (1.38%) reflects nitrogen and oxygen incorporation, signifying a mixed hydrocarbon nature suitable for further upgrading to refined fuels. Similar result was observed from the results by Fajar et al., (2024), on different hydrocarbons gotten from pyrolyzed waste tyre oil content.

Overall, the GC–MS profile confirms that the pyrolyzed tyre oil contains a rich blend of light aromatics, alkenes, and oxygenated hydrocarbons, aligning closely with the chemical structure of conventional fossil fuels. This composition underscores the potential of waste tyre pyrolysis oil as a viable alternative fuel for automotive applications after minimal refining. Environmentally, this result is profoundly impactful as it supports sustainable waste management, reduces landfill accumulation of tyres, and lowers greenhouse gas emissions through the recovery of energy-rich compounds from waste materials, advancing the circular economy within the automotive and energy industries.

Conclusion

This study successfully designed, fabricated, and experimentally evaluated a functional pyrolysis plant capable of converting waste tyres into energy-rich oil and valuable char under controlled thermochemical conditions. The components of the plant are not complicated and requires less maintenance. The system achieved optimal performance at a maximum reactor temperature of 600°C and processed 30kg of tyre feedstock per batch within 5.83hours, demonstrating excellent energy efficiency with a total heat input of 41,943kJ. The integrated heat exchanger maintained effective condensation, highlighting the design's engineering reliability and suitability for decentralized waste-to-energy operations.

Physicochemical characterization revealed that the derived oil possessed desirable fuel-like properties, including a calorific value of 36.82 MJ/kg, viscosity of 3.95 mPa·s, density of 840 kg/m³, and low ash and moisture contents, indicating high combustion efficiency. Ultimate analysis further confirmed a high carbon (83.10 wt.%) and low sulfur (1.54 wt. %) composition, supporting its environmental compatibility and potential as a cleaner-burning fuel. GC–MS analysis identified hydrocarbon compounds such as D-Limonene, p-Cresol, and Naphthalene derivatives, confirming the presence of light and aromatic fractions typical of conventional diesel. Collectively, these results validate the technological feasibility and sustainability of tyre pyrolysis as a viable pathway for converting solid waste into alternative fuels. In the short term, this process offers an efficient solution to tyre waste management and fossil fuel substitution. In the long term, it contributes to sustainable industrialization, circular economy advancement, and carbon footprint reduction within the automotive and energy sectors. The study therefore provides a scientific and engineering foundation for scaling up pyrolytic conversion systems toward commercial applications and cleaner energy futures.

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Biogas Production Efficiency in 3D-Printed Digesters: A Comparative Study of Six Geometric Configurations

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Abstract

This study examines the influence of digester geometry on biogas production efficiency using six distinct shapes: cuboid, cylindrical, hexagonal, pentagonal, square, and triangular, with duplicate digesters serving as controls. Twelve digesters, each with a 5-liter capacity, were fabricated via advanced 3D printing and tested using a cow dung–water mixture (2:1 ratio) under controlled anaerobic conditions. A 28-day hydraulic retention time was maintained, with internal and external temperatures continuously monitored to ensure optimal digestion. Biogas yield and composition were measured using laboratory analysis. The results indicate that optimal temperatures between 35 °C and 55 °C significantly enhanced methane production. Among the geometries tested, pentagonal and hexagonal digesters achieved the highest cumulative biogas yields (3867.5 cm³), followed by square (3092.5 cm³), cuboid and cylindrical (2592.5 cm³), with triangular digesters producing the least (1037.5 cm³). These findings demonstrate that digester geometry significantly influences biogas production efficiency and highlight the potential of 3D printing as a tool for optimizing digester design. The study also highlights the role of operational parameters—such as feedstock composition, temperature, pH, and organic loading rate—in maximizing biogas yield.

Keywords: bio-digester geometry, biogas production, 3D-printed bio-digesters, biogas yield optimization, substrate temperature management, anaerobic digestion.

Introduction

Biogas, a methane-rich gas generated through the anaerobic digestion of organic waste by bacteria, represents a sustainable and renewable energy source that holds significant potential despite its unpleasant odour. It offers a viable alternative for electricity generation, home heating, and machinery operation. With the global population projected to approach 10 billion by 2050, Oluwani, O. (2022). and energy consumption expected to rise by 1.3% annually, leading to a 70% increase in total demand by mid-century, there is an urgent need for sustainable energy solutions to meet these escalating demands.

As concerns over the environmental repercussions of fossil fuel usage intensify, the need for renewable energy sources like biogas has become increasingly critical. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) reports that human activities have increased Earth's temperature by approximately 1°C since the pre-industrial era, highlighting the urgency of addressing climate change. This shift towards renewable energy has catalysed research into various factors influencing biogas production.

Numerous studies have examined parameters affecting biogas yield and quality, such as feedstock composition, pH levels, and optimization of anaerobic digestion processes. Recent investigations, including Mbachu et al. (2021a), have explored the sustainability of biomass-to-biogas conversion systems, while others have focused on enhancing biogas production from specific substrates, including plant extracts from elephant grass and plantain pseudostems. Additionally, advancements in mathematical modeling have improved the prediction of biogas yields in different biodigester configurations, with contributions from Okwu et al. (2020) utilizing fuzzy logic and artificial neural networks for output predictions.

The influence of digester surface area on biogas yield has also been a focal point of study. Notably, Gboloba A.O. (2017) conducted a two-factor experiment analyzing the effects of manure type and biodigester surface area, revealing that the surface area ratio of diameter to height significantly affects biogas production efficiency. Ganas (2022) further explored the impact of the height-to-diameter ratio on biomethanation of market vegetable waste, indicating a minor influence on methane production. Lay et al. (2019) conducted computational simulations on various biodigester shapes, concluding that spherical designs may optimize mixing efficiency due to reduced dead zones and shorter substrate flow paths. Oloko-Oba et al. (2018) assessed three biodigester shapes, finding that cylindrical designs achieved the highest biogas yields, followed by spherical and rectangular models. Chiabuotu et al. (2024) compared triangular and hexagonal digesters, establishing both shapes' viability for biogas production from cow dung and water, with the hexagonal design yielding higher-quality methane.

Beyond operational parameters, the geometry of digesters has emerged as a crucial factor influencing biogas production. Prior research has underscored the importance of digester design elements—including surface area, diameter, height, and inlet-outlet configurations—in maximizing biogas output. Noteworthy contributions from Florentino (2003), Matheri et al. (2016), and Ganas (2022) have explored diverse digester configurations in relation to biogas yields. Recent studies, such as those by Chiabuotu et al. (2024), have examined the effects of digester geometry, indicating that alternative shapes optimizing surface area-to-volume ratios may outperform traditional cylindrical or rectangular designs.

Despite this expanding body of research, a gap persists regarding the impact of diverse digester geometries on biogas production under various operational conditions. The potential of digester shape to enhance mixing efficiency and the overall anaerobic digestion process remains inadequately explored. This study aims to address this gap by investigating the effect of six distinct digester shapes—pentagonal, cuboid, hexagonal, cylindrical, square, and triangular—on biogas production, all designed through 3D printing technology.

By employing cow dung mixed with water in a 1:2 ratio as the feedstock over a 28-day retention period, we will analyze the resultant biogas yields to determine how geometric configurations influence gas production efficiency. This research aspires to yield insights into the relationship between digester geometry and biogas yield, ultimately identifying optimal designs that enhance production capacity. The findings are expected to contribute to advancements in biogas technology and sustainable waste management practices, and provide actionable recommendations for manufacturers, farmers, and stakeholders within the biogas sector.

Materials and Method

Material Selection and Characterization

Bio-digester Material

Acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) copolymer was selected as the primary material for bio-digester fabrication due to its superior mechanical and chemical properties. The material exhibits excellent impact resistance, rigidity, chemical durability, and strong adhesion properties while being resistant to solvent-induced cracking. At operating temperatures of 90°C and above, ABS demonstrates an ultimate tensile strength of 12 MPa with a modulus of elasticity of 0.74 GPa.

Post-processing Treatment

Post-printing surface treatment involved mechanical smoothing using emery cloth, followed by gap filling with an acetone/ABS slurry to ensure design accuracy and uniform surface finish. The treatment process was essential for achieving optimal design accuracy and ensuring leak-proof, uniformly finished surfaces. Input and outflow manifold holes were precision-drilled and fitted with PVC components, which were subsequently secured using PVC adhesive and Giwa Epoxy sealant to ensure leak-proof connections throughout the system.

Additive Manufacturing Process

Printer Specifications

The bio-digesters were fabricated using an Original Prusa i3 MK3S+ printer (a widely used 3D printer model developed by Prusa Research), which offers comprehensive manufacturing capabilities suitable for this application. The printer features a build volume of 250 mm × 210 mm × 210 mm, with layer height resolution ranging from 0.05 to 0.35 mm and a filament diameter of 1.75 mm. The system operates at a standard print speed of 60 mm/s with a maximum travel speed of 200 mm/s. The printer's thermal capabilities include a maximum nozzle temperature of 300°C and a maximum heat-bed temperature of 120°C. Power consumption varies between 80w for PLA and 120w for ABS printing, with multiple connectivity options including USB, Wi-Fi, and Ethernet for optimal operational flexibility.

Bio-digester Design and Fabrication

The experimental design incorporated six distinct bio-digester geometries as shown in Figures 1 – 6, all designed using SolidWorks CAD software: square, rectangular, cylindrical, hexagonal, pentagonal, and cuboid. Each design maintained consistent specifications with a total volume of 4 litres and a wall thickness of 2.5 mm. The digesters were designed to accommodate 2.8 litres of substrate (70% of total volume), with the remaining 1.2 litres reserved for gas collection. The volume of the digester reserved for gas collection is obtained using equation 1.

$$V_d = V_{gs} + V_{gc}$$

Where, V_d is the total volume of the digester (4 Liters); V_{gs} is maximum volume of substrate intake for the digester (2.8 Liters) and V_{gc} is the volume of the chamber reserved for gas collection, which is computed as 1.2 Liters.

Figure 1. Square Digester

Figure 2. Triangular Digester

Figure 3. Hexagonal Digester

Figure 4: Pentagonal Digester

Figure 5. Cylindrical Digester

Figure 6. Cuboidal Digester

Component Integration

Each bio-digester was equipped with a comprehensive set of components to ensure optimal functionality. The gas collector unit consisted of an IVF drip set integrated with a 3.50-10 TR87 C.C. Super tube. The inlet unit comprised a 1¼" PVC assembly, including back nut, cover, and pipe, while the outlet unit featured a ½" PVC pipe with ball valve for controlled discharge. ZUMA PVC gum and 4-minute Giwa Epoxy steel hardener and resin were employed as sealants to ensure system integrity.

Experimental Setup and Procedures

Feedstock Preparation

Fresh cow dung served as the primary substrate, carefully mixed with water in a 1:2 ratio to achieve optimal consistency for anaerobic digestion. The feedstock underwent a 24-hour ambient temperature conditioning period to allow for settling and initial gas release. Initial pH and temperature measurements were recorded at the time of loading to establish baseline conditions for the experiment.

Experimental Design

The study employed a randomized complete block design with duplicate digesters for each geometry serving as controls. The experiment was conducted over a 28-day retention period under ambient conditions. Control digesters were utilized to establish baseline biogas production measurements, quantify geometry-specific impacts on production, account for non-geometric variables affecting production, and enable statistical validation of results. Figure 7 shows the different digester shapes with the collecting tubes.

Figure 7: The Different Digester Shapes with the Collecting tubes

Biogas Collection and Analysis

The biogas collection system utilized bicycle tire tubes connected to gas outlet valves, employing a water displacement method for precise volume measurement. Collected gas was transferred to sealed gas sampling bags for subsequent analysis. Gas composition analysis was conducted using an Agilent 6890N gas chromatograph (Agilent Technologies, USA) following ASTM D1946-20 standards to determine methane (CH₄) content, carbon dioxide (CO₂) levels, and trace gas compositions.

Data Analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) to evaluate the effect of digester geometry on biogas yield, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$. The comprehensive analysis encompassed a comparison of biogas production rates across geometries, assessment of gas composition variations, evaluation of temporal production patterns, and analysis of geometry-specific production efficiencies. This thorough analytical approach enabled a detailed understanding of the relationship between digester geometry and biogas production performance.

Results and Discussion

Performance Analysis of Different Digester Geometries

pH Evolution During Anaerobic Digestion

The monitoring of pH dynamics throughout the 28-day retention period, as shown in Table 1, revealed significant variations that align with the typical phases of anaerobic digestion. Initially, pH values ranged from 6.60 to 6.85 across all six digesters, reflecting the mildly acidic characteristics of the cow dung substrate. During the first two weeks, a systematic decline in pH was observed, reaching a minimum of 5.20 by day 14, indicating intense hydrolytic and acidogenic activity. This observation aligns with the findings of Taherdanak et al. (2016), who emphasized the critical role of pH in microbial growth during anaerobic digestion. The subsequent increase in pH to 5.60-5.70 from day 15 onwards marked the transition to methanogenesis, though these values remained below the optimal range of 6.5-7.5 for efficient methanogenic activity. This pH pattern is consistent with recent studies by Ali et al (2021), highlighting the importance of pH stabilization for enhancing microbial activity and biogas yield

Table 1: pH Table

	Hexagonal Digester Mean	Cylinder Digester Mean	Square Digester Mean	Triangle Digester Mean	Cuboid Digester Mean	Pentagon Digester Mean
Day	pH	pH	pH	pH	pH	pH
1	6.60	6.85	6.73	6.79	6.76	6.77
2	6.70	6.95	6.83	6.89	6.86	6.87
3	6.50	6.75	6.63	6.69	6.66	6.67
4	6.40	6.65	6.53	6.59	6.56	6.57
5	6.30	6.55	6.43	6.49	6.46	6.47
6	6.20	6.45	6.33	6.39	6.36	6.37
7	6.10	6.35	6.23	6.29	6.26	6.27
8	6.00	6.25	6.13	6.19	6.16	6.17
9	5.90	6.15	6.03	6.09	6.06	6.07
10	5.80	6.05	5.93	5.99	5.96	5.97
11	5.70	5.95	5.83	5.89	5.86	5.87
12	5.60	5.85	5.73	5.79	5.76	5.77
13	5.50	5.75	5.63	5.69	5.66	5.67
14	5.40	5.65	5.53	5.59	5.56	5.57
15	5.45	5.65	5.55	5.60	5.58	5.59
16	5.35	5.55	5.45	5.50	5.48	5.49
17	5.25	5.45	5.35	5.40	5.38	5.39
18	5.15	5.35	5.25	5.30	5.28	5.29
19	5.05	5.25	5.15	5.20	5.18	5.19
20	4.95	5.15	5.05	5.10	5.08	5.09
21	4.85	5.05	4.95	5.00	4.98	4.99
22	4.75	4.95	4.85	4.90	4.88	4.89
23	4.65	4.85	4.75	4.80	4.78	4.79
24	4.55	4.75	4.65	4.70	4.68	4.69
25	4.45	4.65	4.55	4.60	4.58	4.59
26	4.35	4.55	4.45	4.50	4.48	4.49
27	4.25	4.45	4.35	4.40	4.38	4.39
28	4.15	4.35	4.25	4.30	4.28	4.29

The initial pH of the substrate for all six digesters was noted to be between 6.60 and 6.85, attributed to the mildly acidic properties of cow dung. Over the first ten days, the pH

gradually declined from 6.60 to 5.90, indicating that hydrolytic bacteria were breaking down complex organic materials into simpler compounds, followed by acidogenesis. This

Figure 8. The pH plot

downward trend continued, and by day 14, the pH dropped to a low of 5.20, reflecting an accumulation of volatile fatty acids and a predominance of acidogenesis. The pH plot is shown in Figure 8 below.

Temperature Profile Analysis

Throughout the experimental period, the digesters maintained operation within the mesophilic temperature range, with values fluctuating between 34.25°C and 37.25°C as shown in Figure 9.

Figure 9. Substrate Temperature Plot.

This temperature profile aligns with recent research by Wang et al. (2019), indicating that mesophilic conditions are optimal for stable biogas production. The relatively narrow temperature variation of approximately 3°C demonstrates good thermal stability, which is crucial for maintaining consistent bacterial activity. Comparative studies by Sivasankaran et al (2020) have shown that mesophilic conditions yield the highest cumulative biogas production compared to psychrophilic and unregulated conditions. The observed cooling trend towards the experiment's conclusion, where temperatures declined to 34.25°C, could potentially impact microbial activity, as supported by the findings of Rajaonison et al. (2020), which highlight the significance of temperature management in biogas production systems. Table 2 shows the mean temperature result.

Table 2: Mean Temperature Result

	Hexagonal Digester Mean	Cylinder Digester Mean	Square Digester Mean	Triangle Digester Mean	Cuboid Digester Mean	Pentagon Digester Mean
Day	Temp. (°C)	Temp. (°C)	Temp. (°C)	Temp. (°C)	Temp. (°C)	Temp. (°C)
1	37.10	37.25	37.18	37.21	37.20	37.21
2	37.20	37.20	37.20	37.20	37.20	37.20
3	37.20	37.30	37.25	37.28	37.26	37.27
4	37.10	37.15	37.13	37.14	37.13	37.13
5	37.25	37.25	37.25	37.25	37.25	37.25
6	37.15	37.15	37.15	37.15	37.15	37.15
7	37.05	37.05	37.05	37.05	37.05	37.05
8	36.95	36.95	36.95	36.95	36.95	36.95
9	36.85	36.85	36.85	36.85	36.85	36.85
10	36.75	36.75	36.75	36.75	36.75	36.75
11	36.65	36.65	36.65	36.65	36.65	36.65
12	36.55	36.55	36.55	36.55	36.55	36.55
13	36.45	36.45	36.45	36.45	36.45	36.45
14	36.35	36.35	36.35	36.35	36.35	36.35
15	35.55	35.35	35.45	35.40	35.43	35.41
16	35.45	35.25	35.35	35.30	35.33	35.31
17	35.35	35.15	35.25	35.20	35.23	35.21
18	35.25	35.05	35.15	35.10	35.13	35.11
19	35.15	34.95	35.05	35.00	35.03	35.01
20	35.05	34.85	34.95	34.90	34.93	34.91
21	34.95	34.75	34.85	34.80	34.83	34.81
22	34.85	34.65	34.75	34.70	34.73	34.71
23	34.75	34.55	34.65	34.60	34.63	34.61
24	34.65	34.45	34.55	34.50	34.53	34.51
25	34.55	34.35	34.45	34.40	34.43	34.41
26	34.45	34.25	34.35	34.30	34.33	34.31
27	34.35	34.15	34.25	34.20	34.23	34.21
28	34.25	34.05	34.15	34.10	34.13	34.11

Biogas Production Performance

The cumulative biogas production analysis revealed varying yields among the different geometric designs over the 28-day hydraulic retention time, as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Mean Total Yield (CM3) Plot by Digesters

The pentagonal and hexagonal digesters demonstrated the highest production at 3,867.50 cm³, followed by the square digester at 3,092.50 cm³. The cylindrical and cuboidal digesters showed moderate performance with 2,592.50 cm³, while the triangular digester yielded the lowest production at 1,037.50 cm³. These variations in production efficiency can be attributed to differences in mixing patterns and headspace geometry, which recent studies by Leonzio (2018) have shown to significantly impact the anaerobic digestion process. The influence of geometric design on mixing dynamics and gas flow patterns has been demonstrated to affect the overall efficiency of biogas production, particularly in small-scale digesters, as noted by Neuner et al (2024). Table 3 shows the digester cumulative volume table.

Table 3: Digester Cumulative Volume Table

S/N	Digester	main and Control Digesters	Total Yield (cm³)	Mean Yield (cm³)	Frequency, n	Std Deviation
1	Pentagon	Pentagon 1	2750.00	3867.50	2	1584.9
		Pentagon 2	4985.00			
2	Cuboid	Cuboid 1	2195.00	2592.50	2	560.4
		Cuboid 2	2990.00			
3	Hexagonal	Hexagonal 1	2750.00	3867.50	2	1584.9
		Hexagonal 2	4985.00			
4	Cylinder	Cylinder 1	2195.00	2592.50	2	560.4
		Cylinder 2	2990.00			
5	Square	Square 1	3390	3092.50	2	420.4
		Square 2	2795			
6	Triangle	Triangle 1	915	1037.50	2	173.3
		Triangle 2	1160			

Statistical Analysis of Digester Performance

The statistical analysis of biogas yield across different digester geometries employed a one-way ANOVA, revealing an F-statistic of 2.28 (F(5,6)) with a p-value of 0.172. The analysis produced a between-groups sum of squares of 11,093,541.67 and a mean square of 2,218,708.33, with a residual mean square of 972,379.17. These results indicate no statistically significant differences in biogas yield among the six digester geometries at the 0.05 significance level. This finding adds to the growing body of research on digester design optimization, where recent studies by Cinar et al. (2021) have shown that the influence of geometric configuration on biogas yield is complex and often interrelated with other operational parameters. The statistical methodology employed in this study reflects current trends in biogas research, where advanced statistical techniques are used to evaluate process parameters and their interactions. Table 4 shows the ANOVA Analysis Result.

Table 4: ANOVA Analysis Result

	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom (df)	Mean Square	F	P
Digesters	11093541.67	5	2218708.33	2.28	0.172
Residual	5834275	6	972379.17		
Total	16927816.67	11			

Impact of Operating Parameters

The observed pH evolution pattern demonstrates the complex interplay between different phases of anaerobic digestion. The initial acidic conditions and subsequent pH changes reflect the sequential nature of the biological processes involved. Recent studies by Wang et al. (2022) have emphasized the importance of maintaining optimal pH ranges for maximizing biogas yield. The mesophilic temperature range maintained throughout the experiment (34.25°C-37.25°C) (Obiukwu and Nwafor 2014) aligns with current research by Shilpy et al. (2025), indicating that this temperature regime provides the best balance between process stability and biogas production efficiency. The relationship between temperature stability and biogas yield observed in this study corresponds with recent findings by Rajaonison et al. (2020), which highlight the critical role of temperature management in anaerobic digestion systems.

Geometric Design Implications

While variations in cumulative biogas production were observed among different digester geometries, the statistical analysis revealed these differences were not significant. This finding adds to the growing body of research on digester design optimization, where recent studies by Leonzio (2018) have shown that the influence of geometric configuration on biogas yield is complex and often interrelated with other operational parameters. The performance variations observed among different shapes suggest that factors such as mixing patterns and headspace geometry play important roles in the digestion process, as supported by recent literature by Neuner et al (2024) on small-scale digester design.

Process Optimization Considerations

The lack of statistically significant differences among digester geometries suggests that optimization efforts should consider a broader range of operational parameters. Recent advances in artificial intelligence and kinetic modeling, as discussed by Cinar et al. (2021), have demonstrated the importance of considering multiple process variables simultaneously for optimizing biogas production. The results of this study, combined with current research trends, indicate that future investigations should focus on the interaction between geometric design and other operational parameters, potentially incorporating advanced statistical methods and artificial intelligence techniques for process optimization. This comprehensive approach would better address the complex nature of anaerobic digestion and provide more effective strategies for maximizing biogas production efficiency.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study provides valuable insights into the influence of digester geometry on biogas production, contributing to the expanding body of literature surrounding anaerobic digestion. The findings reveal that, while variations in digester shapes—specifically those created through 3D printing—do have an inherent potential to impact biogas production, the overall differences in total yield were not statistically significant across the diverse geometries examined. This observation underscores the intricate nature of anaerobic digestion processes, where multiple interacting factors, including operational conditions and substrate characteristics, play a crucial role in determining biogas output. The lack of significant variation in yield among the different digester shapes suggests that geometry alone may not be the primary determinant of biogas production efficiency. Instead, it highlights the necessity of a more integrated approach that considers a comprehensive range of variables. Future research should prioritize the optimization of operational parameters—such as temperature, retention time, and mixing efficiency—as well as the exploration of diverse feedstock combinations. By focusing on these operational factors alongside geometrics, researchers may uncover synergies that enhance biogas production, leading to more efficient and sustainable energy systems.

Furthermore, this study points toward the potential for innovative digester designs that not only consider geometric shapes but also incorporate advanced materials and construction techniques, such as 3D printing. This approach could facilitate the development of bespoke digesters tailored to specific feedstocks and operational environments, ultimately maximizing biogas yield.

Overall, a holistic investigation into both the physical design and operational parameters will be essential for improving the efficacy of biogas production systems. Such endeavors will enhance the reliability of predictions regarding biogas yields, paving the way for more robust and sustainable biogas technologies that can contribute meaningfully to renewable energy agendas and waste management strategies. As the demand for sustainable energy solutions continues to escalate, further exploration in this field is critical to harnessing the full potential of biogas as a renewable energy source.

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SUB-THEME 4:
ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL DIMENSIONS OF
ENVIRONMENTAL SUSTAINABILITY

Exploring the Impact of Exchange Rate on the Lending Rate: A New Evidence from Nigeria

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Abstract

In Nigeria, the discussion on exchange rate fluctuations and the lending rate behaviour has often occupied important position among scholars and monetary policy authorities. However, empirical works that examine the impact of exchange rate on the lending rate are scanty; thus forming part of the motivations for this study. This present study therefore seeks to investigate the role of exchange rate in influencing the lending rate in Nigeria. The study used annual dataset which ranged from 1981-2022. Also, the auto regressive distributed lag (ARDL) bounds method was used for the estimation of the results. The long-run result indicates that exchange rate has a negative and significant impact on the lending rate. However, in the short-run one period lag of inflation rate impacted positively and significantly on the lending rate. Finding also reveals that the impact of interest rate spread is positive and significant in both the time horizons, while the impact of one period lag of money supply is positive and significant. Flowing from the findings, the authors suggest that several measures should be carried out to improve business prospects in the economy so that the long-run downward pressure of exchange rate depreciation on the lending rate can be utilized to grow the economy.

Keywords: ARDL, Exchange rate, lending rate, money supply.

Introduction

The study of the link between exchange rate and interest rate has often been of immense importance to policymakers, the academia and business people alike. In particular, the role of exchange rate in facilitating trade and investment across borders has made such study significant (Hnatkovska *et al.*, 2013). Also, the role of interest rate in stimulating investment and facilitating capital inflows has made the study essential. The essence of the link between exchange rate and interest rate has motivated some scholars to develop theories meant to facilitate a broader understanding of the relationship such as the overshooting theory by Dornbusch (1976).

Understanding the nexus between exchange rate and interest rate is paramount in developing countries because such could assist in the formation of expectations as well as create consciousness on the macroeconomic performance. As noted by Holtemöller and Mallick (2016), the fact that emerging economies have resorted to embrace either inflation-targeting or exchange-rate targeting as measures to ensure macroeconomic stability can be attributed to the knowledge of the relationship between exchange rate and interest rate. It thus presupposes that lack of adequate understanding of the relationship between the two variables could influence monetary policy setting. Analyzing the co-movement between exchange rate and interest rate is therefore paramount policy wise.

In Nigeria, interest rate behaviour, particularly the lending rate has always been a topical issue among policymakers and scholars. The concern of monetary policy authorities is to manipulate the monetary policy rate (MPR) in order to influence the lending rate. Apart from the MPR, other tools of monetary policy used to influence the lending rate are open market operation (OMO), foreign exchange net open position (NOP), cash reserve ratio (CRR) and liquidity ratio (Ogunniyi&Akam,2020). In order to achieve the inflation-targeting policy thrust, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) often tinkers with these policy tools. A major variable targeted through this exercise is the lending rate which is manipulated to curtail the inflationary pressure excessive lending poses. The literature has documented studies that have investigated the nexus between exchange rate and interest rate in Nigeria with little emphasis placed on the impact of exchange rate, particularly on the lending rate. However, exchange rate plays crucial role in influencing the lending rate through various transmission mechanisms. One of such mechanisms is through capital inflows. A weak domestic exchange rate for instance makes domestic investment assets to be cheap in relation to that of other countries which has the tendency to stimulate the penetration of investments into the home country. Such penetration of capital has the tendency to improve the liquidity position of the recipient country, raising money supply and thus lowering the lending rate. Given such scenario, policy aimed at influencing the lending rate will be more portent if the factors that shape its movement such as exchange rate are factored in the implementation. However, whether this hypothesized relationship between exchange rate and the lending rate exists significantly in Nigeria is a phenomenon that requires empirical validation. To give fillip to the need for this study, information in Fig.1 reveals that the link between exchange rate and the lending rate does not follow a regular pattern. Evidence shows that in some periods when exchange rate depreciates, the lending rate rises such as periods prior to 1999. However, in some periods when exchange rate appreciates the lending rate rises such as in periods after 1999.

Figure 1: Trend in Exchange Rate and the Lending rate
(Source: World Development Indicators)

Flowing from the aforementioned, this study seeks to investigate the impact of exchange rate movement on the lending rate in Nigeria. The current exchange rate depreciation in Nigeria occasioned by the policy on exchange rate liberalization and the likely impact it could have on the lending rate has made the current study a compelling endeavor. To achieve the study's objective, the auto regressive distributed lag (ARDL) bounds method which links both the short-run and the long-run impact is utilized.

Empirical Literature

Due to the dynamic link between interest rate and exchange rate, some studies have examined the impact of interest rate on exchange rate while some have examined the impact of exchange rate on interest rate. For the studies that focus on the impact of exchange rate on interest rate, finding in a study that involve 10 OECD countries, Ozcelebi (2018) shows that volatility in exchange rate results into a change in interest rate. Avdjiev *et al.* (2019) observe a decrease in cross-border lending arising from domestic currency depreciation for firms that depend on external funds. This finds support in a study by Keshtgaret *et al.* (2020) which reveal that exchange rate plays a role in raising the ratio of bank lending. In a related vein, Manthoset *et al.* (2022) find that an increase in exchange rate volatility resulted into an increase in loan spreads for loans extended in a currency that differs from that of the lender. In further support of the foregoing results, Becker *et al.* (2024) reveal that the appreciation of the US Dollars leads to a an improvement in net lending flows. However, in the long-run, the study reveals a strong and positive response. A study in the Philippines by Bagsic *et al.* (2025) find that bank lending expanded in period of currency depreciation; especially foreign and big banks whose lending is denominated in US Dollars.

However, studies that focus on the impact of interest rate on exchange rate have used several forms of interest rate such as the monetary policy rate, the Treasury bills rate, the lending rate and others. In a panel of seven major central banks, finding by Ferrari *et al.* (2017) indicates that an unanticipated increase in policy rate leads to instant currency appreciation. In a related vein, Kerssenfischer (2019) reveals that exchange rate rises on account of a contractionary monetary policy shock. This result finds corroboration in a study by Kugler (2020) which indicates that unexpected increase in short-term rate encouraged an appreciation of the Swiss franc. However, Grisse (2020) finds that a contractionary monetary policy causes an appreciation of the Swiss franc. In Nigeria, Ogunniyi and Akam (2020) reveal that a decrease in interest rate results into domestic currency appreciation before the global financial crisis. In Ghana, Akoto (2020) finds that interest rate exhibited a strong and negative relationship with exchange rate over the study period. In another study in Nigeria, Babalola (2021) indicates that in the short-run only Treasury bill rate impacts significantly on exchange rate, however; in the long-run the impact of other variables such as the lending rate is significant. In a study involving some sub-Saharan African countries (Nigeria, Ghana, Gambia, Sierra Leone and Liberia), Sylvia *et al.* (2022) indicate that interest rate is among the factors that encourages exchange rate depreciation. In a study involving Ghana, Armah *et al.* (2023) indicated a slow but positive response of exchange rate to shock in interest rate differential in the short-run. Umoru *et al.* (2023) shows that interest rate has a significant and positive impact on the volatility in exchange rate in Côte D'Ivoire, while in the short-run the impact was significant and negative in Cameroon. As a further proof, Fink *et al.* (2024) indicates that the announcement of monetary policy influenced the Swiss franc through its impact on medium- to longer-term expectations.

Theoretical Framework

In literature, the relationship between exchange rate and interest rate has found some theoretical backing. This study is guided by the overshooting theory by Dornbusch (1976) which lays emphasis on the link between exchange rate and interest rate. The central argument of the theory is that nominal exchange rate appreciates instantaneously when interest rate increases and then will depreciate in accord with uncovered interest parity (UIP). The instantaneous reaction of financial markets to rise in interest rate which is dictated by the

UIP condition is responsible for the initial appreciation. The overshooting model is stated as follows:

$$R = R^* + (E^e - E) / E \quad (1)$$

where

R and R^* represent the home country's nominal interest rate and that of foreign country, respectively, E represents spot barter price of foreign currency in relation to home currency and E^e represent the future expectation of exchange rate. If the expected rate of depreciation, that is $(E^e - E) / E$ is introduced, such will lead to the comparability of interest rate in the same country. The assumption of uncovered interest parity (UIP) implies that investors will move capital from a country where interest rate is low to a country where interest rate is high. This development will cause the recipient country's exchange rate to appreciate. Equation (1) may be restated as:

$$R - R^* = E^e - E \quad (2)$$

Equation (2) can be interpreted to mean that if there is a short-run loose monetary policy in the home country which is associated with a fall in R and an increase in E^e , the rise in E which is greater than E^e ensures that equation (2) maintains a balance assuming there is a fixed R^* . Consequently, in both short-run and the long-run, when prices rise, real money supply also rises and this increases R but reduces E in order to maintain equilibrium in equation (2)

Methodology

In this paper, annual dataset that spanned the period from 1981-2022 was used to evaluate the link between exchange rate and lending rate in Nigeria. The variables considered are the lending rate which is the dependent variable and exchange rate which is the independent variable. Other explanatory variables are inflation rate, broad money supply (a proxy for money supply) and gross domestic product (GDP). Data for all the variables were obtained from the World Development Indicators. The lending rate and inflation rate are measured in percentage. Also, interest rate spread is measured in percentage and it is calculated as lending rate minus deposit rate. GDP is measured in constant 2015 US Dollars. Also, while exchange rate is measured in local currency unit per US Dollars, M2 is measured in current local currency unit. To enhance results interpretation and for normalization, we logged both M2 and GDP.

The study conducted some pre-diagnostic tests meant to examine the behaviour of the variables included in the model. These include the descriptive statistics, correlation matrix and unit root tests. Both the augmented Dickey-Fuller and Philip-Perron tests were adopted to examine the unit root. The autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) bounds test was used to test for the cointegration among the variables. Post-diagnostic tests were equally conducted to identify if the series suffer from heteroskedasticity and serial correlation and whether the model is well specified and stable.

Model Specification

The baseline model that guided the study is specified as follows:

$$LR_t = (EXCHR_t, INFLR_t, INTRS_t, LM2_t, LGDP) \quad (1)$$

Equation 1 is expressed in the ARDL form as follows:

$$\Delta LR_t = \eta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^k \eta_1 \Delta LR_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^k \eta_2 \Delta EXCHR_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^k \eta_3 \Delta INFLR_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^k \eta_4 \Delta INTRS_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^k \eta_5 \Delta LM2_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^k \eta_5 \Delta LGDP_{t-1} + \lambda_1 LR_{t-1} + \lambda_2 EXCHR_{t-1} + \lambda_3 INTRS_{t-1} + \lambda_4 LM2_{t-1} + \lambda_5 LGDP_{t-1} + \mu_t \quad (2)$$

where:

LR = lending rate, $EXCHR$ = real exchange rate, $INFLR$ = inflation rate, $INTRS$ = interest rate spread, $LM2$ = log of broad money supply (a proxy for money supply), $LGDP$ = log of gross domestic product and μ_t is a stochastic term. The coefficients of the short-run parameters are: $\eta_1, \eta_2, \dots, \eta_5$ while the coefficients of the long-run parameters are: $\lambda_1, \lambda_2, \dots, \lambda_5$

For the test of the existence of long-run relationship among the variables, the study is guided by the following null hypothesis: $H_0 : \lambda_1 = \lambda_2 = \lambda_3 = \lambda_4 = \lambda_5$ (presence of cointegration). Alternatively the hypothesis indicating the absence of cointegration is stated as follows: $H_1 : \lambda_1 \neq \lambda_2 \neq \lambda_3 \neq \lambda_4 \neq \lambda_5$. If cointegration is established, the following error correction model (ECM) is specified:

$$\Delta LR_t = \eta_0 + \sum_{j=1}^k \eta_1 \Delta LR_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^k \eta_2 \Delta EXCHR_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^k \eta_3 \Delta INFLR_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^k \eta_4 \Delta LM2_{t-1} + \sum_{j=1}^k \eta_5 \Delta LGDP_{t-1} + \lambda_1 LR_{t-1} + \lambda_2 EXCHR_{t-1} + \lambda_3 INTRS_{t-1} + \lambda_4 LM2_{t-1} + \lambda_5 LGDP_{t-1} + \varphi ECM_{t-1} + \mu \quad (3)$$

Where:

ECM = error correction model and φ is the coefficient of the error correction model

Results and Discussion

Findings in Table 1 reveal that that variable with the highest mean value is exchange rate (113.64), but interest rate spread has the lowest mean value (6.48). It is also found that the gap between the mean and the median of all the variables is low which is an indication that the variables are symmetric is. Equally, evident suggests that exchange rate has the highest range; implying that it exhibited high volatility within the period of study. On the other hand, GDP is found to have low range; showing that it has less volatile. Apart from interest rate spread and M2 which exhibited negative skewness (skewed to the right), others are negatively skewed (skewed to the left). Results also indicate that all the variables are heavily-tailed since their kurtosis is positive.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	LR	EXCHR	INFLR	INTRS	LM2	LGDP
Mean	17.44	115.64	16.23	6.48	11.81	11.39
Median	16.92	114.89	10.75	6.95	12.15	11.35
Maximum	31.65	425.97	75.40	11.06	13.71	11.74
Minimum	9.43	0.00	0.68	0.31	0.00	11.05
Std. Dev.	4.66	119.1	14.16	2.65	2.19	0.23
Skewness	0.45	1.02	2.22	-0.74	-3.75	0.14
Kurtosis	3.79	3.22	8.90	3.04	21.04	1.43
Jarque-Bera	2.53	7.44	95.71	3.92	668.5	4.43
Probability	0.28	0.02	0.00	0.14	0.00	0.10
Sum	732.7	4856.9	682.00	272.34	496.06	478.4
Sum Sq. Dev.	890.8	582528.1	8223.9	288.3	197.7	2.33
Observations	42	42	42	42	42	42

In Table 2, results of the correlation matrix indicate that the correlation between lending rate and exchange rate is relatively low and negative just as its correlation with GDP. However, the correlation between the lending rate and inflation rate, interest rate spread and M2 is relatively low and positive. It is found that the correlation between one explanatory variable and the other is low which indicates a case of low multicollinearity. This implies that the individual impact of each explanatory variable on the dependent variable could easily be isolated.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix

	LR	EXCHR	INFLR	INTRS	LM2	LGDP
LR	1.	-0.17	0.43	0.49	0.09	-0.13
EXCHR	-0.17	1	-0.32	0.41	0.58	0.83
INFLR	0.43	-0.32	1	0.04	-0.13	-0.37
INTRS	0.49	0.41	0.04	1	0.35	0.52
LM2	0.09	0.58	-0.13	0.35	1	0.30
LGDP	-0.13	0.82	-0.37	0.52	0.30	1

The results of unit root in Table 3 reveal that only inflation rate achieved stationarity (absence of unit root) at level. However, other variables became stationary after first differencing. In a nutshell, while inflationary rate is integrated of order zero, *ie I(0)*, other variables are integrated of order one, *ie I(1)*. This shows that the series have an admixture of order of integration.

Table 3: Unit Roots Test

Variable	ADF		PP		Order of Integration
	Level	First Diff.	Level	First Diff.	
LR	-2.45	-5.46	-2.47	-6.96	<i>I(1)</i>
EXCHR	-1.94	-2.03	-1.95	-2.03	<i>I(1)</i>
INFLR	-3.32	-7.78	-3.32	-10.86	<i>I(0)</i>
INTRS	-2.36	-6.74	-2.36	-9.55	<i>I(1)</i>
LM2	-1.45	-2.22	-1.45	-2.23	<i>I(1)</i>
LGDP	-0.57	-5.43	0.21	-5.41	<i>I(1)</i>

The ARDL result in Table 4 indicates that the coefficient of the error term is negative and significant, indicating the existence of long-run relationship. Apart from been an evidence of long-run relationship among the variables, the result also indicate that about 57% of the errors generated in each period is automatically corrected by the system in the subsequent period. The results of the individual coefficients indicate that in the short-run exchange rate impacted positively on the lending rate but the result is not significant. However, in the long-run exchange rate impacted negatively and significantly on the lending rate. The long-run result indicates that if exchange rate depreciates one Dollar, the lending rate declined by 0.04 percent. This result finds an empirical corroboration in the studies done in the past (Avdjiev *et al.*, 2019; Bagsic *et al.*, 2025). The implication of the result is that when the country’s currency depreciates, such results into a fall in the lending rate. One channel through which this could be possible is domestic investment assets. A depreciating currency makes domestic asset prices to be cheap relative to foreign assets. Given this scenario, the demand for domestic investment will be high and such has the tendency to improve the liquidity position in the economy, especially the liquidity of lending institutions. Such improved liquidity no doubt will encourage a decline in the lending rate. We contend that the reason why the impact is significant only in the long-run is because of the time it takes on the part of lending institutions to adjust their lending rate in the face of improved liquidity build-up. Frequent depreciation of the Nigerian currency over the years thus suggests the tendency for the lending institutions to adjust their lending ratedownward and this could be more so in recent times due to the current policy on exchange rate liberalization which has affected the value of the naira.

In another vein, it is found that inflation rate exerted a significant positive influence on the lending rate in the short-run after one period lag. The result indicates that if inflation rises by one percent, lending rate rises by 0.09 percent after one period lag. The plausible reason for this result could be the effect of the contractionary monetary policy stance of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN), especially in times of high inflation. The major monetary policy objective of the CBN is inflation-targeting. To achieve this objective, the Bank often intervenes during period of inflation through some measures such as raising the monetary policy rate (MPR), the cash reserve requirement or other means. In particular, raising the MPR has the tendency to drag other rates up. One implication of this result is that when inflation is high, it will be impossible to officially lower the domestic interest rate. The reason the result is significant after one period lag could be due to the time between monetary policy

intervention and the time when the policy begins to have impact on the lending behaviour of the financial institutions. From another perspective, findings indicate that interest rate spread impacted positively and significantly on the lending rate in both the short-run and the long-run. This result is not surprising considering that lending institutions make much profit when the interest rate spread is high. Therefore, the tendency to increase the profit through raising interest rate spread implies that the lending rate has to be high. In Nigeria, high lending rate in the face of low saving rate (high interest rate spread) has always been an issue of concern among bank depositors. The phenomenon of high interest rate spread has been noted to be among the characteristics of a less-developed financial system (Owusu-Antwiet *al.*, 2017).

It is found that while money supply impacted the lending rate positively and significantly after one period lag, the impact is found to be negative and significant in the long-run. We are of the view that the monetary policy intervention meant to reduce the inflationary impact of increased money supply could be responsible for the short-run positive impact. As noted earlier, such contractionary policy which is often designed to work in the short-run often raises the lending rate through the official increase in the MPR or other monetary policy measures such as increase in the reserve requirement. However, the long-run result is in line with a priori expectation as it is expected that due to the inverse relationship between money supply and interest rate, increase in money supply entails a fall in interest rate. Finally, finding indicates that GDP impacted the lending rate positively and significantly in the short-run. Among the plausible reasons for the result is the inflationary pressure which improve GDP portends. In period of rising GDP, there is often a flurry of economic activities which have the tendency to be inflationary. An intervention to curtail such inflationary tendency often leads to an increase in the lending rate.

Table 4: ARDL Results

Short-run Results				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(EXCHR)	0.02	0.02	0.59	0.55
D(INFLR)	0.02	0.03	0.67	0.50
D(INFLR(-1))	0.09	0.03	2.63	0.02
D(INTRS)	0.64	0.25	2.52	0.02
D(LM2)	-0.66	0.89	-0.74	0.46
D(LM2(-1))	20.16	7.79	2.58	0.01
D(LGDP)	75.54	29.63	2.54	0.02
CointEq(-1)	-0.57	0.12	-4.61	0.00
Long-run Results				
EXCHR	-0.04	0.02	-1.76	0.09
INFLR	-0.013	0.08	-0.16	0.87
INTRS	1.12	0.40	2.80	0.00
LM2	-18.46	7.63	-2.41	0.02
LGDP	0.85	19.11	0.04	0.96
C	182.78	225.82	0.80	0.42

The results of post-diagnostic tests in Table 5 which are evaluated at the 5% level of significance indicate that the error term does not suffer from the problem of heteroskedasticity (error terms have constant variance). The result also indicates that the model does not have an issue with serial correlation since at the 5% level; we cannot reject the null hypothesis of an absence of serial correlation. Finding also reveals that the model is well-specified since the p-value of the Ramsey RESET test is higher than the 5% level of significance. The result of normality indicates that the p-value of the Jarque-Bera test is greater than 5%, suggesting that the errors are normally distributed. Figures 3 and 4 show that the plot of the CUSUM and CUSUMS Square statistic fall inside the critical bands of the 5% confidence interval, indicating that the parameters of the model are stable overtime.

Table 5: Results of Post Diagnostics

Test	P-value
Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey	0.28
Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test	0.14
Ramsey RESET Test for model specification	0.26
Jarque-Bera Test for normality	0.21

Figure 2: Result of Stability Test

Figure 3: Plot of CUSUM of Recursive Residuals

Figure 4: Plot of CUSUM of Squares Recursive Residuals

Conclusion

In this study, emphasis is placed on investigating the impact of exchange rate movement on the lending rate in Nigeria under the framework of the ARDL. While some studies have examined the impact of interest rate on exchange rate in Nigeria, there is scanty literature on the impact of the lending rate and this present study contributes to extant literature.

The study finds that exchange rate impacts the lending rate negatively and significantly in the long-run. It is also found that inflation exerted a positive and significant impact on the lending rate in the short-run after one period lag. More so, findings reveal that while the impact of interest rate spread is positive and significant in both the short-run and the long-run, the impact of money supply is positive and significant in the short-run after one period lag but negative and significant in the long-run. These results have implications for monetary policy implementation in Nigeria. One of the implications is the impact of the current policy on floating the domestic currency on the value of the naira. Due to this policy, the naira has

witnessed huge depreciation in recent times. Flowing from the finding of the present paper, such depreciating value of the naira has the tendency to attract foreign investment into the economy. Such development results into a decline in the lending rate which though is good for investment but could affect the attainment of the price stability objective of the monetary authorities. By encouraging increased capital inflows, domestic currency depreciation results into an increase in the liquidity position of the lending institutions; incentivizing them to extend more credit facilities. Such development could be inflationary, especially if the credits extended do not support growth. It is against this backdrop that the authors suggest that several measures should be carried out to improve business prospects in the economy so that the long-run downward pressure of exchange rate depreciation on the lending rate can be utilized to grow the economy. This is necessary because economic productivity propelled by low lending rate is less inflationary unlike when such is channeled to unproductive ventures.

However, the fact is that notwithstanding the current naira depreciation, the lending rate in Nigeria still relatively high which could be attributed to so many factors which this study did not take into consideration. Non-inclusion of these factors in the study represent one of the study's limitations which future studies should take into cognizance.

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Innovation and Sustainability of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises in Imo State: The Moderating Effect of Information Technology Adoption

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Abstract

This study examined the relationship between innovation and sustainability of Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) in Imo State, Nigeria, with Information Technology (IT) adoption as a moderating variable. Grounded in the Resource-Based View, Dynamic Capability Theory, the study argues that innovation capabilities and IT adoption jointly strengthen firms' sustainable performance. A correlational research design was employed, and the population comprised 1,886 registered SMEs in Imo State, from which a sample of 329 SMEs was determined using the Taro Yamane formula. A stratified proportional random sampling technique was adopted to ensure adequate representation of SMEs sectors. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire, 291 valid responses depicting a response rate of 88.45% were analyzed using descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, and Zero-order partial correlation analysis to test the moderating effect via SPSS version 26. Validity was ascertained through expert review while reliability were measured using Cronbach's alpha and all the variables were above 0.70. Results revealed significant positive relationships between product, process, and marketing innovations and economic, social, and environmental sustainability measures of SMEs at a 5% significance level, and IT adoption strengthened this relationship across all innovation dimensions. The findings suggest that SMEs that adopt innovative practices while leveraging IT are more likely to achieve sustainable business performance. The study concludes that innovation practices enhance SME sustainability when supported by IT adoption. The study recommends that SMEs institutionalize innovation culture, invest in IT adoption, seek government support for digital transformation, and engage in capacity-building programs for sustainable practices.

Keywords: Innovation, Sustainability, Information Technology Adoption, SMEs, Sustainable Business Performance.

Introduction

In an era marked by rapid technological advancement and environmental consciousness, innovation has emerged as a vital driver of sustainable competitiveness among Small and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs). SMEs in Nigeria, particularly in Imo State, play a crucial role in economic growth and employment generation. However, their sustainability has been increasingly threatened by rising competition, technological disruption, and environmental challenges (Olaleye et al., 2024). Innovation, encompassing product, process, and marketing dimensions, enables SMEs to adapt, differentiate, and survive in volatile markets (Ndubuisi et al., 2024). Despite growing recognition of innovation's role, the link between innovation and sustainability in Nigerian SMEs remains inadequately understood. Most existing studies have examined innovation's effect on firm performance (Akinwale et al., 2021; Eze & Chinedu, 2022) without sufficiently addressing its long-term sustainability implications.

Moreover, the effect of IT adoption as a moderator in this relationship has received limited empirical attention in the Nigerian SME context, despite its proven influence in enhancing business agility and innovation performance in developed economies (Hossain et al., 2023). Moreover, many SMEs lack the technological capabilities to fully leverage their innovative practices, which limits their ability to achieve holistic sustainability outcomes (Campbell Institute, 2020). Therefore, this study was motivated by several gaps in prior literature. First, most studies in the Nigerian SME sector have focused on innovation’s impact on firm growth and profitability, neglecting sustainability outcomes (Eze et al., 2022). Second, few empirical works have explored the moderating effect of IT adoption between innovation and sustainability, particularly within developing economies (Okafor & Nnadi, 2024; Zhang et al., 2023). Finally, as observed from literature, there is scarcity of empirical data on context-specific evidence from South-Eastern Nigeria especially Imo State on the study variables. In response to these gaps, this study seeks to examine the moderating effect of IT adoption on the relationship between innovation (product, process, and marketing) and sustainable business performance (economic, social, and environmental) of SMEs in Imo State, Nigeria. By addressing these issues, the study contributes to the growing body of literature on innovation-led sustainability in developing economies and provides practical insights for policy and management interventions. Moreover, the study provides empirical evidence to guide SME managers in integrating innovation and technology to achieve long-term sustainability outcomes.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework of Innovation and Sustainability of Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises in Imo State.

Source: Innovation (OECD, 2018; Kotler & Keller, 2021); and Sustainability (Elkington, 1997)

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework

This study is anchored on the Resource-Based View (RBV) and Dynamic Capability Theory.

Resource-Based View (RBV)

The RBV theory suggests that firms gain competitive advantage through valuable, rare, and inimitable resources, including innovation and IT (Barney, 1991). Innovation whether in products, processes, or marketing constitutes a strategic internal capability that enables SMEs to differentiate their offerings, optimize operations, reduce costs, and enhance customer satisfaction. According to RBV, innovation capability is an intangible asset that directly strengthens a firm's long-term sustainability outcomes. In SMEs, innovation (product, process, and marketing) and IT adoption serve as strategic resources that enhance competitiveness and sustainability. Moreover, innovation capabilities, knowledge assets, technical skills, creative routines serve as strategic resources that enhance sustainability performance. SMEs with strong product and process innovation capacities are better positioned to respond to market changes and environmental pressures. Therefore, RBV explains how innovation is a unique internal resource that drives sustainability.

Dynamic Capability Theory (DCT)

Dynamic capabilities are higher-order strategic processes that enable firms to renew competencies and remain competitive in volatile settings. This theory extends RBV by emphasizing firms' ability to integrate, build, and reconfigure resources in rapidly changing environments enhances performance, highlighting the role of IT adoption in leveraging innovation (Teece, 2007). Teece (2007) classifies dynamic capabilities into three clusters: (i) Sensing which is the ability to identify, interpret and anticipate opportunities or threats in the external environment. For SMEs in Imo State, this includes recognizing changes in customer preferences, new sustainability regulations, or emerging digital trends; (ii) Seizing which entails the capacity to mobilize resources to capture recognized opportunities, such as developing new products, adopting digital systems or implementing greener processes; (iii) Reconfiguring/Transforming, which is the ability to continuously realign and renew resources, capabilities, processes and technologies in response to market changes. Innovation is considered a dynamic capability, enabling SMEs to sense opportunities, seize them, and transform operations. IT adoption strengthens these capabilities by supporting digital workflows, knowledge sharing, and operational flexibility, ultimately enhancing sustainable performance. Thus, dynamic capabilities theory explains how innovation and IT adoption help SMEs adapt and achieve sustained performance in dynamic environments.

Innovation

Innovation is widely recognized as a central driver of competitiveness, differentiation, and long-term sustainability for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). Compared to larger firms, SMEs typically operate under resource constraints, limited technological capacity, and narrower market access, making innovation an essential survival strategy rather than an optional activity. Research consistently conceptualizes innovation as a multidimensional construct encompassing product, process, and marketing innovation, with each dimension contributing distinctly to firm performance (Schumpeter, 1934; OECD, 2018; Kotler & Keller, 2021). Innovation generally refers to the development and implementation of new or significantly improved products, processes, or methods. Schumpeter (1934) describes innovation as "new combinations" that drive economic development. The Oslo Manual (OECD, 2018) similarly defines innovation as the introduction of novel or substantially improved products, production processes, marketing techniques, or organizational methods to enhance firm competitiveness.

Within SMEs, innovation tends to be more incremental, flexible, and customer-driven due to entrepreneurs' close market interactions and agile decision-making structures (Saunila, 2020); and further posits that a combination of all three dimensions has a stronger impact on performance than any individual dimension alone. Also, Gonzales-Gemio et al. (2020) advanced that Innovation enhances responsible business practices and strategic sustainability in SMEs. The three predominant innovation dimensions product, process, and marketing innovation serve as frameworks for understanding how SMEs respond to market turbulence, technological change, and competitive pressures. Product innovation introduces new or improved goods/services, meeting evolving customer needs. Process innovation improves production or delivery methods, enhancing efficiency and reducing costs. Marketing innovation involves novel approaches to promotion, pricing, distribution, and product presentation, expanding market reach. Collectively, these innovations enable SMEs to respond to competition, improve performance, and drive sustainability

Product Innovation

It is the introduction of new or significantly improved goods or services in terms of features, performance, quality, or technological characteristics (OECD, 2018). It enhances competitive advantage and supports sustainability by offering environmentally friendly or socially beneficial products. This dimension is crucial for SMEs as it enables differentiation, customer attraction, and expansion into new markets. Empirical evidence demonstrates that product innovation positively influences SME performance, including profitability and sales growth (Le et al., 2023). SMEs often achieve such innovation through customer feedback, entrepreneurial vision, flexible structures, and collaborative learning with suppliers and customers. This aligns with findings that product innovation in SMEs is often incremental and market-driven due to limited research and development (R&D) budgets but still significantly enhances competitiveness (Saunila, 2020).

Process Innovation

Process innovation refers to improvements in production and operational processes, including automation, waste reduction, and quality enhancement. It includes technological upgrades, workflow redesign, automation, lean practices, and digital enhancements (OECD, 2018). Although less visible than product innovation, process innovation is critical for SMEs because it enhances efficiency, reduces cost, and improves output quality. Thus, it directly contributes to environmental and economic sustainability by reducing material use, minimizing costs, and improving efficiency. Recent empirical findings show that process innovation is strongly associated with productivity improvements in developing economy SMEs (Islami & Mulolli, 2024). Their study emphasizes that even incremental process changes such as digital billing, simplified workflow procedures, and equipment upgrades can yield substantial gains in operational performance. Process innovation, therefore, strengthens SMEs' internal capacity to deliver improved products more efficiently, reinforcing overall competitiveness.

Marketing Innovation

Marketing innovation involves adopting new marketing methods related to product design, positioning, promotion, pricing, or distribution (OECD, 2018). With the rapid expansion of digital technologies, marketing innovation has become a major driver of SME competitiveness. It supports sustainability by strengthening customer engagement and ensuring long-term market relevance through ethical and value-driven strategies. Dwivedi and Pawsey (2023) found that digital marketing innovation, including social media marketing,

online branding, mobile advertising, and new pricing strategies, significantly enhances SMEs' market reach and customer engagement. These innovative marketing approaches allow SMEs to overcome geographical limitations, communicate value more effectively, and tap into new customer segments. Marketing innovation thus represents a low-cost, high-impact approach for SMEs particularly beneficial in environments with limited access to capital or research and development resources.

Sustainability

Sustainability has emerged as a central theme in contemporary organizational research, driven by increasing global concern for economic resilience, social well-being, and environmental protection. In the business context, sustainability refers to the balanced pursuit of economic viability, social responsibility, and environmental stewardship (Elkington, 1997; OECD, 2020). For firms especially small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) sustainability practices enhance long-term competitiveness, stakeholder legitimacy, and resilience in turbulent environments (Agyekum et al., 2021). The modern view of sustainability derives from the Brundtland Report, which defines sustainable development as the ability to meet the needs of the present without compromising that of the future generations to meet their own needs (World Commission on Environment and Development, 1987). Elkington (1997) further operationalized this through the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) framework economic, social, and environmental sustainability widely adopted in management and organizational research. The TBL framework argues that organizational sustainability requires simultaneous attention to financial performance, community well-being, and ecological responsibility. These three pillars serve as a foundation for analyzing sustainability practices in firms of all sizes, including SMEs. Sustainability is paramount in any business endeavours because, it aids resource conservation, long term success and creates balance between human activities and the environment as well as resilience to economic and environmental shocks. This review synthesizes conceptual and empirical developments on the three core dimensions of sustainability: economic, social, and environmental sustainability.

Economic Sustainability

This refers to a firm's ability to maintain long-term financial viability, create value, and ensure continued productivity and profitability while efficiently using resources (OECD, 2020). For SMEs, economic sustainability involves strategies such as prudent cost management, innovation investment, financial resilience, and long-term growth planning. Scholars argue that economically sustainable firms integrate resource efficiency, stable cash flow, and risk management into their operational strategies (Agyekum et al., 2021). Economic sustainability is therefore not only about short-term profitability but also about creating enduring economic value for stakeholders (Elkington, 1997). Empirical research shows that SMEs with strong economic sustainability practices often exhibit higher productivity, stronger competitiveness, and improved survival rates (Mohammed & Masa'deh, 2022). Thus, this implies that SMEs can continue operations, create employment, and generate value for stakeholders. The typical components include: (i) long-term financial planning; (ii) efficient resource utilization ;(iii) investment in innovation; (iv) stable employment practices; and (v) cost-effective operations. Therefore, economic sustainability thus strengthens the firm's ability to withstand market fluctuations and enhances resilience in competitive environments.

Social Sustainability

Social sustainability encompasses practices that improve the well-being of employees, communities, and society at large. It includes fairness, human rights, employee welfare,

community engagement, and ethical practices (WCED, 1987; Elkington, 1997). It emphasizes ethical business conduct, fair treatment of employees, community engagement, and stakeholder welfare (Udoka & Oduro, 2022). In SMEs, social sustainability is particularly relevant due to the close ties these firms have with local communities and their employees. Socially responsible practices such as employee training, workplace safety, fair compensation, and equitable treatment lead to enhanced employee commitment, lower turnover, and improved organizational reputation (Amoako & Lyon, 2020). Hence, SMEs that integrate social responsibility into their operations, such as fair labour practices or community development initiatives, foster trust and long-term relationships that are critical for enduring success. The key aspects of social sustainability include: (i) employee health, safety, and welfare; (ii) fair labour practices and diversity; (iii) ethical business conduct; (iv) community development and engagement; and (v) human capital development. Empirical studies emphasize that SMEs adopting social sustainability practices experience stronger stakeholder trust and improved customer loyalty, ultimately enhancing their competitive advantage (Agyekum et al., 2021).

Environmental Sustainability

Environmental sustainability focuses on reducing negative environmental impacts and promoting responsible use of natural resources. It includes waste reduction, pollution control, eco-efficiency, renewable energy usage, and compliance with environmental regulations (OECD, 2020). Thus, involves adopting eco-friendly practices, such as resource efficiency, waste reduction, pollution control, and compliance with environmental standards (Onwuka & Olamide, 2020). For SMEs, environmental sustainability practices such as energy efficiency, green product design, recycling, and cleaner production contribute to reduced operational costs and improved environmental performance. Research shows that environmentally sustainable SMEs often benefit from improved market reputation, access to green markets, and regulatory compliance advantages (Amoako & Lyon, 2020). Hence, SMEs that innovate in ways that reduce environmental impact contribute to sustainability while potentially gaining market advantages through green products or operations. The major components include: (i) waste minimization and recycling; (ii) energy and water conservation; (iii) pollution prevention; (iv) use of eco-friendly materials; and (v) adoption of green technologies. Empirical findings reveal that environmental sustainability not only reduces operational risks but also enhances long-term strategic positioning, especially in industries under strict regulatory scrutiny (Mohammed & Masa'deh, 2022). Consequently, evidence demonstrates that the integration of economic, social, and environmental sustainability yields superior competitive advantage compared to adopting a single sustainability dimension (OECD, 2020).

Moderating Effect of Information Technology (IT) Adoption on the Relationship between Innovation and Sustainability

Information Technology (IT) adoption is widely recognized as a strategic enabler that enhances the effectiveness of innovation in achieving sustainable outcomes in SMEs (Hossain et al., 2023; Yuwono et al., 2024). In practice, IT adoption can include cloud computing, enterprise resource planning (ERP) systems, customer relationship management (CRM) software, digital marketing platforms, and mobile applications. While innovation through product, process, and marketing improvements directly influences economic, social, and environmental sustainability, the degree to which these innovations translate into measurable sustainable performance often depends on the extent of IT integration. IT adoption provides SMEs with digital tools and platforms for process automation, product design optimization, data-driven decision-making, and marketing analytics, allowing

innovative initiatives to be implemented more efficiently and at a larger scale. It is particularly critical in developing countries where SMEs face resource constraints and require technology to bridge capability gaps (Yuwono et al., 2024). For instance, a firm introducing an eco-friendly product (product innovation) may rely on IT enabled production monitoring systems (process innovation) and digital marketing campaigns (marketing innovation) to maximize its economic, social, and environmental impact. Conceptually, IT adoption strengthens the innovation sustainability nexus, acting as a moderator that amplifies the positive effects of innovation on sustainable business performance. Therefore, SMEs that combine high levels of innovation with effective IT adoption are more likely to achieve holistic sustainability outcomes, balancing profitability, social responsibility, and environmental stewardship (Udoka & Oduro, 2022; Mishrif & Khan, 2023).

Relationship between Innovation and Sustainability

Innovation and sustainability are closely interconnected in the operations of SMEs, as innovation provides the mechanisms through which sustainable practices are implemented and enhanced. Innovation comprising product, process, and marketing innovations enables firms to improve efficiency, reduce costs, create new market opportunities, and respond proactively to environmental and social challenges (OECD, 2018; Kotler & Keller, 2021). Product innovation allows SMEs to design eco-friendly products or services that reduce resource consumption and waste, thereby enhancing environmental sustainability (Udoka & Oduro, 2022). Process innovation improves operational workflows, reduces energy usage, minimizes production waste, and ensures better compliance with environmental standards, contributing simultaneously to economic and environmental sustainability (Olaleye et al., 2024). Marketing innovation, on the other hand, enables SMEs to communicate sustainability-oriented products or services effectively, increasing consumer awareness and adoption while promoting social responsibility (Eze et al., 2022).

The integration of innovation into business processes also drives economic sustainability by increasing efficiency, lowering costs, and improving profitability. It strengthens social sustainability by fostering ethical practices, promoting stakeholder welfare, and enhancing community engagement. Similarly, innovation enhances environmental sustainability by encouraging resource-efficient operations and sustainable supply chain practices (Onwuka & Olamide, 2020). Furthermore, IT adoption acts as a moderator in this relationship. Thus, by providing digital platforms for product design, process optimization, and marketing analytics, IT strengthens the capacity of SMEs to translate innovative initiatives into measurable sustainable outcomes (Hossain et al., 2023; Yuwono et al., 2024). In essence, SMEs that integrate innovation with effective IT adoption are better equipped to achieve holistic sustainability, balancing economic growth with social responsibility and environmental stewardship.

Empirical Review

Recent empirical studies have investigated the relationship between innovation, sustainability, and IT adoption in SMEs, highlighting both direct and moderating effects. Olaleye et al. (2024) examined Nigerian SMEs and found that innovation capability significantly enhances business sustainability, with organizational resilience acting as a partial mediator. This underscores the practical role of innovation in achieving economic, social, and environmental objectives. In the same light, Alake et al. (2024) investigated business model innovation and technological capabilities in Nigerian SMEs, concluding that innovations in products and processes, supported by technology, significantly improve SMEs' resilience and sustainable performance. Omoyele et al. (2023) found that business model innovation is a key driver of

sustainable entrepreneurship, demonstrating that SMEs introducing novel products, processes, or marketing approaches achieve higher sustainability outcomes.

Mishrif and Khan (2023) explored IT adoption as a survival strategy during COVID-19, reporting that SMEs leveraging digital technologies were better able to sustain operations and implement innovative practices, highlighting the moderating role of IT in innovation and sustainability linkages. Yuwono et al. (2024) conducted a systematic review of ICT adoption in SMEs and reported that technology adoption facilitates innovation diffusion, process efficiency, and market responsiveness, directly enhancing sustainability performance. Moreover, Ardiansah et al. (2024) found that SMEs in Indonesia adopting ICT tools experienced enhanced operational efficiency and sustainable performance, with perceived usefulness and compatibility of technology significantly affecting adoption levels. Furthermore, Onyemaobi and Ifere (2024) examined manufacturing SMEs in Nigeria, showing that innovation practices positively influence economic, social, and environmental sustainability, accounting for approximately 45% of variance in sustainable outcomes. Similarly, Udoka and Oduro (2022) investigated SMEs across Nigeria and Ghana and confirmed that innovation positively impacts sustainability, while emphasizing the potential of IT adoption to strengthen this relationship. These studies collectively indicate that innovation (product, process, and marketing) is a critical predictor of sustainability in SMEs.

Research Gaps

Despite the growing recognition of the role of innovation and IT adoption in enhancing SME performance, several gaps remain in the Nigerian context. First, most Nigerian SME studies emphasize profitability and growth rather than holistic sustainability outcomes. Second, while IT adoption is recognized as an enabler of innovation, few studies have examined how IT adoption strengthens the link between innovation and sustainability in emerging economies. Third, few studies have simultaneously examined all three dimensions of innovation (product, process, marketing) alongside all three pillars of sustainability (economic, social, environmental), particularly within SMEs in Imo State. Lastly, as observed from literature, there is a paucity of empirical data on context-specific evidence from South-Eastern Nigeria, particularly Imo State, despite its high SME concentration. This creates a significant knowledge gap regarding how innovation and IT adoption together influence sustainable business performance in this regional context. Addressing these gaps, this study investigates the moderating effect of IT adoption on the relationship between innovation and sustainable business performance of SMEs in Imo State, providing comprehensive insights for managers and policymakers seeking to enhance SME sustainability.

Methodology

This study adopted a correlational research design to examine the relationship between innovation and the sustainability of small and medium enterprises (SMEs) in Imo State, and to test the moderating effect of information technology (IT) adoption. The population comprised 1,886 registered SMEs in Imo State, obtained from the Imo State Ministry of Commerce and Industry (2024). A sample size of 329 SMEs was determined using Taro Yamane's (1973) formula at a 5% margin of error. A stratified proportional random sampling technique was employed to ensure fair representation across the sectors (manufacturing, services, Agriculture, trading) and the three senatorial zones (Owerri, Orlu and Okigwe) in Imo State. Out of the 329 distributed questionnaires, 291 were correctly completed and returned, yielding an effective response rate of 88.4 %. The instrument used was a structured questionnaire based on existing validated scales.

Content validity was ensured through expert review by three academics specializing in innovation and SME studies. A pilot test with 30 SMEs outside the sample yielded Cronbach’s alpha coefficients above 0.70 for all constructs, indicating acceptable internal consistency. The variables were measured on 3 items each while the responses were rated on a five-point Likert scale (1=Strongly Disagree to 5=Strongly Agree). The study adopted descriptive and inferential statistics in analyzing the data using SPSS (Version 26). Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation) were used to summarize the responses for all variables. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient tested the relationships between innovation dimensions (product, process, marketing and the measures of sustainability (economic, social, environment). Zero-Order Partial Correlation examined the moderating effect of IT adoption on these relationships. The tests were set at 0.05 significance level.

Results and Discussion of Findings

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Variables

Variables/Dimensions	N	Mean(M)	Standard Deviation(SD)	Interpretation (Mean)
Product Innovation	291	3.93	0.64	High
Process Innovation	291	3.79	0.67	High
Marketing Innovation	291	3.88	0.59	High
IT Adoption	291	3.92	0.65	High
Economic Sustainability	291	3.86	0.72	High
Social Sustainability	291	3.74	0.66	High
Environmental Sustainability	291	3.83	0.68	High

Source: Field Survey, 2025 and SPSS Version 26.0

Table 1 depicts the descriptive statistics of the study variables: innovation and its dimensions (product, process and marketing); the moderating variable (IT Adoption) and sustainability and its measures (economic, social and environmental) with their various mean values and standard deviations. The mean scores (3.74 to 3.93) indicate that innovation practices, sustainability measures, and IT adoption levels among SMEs in Imo State are generally high, implying active engagement with innovative and sustainable practices facilitated by technology. Also, SD values (0.59 to 0.72) depicts low variability meaning opinions are largely consistent.

Table 2: Correlation Matrix of Product Innovation and Measures of Sustainability

Variable		Economic Sustainability	Social Sustainability	Environmental Sustainability
Product Innovation	Correlation Coefficient(r)	0.697**	0.685**	0.677**
	P-value	0.000	0.002	0.001
	N	291	291	291

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Survey, 2025 and SPSS Version 26.0

Table 2 shows that product innovation has strong positive significant association with economic ($r = 0.697$; $p=0.000$); social ($r = 0.685$; $p=0.002$) and environmental ($r = 0.677$; $p=0.001$) sustainability respectively at 0.05 significant level. Consequently, the below stated null hypotheses ($H0_1$; $H0_2$ and $H0_3$) were rejected and their alternate hypotheses were accepted. This infers that significant correlation exist between innovation and sustainability of SMEs in Imo State.

$H0_1$: There is no significant relationship between product innovation and economic sustainability of SMEs in Imo State.

$H0_2$: There is no significant association between product innovation and social sustainability of SMEs in Imo State.

$H0_3$: There is no significant correlation between product innovation and environmental sustainability of SMEs in Imo State.

Table 3: Correlation Matrix of Process Innovation and Measures of Sustainability

Variable		Economic Sustainability	Social Sustainability	Environmental Sustainability
Process Innovation	Correlation Coefficient(r)	0.742**	0.683**	0.664**
	P-value	0.000	0.001	0.003
	N	291	291	291

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Survey, 2025 and SPSS Version 26.0

Table 3 reveals that process innovation has strong positive significant relationship with economic ($r = 0.742$; $p=0.000$); social ($r = 0.683$; $p=0.001$) and environmental ($r = 0.664$; $p=0.003$) sustainability respectively 0.05 significant level. Thus, the below stated null hypotheses ($H0_4$; $H0_5$ and $H0_6$) were rejected and their alternate hypotheses were accepted.

This implies that significant association exist between innovation and sustainability of SMEs in Imo State.

H0₄: There is no significant association between process innovation and economic sustainability of SMEs in Imo State.

H0₅: There is no significant link between process innovation and social sustainability of SMEs in Imo State.

H0₆: There is no significant relationship between process innovation and environmental sustainability of SMEs in Imo State.

Table 4: Correlation Matrix of Marketing Innovation and Measures of Sustainability

Variable		Economic Sustainability	Social Sustainability	Environmental Sustainability
Marketing Innovation	Correlation	0.803**	0.721**	0.698**
	P-value	0.000	0.001	0.001
	N	291	291	291

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Survey, 2025 and SPSS Version 26.0

Table 4 indicates that marketing innovation has very strong positive significant association with economic ($r = 0.803$; $p=0.000$) and strong positive significant association with social ($r = 0.721$; $p=0.001$) and environmental ($r = 0.698$; $p=0.001$) sustainability respectively 0.05 significant level. Based on the above result, the below stated null hypotheses (H0₇; H0₈and H0₉) were rejected and their alternate hypotheses were accepted. This means that that there are significant link between innovation and sustainability of SMEs in Imo State.

H0₇: There is no significant correlation between marketing innovation and economic sustainability of SMEs in Imo State.

H0₈: There is no significant association between marketing innovation and social sustainability of SMEs in Imo State.

H0₉: There is no significant link between marketing innovation and environmental sustainability of SMEs in Imo State.

Table 5: Moderating Effect of IT Adoption (Zero-Order Partial Correlation) on the Relationship between Innovation and Sustainability

Correlation Type	Innovation-Sustainability	Interpretation
Zero-order(without moderator)	0.646**	Moderate strong positive relationship
Partial correlation(controlling for IT Adoption)	0.758**	Relationship strengthened after controlling for IT Adoption

** Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Field Survey, 2025 and SPSS Version 26.0

From table 5 above, illustrates when IT adoption is controlled the correlation between innovation and sustainability increases from 0.646 to 0.758. This implies IT adoption enhances (moderates positively) the relationship between innovation and sustainability. A positive moderation means that SMEs with higher IT adoption achieve stronger sustainability outcomes from their innovation activities. Based on the result, we reject the below H_{010} and accept the alternate hypothesis, which shows that IT adoption significantly moderates the relationship between innovation and sustainability.

H_{010} : IT adoption does not significantly moderate the relationship between innovation and sustainability of SMEs in Imo State.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study reveal consistently strong and statistically significant correlations across economic, social, and environmental sustainability dimensions. Product innovation demonstrated strong positive correlations with economic ($r = 0.697, p=0.000 < .05$), social ($r = 0.685, p=0.002 < .05$), and environmental sustainability ($r = 0.677, p=0.001 < .05$). This indicates that SMEs that introduce new products or significantly improve existing ones tend to perform better across multiple sustainability indicators. This finding aligns with Al-Ansari et al. (2021), which revealed that product innovation significantly enhances sustainability outcomes. Similarly, Danso et al. (2020) confirmed that product innovation fosters environmental and social sustainability by promoting resource-efficient offerings. Similarly, process innovation also showed strong positive relationships with economic ($r = 0.742, p = 0.000 < .05$), social ($r = 0.683, p=0.001 < .05$), and environmental sustainability ($r = 0.664, p=0.003 < .05$). This suggests that SMEs’ adoption of improved production methods, digital workflows, and efficient operation techniques significantly boosts their overall sustainability. This outcome corresponds with Salisu and Bakar (2020), who observed that process innovation improves operational efficiency and directly strengthen both financial and non-financial sustainability of SMEs.

Likewise, Oduro (2021) found that innovations in production processes reduce waste and improve environmental performance among SMEs. Furthermore, marketing innovation recorded the strongest correlations with all sustainability measures: economic ($r = 0.803, p =$

0.000 < .05), social ($r = 0.721$, $p = 0.001 < .05$), and environmental sustainability ($r = 0.698$, $p = 0.001 < .05$). This demonstrates that adopting new marketing strategies such as digital promotion, branding, and revised pricing models has the most substantial influence on SME sustainability. This finding is consistent with Al Barwari et al. (2025), whose study confirmed that marketing innovation improves economic and social resilience in SMEs. Similarly, Nguyen and Luu (2021) found that digital marketing innovation fosters environmental responsibility through efficient communication and reduced material usage. Lastly, findings provide empirical support for both the Resource-Based View (RBV) and the Dynamic Capabilities Theory (DCT) in explaining how innovation drives the sustainability of SMEs in Imo State, with IT adoption strengthening these relationships. In line with RBV, the study confirms that innovation equips firms with strategic resources that enhance profitability, strengthen stakeholder relationships, and improve environmental compliance. The results thus reinforce the RBV assumption that unique innovation capabilities serve as internal strengths that determine long-term firm sustainability.

The findings also closely align with the assumptions of the Dynamic Capabilities Theory (DCT). DCT argues that in rapidly changing environments, firms must continually reconfigure their resources and processes to remain competitive. The significant effect of IT adoption as a moderating variable supports the idea that digital tools enhance SMEs' ability to sense market opportunities, seize innovation potential, and reconfigure operations for sustainable outcomes. The strengthening effect of IT adoption shows that SMEs that integrate IT are better able to adapt, innovate, and maintain sustainability in dynamic conditions. Thus, the study validates DCT by demonstrating that technological capability enhances the impact of innovation on sustainability. Collectively, RBV explains why innovation drives sustainability, while DCT explains how IT adoption enhances SMEs' ability to deploy and reconfigure innovative resources effectively. Together, the theories provide a comprehensive understanding of the mechanisms through which innovation and digital capability support sustainable SME development in Imo State.

Conclusion

This study examined the moderating effect of information technology (IT) adoption on the relationship between innovation and sustainability of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in Imo State, Nigeria. Based on responses from 291 SMEs, the findings indicate that product, process, and marketing innovations significantly enhance the economic, social, and environmental dimensions of sustainability. The results further reveal that IT adoption exerts a moderating influence, reducing the direct effect of innovation on sustainability when controlled, suggesting that technological integration changes how innovation outcomes manifest in firm performance. However, the moderation outcome implies that the benefits of innovation depend on how effectively firms utilize technology to support innovation implementation, customer engagement, and process automation. The study concludes that innovation and IT adoption jointly foster sustainable business models that can help Nigerian SMEs thrive in volatile environments.

Recommendations

The under listed recommendations were put forward for adoption by SMEs Owners and their managers:

1. Adopt relevant IT solutions by integrating appropriate IT tools and systems to complement their innovation practices, enhancing efficiency and decision-making.

2. Develop innovation-focused strategies by deliberately plan and implement product, process, and marketing innovations to improve sustainable business performance.
3. Promote employee training and IT literacy on the effective use of IT resources alongside innovation initiatives, ensuring maximum impact on sustainability outcomes.
4. Monitor and evaluate sustainability outcomes by regularly assessing economic, social, and environmental performance aimed at identifying areas for improvement and aligning innovation and IT adoption with long-term sustainability goals.

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Environmental Sustainability and Sustainable Development: Ethical Perspective

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Abstract

This work views environment as a concept more than mere surroundings or external conditions. Most philosophers consider the said view as peripheral; a modern man's concept which is materialistic. Our research attempts to recover the deeper meaning of environment lost by modernism. The deeper meaning of environment suggests that it is actively alive; not necessarily tangible, and therefore not seen as mere externality. The materialist, external, modern or surface meaning of environment suggests a confrontation between the human and nonhuman world. Against this backdrop, this paper, in accordance with Leopold urges us to consider our place in, as opposed to our control over, and our duty to, rather than merely our use of, the natural world. This implicates the ethical or moral obligation of man towards his environment. He must not like men of the modern era merely think of confronting and conquering his environment. Man must naturalize man and humanize nature as well – because man is part and parcel of the environment. He is just but one of the citizens within the biotic community. This illustrates the indisputable fact that there exists a mutual relationship between humans and the environment; while man relies on the environment for resources, the latter relies on the rational man for care. This interdependence is critical for the survival of both man and the environment. This work adopts dialectical polemics method in defense of the above human-environment deep relationship. Many approaches have been proposed in an attempt to mitigate environmental challenges. However, this paper prefers ecocentric approach which sees to a holistic sustenance of both human and nonhuman world. It equally suggests proper enlightenment and good environmental policies to assist in the project of sustainable development.

Keywords: Environment, Ethics, Biotic Community, Sustainable Development, Environmental Policy and Sustainability.

Introduction

Ethics is deeply intertwined with the preservation and protection of our environment. In its essence, Ethics involves principles and values that guide individuals and society in making moral decisions. When applied to environmental issues, ethical considerations become paramount in ensuring the sustainability and well-being of our planet.

The relationship between ethics and the environment has become increasingly important in recent years. As the world grapples with the challenges of climate change, pollution, and biodiversity loss, it is clear that our actions have a significant impact on the planet. Morality (Ethics) plays a crucial role in shaping our attitudes and behaviors towards the environment, and it is essential to explore the principles and practices that guide our interactions with the natural world (Rolston 1–3).

Sustainable development, which refers to the practice of meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs, is very crucial. This is because studies have shown that human work and activities have tremendous

impact on the environment. In fact, human activities are said to be the major cause of environmental degradation and disaster (Nkemjika 33).

In the same vein, Collins-Chobanian observes that many studies link the environmental crisis to a general shortage of ethics. In her words: “The historically unparalleled levels of consumption and the consequent environmental degradation have brought into question the earth’s carrying capacity. Many assert that without reevaluations of and drastic changes in our ways of life, we will not come out of this crisis” (161).

In other to sustain the earth, our common home, Pope Francis (late) proposed the concept known as “integral ecology” (54). Similarly, this paper suggests *sustainable development* as a panacea to environmental crisis bedeviling our common home. Again, this can be achieved via a holistic approach – where through right education, humans as rational beings are meant to understand their responsibility towards the environment and hence, apply, when necessary, the anthropocentric, biocentric and/or ecocentric approaches; or what Pope Francis called “integral ecology” – which translates into integral development; an integrated approach that strives to not only restore the dignity of man, but equally protect nature, in other words, the environment (Pope Francis 91).

This is because the biotic community is, according to Leopold’s “Land Ethic,” not only made up of humans, rather, trees, lands, and animals also constitute the ecological community; and as such worthy of respect (*A Sand County Almanac and Sketches Here and There* 209). Due to the interconnectedness of the environment, Carson argues that things in the natural world are connected. Damage in any citizen of the biotic community has far-reaching consequences for the entire ecosystem (56). Lastly, this paper recommends the application of the above-mentioned holistic approach by individuals, governments or states – through right and sustainable environmental policies for a better environmental management.

Environment: Etymology and Meaning

Environment is derived from the Old French word “environ” which means “in circuit” or “turning around” (Cheng 200). It is derived from the prefix “en” (in) and “viron” (circle or circuit). Environment, in essence, refers to the surroundings or external conditions that influence an organism or ecosystem. However, in order to differentiate Tao’s conception of environment with that of the modern conception, Cheng points out that the latter is materialistic; lacking essential depth in its conception of environment. He avers:

... it is clear that the essential depth meaning of environment was lost in modern man’s conception of environment. The modern man’s conception of environment is founded on the surface meaning of environment, which is typified by technology and science; with its underlying philosophy of modern-day materialism The concept of environment of modern man was very much objectified, mechanized, rigidified, dehumanized, and possibly even de-enlivened, and so de-environmentalized. Environment is no longer an environment at all; environment becomes simply “the surroundings,” the physical periphery, the material conditions and the transient circumstances. The environment is conceived as passive deadwood, and very often as only visible and tangible externalia. (201).

Contrary to the above, the deeper meaning of environment suggests that it is actively alive, not necessarily visible or tangible, and therefore cannot be seen as a mere externality. Furthermore, environment, according to Cheng, cannot be treated as a transient material object or tool. “Environment is more than the visible, more than the tangible, more than the

external, more than a matter of quantified period of time or a spread of space. It has a deep structure as well as a deep process, as the concept of Tao indicates” (201).

The materialistic, external, modern or surface meaning of environment suggests a confrontation between the human and nonhuman world. Whereas the deep concept of environment suggests “... the internal relation of man to his surroundings based upon an integrative interdependence and a harmony between man and the world” (Cheng 201). In consonance with Rene Descartes, the father of modern philosophy; “the nonhuman world is to be rationally studied, researched, and exploited for the maximum utility of serving man. This will to conquer and dominate nature (environment) is, of course, premised on the externality of nature to man ...” (Cheng 201).

Nature is holistic. Man is part of nature. In other words, he is part and parcel of environment. “To conquer nature (i.e., environment) and exploit it is a form of self-destruction and self-abasement for man” (202). Man must naturalize man and humanize nature as well. He must treat nature as his equal. Man is a citizen within the biotic and/or ecological family – with the attendant right and obligation towards his environment and its sustainability. This implies that “there is a mutually dependent relationship between humans and the environment. Humans rely on the environment for resources like water and food, while the environment relies on humans to care for and respect it. This interdependence is critical for the survival of both humans and the environment”(Nkemjika 33).

In other words, “The earth (environment) provides humans with the resources they need to live and flourish, and humans have a responsibility to care for and protect it in return” (Nkemjika 34). *The Catechism of the Catholic Church* has a similar view: All men and women have the right to use the goods of the earth and to enjoy its fruits. They have a duty correspondingly to their role as intelligent and free beings to use these goods responsibly (2415).The above implicates the moral or ethical perspective of environmental sustainability – which is the crux of this work.

Ethics

Ethics is the branch of philosophy that deals with moral principles and values. It involves the study of what is right and wrong, good and bad, and how we ought to live our lives. Ethics provides a framework for making decisions and taking actions that are guided by moral principles, such as respect, fairness, and responsibility. In the context of the environment, Ethics helps us to consider the impact of our actions on the planet and its inhabitants, and to make choices that promote sustainability and conservation (Rolston 5–6).

Ethics encompasses a set of moral principles that govern human behavior and interactions. It involves distinguishing right from wrong, good from bad, and just from unjust actions. In the context of Environmental Ethics, individuals and societies are called upon to consider the impact of their actions on the natural world and future generations (Weiss 24–26).

What is Environmental Ethics?

Environmental Ethics is a subfield of ethics that focuses specifically on the moral relationship between humans and the natural world. It explores the ethical principles and values that guide our interactions with the environment, and it challenges us to consider the long-term consequences of our actions. Environmental Ethics encompasses a range of perspectives, including anthropocentric (human-centered), biocentric (life-centered), and ecocentric (ecosystem-centered) approaches (Rolston 10–13). It also draws on various disciplines, including philosophy, science, and policy, to develop a comprehensive understanding of our responsibilities towards the environment (Agyeman et al. 12–15).

Leopold's "Land Ethic" and the Biotic Community

Before now, ethical principles were not extended to the environment. According to Leopold; "There is no ethic dealing with man's relation to land and to the animals and plants which grow upon it. Land ... is still property. The land-relation is still strictly economic, entailing privileges but not obligations" (Leopold, "The Land Ethic" 166; qtd. in Collins-Chobanian 161). The extension of ethics to the land (i.e., man and his environment) is considered by Leopold as an evolutionary possibility and ecological necessity.

Aldo Leopold's *A Sand County Almanac* (first published in 1949), often regarded as the genesis of contemporary Western Environmental Ethics, urges humans to consider their place in, as opposed to their control over, and their duties to, rather than merely their use of the natural world. Leopold provided the "land ethic" as a guide in determining the moral justification of our actions in relation to our environment. "The land ethic places the preservation of the biotic community's integrity, stability, and beauty at the center of moral concern" (qtd. in May et al. 165). Leopold's Land Ethic runs thus: "A thing is right when it tends to preserve the integrity, stability, and beauty of the biotic community. It is wrong when it tends otherwise" (*A Sand County Almanac* 262). The above ethic recognizes the interrelated nature of ecosystems, which are composed of living and non-living entities;

... both living and nonliving matter have inherent value and 'standing' for ethical consideration. This view is often called 'deep ecology' and is also known as the 'biocentric' or 'ecocentric' approach. Deep ecology broadens our ethical duties even further than a sentientist approach does. From the viewpoint of deep ecology, the entire ecosystem has intrinsic value and may not be used (as an instrument) to merely further specific interests. Under this approach, we are obliged to take the entire ecosystem into account as an object of moral concern while pursuing our human interests. (Collins-Chobanian 161-162).

In short, "Leopold argues for a 'land ethic' which carries duties to the environment, including duties to love and respect the land and its (inherent) value." Unfortunately, since 1949 – when Leopold published his magnum opus, many states are yet to extend ethical principles to the environment; "the environment still lacks ethical standing" (Collins-Chobanian 162).

Expounding on the concept of biotic (or ecological) community, Leopold points out that "all ethics so far evolved rest upon a simple premise: that the individual is a member of a community of interdependent parts." The individual's instincts prompt him to compete for his place in the community, but his ethics prompt him also to cooperate (perhaps in order that there may be a place to compete for). Leopold's land ethic in relation to the biotic community "enlarges the boundaries of the community to include soils, waters, plants, and animals, or collectively: the land."

He continues; "A land ethic of course cannot prevent the alteration, management, and use of these 'resources,' but it does affirm their right to continued existence ... their continued existence in a natural state" ("The Land Ethic" 166). This implies that Leopold is not very comfortable with *uncensored* genetic modification of organisms (GMO). Leopold's land ethic changes the role of humans (*Homo sapiens*) from conqueror of the land-community to plain member and citizen of it. "It implies respect for his fellow members, and also respect for the community as such" (166). Lastly, Leopold's land ethic preaches and reflects "ecological conscience" – which "in turn reflects a conviction of individual responsibility for

the health of the land” (173). Historical evidence demonstrates that the conqueror role of man vis-à-vis his environment is self-defeating.

Major Environmental Theories

Environmental ethics, as earlier mentioned, is a branch of philosophy that explores the moral relationship between humans and the natural world. There are several environmental theories that have been developed to guide our interactions with the environment. However, this paper only considers the following major three:

Anthropocentrism

“Anthropocentrism asserts that we have ethical duties only to humans, thus precluding direct duties to the environment” (Collins-Chobanian 161). It is a human-centered approach that prioritizes human needs and interests above those of the environment. This theory holds that the environment has value only insofar as it serves human purposes. Anthropocentrism has been criticized for its narrow focus on human interests and its failure to consider the intrinsic value of non-human entities (Rolston 31–33). Pope Francis stresses further: “that human beings are the measure of all things (anthropocentrism), is the root cause of environmental degradation” (qtd. in Nkemjika 34).

Biocentrism

This is a life-centered approach that recognizes the inherent value of all living beings. This theory holds that all living organisms have a right to exist and flourish, regardless of their utility to humans. Biocentrism emphasizes the importance of preserving biodiversity and promoting the well-being of all living beings (Rolston 40–43).

Ecocentrism

Ecocentrism is an ecosystem-centered approach that prioritizes the health and integrity of ecosystems. This theory holds that ecosystems have inherent value and should be protected for their own sake, rather than solely for human benefit. Ecocentrism emphasizes the importance of preserving ecosystem services and promoting ecological sustainability (Rolston 50–52).

Some Environmental Issues and Challenges

The environment faces numerous challenges and issues. Some of them are:

Climate Change

Climate Change is one of the most pressing environmental issues of our time. It refers to the warming of the planet due to the increasing levels of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere. Climate change has severe consequences, including rising sea levels, more frequent natural disasters, and altered ecosystems (Agyeman et al. 56–58). Epstein and Ferber are of similar opinion:

... issues like climate change, which includes global warming, rising sea levels, extreme weather events, and changing weather patterns. These result from the excessive use of fossil fuels, which bring about a great concentration of greenhouse gases (carbon dioxide, methane, nitrogen oxides, and others). Exposure to these atmospheric pollutants produces a broad spectrum of health hazards, especially for the poor countries of the world, and this causes millions of premature deaths. (qtd. in Nkemjika 33)

Biodiversity Loss

This refers to the decline in the variety of species and ecosystems on the planet. This loss can have severe consequences, including reduced ecosystem services, decreased crop yields, and loss of medicinal resources (Rolston 60–61). In the words of Nkemjika: “... there has been a loss of biodiversity and natural habitats as a result of industrialization. Deforestation for industry and factories has left the soil vulnerable to desertification and erosion” (33-34).

Pollution

Pollution refers to the release of harmful substances into the environment. This can include air pollution, water pollution, and soil pollution. Pollution can have severe consequences, including human health problems and environmental degradation (Agyeman et al. 63–65); “... increased water and air pollution and depletion of natural resources are unarguably epidemic” (Nkemjika 34).

Resource Depletion

Resource Depletion refers to the overuse or degradation of natural resources, including water, soil, and minerals. This can have severe consequences, including reduced economic productivity and increased poverty (Weiss 40–42). Citing Epstein and Ferber, Nkemjika (in his discourse on human work and activities in relation to environmental degradation) buttresses: antithetically, ours is a generation where it seems that human work and activities have done more harm than good to the biotic community (33). Epstein and Ferber observe that humans currently use resources available in their environment in excessive, degrading and unsustainable manner – which has resulted to harmful environmental situations. These situations, according to them are very serious and frightening (qtd. in Nkemjika 33).

According to Nkemjika: “... work itself is not bad, but excessive plundering of the natural world (i.e., environment) to meet selfish needs is especially damaging. The same can be said about industrialization. It has brought many benefits, but it is harmful when it becomes the sole focus of development” (34). On this note, while promoting work, science and technology together with their economic gains, Pope John Paul II cautions workers (scientists, technologists, etc.) to protect the environment (qtd. in Nkemjika 34).

Role of Ethics in the Formulation of Environmental Policy

Ethics plays a crucial role in shaping environmental policy and decision-making processes at local, national, and global levels. Environmental policies reflect society's values and ethical considerations regarding the use of resources, conservation efforts, pollution control, and sustainable development. By integrating ethical principles into environmental policy, governments and organizations can prioritize long-term sustainability, biodiversity conservation, and the health of ecosystems (Weiss 88–90). Ethics can inform policy decisions in several ways:

Precautionary Principle and Sustainability Approach

Ethics encourages policymakers to take a precautionary approach when dealing with environmental issues, considering the potential long-term consequences of their actions. Concerning sustainability, Ethics promotes sustainable practices that balance human needs with environmental protection, ensuring that natural resources are managed responsibly (Agyeman et al. 72–73).

Justice, Equity and Accountability

Ethics highlights the importance of justice and equity in environmental policy, recognizing that environmental degradation often disproportionately affects vulnerable populations

(Agyeman et al. 88–91). Collins-Chobanian discussed this via her concept of “Environmental Racism” – which, according to her, “is the intentional targeting of communities where people of color live, for both the generation and storage of toxic waste” (163). She condemned this practice in strong terms. On the question of accountability, Ethics emphasizes the need for accountability in environmental decision-making, ensuring that policymakers are responsible for their actions and their impact on the environment (Weiss 93–94).

Sustainable Development and Environmental Decision Making

Sustainable development refers to the practice of meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Environmental decision making is critical to achieving sustainable development, as it requires balancing human needs with environmental protection. Environmental decision making requires a careful consideration of the potential impacts of human activities on the environment (Weiss 102–104).

In consonance with Nkemjika, this paper calls on political systems (locally and internationally) to realize their crucial role of promoting integral ecology and sustainable development, which includes “creating policies that support the common good, protecting the environment, and addressing issues like poverty, climate change, and social justice.” All hands must be on deck; individually, we must adopt the attitude of “affective and altruistic engagement with our environment in order to forestall degradation of any sort” (Nkemjika 34). Human activities should not cause harm to the environment (our common home) or threaten the future of the biotic community.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The integration of ethics and environmental care is essential for fostering a harmonious relationship between humans and nature. By upholding ethical values, such as respect, responsibility, and stewardship, we can create a more sustainable world for current and future generations. It is our collective moral duty to protect and preserve the environment, guided by ethical principles and a deep sense of care and respect for the natural world. Ethics play a crucial role in shaping our attitudes and behaviors towards the environment. By exploring the principles and practices of Environmental Ethics, we can develop a deeper understanding of our responsibilities towards the planet and its inhabitants. As we move forward, it is essential to prioritize Ethics in environmental policy, ensuring that our decisions promote sustainability, justice, and accountability (Rolston 110–112; Weiss 120–122). This research, like Leopold, preaches ecological conscience and thus recommends as follows:

Farmers should be encouraged to adopt not only the practices that economically profits them alone, rather, they are encouraged to adopt farming practices that benefits the ecological community – which in other words, sustains our environment in the long run. A good example is the practice of taking the grass to the cattle instead of the other way round; for this will also curb the incessant clash between farmers and herders in our country, Nigeria.

There should be serious educational enlightenment on the gains of environmental sustainability before dishing out laws or policies which are equally essential. Here, expert advice is required by environmentalists and relevant stakeholders. Also, the environmental laws and policies should be impartial; driven not by selfish interests, but should include obligation – i.e., duty to the environment. For example: in order to check flooding, every household, especially in the cities, must not cement the whole compound; a portion must be interlocked or grassed.

The environmental policies should include incentives for individuals and farmers who strive to observe their duties to the environment. In fact, Governments should support farmers in this regard in order to reduce economic loss. However, there should be a balance between the economic and social needs of the society vis-à-vis environmental sustainability. Here, Environmental Ethics has a major role to play.

In fact, the study (or knowledge) of Environmental Ethics should be made compulsory not only for students, but also for the staff of environmental and agricultural institutions like ours – where we should be taught for instance that:

... a system of conservation based solely on economic self-interest is hopelessly lopsided. It tends to ignore, and thus eventually to eliminate, many elements in the land (or biotic) community that lack commercial value, but that are ... essential to its healthy functioning. It assumes, falsely, ... that the economic parts of the biotic clock will function without the uneconomic parts. It tends to relegate to government many functions eventually too large, too complex, or too widely dispersed to be performed by government. (Leopold, "The Land Ethic" 170)

While the government must play her role, an ethical obligation on the part of private enterprises and individuals regarding environmental sustainability is a very visible remedy. Man should see himself not necessarily as a conqueror of nature; rather, he should see himself as a biotic citizen in ecological community. This will change his attitude towards his environment – which he now *values* greatly. By value, we do not mean the limited economic value, but value in a broader, philosophical sense. He must examine environmental problems holistically in terms of "what is ethically and esthetically right, as well as what is economically expedient." In the context of our discourse, "a thing is right when it tends to preserve the integrity, stability, and beauty of the biotic community" (Leopold, "The Land Ethic" 175). Ecocentric (not necessarily anthropocentric) approach is therefore, the right approach to environmental sustainability and sustainable development.

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Environmental Sustainability and Economic Growth in Nigeria

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Abstract

This research investigated the nexus between environmental sustainability and economic growth in Nigeria using quarterly data from 2010 to 2024. The industrialization drive of Nigeria has given rise to issues of environmental sustainability due to climate change. This study used real gross domestic product as a measure of economic growth while the environmental sustainability variables were greenhouse gas emission, bank credit to industrial sector, government capital expenditure on environment and industrial solid waste. The data were sourced from the World Development Indicator and the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin. The data were analyzed using the error correction model. The result indicated that greenhouse gas emission had positive but not significant effect on economic growth while bank credit to industrial sector increased economic growth significantly. Further findings revealed that government capital expenditure on environment and industrial solid wastes have negative effects on economic growth of Nigeria. The study concludes that Nigeria is on the right track towards achieving environmental sustainability and long run economic growth. However, the negative consequence of industrial solid waste on the economy is a serious cause for worry as Nigeria advances in her industrial development drive. It was recommended among other that Nigeria should pursue clean energy sources with the promotion of green financing initiatives in order to safeguard the environment and also advance economic growth of the country.

Keywords: Economic Growth, Environmental Sustainability, Government Capital Expenditure, Greenhouse Gas, Industrial Solid Waste.

Introduction

The United Nations reeled out sustainable development goals in 2016 which aims at pursuing sustainable development which has become the bedrock of every developmental effort of governments across various countries of the world. In Nigeria, the pursuit of environmental sustainability is of immense importance due to entrenched challenges of poverty, income disparity, and limited access to basic services. Nigeria faces socio-economic challenges, including high unemployment rates, income inequality, and inadequate infrastructure and at the same time the country is being plagued by environmental issues like deforestation, pollution, and climate vulnerability which worsen societal disparities (Nneka et al., 2023). The pursuit of rapid economic growth often comes at the cost of environmental degradation, posing significant challenges to achieving sustainability of the environment (Omisore, 2018). Despite the nation's rich natural resources and potential for economic expansion, the absence of comprehensive environmental sustainability measures has raised concerns regarding its impact on economic growth (Ofori *et al.*, 2023).

Over the past decades, Nigeria's economic growth has largely depended on fossil fuels, particularly crude oil, as the major source of energy. However, this dependence has resulted

in adverse environmental consequences, especially the emission of carbon dioxide, which contributes significantly to global warming and acid rain (Okonkwoet *al.*, 2021; Maji, Sulaimanet *al.*, 2019). The need to balance economic growth with environmental sustainability has increased the urgency to adopt other forms of energy or energy alternatives. Nigeria's overdependence on fossil fuels for energy generation has not only contributed to environmental degradation but has also limited the country's ability to meet the growing energy demand of its population (Okoh and Omachi, 2025). The increased threat of environmental degradation in Nigeria undermines productivity, hinders private investment, and constrains economic growth. Furthermore, the environmental issues exacerbate the vulnerability of Nigeria's economy, highlighting the urgent need for economic sustainability.

There is problem of insufficient knowledge in the area of environmental sustainability and economic growth from the economic perspective. For example, while studies in this area have focused more attention on renewable energy, carbon emission and their effect on the economy, there is a seemingly lack of research efforts and attention on greenhouse gas emission, government capital expenditure on environmental sustainability and industrial solid waste management. These three variables mentioned have been confirmed in various literature to have profound effect on the economy when properly managed (Tenaw & Beyene, 2021; World Bank, 2022; Zhang, Zhao, Li & Li, 2018). Economic growth come with several challenges in form of externalities such as environmental degradation greenhouse effect and various kinds of solid waste pollution thereby leading to growth with very high social costs. In order to properly address issues of environmental sustainability, there must be a sufficient knowledge of the extent of environmental sustainability already in practice and how they have affected the economy. This will help to drive sustainability policies that will ensure long term economic growth. Thus, this present study serves this purpose by addressing the problem of insufficient knowledge in this area of study.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to analyze the effect of environmental sustainability on economic growth of Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- evaluate the effect of green house emissions on economic growth in Nigeria;
- evaluate how access to bank credits by industrial sector influences economic growth in Nigeria;
- Analyze how government capital expenditure on environmental sustainability affects economic growth in Nigeria;
- Investigate the extent to which industrial solid waste has affected economic growth of Nigeria.

Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses will be tested in the course of the research:

H₀₁: There is no significant impact of greenhouse emissions on economic growth of Nigeria.

H₀₂: There is no significant impact of bank credit to industrial sector on economic growth of Nigeria.

H₀₃: Government capital expenditure on environmental sustainability has no significant effect on economic growth of Nigeria.

H₀₄: Industrial solid waste has no significant impact on economic growth of Nigeria.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

The concept of sustainability was formulated at the first united nation conference on environment in 1972, but it has only really taken shape since 1987 (World Bank, 2022). Environmental sustainability is holistic and all-encompassing and ensures that growth of economy does not destabilize environmental order. Jhingan (2006) in his 36th edition of economic development and planning (page 22ii) maintained that sustainable development aims at the creation of sustainable improvements in the quality of life for all as the principle goal of development policy. He stated that sustainability must be one which will improve economy, the natural resources and environment, physical capital without making future generation worse off. Industrial growth and development without regulations leads to water air, pollutions soil degradation, loss of bio diversity etc. (Jhingan, 2006).

Greenhouse gas emission is defined as the outpour of gases into the atmosphere which traps heat and exacerbates global warming and change in climate (Feng, Shafiei, Foo & Yefeng, 2024). Gases under this category include carbon dioxide, methane, nitrous oxide etc. Greenhouse gases have potential damaging effect on the environment through rising atmospheric temperature and disrupting natural weather conditions. With rapid industrialization comes the resultant effect of possible threat to environmental sustainability because industrial wastes increases with increased industrial production (Manal, 2025). Governments of developing countries including Nigeria have committed funds towards ensuring sustainable environment and it estimated that globally, about 1.5% to 1.7% of total gross domestic product have been committed to environmental sustainability. In Nigeria, this figure is still well below 1% as at end of 2024 (CBN, 2024).

Theoretical Review

The theory of environmental sustainability states that human needs should be balanced with the long term health and stability of the ecosystem within which humans interact. Jodha (1990) quoted by Grace O. Evbuomwan *et al.*, (1990) noted that environmental sustainability is the ability of a system to maintain a well-defined level of performance over time and if required, to enhance output without damaging the essential ecological integrity of the system. Environmental sustainability explains that development efforts should be undertaken in a manner that will not frustrate the ability of future generations to meet their needs. Environmental sustainability requires that the management of the environment should be in such a way that ensures that the environment and its natural resources give their optimum yield and preserved for the benefit of both present and future generations.

By relating this theory to this present research, what this theory implies is that in the process of chasing improved economic growth, environmental factors such as greenhouse gas emissions and other solid wastes should be kept at their barest level so as not to endanger the environment and future generation. Thus, it further implies economic growth with proper consideration of environmental effects and strategies put in place to mitigate these environmental effects. This research takes on the environmental sustainability variables (greenhouse gas emission, industrial solid waste, government expenditure on environment and bank credit to industrial sector) as key determinants of economic growth in order to test their effect on growth whether it is positive or negative. If these environmental sustainability

variables are positive, it implies that the theory of environmental sustainability is upheld for Nigeria. However, if they are negative, the implication is that this theory is not being upheld in the case of Nigeria.

Empirical Review

Erhun (2015) sought a sustainable approach to economic development in Nigeria. The paper discussed the best practices that can make significant contribution to the emergence of sustainable economic development in Nigeria. The study discussed the essentials to sustainable economic development, drawing on economic development best practices as well as environmental best practices to create an integration of sustainability and economic development. The study concluded that harmony between man and nature is the prerequisite for sustainable development, depicting that the development of humanity should not be on the cost of environmental health.

The study of Ndubuisi-Okolo, Anekwe and Ekwochi (2020) revealed that environmental degradation, corruption, poverty, youth restiveness, political instability, Boko Haram insurgencies were the major challenges confronting environmental sustainability and sustainable development in Nigeria. It was concluded that oil producing firms need to subject themselves to the fair requirements of the society through discharging their social responsibilities and also ensuring that the environment is adequately protected and sustained.

Ukoli (2021) studied the nexus between industrialization renewable electricity and foreign direct investment from 1980 to 2023. Results showed that the gross domestic product per capital and its square shows strong positive and negative impact on CO₂ emission respectively and CO₂ emission was found to be reduced by renewable electricity and foreign direct investment.

Sijuwola and Fadogba (2023) examined the effect of carbon emissions on inclusive growth in Nigeria using analyzed annual time series data for the period 1970 to 2022. The study employed the Autoregressive Distributed Lagged Model. The findings showed that the effect of carbon emissions on inclusive growth was positive in the short-run but inversely on the long run. Additionally, the short run effect was insignificant while the long run was significant. Carbon emissions are negatively related to inclusive growth in Nigeria.

Ajudua (2019) studied the effect of environmental degradation on economic growths in Nigeria for period 1986 – 2016 using error correction model (ECM). They found that there exist a long term relationship between environment, growth, quantity of gas flared and quantity of oil spillage which here led to environmental degradation in Nigeria in their study.

Oboro (2024) investigated environmental sustainability and economic growth with evidence from Nigeria using error correction model. The study examined the relationship between CO₂ emissions and their major determinants, including economic growth, trade openness consumptions or production activities might generate costs, which are not paid for by consumer or producer (bad goods) as a result cost are imposed on societies which are not accounted for.

Ifurueze and Igbru (2021) studied environmental degradation and economic growth, an empirical perspective from Nigeria, using sample from 2011 to 2020, time series data and Augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) test and Johansen co-integration test to evaluate the effect of foreign direct investment per capital, GDP and population density on carbon dioxide

emission. The results showed that per capita GDP and population density have significant effect on environmental degradations but foreign direct investment effect on environmental degradation show no significant effect on the environmental degradation as was measured by carbon dioxide.

Fenget *al.* (2024) explored the intricate relationship between economic development and ecological degradation in China. Fueled by the pursuit of sustainable development alongside economic growth, the study included dimensions like carbon footprint, air and water pollution, and resource consumption in thirty-three provinces of China for the period of 2005–2015. The study highlighted the trade-offs and co-benefits between environmental conservation and development, and found that sustainable clean water investments synergize with the protection of land-based ecosystems and climate action plans. The findings enhanced the understanding of China's sustainable development process, providing relevant knowledge to practitioners, policymakers, and scholars to tackle similar issues worldwide.

Samuel, Adegbola, Shittu, Falana and Obidiah (2024) studied economic growth and environmental sustainability using empirical evidence from selected African Countries. The Fixed Effect (FEM) method regression model was employed for the panel data. The analysis revealed that the coefficient of GDP growth rate was positive and statistically significant. The study concluded that economic growth contributed positively and significantly to environmental degradation through the emission of greenhouse gases but substantially declined as the economy grows further.

Oboro (2024) examined the relationships between CO₂ emissions and their major determinants, including economic growth, trade openness, industrialization, Renewable electricity and Foreign direct investment from 1980 to 2023. Results showed that the GDP per capita and its square have a strong positive and negative impact on CO₂ emissions, respectively. Their analysis also revealed an inverted U-shaped relationship between economic growth and CO₂ emissions. Trade openness, and industrialization positively affected CO₂ emissions, but long-term CO₂ emissions was found to be reduced by renewable electricity and foreign direct investment.

Manal (2024) explored the impact of renewable energy on economic transformation and sustainable development. Comprehensive literature review revealed that adopting renewable energy reduces ecological footprints and greenhouse gas emissions, promoting environmental sustainability. Specific renewable energy sources, particularly wind energy, were identified as effective catalysts for sustainable economic development. The study highlighted the significance of hydrogen as a clean energy carrier, along with its production from renewable sources, is also emphasized. The findings further underscored the crucial role of renewable energy technologies in driving economic transformation and sustainable development by enhancing environmental sustainability, stimulating economic growth.

Okoh and Omachi (2025) examined the impact of renewable energy consumption on economic growth in Nigeria from 1990 to 2024, applying the Auto-regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds testing approach and the Vector Auto-regressive (VAR) Granger causality framework. The results indicated that renewable energy consumption does not exert a statistically significant impact on economic growth in either the short or long run. Conversely, gross capital formation and foreign direct investment exhibit marginal positive effects on GDP. Renewable energy, capital formation, and FDI significantly influenced labor force dynamics. These findings suggest that despite Nigeria's renewable energy potential, its current contribution to economic performance remains limited.

Literature Gap

Evidence shows that most literature on environmental sustainability and economic growth used carbon emission (Oboro, 2024; Ifurueze & Igbru, 2021; Sijuwola & Fadogba, 2023), renewable energy (Okoh & Omachi, 2025). These studies did not incorporate the effect of greenhouse gas emissions as an environmental sustainability variable. The intervening effect of government efforts towards environmental sustainability and private sector efforts have not been recognized in the model formulation from previous studies. Hence, this creates a gap in literature which this present study intends to fill.

Methodology

This study adopts the quasi-experimental research design. This is justified based on the fact that the study establishes a relationship between a dependent variable and a set of independent variables. Also, the data are secondary data sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and World Development Indicator 2024 editions. The data were transformed into natural logarithm forms to ensure standardization and avoid spurious regression. The justification of use of the error correction model which is an off-shoot of the ordinary least square regression model is that the unit root test showed that the data were all stationary after first differencing and also cointegrated. Furthermore, the least square estimation is best, linear and unbiased and so it gives a near-true representation of what is obtainable in the real life scenario regarding the environmental sustainability variables.

Model Specification

The model is a modification of the work of Ifurueze and Igbru (2021) where-in they used foreign direct investment per capital, carbon dioxide emission and population density as independent variables while gross domestic product was the dependent variable. This present study recognizes the importance of greenhouse gas emission as an environmental sustainability variable which necessitated its inclusion in the specification as a way of modifying previous model of Ifurueze and Igbru (2021). Also, other intervening variables are included in the model which is specified as follows:

$$RGDP = f(GHG, BCR, CAX, ISW) \quad [1]$$

Where **RGDP** is real gross domestic product (in billions of naira), **GHG** is greenhouse gas emission (in metric ton), **BCR** is bank credit (in billions of naira) and **CAX** is government capital expenditure (in billions of naira), and **ISW** is industrial solid waste.

The specification in [1] above can be represented in linear econometric form as follows:

$$RGDP_t = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 GHG_t + \beta_2 BCR_t + \beta_3 CAX_t + \beta_4 ISW_t + \varepsilon_t \quad [2]$$

$$\ln RGDP_t = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \ln GHG_t + \beta_2 \ln BCR_t + \beta_3 \ln CAX_t + \beta_4 \ln ISW_t + \varepsilon_t \quad [3]$$

Where \ln is the natural logarithm sign, α_0 is the intercept of the model, β_1 to β_3 is the unknown coefficients of the model and ε_t is the stochastic error term.

The a-priori expectation is that the environmental sustainability variables should have positive and significant effect on gross domestic product i.e. $\beta_1 > 0$, $\beta_2 > 0$, $\beta_3 > 0$ and $\beta_4 > 0$.

Data Analysis

The analysis starts with the descriptive statistics of the data. The test for unit root using the Augmented Dickey Fuller test follows before the Johansen cointegration test and then the model estimation.

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	RGDP	GHG	BCR	CAX	ISW
Mean	68,185.27	150,000,000.00	16,992.91	4,134.17	17,620,000
Median	69,832.88	151,000,000.00	16,061.17	3,697.17	11,320,313
Maximum	74,911.46	157,000,000.00	29,799.85	8,472.76	45,500,000
Minimum	54,404.32	136,000,000.00	9,131.80	572.81	82,500,000
Std. Dev.	5,833.90	4,826,320.00	6,073.51	1,720.46	10,746,527
Skewness	-0.95	-1.18	0.54	0.75	1.11
Kurtosis	2.72	3.89	2.19	3.60	2.85
Jarque-Bera	9.31	15.97	4.55	6.59	12.43
Probability	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.04	0.00
Observations	60	60	60	60	60

Source: Computed by the Researcher from original data

Table 1 shows that real GDP averaged ₦68.1 trillion for the period 2010:Q1 to 2024:Q4. Within the same period, greenhouse gas emission averaged 150 million metric tons, bank credit to industrial sector and capital expenditure on environmental averaged ₦16.9 trillion and ₦4.13 trillion respectively while industrial solid waste was 17.62 million tonnes on the average. The maximum greenhouse gas emission for the period was 157 million tonnes while maximum industrial solid waste was 45.5 million tonnes. Bank credit and capital expenditure reached an all-time high of ₦29.8 trillion and ₦8.47 trillion. The standard deviation of the variables (GDP, BCR, CAX and ISW) depicts high dispersion from the mean and greater variability within the data sets. However, the standard deviation of greenhouse gas emission is low which entails that the data point is clustered closely around the mean. This creates a dissimilar data set hence the need for standardization through conversion of the data sets to natural logarithm forms.

Furthermore, the data on bank credit (BCR), capital expenditure (CAX) and industrial solid waste (ISW) are positively skewed as shown in the Skewness statistic, while data for RGDP and greenhouse gas emission (GHG) are negatively skewed. The Jarque-Bera statistics have probability values that are all less than 0.05 critical value meaning that the data come are not normally distributed hence the need to standardize the data to avoid spurious regression.

Table 2: Unit Root and Cointegration Tests

ADF test stat (<i>p-value</i>)			
Variable	Level	First difference	Order of Integration
RGDP	-2.3929 (0.3790)	-4.5298 (0.0132)	I(1)
GHG	-0.9119 (0.9470)	-4.1391 (0.0128)	I(1)
BCR	-2.3737 (0.3883)	-6.3088 (0.0216)	I(1)
CAX	1.1985 (0.9999)	-7.1304 (0.0141)	I(1)
ISW	-0.4567 (0.0745)	-6.4684 (0.0063)	I(1)

Cointegration Test			
Variable	Trace Statistic	Max-Eigen Statistic	Remark
None *	38.36746 (0.0262)	36.91290 (0.0274)	Cointegrated
At most 1 *	21.45456 (0.0299)	22.75592 (0.0449)	Cointegrated
At most 2 *	8.698635 (0.3940)	8.557176 (0.3249)	Not Cointegrated
At most 3 *	0.141458 (0.7068)	0.141458 (0.7068)	Not Cointegrated
At most 4 *	0.024678 (0.6854)	0.024689 (0.6642)	Not Cointegrated

Source: Extracted from Eviews Output

The unit root test shows that all the variables are stationary after first differencing. That is to say that they are all integrated at I(1) order. The implication is that the data have demonstrated that their statistical properties do not vary with time and as such can be used for predictive models. The Johansen cointegration test showed two cointegrated equations at 'None' and 'at most 1'. This satisfies the condition that must be satisfied for the existence of long run relationship amongst the variables. Since there is long run relationship amongst the I(1) variables, the study proceeds with the model estimation.

Table 3: Error Correction Model Estimation

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	-0.943674	6.703860	-0.140766	0.8886
GHG	0.531096	0.353739	1.501380	0.1398
BCR	0.216248	0.022007	9.826166	0.0000
CAX	-0.001140	0.018308	-0.062287	0.9506
ISW	-0.026743	0.003458	-7.733661	0.0021
ECM(-1)	-0.061729	0.013403	-4.605611	0.0045
R-squared	0.850604	F-statistic		68.32340
Adjusted R-squared	0.838154	Prob(F-statistic)		0.000000
Durbin-Watson stat	1.759371	Akaike info criterion		-4.450926

Source: Extracted from Eviews Output

The estimates in Table 3 show that greenhouse gas emission has positive relationship with economic growth of Nigeria. That is to say that a unit change in greenhouse gas emission

increases Nigeria's real gross domestic product by 0.5311 units but the *p-value* of 0.1398 shows that the positive effect is not statistically significant.

Similarly, bank credit to industrial sector showed positive relationship with economic growth increasing it by 0.2162 units. The *p-value* of 0.0000 indicates that the positive effect of bank credit to industrial sector on economic growth is statistically significant.

Conversely, capital expenditure on environmental sustainability has negative relationship with economic growth of Nigeria decreasing it by 0.0011 units. The *p-value* of 0.9506 indicates that the negative effect of government capital expenditure on environmental sustainability is not statistically significant at 5% level. Industrial solid waste also decreased economic growth by 0.0267 units. The probability value of 0.0021 implies that the negative effect was significant.

The error correction coefficient is negative and significant and it means that the model is effectively correcting the deviations experienced from the long run long run convergence. In other words, when real gross domestic product is out of balanced, it will gradually move back towards equilibrium at the speed of 6.17% annually.

The adjusted R-squared value of 0.8382 indicates that the environmental sustainability variables (greenhouse gas emission, bank credit to industrial sector and government capital expenditure on environment) accounted for 83.82% of the changes in real gross domestic product. This also implies that 16.18% are not being accounted for by the variables hence they are being taken care of by the stochastic error term.

Test of Hypotheses One

H₀₁: There is no significant impact of greenhouse emissions on economic growth of Nigeria.

For the first hypothesis, the t-statistic value for GHG is 1.501 and the probability value is 0.1398 (Table 3). Since the probability value is greater than 0.05 critical value, the null hypothesis is accepted and the study concludes that there is positive but insignificant impact of greenhouse emissions on economic growth of Nigeria.

Test of Hypotheses Two

H₀₂: there is no significant impact of bank credit to industrial sector on economic growth of Nigeria.

For the second hypothesis, the t-statistic value for BCR is 9.826 and the probability value is 0.0000 (Table 3). Since the probability value is less than 0.05 critical value, the null hypothesis is rejected and the study concludes that there is positive and significant impact of bank credit to industrial sector on economic growth of Nigeria.

Test of Hypotheses Three

H₀₃: Government capital expenditure on environmental sustainability has no significant effect on economic growth of Nigeria.

For the third hypothesis, the t-statistic value for CAX is -0.0623 and the probability value is 0.9506 (Table 3). Since the probability value is greater than 0.05 critical value, the null hypothesis is accepted and the study concludes that government capital expenditure on

environmental sustainability has negative and no significant effect on economic growth of Nigeria.

Test of Hypotheses Four

H₀₄: Industrial solid waste has no significant impact on economic growth of Nigeria.

For the fourth hypothesis, the t-statistic value for ISW is -7.734 and the probability value is 0.0021 (Table 3). Since the probability value is less than 0.05 critical value, the null hypothesis is rejected and the study concludes that industrial solid waste has significant impact on economic growth of Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The study revealed that there was positive but insignificant impact of greenhouse emissions on economic growth of Nigeria. Data on greenhouse gas emission showed that Nigeria averaged 150 million metric tons of greenhouse gas emission within the period 2010 to 2024. What this implies is that industrialization activities in Nigeria which involves the release of gases into the atmosphere thereby trapping heat and contributing to global warming, has led to decline in economic growth in Nigeria. Greenhouse gas is a collection of carbon dioxide, methane and nitrous oxide and it has shown to decrease productivity in Nigeria for the period under review. Samuel *et al* (2024) made similar finding that greenhouse gases substantially decline economic growth of African Countries. Other studies such as Manal (2024) and Ifurueze and Igbru (2021) found negative consequences of greenhouse gas on the economy.

Bank credit to the industrial sector which represents the amount of investment of the private sector in production has contributed positively and significantly to economic growth of Nigeria for the period under study. By implication, the contribution of the industrial sector to production is further fueled by their access to credit which produces more wastes that adds to environmental sustainability issues. Thus, with the growth of industrial sector's access to credit, the Nigerian economy is growing at a similar rate despite the environmental consequences of such growth. Erhun (2015) noted that the development of humanity should not be on the cost of environmental health hence increased production should be met with adequate consideration of the environment.

Further analysis revealed that government capital expenditure on environmental sustainability which averaged ₦4.134 trillion exerted negative effect on economic growth. This implies that government expenditure on environment is insufficient and has not had the desired effect on the economy. Invariably, there is lack of prioritization of environmental sustainability in Nigeria's economic planning which was also acknowledge by previous studies such as Sijuwola and Fadogba (2023), Ajudua (2019). According to Fenget *al.* (2024), sustainable clean water investments synergize with the protection of land-based ecosystems and climate action plans and so neglect of this critical climate action portends serious danger to the economy. With the Nigerian government launch of the green bond which seeks to fund projects that support sustainable development, there is increased anticipation of positive outcome of capital expenditure on the economy.

Industrial solid waste exerted negative effect on the economy decreasing it by 0.0267 units every quarter. This implies that as the industrial sector is increasing in its capacity due to expansion, industrial solid waste is increasing and this has negative consequences on the economy. Thus, environmental sustainability is being threatened by increased industrial solid

waste in Nigeria. The study of Ajudua (2019) upheld the negative effect of industrial waste on the environment and the economy by asserting that quantity of gas flared and quantity of oil spillage led to environmental degradation in Nigeria.

The overall assessment from the model analysis is that environmental sustainability variables (greenhouse gas emission, bank credit to industrial sector and government capital expenditure on environment) accounted for 83.82% of the changes in real gross domestic product. This means that these variables that have been hitherto neglected by previous researchers account for a greater percentage of changes in the economy of Nigeria.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concludes that Nigeria is on the right track towards achieving environmental sustainability and long run economic growth. However, the negative consequence of industrial solid waste on the economy is a serious cause for worry as Nigeria advances in her industrial development drive. The positive effect of greenhouse gas emission on the economy and the positive effect of bank credit to the industrial sector on the economy points to a step in the right direction. However, government efforts towards achieving environmental sustainability is being hampered by underfunding of environmental friendly projects and increased generation of industrial solid waste which threatens environmental sustainability. However, the recent launching of the sovereign green bond is a step in the right direction towards sustainable environmental policies that will drive economic growth. Thus, in order to achieve the aim of a sustainable environment and achieve the needed growth in the economy, it is recommended that:

1. Nigerian government should designate a significant portion of her expenditure on capital projects such as solar electrification, clean water initiatives etc. This will help achieve the needed growth in the economy through environmentally friendly projects.
2. Banks should promote elements of environmental, social and governance (ESG) criteria into their lending decisions by promoting initiatives of green financing by industrial sector. This initiative will help to increase production but decrease the environmental consequences of increased industrialization thus promoting long run economic growth.
3. The transition to renewable energy should be top priority of both government and private sector industrialists. Decreasing greenhouse gas emission by over fifty per cent will be a booster to ensuring long term economic growth through energy conservation and decrease in production cost.
4. Industrial solid waste should be properly managed in order to prevent land degradation and the resultant climate change consequences. This calls for increased government attention to solid waste management.

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Environmental Pollution and Public Health in Nigeria

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Abstract

Environmental pollution continues to threaten sustainable development in Nigeria, with open dumping of solid waste remaining the most prevalent and environmentally damaging disposal method. This study investigates the relationship between environmental pollution and public health by using open dumping rate as the independent variable, and crude death rate and infant mortality rate as dependent variables. The objective is to assess how increasing exposure to indiscriminately disposed waste influences mortality outcomes across the population. A quantitative research design was adopted, relying on secondary data obtained from national and international statistical sources. The analysis employed regression techniques to determine the extent to which variations in open dumping rate explain changes in key public health indicators. Conceptually, open dumping contributes to deteriorating environmental conditions through contaminated water sources, proliferation of disease vectors, toxic emissions, and blocked drainage channels that heighten the incidence of infectious diseases. The empirical findings reveal a positive and statistically significant relationship between open dumping rate and both crude death rate and infant mortality rate. This indicates that communities with higher levels of unmanaged waste experience disproportionately worse health outcomes. The study concludes that addressing open dumping is crucial for reducing mortality and improving overall public health. It recommends the expansion of formal waste management systems, stricter enforcement of environmental regulations, investment in sanitary waste facilities, and community awareness programmes aimed at curbing indiscriminate dumping practices.

Keywords: Environmental Pollution; Open Dumping Rate; Public Health; Crude Death Rate; Infant Mortality Rate

Introduction

Background of the Study

Environmental pollution has emerged as one of the most pressing public health challenges in developing countries, including Nigeria. Rapid urbanization, population growth, limited waste management infrastructure, and poor environmental governance have intensified pollution across Nigerian cities and rural communities. Among the major forms of pollution, open dumping of solid waste remains the most widespread, as an estimated large proportion of municipal waste is disposed of in uncontrolled dumpsites. Open dumping releases toxic substances, pathogenic organisms, and particulate matter into the air, soil, and groundwater, exposing surrounding populations to severe health risks.

The health consequences of environmental pollution in Nigeria have been widely reported. Pollutants from open waste dumps contribute to respiratory infections, diarrheal diseases, vector-borne illnesses, chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases, and increased vulnerability to environmental hazards. These health burdens reflect in key public health indicators, particularly the crude death rate and infant mortality rate, which continue to be among the

highest in Sub-Saharan Africa. Infants and children living near open dumps are especially vulnerable due to weaker immune systems and frequent exposure to contaminated air, water, and soil.

Given the increasing volume of municipal waste and the persistence of open dumping practices, understanding how environmental pollution affects public health outcomes is essential for evidence-based policy formulation and sustainable public health planning in Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Despite various national and state-level waste management interventions, Nigeria continues to rely heavily on open dumping as the dominant method of solid waste disposal. The uncontrolled nature of open dumpsites creates breeding grounds for vectors, generates toxic leachates, and emits harmful gases. These health hazards have contributed to rising morbidity and mortality trends, reflected in high crude death and infant mortality rates across the country.

However, empirical studies in Nigeria have disproportionately focused on air pollution, water pollution, or individual health outcomes, with limited attention to how open dumping—one of the most pervasive pollution practices—affects broad public health indicators. As uncontrolled waste disposal expands due to rapid population growth, the associated health risks may worsen if not addressed through research-informed interventions. This creates a critical need to investigate the specific public health implications of open dumping in Nigeria.

Research Gap

While existing studies examine environmental pollution in relation to specific diseases, few have provided an integrated assessment of open dumping rate as a proxy for environmental pollution and its direct association with public health conditions measured through crude death rate and infant mortality rate. There is insufficient empirical evidence that links national waste disposal patterns to macro-level health outcomes in Nigeria. This study addresses this gap by providing a systematic analysis of the relationship between environmental pollution—through open dumping practices—and public health indicators over time.

Objectives of the Study

General Objective

To examine the effect of environmental pollution, proxied by open dumping rate, on public health in Nigeria.

Specific Objectives

1. To assess the impact of open dumping rate on crude death rate in Nigeria.
2. To examine the effect of open dumping rate on infant mortality rate in Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. To what extent does open dumping rate influence crude death rate in Nigeria?
2. How does open dumping rate affect infant mortality rate in Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

Null Hypotheses (H_0)

H₀₁: Open dumping rate has no significant effect on crude death rate in Nigeria.

H₀₂: Open dumping rate has no significant effect on infant mortality rate in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Environmental Pollution (Open Dumping): Open dumping refers to the unsanitary, uncontrolled disposal of municipal solid waste (MSW) in open sites without environmental protection measures (e.g., liners, leachate control, gas collection). In Nigeria, open dumps remain prevalent due to rapid urbanization, weak regulatory enforcement, limited waste infrastructure, and insufficient formal collection services.

Such sites generate multiple forms of pollution: leachate that contaminates soil and groundwater; emissions of gases (e.g., methane, hydrogen sulfide) from decomposing waste; and pathogen proliferation, creating environmental health hazards.

Researchers also document the geochemical impacts: for example, a study in Lagos found that dumpsites significantly altered soil chemistry (e.g., sulfate, phosphate, conductivity), suggesting persistent contamination.

Public Health (Crude Death Rate and Infant Mortality Rate): Public health, in the context of this study, is proxied by macro indicators: crude death rate (CDR) and infant mortality rate (IMR). These indicators capture population-level health burdens. While many environmental health studies focus on specific diseases (respiratory, vector-borne, gastrointestinal), CDR and IMR reflect broad, aggregated risk. This link is critical: environmental pollution contributes to disease burden, which in turn is reflected in elevated mortality at different life stages.

Environmental Characterization of Dumpsites

In Lagos, soil and water assessments around major dumpsites revealed significant pollution: soil pH, sulfate, phosphate, and conductivity levels were disturbed, indicating chemical contamination that can lead to public health risks.

In Benin City (Ikhueniro dumpsite), a survey of households close to (< 250 m) vs. farther (> 250 m) from the dump revealed that those near the site reported more adverse health conditions, showing proximity risk.

Empirical work in Nigeria highlights that improper waste disposal especially through open dumping is perceived by communities to contribute to disease burdens such as malaria, diarrheal illnesses, respiratory problems, and more.

For instance, a household-level study in Bekwarra LGA found that indiscriminate waste disposal and poor containerization led to vector breeding, clogged drains, and disease transmission (e.g., cholera, malaria), illustrating how environmental pollution translates to health risk.

In Imo State, residents reported perceived health effects from their disposal practices: malaria, cough, skin irritation, etc., indicating local awareness of environmental-health pathways. These conceptual linkages illustrate how open dumping as a proxy for pollution can logically be associated with elevated infant mortality and general death risk.

Theoretical Review

1. Ecosocial Theory: Proposed by Nancy Krieger, the ecosocial theory emphasizes how social, economic, and environmental factors accumulate in the body over time to produce disease patterns (i.e., “embodiment,” “pathways to embodiment”).

In the Nigerian open-dumping context, ecosocial theory suggests that living in or near dump sites is not just an environmental risk but also a social and economic one. Residences near open dumps may reflect marginalized or low-capacity communities, increasing susceptibility due to poorer infrastructure, lower access to health care, or weaker regulatory protection.

The cumulative exposure to pollutants (leachate, gases, vectors) can manifest in higher mortality (crude death rate) and infant deaths over time, aligning with ecosocial constructs of cumulative disadvantage and vulnerability.

2. Exposome theory: The concept of the exposome describes the totality of environmental exposures an individual experiences from conception onward (external and internal), shaping health trajectories.

Open dumping contributes to a significant portion of the external exposome: chemical exposures (heavy metals, organics), biological exposures (pathogens), and physical exposures (dust, particulates).

These exposures, especially in early life (e.g., in utero, infancy), may influence infant mortality risk and long-term mortality, providing a useful framework for linking environmental dumping to macro-level public health outcomes.

Empirical Review

Onicha, A.D. (2024) Study the role of solid waste, urbanization and pollution in under-five mortality Time-series econometric analysis (ARDL/DARDL) of solid waste / pollution and under-five mortality. Finds a long-run cointegration: solid waste / pollution indicators are significantly associated with higher under-five mortality (short- and long-run effects reported).

Lovo, S. (2021 / 2022 / 2024 series) study the impact of e-waste dumping sites on child mortality (Ghana & Nigeria focus) the study exploiting placement of large e-waste dumping sites; compares neonatal & infant mortality rates before/after and by distance to sites. **people** Living near e-waste / dumping sites increases neonatal and infant mortality effects emerge 2–3 years after site establishment; moving 1 km away reduces neonatal/infant mortality by several deaths per 1,000 births.

Bruederle, A. & Hodler (2019 / 2017) study the effect of oil spills on infant mortality in Nigeria Using Quasi-experimental analysis exploiting locations and timing of onshore oil spills to estimate causal effects on neonatal/infant mortality. and find out that living Nearby oil spills are associated with large increases in neonatal and infant mortality (robust across specifications). Oil-related contamination often involves open dumping, spills and polluted

water/soil in affected communities; this study links environmental contamination to infant mortality directly.

Ichipi, E.B., et al. (2023, International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health) — Impact of illegal dumping of solid waste in Lagos State A Cross-sectional field study and environmental assessment of illegal dumping sites; health surveys of affected communities. Result show that Illegal/unsanitary dumping is associated with reported increases in respiratory and gastrointestinal illness and indicators that plausibly raise infant/child morbidity and mortality risk; authors discuss exposure pathways (water contamination, vectors, burning).

Omang, D.I. et al. (2021) — Public health implication of solid waste generated by households (Nigeria) (PMC review) Mixed literature review, community survey evidence synthesizing MSW practices and reported health effects across Nigeria. Result show High prevalence of open dumping and open burning; documented associations between poor waste management and diarrhoeal, vector-borne and respiratory diseases — direct contributors to child mortality and to higher crude death rates in affected location

Empirical studies in Nigeria and elsewhere provide strong evidence for links between open dumping (or poor waste management) and public health impacts, even if not always directly on crude death rate or infant mortality. Below are key findings:

Open Dump Health Hazards in Urban Nigeria

A cross-sectional mixed-methods study in urban Nigerian settlements found that about 72% of respondents used open dumps for waste disposal; they reported health outcomes such as malaria, skin irritation, and respiratory difficulty.

In Kano metropolis, a study reported that 75% of households practiced open dumping; more than half recognized a link between their waste practices and disease risk (malaria, cholera, dysentery).

In Imo State, empirical data reveal that residents perceive their waste disposal habits to be associated with diseases: malaria, cough, skin irritation, etc.

Disease Linkages & Mortality

A nationwide (or multi-city) study found that increasing solid waste (a proxy for poor environmental management) is significantly associated with under-five mortality (a component of infant mortality). Specifically, in an ARDL (autoregressive distributed lag) model, a unit increase in waste was linked to a rise in under-five mortality.

In the Niger Delta (Port Harcourt region), a study on household waste dumping in Obio-Akpor LGA linked disease outbreaks (diarrhea, cholera, malaria) to proliferation of dumpsites, weak waste services, and poor environmental governance.

On a broader scale, the World Bank's cross-country economic study on e-waste dumping reported that children born after the establishment of dumpsites had significantly higher infant (and neonatal) mortality rates, a result applicable to Nigeria as one of the studied countries.

A study in Enugu, Nigeria, documented a cholera outbreak (14 deaths in 3 days) associated with poor waste management practices.

A recent study in Imo State (2024) found strong perception among residents that their disposal practices (including open dumping) are linked to cough and malaria, highlighting continuing public awareness of environmental-health risk.

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopts an ex-post facto research design. This design is suitable because the variables of interest—open dumping rate, crude death rate, and infant mortality rate—already exist in published national data sources, and cannot be manipulated by the researcher. The design allows the study to examine the historical relationship between environmental pollution (proxied by open dumping) and public health outcomes in Nigeria over time. The approach supports statistical analysis to determine the nature and strength of associations among the variables.

Sources of Data

The study uses secondary data obtained from credible agencies, including:

National Bureau of Statistics (NBS)

World Bank World Development Indicators (WDI)

UNICEF and WHO Global Health Observatory (GHO)

National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA)

Federal Ministry of Environment annual reports

National Waste Management Baseline Studies

These sources provide consistent and publicly verifiable time-series data for open dumping rates, crude death rates, and infant mortality rates across the study period.

Variables of the Study

Independent Variable (X): Environmental Pollution

Measured through Open Dumping Rate: the percentage or proportion of total municipal solid waste disposed of in open, uncontrolled dumpsites annually.

Dependent Variable (Y): Public Health

Measured through two health indicators:

1. Crude Death Rate (CDR) – number of deaths per 1,000 population in a given year.
2. Infant Mortality Rate (IMR) – number of infant deaths (children below age one) per 1,000 live births annually.

Model Specification

To evaluate the effect of environmental pollution on public health, the study employs a multiple linear regression model estimated separately for each health indicator.

Model 1: Effect of Open Dumping on Crude Death Rate

$$CDR_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ODR_t + \mu_t$$

Model 2: Effect of Open Dumping on Infant Mortality Rate

$$IMR_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ODR_t + \mu_t$$

Where:

= Crude death rate at year t

= Infant mortality rate at year t

= Open dumping rate at year t

= Intercept

= Coefficient of open dumping (expected to be positive)

= Stochastic error term

Method of Data Analysis

The study applies descriptive statistics (mean, trend analysis, standard deviation) and inferential statistics (regression analysis, significance testing). The analysis involves:

1. Unit Root Test (Augmented Dickey-Fuller):

Conducted to determine the stationarity of each time-series variable.

2. Regression Estimation:

Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) is employed, as the model includes one independent variable and satisfies classical regression assumptions.

3. Diagnostic Tests:

Serial correlation test (Durbin-Watson)

Heteroskedasticity test

Normality test

Model significance (F-test)

Parameter significance (t-test)

Validity and Reliability of Data

The study relies on nationally and internationally recognized sources whose data collection methods follow standardized procedures. Reliability is ensured by using consistent indicators across years. Validity is supported by selecting variables that are widely recognized as proxies for environmental pollution and public health in empirical and policy literature.

Data analysis and Interpretation of Results

Descriptive Analysis

	CDR	IMR	ODR
Mean	14.06760	78.37600	68.06000
Median	13.62000	81.90000	68.00000
Maximum	17.90000	109.8000	80.00000
Minimum	11.42000	-53.70000	56.00000
Std. Dev.	2.170173	30.73800	7.276274
Skewness	0.423297	-3.253768	0.022315
Kurtosis	1.772393	14.93469	1.790906
Jarque-Bera	2.316397	192.4841	1.524896
Probability	0.314052	0.000000	0.466523
Sum	351.6900	1959.400	1701.500
Sum Sq. Dev.	113.0317	22675.79	1270.660
Observations	25	25	25

Source: E-Views 10 Output (2025)

The table above contains the descriptive statistics of the data used for this study. The table shows that the means of CRD (crude death rate per 1000 people), IMR (infants mortality rate per 1000 live birth), and ODR (open dumping rate/open burning widespread) between 2000 and 2024 are about 14.07%, 78.38% and 68.06% respectively with corresponding standard deviations of 2.17%, 30.74% and 7.28%. The table equally shows that the variables CRD and ODR are normally distributed as their probability values of Jarque-Bera statistic (0.314052 and 0.466523) are greater than zero. Similarly, these two variables are skewed to the right with positive skewness values of 0.423297 and 0.022315 respectively. In essence, the variable IMR is not normally distributed and it is negatively skewed.

Unit Root Test

Variables	ADF Statistic	Critical Value (5%)	P-Value	Level of Integration
CDR	-4.259916	-2.998064	0.0032	I(1)
IMR	-3.466066	-3.029970	0.0212	I(1)
ODR	-3.169145	-2.998064	0.0353	I(1)

Source: Extract from E-Views 10 Output (2025)

Unit root test shows that the variables, CDR, IMR and ODR, are stationary at first difference as their probability values at first difference (0.0032, 0.0212 and 0.0353) are greater than 0.05 (5%) level of significance. Given this result, the study adopted the Johansen cointegration analytical approach.

Johansen Cointegration

Date: 11/24/25 Time: 12:21				
Sample (adjusted): 2002 2024				
Included observations: 23 after adjustments				
Trend assumption: Linear deterministic trend				
Series: CDR IMR ODR				
Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 1				
Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)				
Hypothesized		Trace	0.05	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.972337	113.4473	29.79707	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.725047	30.93079	15.49471	0.0001
At most 2	0.052246	1.234186	3.841466	0.2666
Trace test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level				
* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level				
**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values				
Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)				
Hypothesized		Max-Eigen	0.05	
No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Statistic	Critical Value	Prob.**
None *	0.972337	82.51656	21.13162	0.0000
At most 1 *	0.725047	29.69660	14.26460	0.0001
At most 2	0.052246	1.234186	3.841466	0.2666
Max-eigenvalue test indicates 2 cointegrating eqn(s) at the 0.05 level				
* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level				
**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values				

Source: Extract from E-Views 10 Output (2025)

Since there is at least one cointegrating equation in the Trace statistic and Maximum Eigen value result, it follows that there is cointegration between the variables. This implies that there is a long run equilibrium relationship between the variables.

Granger Causality Test

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests			
Date: 11/24/25 Time: 12:22			
Sample: 2000 2024			
Lags: 2			
Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
IMR does not Granger Cause CDR	23	98.1445	2.E-10
CDR does not Granger Cause IMR		2.17227	0.1429
ODR does not Granger Cause CDR	23	2.45984	0.1137
CDR does not Granger Cause ODR		2.00790	0.1632
ODR does not Granger Cause IMR	23	0.69134	0.5137
IMR does not Granger Cause ODR		8.23290	0.0029

Source: E-Views 10 Output (2025)

Pairwise granger causality test revealed that there is a unidirectional relationship between infant mortality rate (IMR) and crude death rate (CDR); and between infant mortality rate (IMR) and open dumping rate/open burning widespread (ODR). This is because in both cases, the probability values of F-statistic (2.E-10 and 0.0029) are greater than 5% (0.05).

ECM Estimation 1

Dependent Variable: D(CDR)				
Method: Least Squares				
Date: 11/24/25 Time: 13:51				
Sample (adjusted): 2001 2024				
Included observations: 24 after adjustments				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	0.836753	0.329448	2.539867	0.0191
D(ODR)	1.096504	0.324836	3.375558	0.0029
ECM(-1)	-0.630525	0.108411	0.585966	0.0451
R-squared	0.359668	Mean dependent var		-
Adjusted R-squared	0.298684	S.D. dependent var		0.262500
S.E. of regression	0.215218	Akaike info criterion		-
Sum squared resid	0.972696	Schwarz criterion		0.117860
Log likelihood	4.414324	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-
F-statistic	5.897747	Durbin-Watson stat		0.078793
Prob(F-statistic)	0.009274			1.341059

Source: E-Views 10 Output (2025)

The first Error Correction Model (ECM) estimates revealed that if open dumping rate/open burning widespread is held constant for the period, crude death rate will reduce to about 0.83% per annum. It also shows that crude death rate has a positive relationship (1.096504) with open dumping rate/open burning widespread whereby a percentage increase in open dumping rate/open burning widespread leads to about 1.1% increase in crude death rate and vice versa. With respect to the first hypothesis, the above table reveals that there is a significant relationship between crude death rate and open dumping rate/open burning widespread because the probability value of t-statistic (0.0029) is lesser than 0.05 (5%), which is the adopted level of significance. Finally, the ECM equation has the desired negative and significant signs of -0.630525 and 0.0451; and this implies that in event of a shock to the established long run relationship between crude death rate and open dumping rate/open burning widespread, the speed of convergence is about 63.05% per annum.

ECM Estimation 2

Dependent Variable: D(IMR)				
Method: Least Squares				
Date: 11/24/25 Time: 13:53				
Sample (adjusted): 2001 2024				
Included observations: 24 after adjustments				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1.715629	2.612463	0.656709	0.5185
D(ODR)	4.017819	2.586170	1.553579	0.1352
ECM(-1)	-0.183419	0.137766	-1.331381	0.0173
R-squared	0.169546	Mean dependent var		-
Adjusted R-squared	0.090455	S.D. dependent var		2.337500
S.E. of regression	1.828177	Akaike info criterion		1.916930
Sum squared resid	70.18689	Schwarz criterion		4.160985
Log likelihood	-46.93182	Hannan-Quinn criter.		4.308242
F-statistic	2.143680	Durbin-Watson stat		4.200052
Prob(F-statistic)	0.142173			1.281661

Source: E-Views 10 Output (2025)

The second ECM estimates revealed that the intercept of the second model is 1.715629 and this implies that holding open dumping rate/open burning widespread constant, infant mortality rate will be about 1.72% per annum. The result also shows that the regression coefficient of the model is 4.017819, which indicates the existence of a positive relationship between open dumping rate/open burning widespread and infant mortality rate. It also indicates that an increase in the former will leads to about 4.02% increase in the latter and vice versa. With respect to hypothesis testing, the result puts the value of t-statistic at 1.553579, with a probability value of 0.1352, which suggests that there is no significant relationship between infant mortality rate and open dumping rate/open burning widespread because the p-value of t-statistic is greater than 5% (0.05) level of significance. The table equally shows that the ECM equation has the desired negative (-0.183419) and significant signs (0.0173); which implies that in event of any distortion to the established long run

relationship between infant mortality rate and open dumping rate/open burning widespread, the speed of adjustment per annum is about 18.34%.

Diagnostic Tests

Test	Criterion	Test Statistic	P-value	Decision
Normality	Jarque-Bera	0.677371	0.712707	Present
Serial Correlation	Breusch-Godfrey	2.861033	0.0964	Absent
Heteroscedasticity	Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey	0.353271	0.7875	Absent
RESET	Ramsey	0.194047	0.6668	Present

Source: Extract from E-Views 10 Output (2025)

The table above shows that there is no presence of serial correlation and heteroscedasticity in the models; the models were well specified and they are normally distributed. In essence, there is no correlation between successive values of the error terms and the variances of the errors are constant (homoscedastic). This is because the probability values of the respective test-statistic (0.712707, 0.0964, 0.7875 and 0.6668) are greater than 0.05 (5% level of significance). This validates the estimates obtained and further shows that the results are reliable.

Summary of Findings, Conclusion and Recommendations

Summary of Findings

This study examined the effect of environmental pollution on public health in Nigeria, using open dumping rate as the proxy for environmental pollution and crude death rate and infant mortality rate as indicators of public health outcomes. The major findings are summarized as follows:

High Open Dumping Rate and Poor Health Outcomes

The results indicate a consistent rise in open dumping of solid waste across several urban and peri-urban settlements in Nigeria. This persistent increase coincides with elevated crude death rates and high infant mortality rates, suggesting a strong association between unsafe solid waste disposal and deteriorating public health indicators.

Significant Positive Relationship Between Open Dumping Rate and Crude Death Rate

Empirical findings show that higher levels of open dumping significantly contribute to increased crude death rates. The presence of uncontrolled waste disposal sites contributes to the spread of infectious diseases such as cholera, typhoid, and respiratory illnesses, which elevate mortality levels.

Open Dumping Rate Strongly Influences Infant Mortality:

The study reveals that infants are particularly vulnerable to pollution-induced diseases arising from open dumping, such as diarrheal diseases, airborne pathogens, and vector-borne illnesses. Consequently, infant mortality responds significantly to environmental pollution levels.

Weak Enforcement of Waste Management Policies

The outcome of the review suggests that the weak implementation of environmental protection laws, poor municipal waste collection capacity, and lack of public awareness have contributed to the increasing reliance on open dumping across Nigerian communities.

Pollution Hotspots Correspond With Health Burden Hotspots

States and cities with the highest concentration of open dumping sites tend to report higher mortality and morbidity rates, confirming spatial alignment between pollution intensity and adverse health outcomes.

Conclusion

The study concludes that environmental pollution—specifically open dumping of solid waste—poses a significant threat to public health in Nigeria. The analysis demonstrates that open dumping has a measurable and adverse effect on both crude death rates and infant mortality rates. Untreated waste dumps serve as breeding grounds for disease vectors and introduce toxic contaminants into air, water, and soil systems, thereby exacerbating health risks, especially among infants and vulnerable populations.

Overall, the findings underscore the need for an urgent and integrated response by government institutions, development partners, and communities to address the health implications of uncontrolled waste disposal. Improving environmental quality remains a critical pathway to reducing mortality rates and enhancing public health outcomes in Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Strengthen Waste Management Infrastructure:

Federal, state, and local governments should invest in modern waste collection, transportation, and processing facilities to reduce reliance on open dumping.

2. Enforce Environmental Laws and Sanitation Regulations:

Agencies such as NESREA and state environmental protection boards must intensify enforcement of waste disposal regulations and sanction illegal dumping practices.

3. Promote Community-Based Waste Management Initiatives:

Local communities should be encouraged to participate in waste sorting, recycling, and composting programs to minimize waste volumes and reduce pressure on dumping sites.

4. Enhance Public Awareness and Health Education:

Nationwide sensitization campaigns should be implemented to educate citizens on the dangers of open dumping and the need for proper waste disposal practices.

5. Introduce Public Health Surveillance Around Dump Sites:

Health monitoring systems should be established around major open dump locations to track pollution-related diseases and provide early interventions.

6. Adopt Clean Technologies and Circular Economy Models:

Government and private sector actors should invest in waste-to-energy systems, recycling industries, and environmentally friendly innovations to reduce waste buildup.

7. Improve Data Collection for Evidence-Based Policy:

Reliable, timely, and disaggregated environmental and health data should be generated to support strategic planning and periodic evaluation of pollution-control initiatives.

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Governance, Social Crisis and Food Security in Nigeria: Is There a Link?

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Abstract

Despite Nigeria's vast arable land mass, huge endowed natural and human resources, hunger and malnutrition still soars, and persistent social crisis and weak governance have been cited as the basis for her recent awful judgment of food insecure. Against this backdrop, this study empirically examines the connection among governance, social crisis and food security in Nigeria from 2005-2023. Using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag Bounds of Cointegration, the result confirmed that a long-run relationship actually exists among governance effectiveness, control of corruption, violence and food production index over the period under study. The regression results reveal that all the explanatory variables exerted a significant negative impact on food production in the long-run, but in the short-run, their effects were positive. The Toda and Yamamoto Causality results further showed a bidirectional causality between the variables employed in the model. On the basis of this study it can be concluded that government effectiveness, control of corruption, violence and food production are locked in a vicious cycle of mutual reinforcement in Nigeria. Therefore, addressing one factor in isolation is unlikely to yield sustainable results. Consequently, we recommend among others a comprehensive approach by the government that involves strengthening institutional capacity, tackling corruption at all levels, and implementing targeted peace building and food production initiatives to achieve lasting stability and food security in Nigeria.

Keywords: Governance effectiveness, Control of corruption, Violence, Food security, ARDL.

Introduction

One of the most pressing developmental challenges confronting many developing nations, and Nigeria inclusive is food security. According to the Food and Agricultural Organization of the United Nation's Committee on World Food Security (1996), food security is when all people at all times have physical and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and preferences for an active and healthy life. This definition paints a clear picture that to achieve food and nutritious security, food must be available to the people to an extent that will meet some acceptable nutritional standards in terms of calorie, protein and vitamins which the body needs, the possession of the means by the people to acquire it and consistency in its supply. Adeoti cited in Ojo and Adebayo (2012) identified the availability of food and the possession of the ability for its acquisition as its central elements.

Nigeria, blessed with vast arable land, favourable climate, and large agricultural workforce continues to experience persistent food shortages, malnutrition and rising food prices.

Currently, this has become a significant challenge as many families cannot afford three square meals a day, and this threatens the lives and livelihood of millions of Nigerian citizens. According to reports by the Food and Agricultural Organization (FAO) and the World Food Programme (WFP) (2024), over 25 million and 31.8 million Nigerians suffered from acute food insecurity in 2023 and 2024 respectively. This is compounded with malnutrition among women and children, which invariably has a very long-term devastating effect as it cripples the mind and body of children, reduces adult's immune system to fight diseases and consequently deprives the society of its future productive human resources (Ojo & Adebayo, 2012). Nigeria ranks 110th out of 127 countries in the 2024 Global Hunger Index (GHI) with a score of 28.8, indicating serious level of hunger. This is disheartening as Nigeria which was formerly regarded as one of the largest producer of some agricultural commodities is now adjudged as food insecure, hence relies heavily on imported food to meet local demand. This paradox rises critical questions about the underlying causes of the nation's food crisis, extending beyond agricultural production to issues of governance and social stability.

Governance plays a role in food insecurity in Nigeria, exacerbating the challenges bedeviling the country (Bashir & Muhammad-Sani, 2025). Nigeria has consistently recorded low scores on governance indicators like corruption control, government effectiveness, political stability, rule of law and accountability. Apparently, weak institutions, policy inconsistency, corruption, insufficient budgetary allocation to agriculture and lack of accountability hinder the government to effectively respond to the food crisis. Adubi (2021) affirms that poor governance breeds insecurity which in turn affects food production and distribution, creating a wide gap between domestic demand and supply. One major governance challenge to achieving food security in Nigeria is corruption. The diversion and at times outright sell of agricultural inputs and machineries meant for smallholder farmers by corrupt government officials sabotages every effort aimed at achieving food sufficiency in the country (The Nigeria Youth Forum (NYF), 2025). As disclosed by the Corruption Perception Index report of February 2024, Nigeria ranked 140 out of 180 most corrupt countries in the world with a total score of 26 points, indicating high rate of corruption in the country. Consequently, this has constrained the attainment of food sufficiency in the country.

Another major cause of food insecurity in Nigeria is social crisis- mainly insurgency in the Northeast, farmer-herder clashes in the Middle Belt, communal clashes, banditry and separatist agitators in various parts of the country. Undoubtedly, these crisis have further disrupted agricultural activities, displaced farming communities, reduced access to markets and discouraged investment in the agricultural sector, thereby, making it difficult in providing nutritious healthy and stable diets to feed the country's growing population. Nevertheless, Laudable agricultural policies and programmes have been established to achieve food security in Nigeria. Additionally, the recent declaration of a state of emergency on food security by President Bola Ahmed Tinubu in 2023 triggered immediate measures like release of fertilizers and grains, optimizing water resources and bolstering financial support. Interventions to counter the impact of fuel subsidy removal were also introduced alongside landmark agreements with international institutions to enhance agricultural production. Regrettably, these efforts and the established programmes are marred by inadequate implementation characterized by bad governance in the country.

In this regards, the study intends to investigate the extent to which governance failures and social crisis affect food security dynamics in Nigeria from 2005-2023. Also, it intends to examine the causal link between these variables and food production in Nigeria. Understanding this connection is vital for designing effective policies and interventions that

can enhance agricultural performance, promote stability and secure sustainable livelihoods for Nigerians.. Following this introductory section is the empirical review and theoretical framework which is contained in the second section. Section three encapsulates the methodology and data sources while section four analyzes and discusses the results of the study. Finally, conclusion, policy implications and recommendations are stated in the last section.

Literature Review

Empirical Literature

The literature on the nexus among governance, social crisis and food security for developed and developing countries have occupied the attention of researchers in recent times. Some of these empirical studies are:

Igbinedion and Aihie (2015) adopted the paradigms of positivism and interpretivism couched on inductive as well as deductive approaches to shed some light on contemporary issues of good governance and food security in Nigeria. They identified governance crisis, under capitalization, dysfunctional institutions, and poor infrastructural facilities, amongst others as factors responsible for the nation's problem of relative food insecurity. They were of the opinion that to avert the looming food crisis in the country, stakeholders at all levels should embark on the formulation and implementation of a comprehensive and sustainable food security policy aimed at fostering food availability, accessibility, and adequacy for all. They recommended for the government to provide enabling environment via the creation of investment incentives and formulation of policies that will help to enhance the purchasing power of the poor so as to attract business to rural areas.

In another study for Nigeria, Adebayo, Olagunju, Kabir and Adeyemi (2016) examined the impact of terrorism on food security in Northern Nigeria using data from Nigeria Living Standard Survey (NLSS) conducted in 2010. The result of the Ordered Probit model established plausible threat to food security in Northern Nigeria and beyond due to the activities of Boko-Haram. The study suggested that efforts by the government and international community in curbing the adverse effects of Boko-Haram activities on food availability and accessibility should be intensified.

A study by Osabohien, Osabuohien and Urhie (2018) employed the Auto-regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique over the period of 1990-2014 to examine the role of institutional framework on food security. The result revealed that institutional framework in Nigeria exerts a negative effect on food security, due to weak institutional quality in Nigeria. The study further disclosed that the high level of food insecurity in Nigeria is as a result of low attention on food production caused by the pervasive influence of oil that became the major export product. The study advocated for social protection policies to be channeled to agricultural sector in order to protect farmers that are vulnerable to shocks and as well avert risks associated with agriculture. The studies by Ajayi and Adenegan (2018); Sidibe *et al.* (2018) confirm the opinions of Osabohien *et al.* as they noted that achieving food security can be done through the enforcement of rules and laws designed at the national level which remains one of the central institutional mechanisms for efficient multi-scale governance in most countries.

Also, Munene, Swartling and Thomalla (2018) employing the adaptive governance approach shared similar view with Igbinedion and Aihie as they proved that adaptive governance (AG) is the medium to drastically change the link between development and disaster risk, with

potentially far-reaching implications for policy and practice to ensure food security. Bamidele (2020) explores the impact of governance on food security challenges in Nigeria in the era of economic recession in an emerging economy. The study identified Nigeria gloomy economy, population growth, increase in taxation VAT inclusive and closure of boarder as factors responsible for the rising hunger and hardship experienced by the citizens. The study suggested for the government to come up with food policy that ensures adequate food production in the country and as well reawaken and improve upon the entrepreneurial skills in farmers.

A report by the Standing Committee for Economic and Commercial Cooperation of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (COMCEC) (2020) established that good governance is the essential driver of achieving food security and nutrition in a country both in the short and long-terms through sustained growth and sustainable development. This was underscored in its reports which took a cursory look at the role of good governance in ensuring food security and nutrition in the OIC member countries. The COMCEC further disclosed that climate shocks (such as droughts, floods etc), and displacement of people due to conflict are the most common drivers of food insecurity and malnutrition in the OIC areas. The organization advised that the best-practice examples of the United Nations Security General's High Level Task Force be followed by Islamic Organization for food security in its efforts to support good food security governance practices within the OIC.

Osabohien, Ufua, Moses, and Osabuohien (2020) employed a descriptive approach and the Auto-regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique on annual data from 1985 to 2016 to explore the relationship between agricultural governance and food security in Nigeria. The ARDL result revealed that agricultural performance contributes to food security in the long-run. The study further found that increase in corruption rate affects undernourishment by 3.94% while political stability and absence of violence contribute to the attainment of food security. Also, the findings from the descriptive analysis disclosed that Nigeria has the highest number of undernourished people that increased by 22% between 2000 and 2001. The study recommended for accountability in addressing the challenges in the implementation of food security programs. This outcome is bolstered by the views of Bashir and Muhammad-Sani (2025) that identified corruption, patronage politics and weak institutional framework as key governance failures undermining Nigeria's food security.

Additionally, Ogunniyi, Mavrotas, Olagunju, Fadare and Adedoyin (2020) used panel dataset of 15 Sub-Saharan Africa countries from 1996-2015 and System Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) to examine the growth effects of remittances and quality of governance on food security. The study discovered that remittances and the composite index of governance quality positively and significant affects food and nutritional security. The result also confirmed that the control of corruption, government effectiveness, political stability and rule of law scores increase both measures of food and nutrition security. Also, Subramaniam, Masron and Subramaniam (2022) using the dynamic System Generalized Method of Moments shared similar view Ogunniyi *et al* as they utilized panel dataset of 56 developing to prove that institutional factors play a vital in improving the availability of food and access to nutritious food for all people, hence, ameliorating the food supply problem.

Ishola, Balogun, Kutashi and Obe (2022) conducted a study to evaluate food security as an index of good governance strategy in Kwara State. The study adopted survey method using descriptive technique to analyze the data. The finding disclosed that the government less explored the food security programs as source of good governance strategy. They advocated for government to adopt food security programs as good governance strategy to engender

security, peace and development in Kwara State and Nigeria as a whole. Equally, Ojiya, Terwuah and Tersugh (2023) employed the ARDL technique to evaluate food security-corruption nexus and households' welfare in Nigeria. The findings revealed that food insecurity was prevalent when there was interaction between corruption and disaggregated food security components but as control of corruption becomes effective, food security among households fell drastically. The study recommended for empowerment of the various anti-graft agencies in order to curtail corrupt practices.

Similarly, in evaluation of the nexus of climate change, institutional quality and food security in SSA countries, Oyelami, Edewor Folorunso and Abasilim (2023) utilized a panel dataset of 26 African countries spanning 1996-2020 and applied Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression and Cross-Sectional-Autoregressive Distributed Lag (CD-ARDL) techniques to establish that institutional quality negligibly enhance the attainment of food security. The study recommended for re-positioning and refocusing of institutional quality so as to enhance sustainable food security. In another similar study for SSA countries that employed the System Dynamic Panel Data Estimation technique, Ijaiya, Ijaiya, Ijaiya, Ijaiya (2025) revealed that government effectiveness, political stability, absence of violence and terrorism, regulatory quality and adherence to the rule of law positively correlates with food production.

In another vein, Ugbong, Amos and Ukeh (2025) examined the effect of politics and governance on food security in South-South geopolitical zone of Nigeria, using 1200 respondents selected through simple random sampling technique and analyzed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistic. The result showed that there is a significant positive effect of politics and governance on food security in South-South geopolitical zone.

From the papers reviewed so far, it is evident that most past studies focused solely on governance effectiveness and control of corruption, whereas little attention is paid to the implication of violence (which have claimed many lives and left able bodied men and women in refugee camps for years) on food production. Again, major shortfall of these studies is their inability to include employment in agriculture as critical factor for improved food security. Thus, our inclusion of the aforementioned variable in this study is based on the ground that increased labour on farms allows for more land cultivation, efficient farming practices, and the ability to handle larger harvest. In addition, a larger workforce enables diversification of crops and livestock, leading to a more robust and resilient food supply. Thus, from the fallouts in literature, this study addresses the gaps in knowledge and takes up the debate to a new level with respect to the issues of governance, violence, employment in agriculture and food security.

Theoretical Framework

The theoretical structure which this study has anchored on is the Food Entitlement Decline (FED) theory. The FED theory came into being following a reaction to the flaws of the Food Availability Decline (FAD) hypothesis. Adam Smith, in his seminal work "The Wealth of Nations" addressed the cause of famine and food shortages by implicitly emphasizing on the concept of food availability. Smith suggested that food insecurity is primarily caused by sudden decline in food availability, which in turn results in insufficient food to feed the teeming population (Lin and Yang, 2000). Based on the FAD hypothesis, armed conflicts and violence disrupt agricultural production, distribution and access, resulting in a decline in available food for the affected populations. Inadequate access to arable land, water, and modern farming techniques are another deterrent to food production, resulting in wide spread shortage that lead to famine. This traditional supply based FAD account was predominantly

used by authors for the explanation of famine and food shortages until the influential work of Amartya Sen.

The FAD hypothesis was called to question as it failed to explain why countries without shortfall in food production still perish because of hunger. The gap in the explanation resulted in the emergence of the entitlement failure theory in the 1970s advocated by Amartya Sen (1976). Sen asserted that famines are rarely caused by food availability decline (FAD), but rather an effect of either political strife or economic inequality. Sen argued that even when food is available, people can still starve if they lack the entitlement to acquire it, meaning they don't have the means to obtain food. Entitlement here refers to purchasing power of any individual or group to acquire enough nutritious food to eat. According to Sen, peoples entitlements consists among others, the amount of money they possessed, the income they earned, state and donor assistances. Be that as it may, governance via its policies can also cause entitlement failure. When governance is weak and there is widespread corruption, the impact of public spending and donor funding becomes very limited. Corruption within agricultural institutions or agencies can divert resources away from farmers, inflate input costs, and create an uneven playing ground. This assertion gained support from Mehta and Jha (2012) as they inferred that higher levels of corruption would affect food security through postponement and enforcement of stringent food security laws.

However, the theory has been criticized on the bases of some of its shortcomings. Some of such criticisms as identified by Elahi (2006) are that Sen's idea of exchange entitlement is inconsistent with the principles of capitalism, since this economic system operates on the conceptual and legal framework of voluntary exchange. He also maintained that if food is considered as an entitled commodity, other basic necessities of life, like healthcare, education etc. could claim the same status. Furthermore, the approach is founded on a hidden hypothesis that income distributions in non-communist states are economically and politically optimal. However, regardless of these shortcomings, what is notable is that the theory gives a tenable explanation of the causation of starvation and famine to be the socio-economic and political processes.

Methodology

To achieve the objectives of this study, this paper followed a sequence of approaches. First, to check the other of integration of the series, a test of unit root was conducted using both the augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) and the Philip Perron tests. The results of the unit root tests showing that the series have mixed order of integration, that is integrated of order 1(1) and 1(0) indicated that the wald-test under the bounds testing approach to cointegration is more appropriate. Since the existence of cointegration among the variables in the model was established, the study estimated the long-run and short-run impacts in Equations(3.4) and (3.5) below through the ARDL cointegration method. The justification for the selection of this method is based on the advantage that the long and short-run parameters of the model can be estimated simultaneously. The computation of the ARDL statistical procedure was done with version 10 of the E-views econometric software. But before estimating the growth equation, the performance of the model was verified through the diagnostic test. Thereafter, the Toda and Yamamoto causality test was employed to determine the direction of causality among the variables.

Model Specification

The model for this study assumed a functional relationship between indicators of governance quality, social crisis and food production index as proxy for food security. It hinges on the theoretical underpinning of food entitlement decline, which has governance and socio-economic processes as basic explanatory variables that could explain production capacity of a country, especially in the agricultural sector. Governance can influence the level of food security as it has been argued that the quality of a country's governance can determine the extent of growth in food production. Also violence used to proxy social crisis lead directly to reduced agricultural output. The model also allows the incorporation of other variables considered to be essential in the production capacity of a country. Employment rate in agriculture has been noted as major driver of food production in Nigeria. Thus, the model can be simplified implicitly as:

$$FPI = f(GOVEF, CONTC, VOL, EMPA) \quad 3.1$$

Equation (3.1) can be represented in an econometric form as:

$$FPI_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 GOVEF_t + \alpha_2 CONTC_t + \alpha_3 VOL_t + \alpha_4 EMPA_t + \varepsilon_t \quad 3.2$$

Where: $GOVEF_t$ = governance effectiveness, $CONTC_t$ = control of corruption, VOL_t = violence, $EMPA_t$ = employment in agriculture, ε_t = error term, t as attached to each variable indicates its time value.

All things being equal, the theoretical expectation of the coefficients of the explanatory variables is as follows: $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_4 > 0$; $\alpha_3 < 0$. This is predicated on the belief that increase in GOVEF, CONTC and EMPA is expected to enhance the rate of food outcome in Nigeria, while violence will hamper food production.

To estimate the formulated model, logarithmic transformation of some of the variables were used. This is to bring the variables to a more comparable form and as well reduce the problem of heteroscedasticity. Restating Equation (3.2) in ARDL form in line with the framework of Pesaran, Smith and Shin (2001) and as well taking the natural log of some of the variable, we have:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \log(FPI_t) = & \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_1 \Delta \log(FPI_{t-1}) + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_2 \Delta GOVEF_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_3 \Delta CONTC_{t-1} \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_4 \Delta \log(VOL_{t-1}) + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_5 \Delta EMPA_{t-1} + \beta_6 \log(FPI_{t-1}) \\ & + \beta_7 GOVEF_{t-1} + \beta_8 CONTC_{t-1} + \beta_9 VOL_{t-1} + \beta_{10} EMPA_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \end{aligned} \quad 3.3$$

Where: log as attached to a variable indicates its logarithm value, Δ , n, $\beta_0, \beta_1 - \beta_5$ and $\beta_6 - \beta_{10}$, denote the first difference operator, lag length, the intercept, parameters of the short-run dynamics and parameters of the long-run relationship respectively. Other variables are as defined earlier.

Before estimating the ARDL model, it is important to ascertain the existence or absence of cointegration among the variables by restricting the coefficients of the lagged level variables to be equal to zero. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H_0) of no cointegration is stated as:

$$H_0 : \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \beta_4 = \beta_5 = 0$$

H_0 is tested against the alternative hypothesis of the presence of cointegration among the variables as:

$$H_0 : \beta_1 = \beta_2 = \beta_3 = \beta_4 = \beta_5 = 0$$

The above test can be carried out by comparing the computed F-statistic with the critical bounds proposed first by Pesaran and Shin (1999) and developed by Pesaran *et al.* (2001).

In conducting the test, we compared the F-statistic with both the upper 1(1) and lower 1(0) critical values at the 5% level. If the calculated F-statistic is more than the upper critical bound 1(1), the series are cointegrated; if it is less than the lower critical bound 1(0), the series are not. Nonetheless, the result becomes inconclusive if the calculated F-statistic lies between the lower and higher critical bound values. Meanwhile, since the series proved to be cointegrated, the long-run and short-run impacts of each variable on food security would be evaluated. The long-run elasticities were calculated using OLS as shown:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Log}(FPI_t) = & \beta_0 + \beta_1 \log(FPI_{t-1}) + \beta_2 GOVEF_{t-1} + \beta_3 CONTC_{t-1} \\ & + \beta_4 \log(VOL_{t-1}) + \beta_5 EMPA_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \end{aligned} \quad 3.4$$

After examining the long-run estimates, the short-run coefficients shall be examined by constructing an error correction model as depicted in Equation (3.5).

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \log(FPI_t) = & \beta_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_1 \Delta \log(FPI_{t-i}) + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_2 \Delta GOVEF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_3 \Delta CONTC_{t-i} \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_4 \Delta \log(VOL_{t-i}) + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_5 \Delta EMPA_{t-i} + \lambda ECM_{t-1} + \varepsilon_t \end{aligned} \quad 3.5$$

Where λ is the parameter which indicates the speed of adjustment to long-run equilibrium following a shock to the system and is anticipated to be negative and significant to prove the existence of cointegration among the variables. ECM_{t-1} is the lagged error correction term which shows how disequilibrium in the system can be adjusted in the short-run. The study also investigated the direction of causality among the variables using Toda and Yamamoto test for Granger non-causality.

Data and their Sources

Annual time series data from 2005 to 2023 was employed to estimate the model. The selection of the time was based on the availability of data for the variables selected. All the data were extracted from the World Governance Indicator database, except the data on violence and employment in agriculture, which were sourced from the Nigeria Watch Database, an online database on lethal violence in Nigeria and World Bank (WB), World Development Indicator (WDI) 2024 respectively. Food production index is used to proxy food security and is measured in metric tonnes, governance indicators (government

effectiveness, control of corruption) measures how public institutions conduct public affairs, manage public resources, and ensure the realization of human rights, and the measure ranges from -2.5 (weak) to 2.5 (strong), violence used as proxy for social crisis measures the number of lethal violence and conflicts and employment in agriculture is measured as the percentage of the employable population.

Results and Discussion of Findings

This section of the study starts first by presenting and analyzing the results obtained from descriptive statistics.

The descriptive statistics results in Table 1 indicate that food production records the highest annual average and median value of 96.61% and 95.48% respectively as well as the highest volatility as its range is the highest (15.53). The maximum value of 119.85 reveals that the highest metric tonnes of food produced was 119.9% and this was achieved in 2022, indicating potential and resilience within the Nigerian agricultural sector, but the actual positive impact on food security and the economy was heavily diluted by deep-seated systematic and environmental challenges. The results also showed that the means medians of all the variables lies within the maximum and minimum values, suggesting that the variables have high tendency to be normally distributed. In another vein, it revealed a negative mean value of GOVEF and CONTC, indicating weak governance during the period of the study. The skewness result obtained shows that GOVEF and LVOL were negative, indicating a left-skewed distribution while LFPI and EMPA has no skew, thus revealing that their distributions are symmetrical on both sides of the tail. Equally, CONTC is positively skewed, meaning that the distribution is skewed to the right. The kurtosis statistics equally reveal that LFPI, GOVEF, LVOL and EMPA were platkurtic, implying that their distributions were flat relative to normal distribution while CONTC is lepokurtic, suggesting that its distribution is more peaked and fat-tailed than the normal distribution. Finally, the Jarque-Bera result reveals that the series are normally distributed as their probability values are higher than the usual criterion of 0.05.

Table 1. Results of Descriptive Statistics of the Indicators

	LFPI	GOVEF	CONTC	LVOL	EMPA
Mean	96.6074	-1.0326	-0.9869	9.1474	44.6875
Median	95.4800	-1.0200	-1.1000	9.3300	44.2756
Maximum	119.8500	-0.8500	1.0400	10.0400	53.3425
Minimum	75.5400	-1.2100	-1.2700	8.1600	34.3124
Std. Dev.	15.5270	0.0935	0.4977	0.5045	2.6111
Skewness	0.1363	-0.1943	3.8262	-0.2263	0.1478
Kurtosis	1.3958	2.7517	6.1478	2.2152	2.7517
Jarqu-Bera	2.0961	0.16831	3.2103	0.6497	0.1180
Prob.	0.3506	0.9193	0.0000	0.7226	0.9427

Source: Researchers' Compilation (2025) using E-Views 10.

The stationarity results in Table 2 show that the variables (GOVEF, CONTC) were integrated at their levels 1(0), while all other series (LFPI, LVOL, EMPA) achieved stationarity after the first difference at the 5% level of significance. This is to say that the series becomes 1(1) after differencing the series. The ADF results were validated through the PP unit root test. The findings depict that the results of the PP unit root test are a corroboration of those

realized utilizing the ADF. Therefore, the combination of 1(1) and 1(0) exhibited by the series justify the usage of the ARDL technique to estimate the parameters of the model.

Table 2. Estimated Unit Root Test Results of the Indicators

Variable	Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF)				Philip-Perron (PP)			
	At Level	1 st Value	5% Critical Order of Difference	Integration	At Level	1 st Difference Value	5% Critical Order of Difference	Integration
LFPI	-1.0376	-7.6873**	-3.0656	(1)	-0.5439	-6.8817**	-3.0522	(1)
GOVEF	-3.6589**	-	-3.0404	(0)	-3.6589**	-	-3.0404	(0)
CONTC	-3.6934**	-	-3.0404	(0)	-3.6934**	-	-3.0404	(0)
LVOL	-2.1309-3.4031**	-	-3.0656	(1)	-2.0857-5.1038**	-	-3.0656	(1)
EMPA	-0.6362-5.4917**	-	-3.0656	(1)	-0.7430 -5.4917**	-	-3.0656	(1)

Source: Researchers' Compilation (2025) using E-Views 10; Note: ** implies significance at 5% level.

To confirm the robustness of the model estimates for the food security equation, the results were subjected to various econometric tests such as: Jarque-Bera normality test, heteroscedasticity, Ramsey test for model misspecification and serial LM correlation. The diagnostic estimates are summarized below:

Table 3. Diagnostic results for ARDL model

Test	Type of Statistic	Test Statistic	P-value
Jarque-Bera normal test	X ²	0.615470	0.7351
Heteroskedasticity Test: ARCH	X ²	1.161011	0.2995
Ramsey RESET test	F	1.169393	0.2805
Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM test	X ²	2.323130	0.1790

Source: Researchers' Compilation (2025) using E-Views 10

The diagnostic test results reported in Table 3, revealed that the residuals are normally distributed. The findings further revealed that there was no problems of heteroskedasticity, misspecification and serial correlation in the model. Their probability values which were greater than the suggested 5% level of significance substantiate this. The implication of this outcome is that the parameter estimates can be utilized in making economic deductions.

Meanwhile, it is germane to ensure appropriate lag order selection before conducting the cointegration test. In retrospect, four different information criteria have been used, namely: the Hannan-Quinn information criterion (HQ), the Schwarz information criterion (SIC), the Final prediction error criterion (FPE), and the Akaike information criterion (AIC). The results of these information criteria as shown in Table 4 below, showed that both AIC, SIC, HQ and FPE selected lag 2, indicating that the optimal lag adopted in this study is lag 2.

Table 4: Lag Length Selection

Lag Length	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SIC	HQ
0	-90.29	NA	005	11.21	11.46	11.23
1	-33.81	73.09	0.001	7.51	8.98	7.65
2	24.25	40.98*	8.79*	3.62*	6.31*	3.89*

Source: Researchers' Compilation (2025) using E-Views 10; Note: * indicates lag order by the criterion.

Having identified the optimal lag length, the study moved on to test for the cointegrating relationship among the series. The Bounds test result in Table 5 revealed that the computed F-statistic (4.322881) is higher than the upper bounds value of 4.01 at the 5% significance level. The result implies that long-run relationships exist among the variables employed in the model.

Table 5: Bound Test Results for the Existence of Co-integration

Test Statistic	Value	Lag	Significance level	Bound critical values	
				Lower Bound	Upper Bound
F-statistic	4.322881	2		1(0)	1(1)
			1%	3.745.06	
			5%	2.864.01	
			10%	2.45	3.52

Source: Researchers' Compilation (2025) using E-Views 10; Note: Lower and Upper Bounds critical values for the F-statistics at 5% significance level were taken from Pesaran *et al.* (2001).

Based on the above, the results of the short and long-run equilibrium relationship between governance indicators, social crisis and food security in Nigeria from 2005 to 2023 are shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Results of Estimated Long-run and Short-run Coefficients

Variables	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-statistic	P-value
Long-run behavior Dependent Variable: LFPI				
C	95.755271	81.055789	1.633504	0.0410
GOVEF	-44.4706688	31.100857	-1.429886	0.0764*
CONTC	-17.325361	9.648731	-1.795610	0.0103**
LVOL	-9.196517	11.104259	-0.828197	0.0316**
EMPA	-5.130631	2.403422	-2.134720	0.0653*
Short-run dynamics				
D(LFPI(-1))	-0.608800	0.144272	4.219810	0.0029***
D(GOVEF)	15.214432	10.528298	1.445099	0.1864
D(CONTC)	5.927400	4.235688	1.399395	0.0993*
D(LVOL)	-3.146338	3.614785	0.870408	0.0494**
D(EMPA)	8.442092	2.681272	3.148540	0.0136**
ECM _{t-1}	-0.342123	0.109584	-3.122006	0.0142**

Source: Researchers' Compilation (2025) using E-Views 10; Note: ***, ** and * denote significance at 1%, 5% and 10% levels respectively.

Based on the ARDL short and long-run results depicted in Table 6, surprisingly the two governance indicators: governance effectiveness and control of corruption had a negative and significant impact on food production in Nigeria in the long-run which defies theoretical expectation. This finding suggests that current governance and anti-corruption efforts of the government are not reaching the agricultural sector or addressing the key challenges faced by farmers in the country, reflecting weak policy implementation, corruption, and lack of farmer's inclusion in food policies which invariably hinder efforts to improve food

productivity in the country. In other words, most policies to enhance food production in Nigeria exist only on paper, therefore, does not translate into practical changes that farmers feel. Other reasons attributed to this may be the preponderance of corrupt practices such as diversion of funds, machineries and agricultural inputs meant for the development of the agricultural sector which invariably hinder efforts to improve food security in the country. The results indicate that a unit increase in governance effectiveness and control of corruption would reduce food production by 44.47% and 17.33% respectively. Although their relationships appear negative, it is statistically strong, highlighting the importance of addressing governance weaknesses so as to achieve self food sufficiency in Nigeria. These results find corroboration in the findings of Osabohien *et al.* (2020); Ishola *et al.* (2022); Oyelami *et al.* (2023); Bashir and Muhammad-Sani (2025) but contradicts the submissions of Ogunniyi *et al.* (2020); Subramaniam *et al.* (2022); Ugbon *et al.* (2025); Ijaiya *et al.* (2025).

As was expected, violence had a negative and significant impact on food production in Nigeria. This entails that rising violent conflict- whether from insurgency, banditry, farmer-herder clashes, and community conflicts disrupts agricultural activities in the country. This finding supports conflict theories which argue that violence limits farmers' access to farmland, discourages investments in agriculture, destroys crops and livestock, and reduces rural labour supply through displacement or migration, which invariably suppresses food production. The result suggests that a unit increase in violence would decrease food production by 9.20%. This finding conform those submissions of Adebayo *et al.* 2016; Ijaiya *et al.* (2025).

One more terrifying long-run result which defies expectation is the influence of employment in agriculture on food production. Employment in agriculture exerted a negative and significant impact on food production which implies that increasing employment in agriculture does not necessarily lead to higher food production in Nigeria. This finding reflect the presence of disguised unemployment, where a large portion of the labour force in Nigeria contributes little or marginal increase in output due to the use of outdated farming techniques, poor access to inputs, and limited mechanization. Also, even as more people participate in the sector, fragmentation of farmlands and inadequate investment in modern agricultural infrastructure hinder productivity growth in the country. The finding showed that a unit increase in employment in agriculture would lead to 5.13% decrease in food production. Nevertheless, the significance of the variable underscores the pivotal roles of promoting the adoption of modern technologies, implementing consistent and supportive policies and ensuring access to finance to farmers, in a more sustainable and productive agricultural sector.

In the short-run, the coefficient of food production in the past year was negative and significant. Additionally, change in governance effectiveness and control of corruption exerted a positive and significant effects on food production in the short-run contrary with the long-run result. The result suggests that if governance effectiveness and corruption control goes up by 1%, food production will increase by 15.21 units and 5.93 units respectively. Furthermore, change in violence had a negative and significant effect on food production in the short-run in line with results of the long-run growth equation. Employment in agriculture exerted a positive and significant effect on food production contrary to the result of the long-run equation. A unit increase in employment in agriculture would increase food production by 8.44%. Obviously, this short-run result appears more credible given the fact that most food policies in Nigeria are geared towards addressing short term challenges, hence, giving credence to Keynes assertion that, "in the long-run we are all dead" (Keynes, 1936). The coefficient of the error correction term ECM (-1) is negative and significant which supports the result of the cointegrating relationship among the variables. This indicates that in an event

of disequilibrium, there is tendency for the economy to adjust towards long-run equilibrium with a speed of 34%.

Table 7: Results of the granger causality test (TY Augmented Lags Methods)

Dependent Variable	Sources of Causation				
	LFPI	GOVEF	CONTC	LVOL	EMPA
	X^2	X^2	X^2	X^2	X^2
LFPI	-	1.582939	4.477950	4.833421	6.064873
		(0.0532)**	(0.0066)***	(0.0892)*	(0.0482)**
GOVEF	5.541235	-	5.183213	1.202122	3.363740
	(0.0626)*	(0.0749)*	(0.0482)**	(0.1860)	
CONTC	1.956257	1.292887	-	0.839371	52.73656
	(0.0760)*	(0.5239)		(0.6573)	(0.0000)***
LVOL	2.190730	7.343194	1.190983	-	9.508643
	(0.0344)**	(0.0254)**	(0.5513)		(0.0086)***
EMPA	0.671334	1.365071	0.862843	0.535277	-
	(0.7149)	(0.5053)	(0.6496)	(0.7652)	

Source: Researchers' Compilation (2025) using E-Views 10; Note: ***, ** and * denote significance at 1%, 5% and 10% levels respectively. The figures outside the bracket and those in bracket are the X^2 -statistic with their respective P-values.

Table 7 show the outcomes of the Toda and Yamamoto multivariate causality tests. The results showed a bidirectional correlation between governance effectiveness, corruption control, violence and food production in Nigeria, implying that these variables influence each other in both directions. This result raises the possibility that Nigeria could simultaneously work towards improving its governance, security and increasing its agricultural productivity. The findings of Adebayo *et al.* (2016); Osabohien *et al.* (2018); Osabohien *et al.* (2020); Ojiya *et al.* (2023) and Ijaija *et al.* (2025) are in line with those of this study. It does, however, concur with the assertions that poor governance and corruption can exacerbate grievances that lead to conflict, and persistent violence makes governance reforms more difficult to sustain. This creates a circle in which institutions and security conditions influence each other and jointly affect agricultural productivity.

Additionally, the findings showed a unidirectional causality running from employment in agriculture to food production, indicating that policies that improve labour productivity (such as skill development training, farm mechanization, incentives, land access, credit facilities) could improve food output in the country. The arrows indicating the direction of causality between the variables is depicted in Table 8.

Table 8: The causality results among governance, social crisis and food production

Note: arrows indicate the direction of Granger causality between the variables

Conclusions, Policy Implications and Recommendations

Examining the link among governance, social crisis and food production is crucial and requires urgent attention as the cases of hunger and malnutrition abound currently in Nigeria. This study used annual time series data gotten from World Bank, World Development Indicator (WB,WDI), World Governance Indicator (WGI) and Nigeria Watch Database from 2005-2023 to investigate the linkages between the aforementioned variables in Nigeria. The ARDL methodology and the Toda and Yamamoto Multivariate Causality test were utilized in this study. The co-integration result confirmed that a long-run relationship actually exists among the variables employed in the model. The long-run findings revealed that governance, control of corruption, violence and employment in agriculture had a significant negative effect on food security, indicating that poor governance practices (like policy inconsistency, lack of accountability, weak institutions e.t.c), insecurity and inefficient use of labour are key barriers to achieving sustainable food security in Nigeria. The implication is that agricultural policies must be integrated with reforms in governance, anti-corruption efforts, security management and human capital development in order to achieve Sustainable Development Goal (SDG2); which aims at eliminating hunger, achieving sustainable food security and improving nutrition globally by year 2030.

On the other hand, evidence of a positive and significant effects of governance effectiveness, control of corruption and employment in agriculture on food production in Nigeria in the short-run has been shown, hence, indicative of their crucial role on enhancing food security in Nigeria. Apart from these negative and positive effects, the study also noted that a bidirectional relationship existed between governance effectiveness, control of corruption, violence and food production. This implies that the aforementioned variables have a reciprocal links with food production in Nigeria. This cyclical relationship indicates that better governance strengthens agricultural policies, improves implementation of rural development programs, enhances access to farm inputs and reduces diversion of agricultural funds, which in turn, boost food output. Conversely, increased food production contributes to socioeconomic stability, reduces public pressure on government, strengthens state legitimacy, and supports better governance outcomes. Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made: Policies aimed at improving governance should be tailored to directly benefit rural farmers through transparent agricultural financing, effective policy implementation, and reduction of bureaucratic delays in agricultural programs. Additionally, the government should adopt a comprehensive approach that involves strengthening institutional capacity, tackling corruption at all levels, implementing targeted peace building and food production initiatives in order to achieve lasting stability and food security in Nigeria.

Limitations of the study

In this study, data on food production index and violence were drawn from World Development Indicator (WDI) and Nigeria Watch database respectively. The data were available up to 2020, and this would have nearly resulted to small sample bias during analysis. Nonetheless, we surmounted this limitation by interpolating the data up to 2023. Also, among the four fundamental pillars of food security - food availability, food access, food consumption and food stability, we focused only on food availability.

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Imperatives of Physical Distribution (Transportation) as a Catalyst for Sustainable Agricultural Practice and Food Security: The Nigerian Experience (A Review Article)

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Abstract

The role of physical Distribution (transportation) in the socio-economic development of a given nation cannot be over emphasized. This is because transportation network is a catalyst for a sustainable agricultural practice and food security which by extension enhances economic and social development of a nation. Considering its relevance in a nation's economy, the area thus calls for research especially in developing countries like Nigeria with transportation constraints. In this study, the focus was to review extant literatures on studies that examined how Physical Distribution (transportation) impacts agricultural practices and food security. The papers reviewed relate to this topic and which are indexed in popular databases such as Google Scholars, Scopus, Web of Science, Thompson Reuters and the likes. Also in this study, the papers reviewed contained Physical Distribution, transportation, sustainable agricultural practices, food security, economic and social development amongst others as their key words. The study also defined some key conceptual issues for operational purposes. The thematic approach was used to summarize the extant literatures reviewed. The findings from the extant literatures thus reviewed showed a variety of outcomes. Findings from the numerous papers point to the fact that Physical Distribution (Transportation) plays a vital role in Food Security and economic development of a given nation and especially Nigeria. Looking at the importance of effective Physical distribution (transportation) in enhanced agricultural practice and food security, and findings from the various papers thus reviewed, it becomes imperative to recommend factors that may aid its effective operations.

Keywords: Physical Distribution, Transportation, Sustainable Agricultural Practices, Food Security, Social and Economic Development.

Introduction

Marketing activity revolves around the four major Ps of Product, Price, Promotion and place. These elements must mix and complement each other in a suitable proportion as to create a synergy that guarantees the success of the marketing effort (Egu and Akalazu, 2012). Physical distribution represents the 'Place' function of the marketing mix variables which ensures that a given product and service is available at the right place and at the right time. It guarantees the movement of goods including food products from points of production to points of consumption.

From a micro perspective, transportation is one of the components of physical distribution activities. At a macro level, transportation,, plays an important role in the economic life of a

given nation .Even at the global level, transportation is the bases of all socio-economic and political integration and interactions. This is essentially so as a good transportation system is a catalyst for sustainable agricultural practice and food security especially in developing country like Nigeria where agriculture plays a dominant role for economic survival. This being the case, no government can achieve a meaningful progress in its agricultural and economic development programmes without an efficient transportation system. Suffice it to say that one major problem militating against the economic development of many developing countries like Nigeria is poor or inadequate transportation system. Transportation engages in physical distribution of goods through the modes of road, rail, air, water, pipeline and the likes.(Olayiwola and Adeleye,2005)

By so doing, transportation serves as a link between the manufacturer and the final consumer.

Transportation also bridges the spatial gaps amongst the fixed facilities like warehouse, factory, and market. It should be recalled that goods produced by the agricultural practice have little or no value until they are moved to where they are required. By this singular function, transportation increases the value of agricultural products , thus creating time and place utilities while also promoting possession utility...(Ajiboye and Afolayan 2009). It should be mentioned that transportation involves movement of raw materials, semi-processed and finished goods alike. Its relevance in enhancing agricultural practice and food security thus becomes glaring.

Food security in turn connotes the availability, accessibility, utilization and stability of food supplies to ensure that all people have access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food (FAO,2008). Looking at the above, food security is a sine –qua –non to a good and healthy living. When you have food and it is not safe, sufficient or nutritious, it may be said that it is better you do not have food at all. Food security does not stem only from good agricultural practice, but more from effective physical distribution which by extension involves transportation.

From the foregoing, a suitable conceptual framework may be developed for physical distribution (transportation) and food security that involves an understanding of the critical role of transportation in ensuring the availability, accessibility, and affordability of food products

Conceptual Framework – Researcher Desk, 2025.

When the integration of the above components is well and efficiently coordinated, it will likely lead to positive outcomes in areas of food availability and food accessibility especially in rural or remote areas. It may also help in food utilization as proper transportation and storage ensure that the food products are safe, reducing food waste and food borne illnesses to bring food stability. This is achievable as reliable transportation system helps to maintain stable food supplies and by so doing reduces the risk of price shocks or hikes and shortages.

Food Security

Food Security exists when all people at all times, have physical and economic access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food that meets their dietary needs and food preferences for an active and healthy life (World Food Summit, 1996).

Going by the above definition we may illustrate, four main aspects of food security:

Physical Availability of Food

Food availability addresses the “supply side” of food security and is determined by the level of food production, stock levels and net trade

Economic and Physical Access to Food.

An adequate supply of food at the national or international level does not in itself guarantee household level food security. Concerns about insufficient food access have resulted in a greater policy focus on incomes, expenditure, markets and prices in achieving food security objectives.

Food Utilization

Utilization is commonly understood as the way the body makes the most of various nutrients in the food. Sufficient energy and nutrient intake by individuals is the result of good care and feeding practices, food preparation, diversity of the diet and intra-household distribution of food. Combined with good biological utilization of food consumed, this determines the *nutritional status* of individuals

Stability of the other three dimensions over time

Even if your food intake is adequate today, you are still considered to be food insecure if you have inadequate access to food on a periodic basis, risking a deterioration of your nutritional status. Adverse weather conditions, political instability, or economic factors (unemployment, rising food prices) may have an impact on your food security status

For food security objectives to be realized, all four dimensions must be fulfilled simultaneously (e-learning course, on ‘Food Security Concepts, FAO, 2008).

Types of Food Insecurity.

Ordinarily, Food security analysts have identified two general types of food insecurity. These are

Chronic Food Insecurity:

Chronic Food Insecurity is usually for a long-term and it is persistent. It normally occurs when people are unable to meet their minimum food requirements over a sustained period of time. Chronic Food Insecurity usually results from extended periods of poverty, lack of assets and inadequate access to productive or financial resources.

Chronic Food Insecurity can be overcome with typical long term development measures also used to address poverty, such as education or access to productive resources, such as credit. They may also need more direct access to food to enable them to raise their productive capacity.

Transitory Food Insecurity

As the name suggests, Transitory Food Insecurity is short-term and temporary. There is a sudden drop in the ability to produce or access enough food to maintain a good nutritional status. It usually arises from short-term shocks and fluctuations in food availability and food access, including year-to-year variations in domestic food production, food prices and household incomes

Transitory food insecurity is relatively unpredictable and can emerge suddenly. This makes planning and programming more difficult and requires different capacities and types of intervention, including early warning capacity and safety net programmes

The concept of seasonal food security falls between chronic and transitory food insecurity. It is similar to chronic food insecurity as it is usually predictable and follows a sequence of known events. However, as seasonal food insecurity is of limited duration it can also be seen as recurrent, transitory food insecurity. It occurs when there is a *cyclical pattern* of inadequate availability and access to food. This is associated with seasonal fluctuations in the climate, cropping patterns, work opportunities (labour demand) and disease. (e-learning course, on 'Food Security Concepts, FAO, 2008).

When analyzing food insecurity, it is not enough to know the duration of the problem that people are experiencing, but also how intense or severe the impact of the identified problem is on the overall food security and nutrition status. This knowledge will influence the nature, extent and urgency of the assistance needed by affected population groups.

Different 'scales' or 'phases' to 'grade' or 'classify' food security have been developed by food security analysts using different indicators and cut-off points or benchmarks'. A predominant example is:

Measuring the Severity of Undernourishment

The measure for hunger compiled by FAO, defined as undernourishment, refers to the proportion of the population whose dietary energy consumption is less than a pre-determined threshold. This threshold is country specific and is measured in terms of the number of kilocalories required to conduct sedentary or light activities. The undernourished are also referred to as suffering from food deprivation.

Physical Distribution (Transportation)

Physical distribution is one of the key marketing variables that complement one another to achieve desired synergy. Physical distribution is one of the fundamental and important aspect of marketing mix variables that adds enormous value to products by creating place utility, time utility, quantity utility, price utility, form utility and possession utility (Nebo et al., 2020; Ajah et al., 2020). The activities that allow the free movement of agricultural produce from production centers or from the farm to where they are needed by the consumers or industrial customers are known as agricultural marketing (Abugu et al., 2020). According to Abugu et al. (2020), transportation, storage, processing and handling make up these activities. Nevertheless, transportation is more pivotal to the completion of the physical distribution process (Ajah et al., 2020) because a good transportation system is indispensable in ensuring effective distribution of agricultural produce (Ajiboye & Afolayan, 2009). Unfortunately, bad transportation network has continued to plague the free movement of agricultural or farm produce from place to place (Adefalu et al., 2016). Apparently, due to the bad nature of rural Nigerian roads, it became very hard for commuters and other vehicles to penetrate the farms to load and transport farm produce such as yam, cassava, cocoyam, maize, millet, mellon, cowpea, soybean, potato, tomato, plantain, beans, rice, garri, other fruits and vegetables etc., from the farms to the existing local and urban markets. In other words, majority of the farm roads in Nigeria are impassable to the extent that farmers carry their farm input and output on their heads in search of available farms and markets. Unequivocally, Umeh et al. (2018) revealed that the traditional means of transportation such use of head, donkeys, camels, wheel barrows, bicycles, motor cycles, motor van, and tricycles (Keke) are being used for

transporting farm produce in the localities. Moreover, besides the problems of bad road networks and fewer numbers of vehicles, high transportation costs have immensely truncated the growth of agricultural production in Ikwo local government area of Ebonyi State, Nigeria.

Emphatically, the task involved in linking many of the agricultural producing areas with available markets is not easy owing to the fact that agricultural produce are not geographically concentrated but rather dispersed (Kohls & Uhl, 1985). Despondently, inadequate infrastructure and transportation services have posed serious threats to food production and circulation in Nigeria and other developing countries in the world (Ajiboye & Afolayan, 2009). In addition, Ajiboye (2016) revealed that high transportation cost affected the distribution of agricultural produce in Nigeria. Incidentally, during post-harvest or farming season, food storage can be used to forestall food scarcity (Abugu et al., 2020).

Logistics and Supply Chain Management

Logistics and Supply chain management are critical components of every business that involves the production, distribution and delivery of the products and services. Marketing activity revolves around the marketing mix variables of product, price, promotion and place (distribution). The activity of one compliments the other in achieving organizational goals and economic enhancement. This being the case, the role of distribution via logistics and supply chain management in achieving the time, place and possession utilities is paramount. It is often said that a good product with a good price and being well promoted without being at the right place and time when needed, have certainly missed its target. The overall impact of distribution in the total marketing mix-up to achieve organizational objective especially in the proper and efficient movement, storage and control of both raw materials and finished products, cannot be over emphasized.

In carrying out its distribution functions, an organization must take thorough management of its logistics and supply chain. Inclusive therefore in its logistics is the role of warehousing, distribution centres, transportation management, inventory management, freight forwarding, packaging and labeling, sourcing and procurement, production planning and scheduling , demand forecasting and planning etc(World Bank, 2018).

The Council for supply chain management professionals(CSCMP 2020) defines logistics management as that part of supply chain management that plans, implements and controls the efficient, effective forward and reverse flow and storage of goods, services and related information between the point of origin and the point of consumption in order to meet customer's requirements. World Bank (2018) feels logistics and supply chain management are critical components of economic development as they enable the efficient flow of goods, services and information. They further emphasized that the importance of logistics and supply chain management in economic development cannot be overstated as they go a long way to directly impact on economic growth, trade and competitiveness.

Conversely, the supply chain Research Group at the University of Tennessee(Mentzer, 2004) defined supply chain management as the systematic coordination of the traditional business functions within a particular company and across businesses within the supply chain, for the purposes of improving the long-term performance of the individual companies and the supply chain as a whole. Logistics and Supply Chain Management Society(2019) in turn, opines that supply chain is a network of organizations, people, activities, information and resources involved in the production and delivery of a product or service. It encompasses all the activities involved in sourcing, producing and delivering a product or service to the end customer.

Logistics focuses on the movement and storage of goods while supply chain management encompasses the entire process, from sourcing to delivery. Logistics ordinarily is a subset of supply chain management which includes a broader range of activities. Logistics refers to the planning, coordination and execution of the movement and storage of goods, products or resources from one place to another.

The major objective of logistics is to optimize the movement and storage of goods while supply chain management aims to optimize the entire supply chain to meet customer demand. It therefore connotes that marketing logistics aims also to maximize profit and not sales, by bringing about the physical movement of products at reasonable costs to the consumers or producers while maintaining a reasonable level of customer service, this can be achieved by guiding the firm's planning schedules.

Transportation Infrastructure and Modes

Transport is a key to efficient and effective distribution of agricultural products at a cost and time convenient for both the producers and the consumers. However, the rural transport is poor resulting in the high cost of transportation, inefficient distribution and delay in reaching the final markets in Sub-Saharan Africa. The consequences are high crop rot which affects farmer's income and subsequently their level of investment resulting in vicious cycle of low production

The conventional approach towards agricultural transport in Sub-Saharan Africa focuses mostly on motorized transport. This approach is too narrow because it does not reflect the transport requirements and purchasing power of small-scale farmers. A broader approach that includes not only roads, but also paths and tracks; not only trucks but also intermediate means of transport such as donkeys, bicycles and animal carts can considerably improve agricultural transport (Sieber, 2010). Even though the effects of an appropriate approach on agricultural production, marketing and income can be significant, it is more often rejected by decision-makers as primitive and backward.

Current rural travel and transport are dominated by head loading and walking (largely by women) to satisfy the daily travel and goods movement needs of rural populations in Sub-Saharan Africa (John & Carapetis, 1991). Starkey (2001) noted a low adoption of intermediate means of transport (IMT) in rural Africa compared to the rest of the developing world and sees this as a constraint to rural development. (Ahmed & Rustagi, 1987) stated that crops remain un-harvested or become spoilt once harvested because of unavailability of vehicles during harvesting. Tracey-White (2005) also, noted that mobility in rural areas could be hampered by the lack of transportation facilities and unavailability of good roads. Availability of transport facilities is a critical investment factor that stimulates economic growth through increased accessibility, its efficiency and effectiveness (Ajiboye, 1994). All affects the basic function of production, distribution, marketing and consumption in many ways. Transportation also influences the cost of commodity consumed and the purchasing power of the consumers (Ajiboye and Afolayan, 2009). Transport plays a significant role in the structure of food production and marketing, besides, easy transport to market can make all the difference in the level of rural incomes. Transport is seen as a necessary ingredient in all aspects of economic and social development. It plays a key role in getting land into production and in marketing agricultural produce. Poor roads characterize rural areas in Sub-Saharan Africa. In virtually all the cases, these roads are perpetually in a state of disrepair. Yet, it is on these deplorable roads that the rural dwellers trek daily to obtain water,

Rural Transportation System

Rural transportation mostly includes animal traction, car, truck, train and other intermediary means of transport (IMT) such as motorcycle, bicycle, boat and canoe mostly adapted for local transport problems with low and medium loads (Sieber, 1999). Rural roads and transport are essential for sustaining agricultural development. Recognizing this, the World Bank and others in the donor community have provided financial support to African countries to improve their rural road infrastructure (John & Carapetis, 1991). Despite this, traffic on most rural roads still consists mainly of pedestrians often carrying head loads. African governments have relied on parastatal truck fleets for crop transport. Fuel subsidies, and other policy measures have not helped to improve rural transport services. Chronic scarcity of foreign exchange, lack of spare parts and low vehicle imports have also hampered the development of 82 motorized rural transport services. Moreover, the rural poor usually cannot afford these services. These factors call for alternative and affordable means of transport. Therefore, there is a need to explore the potential of bicycles and other intermediate and low-cost means of transport for improving rural access and personal mobility. The development of smallholder agriculture in developing countries is very sensitive to transport strategies. Many isolated farmers have little opportunity to escape poverty, as their potential marketing activities are hampered by inadequate or poor transport facilities. According to Gebresenbet and Bosana (2012), Rural transport is usually classified into on-farm and off-farm transport.

On-farm transportation includes:

- a. transportation within fields
 - i. collecting harvested crops to one point for processing in the fields and temporary storage;
 - ii. distribution of fertilizers and seeds;
 - iii. transporting of firewood, timber and
 - iv. water,
- b. transport of agricultural products from fields to homesteads,
- c. transport of agricultural implements from homesteads to fields and vice-versa,
- d. transport of seeds and fertilizers to the fields;
- e. transport of implements between different plots etc.

Off-farm transportation includes:

- a. transport of agricultural products including animals to local markets,
- b. transportation to grinding mills
- c. transport of industrial products (commercial fertilizers, implements, seeds, etc.) from markets to homesteads,
- d. transportation to health centres and schools, religious centres, and
- e. transportation to towns and bigger markets.

The Rural dwellers produce the food consumed in the cities and most of the agricultural raw materials used by industries. Rural infrastructure constitutes the substance of rural welfare; effort to raise rural welfare must necessarily go beyond the limited approach of rising per capital income through agricultural development but also to make provision for rural transport facilities. Rural areas serve as the base for the production of food and fiber, the major sources of capital formation for a country, and a principal market for domestic manufactures (Olayiwola and Adeleye, 2005).

Methodology.

The paper set out to review extant literatures to examine the impact of Physical Distribution (Transportation) on Food Security and or Agricultural Practices in Nigeria. Physical distribution (Transportation) play a vital role in economic development and sustenance by facilitating the efficient flow of goods, services and information. To review this topic in question, the first approach was to review extant literature. The works so reviewed were those cited in strong data bases like goggle scholars, web of science, Heliyon, MDPI, Elsevier , Scopus and the likes.

Thematically the works were well arranged and chronologically by year of publication. The study focused on articles that had the key words such as physical distribution, transportation, sustainable agricultural practices, food security, social and economic development. Also the articles so reviewed are those that underwent peer review and which were also published in English Language.

Empirical Review

Many articles has tried to look at the relationship or impact of physical distribution and food security.. One such study was carried out by Chandra,(2020) to investigate the status quo of food insecurity among the population residing to transit in various parts of the United States. He used the methodology of Logistic Regression. Findings suggest that respondents who live close to the public transit in the USA and are from large central Metro Countries of Northern, Southern and Western States showed an increase in food insecurity if they were under 65 years of age.

Okolo (2021) carried out a study to consider the effective and efficient physical distribution of agricultural produce in Enugu North senatorial zone of Enugu State, Nigeria. The study sought to determine the influence of poor road transportation network on effective and efficient distribution of agricultural produce in Enugu North senatorial zone. Secondly, it sought to ascertain the influence of inadequate storage facilities on effective and efficient distribution of agricultural produce in the zone. The population of study comprises famers of agricultural produce in the zone which is unknown as there is no registered farmers' association in the area. Cochran's sample size determination was used to determine the sample size of 384. Survey method was used to distribute structured questionnaires to the 384 respondents who eventually returned 250 well filled questionnaires. For the reliability of the study, Cronbach's alpha was used and the value of 0.982 was determined. Analysis of data was done using simple linear regression statistical technique and the findings revealed that poor road transportation network has a significant negative influence on effective and efficient distribution of agricultural produce in Enugu North senatorial zone. Similarly, it was revealed that inadequate storage facilities have a significant negative influence on effective and efficient distribution of agricultural produce in the zone. Thus, government has to encourage the local and international supply of agricultural produce in the entire zone and internationally by building good road network as well as providing adequate storage facilities for farmers aimed at safe keeping and safe delivery of their agricultural produce to avoid post-harvest losses and reduce poverty by improving the farmers' income.

Abdulraheem (2021) in Ibadan, Nigeria looked at the Impact of Transportation on agricultural practices and products in rural areas. He used the survey approach and posed questionnaires to his respondents. Findings identified some effects militating against the effective production practices.

In another study, Andy et al,(2021) in United States of America developing a spatial analysis framework that realistically characterizes the physical transport network and how to use the network transport enough food to meet demand. He applied the Spatial Workflow and evaluated resilience metrics. Findings show that where food is transported more locally and where the network is denser, disturbances have a much lower impact.

Rajasooriar (2022), in Vancouver, Canada. Carried out a study to highlight food access challenges especially in terms of mobility and transport faced by users of non-profit food hubs in Vancouver before and during the COVID-19 Crisis .He applied Online Survey and Semi-Structured follow-up Interviews . It was found that food obtained from non-profit hubs to be either very or somewhat important to their household's overall diet.

Adama et al (2022) in Kogi State, Nigeria tried to determine the effect of infrastructural deficits on food security in Kogi State, Nigeria. Descriptive Survey research was carried out with Ordinary Least Square Regression as the Statistical tool. From the study,it was revealed that power infrastructure deficit, transport infrastructural deficits and health infrastructural deficits have negative significant effects on food security in Kogi State , Nigeria.

Udemgba et al (2023)South East, Nigeria. had the objective to explore the impact of fluctuations in price of road transport fuel on food security in the South East, Nigeria. Mixed method of data collection and Thematic Analysis was applied and findings indicated that the regulation of fuel pump price has undermined the availability of food products in South East, Nigeria.

Sushan (2023) An agriculturists in Bangladesh carried out an empirical study to depict some key strategies to increase the efficiency of transportation system, eg the application of Internet of Things (IoT) in transportation systems. Context Analysis Methodology was applied.

Findings show that successful integration of Smart or Intelligent transportation in Agro-food item transportation, will lead to less loss of perishable items and ensure the maximum utilization of time, money and visits.

Oni, et al (2024) Lagos ,Nigeria did a research to evaluate transportation and agro-food distribution in Sub-Saharan Africa, examines rural transportation system and assesses the rural transport gaps . A Survey study that posed questionnaires. Findings revealed that transportation enhances agro-food distribution in Sub-Saharan Africa.

Lajuwomi (2024) in Cameroun, set out to assess the impact of regional transportation infrastructure in enhancing food security. The study made use of qualitative Method and Secondary Sources. It was found that multifaceted approach including strengthened transportation infrastructure is essential for addressing food security challenges.

Adeniran (2025) in Oyo, State, Nigeria carried out to determine the impact of transport infrastructure on food security in Ogbomosho, Oyo State. The Mixed method approach of qualitative and quantitative data was the methodology. It was learnt that inadequate transportation infrastructure is a critical barrier to food security in the region.

Shahadat (2025). Kansas, USA had the objective to examine the structural and functional components of resilient transportation systems and their direct influence on food security. He applied Systematic Literature Review. Findings highlight the critical role of robust infrastructure, social equity, and governance redundancy and adaptive capacity for maintaining stable food supply for all communities during disruptions.

On another note, Ejeta and Bai (2025) conducted a study in Ethiopia revealing that conventional agriculture harms the environment and threatens sustainability. To address these issues, sustainable agricultural practices (SAPs) have become imperative. This study utilizes a meta-analysis approach to comprehensively assess empirical studies, investigate the impact of SAPs on crop productivity, identify influencing factors, and examine their temporal evolution. The findings reveal that (1) SAP adoption significantly and positively influences crop productivity, with multiple practices exhibiting the most substantial impact, followed by sustainable agricultural technology. Individuals who adopted SAPs achieved crop productivity that was 980 kilograms per hectare higher than those who did not. (2) Factors such as age, farm size, family size, livestock units, credit access, off-farm income, market distance, and cooperative membership negatively affect crop productivity, whereas education and extension services have a positive impact. (3) The positive effects of education and extension services on crop productivity strengthen over time. The strengthening of these variables over time implies a gradual increase in farmer awareness, access to resources, and adoption of SAPs, highlighting their evolving role in driving them. Accordingly, none of the past researchers identified any patterns in the variables influencing crop productivity. Therefore, promoting SAP adoption and prioritizing education and extension services can offer farmers with experience and support, thereby enhancing crop productivity. Future initiatives should therefore combine interdisciplinary methods, technology, and community involvement for ensuring SAP's sustainability and scalability.

In their own study Saccone and Vallino (2025) discovered that Food security has recently passed through profound systemic disruptions because of the simultaneous occurrence of the global pandemic, the Russia-Ukraine war and climate change. While climate-related shocks are expected to increase in the near future, high uncertainty persists on future pandemic events and armed conflicts. This persistency creates the need for a deep understanding of the concurrent and multiple effects of the three crises on global food security. In this regard, the paper reviews the recent empirical evidence on the channels along which each of the three shocks impacted food security, with a particular focus on its four sub-dimensions: food availability, food access, food utilization and food stability. It aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the simultaneous dynamics associated with the three shocks and to advance current debate on global food security by offering: a) an evidence based guide to quickly anticipate the potential effects of similar shocks that may occur in the future; b) a reflection on existing research gaps; c) the ground for the identification of comprehensive policy responses. Findings are discussed from the perspective of informing future lines of research and policy design, with particular emphasis on food price volatility.

In a related study Harris (2025) revealed that Indonesia's agricultural sector is a vital component of its economy, providing employment for millions and contributing significantly to the nation's GDP. However, the environmental impact of traditional agricultural practices, such as deforestation, excessive pesticide use, and inefficient transport systems, has become a pressing concern. As the country moves toward sustainable development, integrating sustainable agricultural practices with enhanced transport infrastructure offers a promising solution to reduce environmental emissions and promote eco-friendly practices.

This article explores the intersection of sustainable agriculture and transport infrastructure in Indonesia. It examines the role of innovative farming techniques, such as agroforestry and organic farming, in minimizing environmental damage. It also highlights how the development of efficient and eco-friendly transport systems can support these practices by reducing carbon footprints and improving supply chain efficiency. By analyzing current

challenges, technological innovations, and policy recommendations, this article outlines how Indonesia can leverage sustainable transport infrastructure to create a more environmentally responsible agricultural sector.

Discussion of Findings

The findings from the extant literatures thus reviewed showed a variety of outcomes. Findings from the numerous papers point to the fact that Physical Distribution (Transportation) plays a vital role in Food Security and economic development of a given nation. Another major finding was that different methodical approaches were applied in the different studies but coming out with almost same result. Some studies used survey method while others used Structural equations as the case may be. This goes a long way to show that there is no single or restricted approach to the study of physical distribution (transportation) as catalyst to agricultural practices and food security. It was also discovered that majority of the papers came from the Asian World with less from Africa especially the Sub-Saharan Africa which to an extent gives impetus to this particular study.

Conclusion

This paper set out to review the imperatives of physical distribution (transportation) as a catalyst to agricultural practices and food security in Nigeria. To achieve this, extant literatures on the topic were reviewed. The fact has been well established that physical distribution plays a pivotal role in the agricultural practices and food security in Nigeria and the world at large. Its obvious importance in food security, does not fore close the fact that it has various challenges, albeit, some prospects or opportunities. Some strategies also abound to combat these challenges to give its operations some lease of life and leveraging it for economic sustenance.

Recommendations

Looking at the importance of effective Physical distribution (transportation) in enhanced agricultural practice and food security, and findings from the various papers thus reviewed, it becomes imperative to recommend factors that may aid its effective operations. The paper therefore recommends that the government and private sectors should invest on physical distribution (transportation) infrastructure, adopt technologies, develop human capital and improve the institutional frameworks.

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Rising Food Inflation in Nigeria: Do Monetary Policy Interventions Matter?

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Abstract

The rising cost of food in Nigeria, especially in recent times has increased the level of hunger and frustrations among Nigerians. Consequently, several policies have been put in place to increase food productivity on one hand and on the other hand reduce the high level of food inflation. This study sought to examine the response of food inflation to the CBN's manipulation of the monetary policy tools. The novelty introduced in this study is the use of the vector autoregressive (VAR) model in the analysis of the response of food inflation to the manipulation of monetary policy tools in Nigeria. The study used monthly data that spanned the period from 2007M12-2024M5, while the VAR framework was adopted for analysis. The study found that food inflation responded positively to shocks in the broad money supply (M2) in all the periods, except in period one. It was also found that while food inflation responded negatively to monetary policy rate (MPR), Treasury bills rate (TBR) and bank reserve in majority of the periods, its response to exchange rate was positive in all the periods. In another respect, findings indicate that the monetary authorities responded positively to shocks in food inflation by manipulating the MPR, TBR and exchange rate. In particular, it was found that the MPR, TBR and exchange rate responded positively to shocks in food inflation within the study period. It is the contention of the study that the fight against food inflation using monetary policy tools should be complemented with fiscal policies. In addition, exchange rate policy should be made to favour food importation in the short-run, while the long-run target should be to increase domestic food production using various measures.

Keywords: Exchange rate, Food inflation, Monetary policy, Money supply

Introduction

The menace of rising food prices in many developing nations has thrown up policy challenges among policymakers, especially in countries whose major monetary policy objective is inflation-targeting. A major consequence of rising food inflation is that a country's food security is undermined, resulting in hunger, malnutrition and a threat to the livelihood of the low-income households (Rwanyamugabo & Mugabi, 2018). The choice of

policy frameworks to tackle food inflation has always been a subject of debate among scholars. In literature, the question has always been whether rising food prices should dictate the position of the central bank (Iddrisu & Alagidede, 2020). Some scholars have observed that the central banks have minor influence on food price because the effect of their intervention is temporary and food prices are driven by supply-side shocks (Alper, Hobdari & Uppal, 2016). It was noted that monetary policy measures which are aimed at curtailing rising food prices could even lead to instability. For instance, the implementation of contractionary monetary policy during period of rising food prices could have an adverse effect on commodity prices because the rise in interest rate occasioned by such policy could adversely impact on cost of production. Producers may be forced to shift part of the burden on consumers through increase in prices and this is especially the case with developing countries that usually face high production cost.

However, there are counter-arguments which posit that demand-side factors such as income could as well instigate higher food prices, thus requiring aggregate demand moderation through the central bank for effective remedy (Šoškić, 2015). On their part, Hammoudeh, Nguyen and Sousa (2015) noted that for the fact that the prices of commodities contain information with respect to possible upward or downward inflation pressure; the monetary authorities should not overlook them when framing monetary policy measures. Furthermore, De Gregorio (2012) noted that the effect of food prices on consumer price index could be adverse as it extends to general inflation such that if cognizance of such scenario is not taken, the effect of food prices could be underestimated. The role of monetary policy in tackling food inflation has also received theoretical support from the monetarists who argued that inflation could occur from an autonomous increase in money supply which generates aggregate demand and leading to increases in the relative price of commodities. The monetarists conclude that an increase in money supply is the main cause of inflation and not necessarily real shocks. In support of this, Fabris (2024) also noted that currently, the general believe in economic theory is that in the long-run, changes in the price level occurs after the process of the harmonization of changes in the money supply has been completed.

The relevance of monetary policy measures designed to tackle food inflation in sub-Saharan Africa and mainly in Nigeria where poverty rates are high and where there is a high dominance of food in the consumer price index (CPI) basket has been observed by Nadani *et al.* (2023). In addition, Samal *et al.* (2022) observed that since the major monetary policy thrust of the monetary authorities is to ensure price stability, consideration should be given to high food prices because, apart from impacting on macroeconomic stability, they also affect small farmers and poor consumers in developing countries who spend a large portion of their income on food. In a country like Nigeria where the main monetary policy thrust of the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) is inflation-targeting, manipulating the monetary policy tools to stabilize food prices is paramount. As contended by Catao and Chang (2015), central banks whose main target is to moderate inflation should give adequate attention to food price evolution. Ali *et al.* (2023) was equally of the view that the literature has recognized the relevance of food inflation as a major factor in the implementation of inflation-targeting monetary policy.

In Nigeria, the phenomenon of food inflation is perhaps more serious and as such requires urgent attention because rising food costs have adversely impacted on the country's food security situation. Umar and Umar (2022) have noted that Nigeria is among the countries that experience high food inflation within the African countries. The 2018 World Bank report revealed that rising food inflation in Nigeria could be as a result of over-dependence on

imported products which often results into high food inflation. This view found empirical evidence in a study by Egwuma *et al.* (2017) which revealed that food import mounted an upward pressure on food price inflation in Nigeria owing to the depreciation of the domestic currency. Other factors have equally conspired to raise food inflation in the country such as kidnapping and banditry in major farming communities which have forced farmers to desert their farms as well as the menace of Herdsmen who parade their cattle to graze on farms. In recent times also, there was a ban on the importation of some food items, particularly rice and this has led to high price of the commodity even though rice is a major staple food consumed by many households in the country. To worsen matters, the twin policy of exchange rate liberalization and the removal of fuel subsidy which were implemented in 2023 led to unprecedented high cost of food. The removal of fuel subsidy in particular pushed food inflation up through increase in transportation cost as it has become very costly moving food items from one location to the other. Equally, exchange rate liberalization has encouraged the depreciation of the local currency, leading to high cost of imported foods. The problem with food prices in Nigeria is that once they rise, they hardly decline and this has found an empirical support in a study by Nzeh *et al.* (2023) which revealed that food inflation in Nigeria is non-mean reverting.

Over the years, some policies and programmes have been implemented to improve food production in the country. For instance, the National Fadama Development Project (FDP) was implemented in early 1990s which aimed to improve the incomes of the Fadama users through the expansion of farm and non-farm activities. In 2003, the National Special Programme for Food Security (NSPFS) was launched and the programme sought to attain food security and reduction of poverty in the rural areas. Equally in 2003, the Root and Tuber Expansion Programme (RTEP) was introduced which aimed to multiply and introduce improved root and tuber varieties. The Presidential Cassava Transformation Initiative (PCTI) was launched in 2003 to improve the export of processed cassava products. As a way to support cassava processing industry and to diversify into the production of various cassava by-products such as flour, the Cassava Transformation Agenda was launched in 2011. In 2016, the Anchor Borrowers' Programme (ABP) was launched and the programme aimed at providing loans to smallholder farmers to improve the production of some agricultural products such as maize, cotton, rice, tubers, wheat and roots. Other similar programmes have equally been put in place recently to enhance food production. Despite all these laudable policies and programmes, food inflation continues to rise in the country.

The quest to tame inflation in Nigeria by the CBN, particularly in recent times has been a burning issue such that a study of this nature is paramount. To calm inflation, the CBN often raises the monetary policy rate (MPR) and the cash reserve requirement with the aim of reducing money supply. The Bank also engages in open market operations in which debt instruments are sold in order to reduce excess liquidity in the system; just as it intervenes in the exchange rate market to regulate the domestic currency. It is therefore paramount to investigate the extent to which these interventions reduce food inflation in Nigeria. It is expected that food inflation should respond negatively to the Implementation of the policies which signifies their effectiveness in taming it. This study is relevant more so, because reducing food inflation using monetary policy tools goes a long way in reducing the overall inflation since food inflation contributes to a large share of overall inflation in Nigeria. The forecasting accuracy of inflation is often distorted by food price volatility and the uncertainty this volatility introduces has an adverse effect on achieving policy target (Iddrisu & Alagidede, 2021). Based on the aforesaid, the aim of this paper is to examine if food inflation in Nigeria responds appropriately to the implementation of monetary policy.

Literature Review

Theoretical Foundations

The theoretical background which this paper is anchored on is the Keynesian theory on inflation. John Maynard Keynes emphasized on cost-push inflation and demand-pull inflation. While the cost-push inflation has to do with changes in price occasioned by supply-side changes such as cost of production, demand-pull inflation focuses on total demand being higher than total supply. The role of the government in regulating inflation therefore finds justification as both demand and supply factors affecting inflation have to be regulated. With respect to the role of monetary authorities, the question of whether the central banks have roles to play in influencing food inflation in particular has raised some theoretical issues. In their view, Alper *et al.* (2016) contended that since food prices are transitory as well as being moved by supply-side, there is little justification for central bank's intervention. To counter this viewpoint, some scholars have argued that since demand factors such as income equally play a role in influencing food prices, there is need for the monetary authorities to moderate aggregate demand which is within their purview.

It has been understood in literature that in developing countries, regulating food inflation is paramount since households in these countries spend a large chunk of their income on food such that if this factor is ignored, the standard of living of these people will suffer ((Alper *et al.*, 2016). The transmission of monetary policy to food prices has been noted to occur through, among others, interest rate and exchange rate channels. Through interest rate adjustment for instance, the lending rate is influenced with its trickle-down effect on investments, consumption and then to food prices (Bhattacharya & Jain, 2020). On the other hand, the exchange rate effect can occur through, for instance the devaluation of the domestic currency. This policy option raises the cost of food importation as well as the importation of food production inputs which ultimately leads to increase in food prices (Haabazoka & Christopher, 2016). Worthy of note is that the theoretical views raised have link with the economic situation in Nigeria. First, Nigeria is among developing countries whose citizens spend a high portion of their income on food. Secondly, a major monetary policy thrust of the CBN is inflation-targeting with inflation rate being a key monetary variable to influence. Thirdly, the country is food import-dependent and with the continuous depreciation of the domestic currency (naira), prices of imported foods will continue to be high.

Empirical Literature

Across different countries, monetary policy has been noted to shape the movement in food inflation. Notwithstanding, the actual impact of monetary policy on food inflation is yet settled as different studies have produced different outcomes. In a panel study, Bhattacharya (2017) revealed that a contractionary monetary policy implemented unexpectedly exerted a positive and significant impact on food inflation both in advanced economies and in emerging economies. This result did not find support in the outcome of a study in India and Pakistan by Wagan *et al.* (2018) which revealed that tight monetary policy lowered food inflation to a significant extent. However, findings in a study in South Africa by Iddrisu and Alagidede (2020) indicated that the implementation of monetary policy impacted food inflation positively and significantly which corroborates the results of earlier study by Bhattacharya (2017). Findings in India by Samal *et al.* (2022) showed that while the long-run result indicated that money supply impacted positively and significantly on food inflation; in the short-run, the impact of real exchange rate was positive and significant. The positive

influence of money supply found a corroboration in a study in Nigeria by Ashiru (2022). In another study that focused on India, Samal and Goyari (2022) confirmed that contractionary monetary policy stabilized food inflation but exchange rate led to increase in food inflation.

In Nigeria, Umar and Umar (2022) found the existence of a positive link between food inflation and exchange rate which supports the findings of studies conducted in India by Samal *et al.* (2022) and Samal and Goyari (2022). In another study in Nigeria, finding by Nadani *et al.* (2023) confirmed the results of earlier studies which found that contractionary monetary policy had a downward pressure on food inflation. This was further confirmed in a study in Pakistan by Ali *et al.* (2023). Another study in Nigeria by Ezebilo *et al.* (2023) revealed that while the lag one of monetary policy rate raised food inflation significantly; lag two reduced it significantly. In Zambia, Chileya *et al.* (2024) found that monetary policy rate and the rise in broad money supply destabilized food inflation, while exchange rate depreciation raised it. The destabilizing influence of monetary policy found support in the findings by earlier studies (Bhattacharya, 2017; Iddrisu & Alagidede, 2020).

The present study contributes to the literature in Nigeria through methodology. The study applies the vector autoregressive (VAR) model in the analysis of the response of food inflation to the manipulation of monetary policy tools. Past studies in Nigeria have used some frameworks such as the auto regressive distributed lag (ARDL) model and non-linear ARDL. These models are proper in their own right; however, they are limited in the sense that they tend to treat the link between food inflation and monetary policy variables to be uni-directional, running from monetary policy tools to food inflation. However, the link between food inflation and monetary policy implementation could be bi-directional. For instance, monetary policy authorities often respond to rising food inflation through raising the MPR or the cash reserve requirement. On the other hand, food inflation is expected to respond to the implementation of contractionary monetary policy; declining when such policy is implemented. Thus, for monetary policy to be effective, knowledge of the possible existence of this bi-directional relationship is paramount. The choice of the VAR model is because of its ability to handle feedback arising from one variable to the other. This paper used recent data that extends to 2024 considering that food inflation was high from 2023 and has been rising astronomically since 2024.

Data Sources and Research Methods

Data Sources

In this study, monthly series were used and the sample period ranged from 2007M12-2024M5. Data on all the series were obtained from the CBN Statistical Bulletin (2024). A six-variable VAR model that comprised of food inflation, MPR, exchange rate, Treasury bill rate (TBR), M2 and bank reserve was adopted. Food inflation, MPR and Treasury bills rate are measured in percentage. However, M2 and bank reserve are expressed in Billions of Naira. The measurement of exchange rate is in nominal form and the exchange rate of the naira to the US Dollars is used in the study. For normalization and ease of interpretation, this study logged the M2 and bank reserve. Table 1 provides a summary of the variable definition and measurement.

Table 1: Variables Used in Analysis

Variables	Symbols	Definition/Measurements	Expected signs
Dependent variable			
Food inflation	FINFL	Food inflation, measured in percentage	NA
Independent variables			
Monetary policy rate	MPR	Monetary policy rate, measured in percentage	+/-
Exchange rate	EXCHR	Nominal exchange rate of naira (per USA Dollar)	+/-
Treasury bills rate	TBR	Treasury bills rate, measured in percentage	+/-
Control variables			
Bank reserve	BRESERV	Bank reserve, measured in Billions of naira	+/-
Broad money supply	M2	Broad money supply, measured in Billions of naira	+/-

In literature, the role monetary policy variables in influencing food inflation remain controversial. While some scholars contend that such intervention could lead to rising food inflation (Alper, Hobdari & Uppal, 2016), others opine that monetary policy implementation could curtail the rise in food inflation (Šoškić, 2015; Hammoudeh *et al.*, 2015). Judging from these two schools of thought, food inflation is expected to respond either positively or negatively to the manipulation of the monetary policy variables.

The MPR was included in the study since it is among the key monetary policy tools of the CBN which shapes the movement in the other domestic interest rates. Similarly, the TBR was included to account for the Banks’s open market operations. By raising these interest rates as a way to fight inflation, food inflation is expected to decline. However, raising them could also lead to rise in food inflation if they affect the cost of capital of food producers especially in the short-run. In the same way exchange rate was included because its variation through official manipulation affects food inflation. While exchange rate depreciation could lead to increase in food inflation through its impact on food importation, exchange rate appreciation could produce an opposite effect. Worthy of note is that Nigeria is a major food importer which is needed to complement the deficit in domestic food supply.

Since money supply is at the heart of inflation, the study included the broad money supply (M2) which serves as a nominal anchor. Increased money supply raises food inflation, however, monetary policy interventions often reduce it and hence, a reduction in food inflation. Credit expansion of the deposit money banks usually fuels inflation, therefore the study included bank reserve to examine how changes in it brought about by monetary policy implementation influences food inflation. It is expected that increase in bank reserve will lead to an increase in food inflation, while its decrease is expected to reduce food inflation.

Model Specification and Estimation Strategy

The following VAR specification guided the study:

$$x_t = \delta + \sum_{i=1}^k \lambda x_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \tag{1}$$

where:

$x_t = (6 \times 1)$ vector of endogenous variables, $\delta = (6 \times 1)$ vector of intercept terms, $\lambda_t =$ fixed coefficient matrix, $\varepsilon_t =$ random term and $k =$ lag order. The matrix form of the VAR model is thus specified as follows:

$$\begin{bmatrix} FINFL_t \\ MPR_t \\ EXCHR_t \\ LBRESERV_t \\ LM2_t \\ TBR_t \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \delta_1 \\ \delta_2 \\ \delta_3 \\ \delta_4 \\ \delta_5 \\ \delta_6 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_{1,1} & \lambda_{1,2} & \lambda_{1,3} & \lambda_{1,4} & \lambda_{1,5} & \lambda_{1,6} \\ \lambda_{2,1} & \lambda_{2,2} & \lambda_{2,3} & \lambda_{2,4} & \lambda_{2,5} & \lambda_{2,6} \\ \lambda_{3,1} & \lambda_{3,2} & \lambda_{3,3} & \lambda_{3,4} & \lambda_{3,5} & \lambda_{3,6} \\ \lambda_{4,1} & \lambda_{4,2} & \lambda_{4,3} & \lambda_{4,4} & \lambda_{4,5} & \lambda_{4,6} \\ \lambda_{5,1} & \lambda_{5,2} & \lambda_{5,3} & \lambda_{5,4} & \lambda_{5,5} & \lambda_{5,6} \\ \lambda_{6,1} & \lambda_{6,2} & \lambda_{6,3} & \lambda_{6,4} & \lambda_{6,5} & \lambda_{6,6} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} FINFL_{t-1} \\ MPR_{t-1} \\ EXCHR_{t-1} \\ LBRESERV_{t-1} \\ LM2_{t-1} \\ TBR_{t-1} \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} \mu^{FINFL_t} \\ \mu^{MPR_t} \\ \mu^{EXCHR_t} \\ \mu^{LBRESERV_t} \\ \mu^{LM2_t} \\ \mu^{TBR_t} \end{bmatrix} \tag{2}$$

Where: δ and λ represent the intercept terms and the coefficients of the regression, respectively. $FINFL_t =$ food inflation at time t , $MPR_t =$ monetary policy rate at time t , $EXCHR_t =$ exchange rate at time t , $LBRESERV_t =$ log of bank reserve at time t , $LM2_t =$ log of broad money supply at time t , $TBR_t =$ Treasury bills rate at time t and $\mu_t =$ a random term.

In this paper, the first approach in the analysis is to conduct a test for unit root to ascertain the series' order of integration. This is necessary since time series data usually move in similar direction and this could result in running a spurious regression. The unit root was tested under the frameworks of the augmented Dickey Fuller (ADF) and the Phillip Perron (PP). To further examine how the series behave, descriptive statistics test was carried out as well as the correlation matrix test. The test for the existence of cointegration was equally conducted using the Johansen cointegration test. The Johansen cointegration test was chosen based on the unit root results that showed that the series became integrated after the first difference. That is, they are $I(1)$. The VAR model was then used to examine the response of food inflation to the manipulation of the monetary policy tools and this was achieved under the frameworks of the impulse response function and the variance decomposition. The reliability of the VAR results was evaluated by conducting tests for the optimal lag length selection and VAR stability.

Results and Discussion

Stylized Facts: Trend in some Relevant Variables

Over the years, food inflation in Nigeria has been volatile despite measures put in place to address it. In Figure 1, the trend in food inflation corroborates this stance. Findings indicate that food inflation began to rise in July 2007 and attained a peak in March 2009 but afterwards it trended low until June 2016 when it began to trend upward. It is the contention of the study that the rise in food inflation between 2007 and 2009 could be owing to the effect

of the global financial meltdown which occurred within these periods and which affected the headline inflation. Between 2018 and 2019, food inflation trended relatively low but from July 2020, it began to exhibit an upward trend. The aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic and the liberalization of exchange rate as well as the removal of fuel subsidy in 2023 were possible causes for the recent increase in food inflation.

Figure 1: Trend in Food Inflation

Source: CBN Bulletin (2024)

Note: FINFL – Food Inflation

In Figure 2, the trend in food inflation and the MPR was evaluated to ascertain the nature of the association between them. In retrospect, monetary policy rate is the benchmark rate which influences other domestic interest rates. The monetary authorities often raise it in periods of rising inflation. Finding in Figure 2 indicates that between 2007 and 2008 when the MPR was high, food inflation was low. However, as the MPR was lowered between 2009 and 2011, food inflation soared. Also, from 2016 when the MPR was relatively low, food inflation exhibited a rising trend. By implication, raising the MPR often places a downward influence on food inflation and vice-versa.

Figure 2: Trend in MPR and Food Inflation

Source: CBN Bulletin (2024)

Next, the association between food importation and exchange rate was evaluated. This is motivated by the fact that Nigeria is a major food importer, such that food importation is sensitive to exchange rate volatility. In Figure 3, it is shown that both food importation and exchange rate move in almost a similar direction. This is revealed between 2008 and 2010 when both variables had a uniform movement. Also, from 2015 both variables exhibited rising trend even though food inflation exhibited more volatility. In 2019 when food inflation exhibited large decline, exchange was equally low. Food inflation was highest in 2011 and within that year, exchange rate trended very low. After 2011 food inflation trended low, while exchange rate trended high. The drastic fall in food import in 2019 could be as a result of the ban placed on Dollars for food import, forcing importers to source foreign exchange through the parallel market which is often expensive. The fact that the rising trend in exchange rate (depreciation) is associated with the rising trend in food import could be interpreted to mean that food importers are motivated to import more when the local currency depreciates since they often raise the prices within such period. The penchant to raise the prices of imported foods within this period is among the reasons for increased food inflation.

Figure 3: Trend in Food Import and Exchange Rate

Source: WDI (2023)

Note: EXCHR – Exchange rate, FIMPORT – Food import

Within the Africa’s big economies referred to as SANE (South Africa, Algeria, Nigeria and Egypt) countries, Figure 4 indicates that food importation in South Africa was the lowest within the sample period and this suggests a relatively high local food supply in the country. Between 2011 and some part of 2012, food importation in Nigeria trailed behind that of South Africa but afterwards, the trend was lower compared to other countries. From 2018 till the end of the period under investigation, Algeria’s food import bill was highest compared to other countries and this is followed by Egypt. In particular, food importation in these two North African countries remained the highest compared to Nigeria and South Africa.

Fig. 4: Trend in Food Import in SANE Countries

Source: World Development Indicators (2023)

Note: FIMPT – food import, NIG – Nigeria, ALG – Algeria, SA – South Africa, EGY - Egypt

Descriptive Statistics

The first test conducted in this study is the descriptive statistics. This is done with a view to ascertain how the series behave with respect to their mean, median and mode as well as their skewness and kurtosis. Table 1 results indicate that food inflation has a high mean value and this is followed by the MPR. Exchange rate is showed to have the least mean value among the variables within the sample period. The standard deviations of the variables, especially exchange rate, M2 and bank reserve are low which indicates that the deviation from their mean values is small. In another respect, the variable with the highest range is food inflation, suggesting that food inflation experienced high volatility compared to others within the period. With respect to skewness, evidence shows that while Treasury bills rate and bank reserve showed negative skewness as they are skewed to the left, other series exhibited positive skewness since they are skewed to the right. Since all the variables show a positive kurtosis, it implies that they are heavy-tailed.

Table 1: Results of Descriptive Statistics

	FINFL	MPR	TBR	LEXCHR	LM2	LBRESERV
Mean	14.19	12.08	7.85	2.36	7.29	6.37
Median	14.00	12.00	8.27	2.29	7.28	6.53
Maximum	34.06	26.25	17.03	3.19	7.99	7.33
Minimum	1.50	6.00	0.00	2.06	6.59	4.98
Std. Dev.	5.86	3.43	4.31	0.24	0.29	0.61
Skewness	0.42	0.76	-0.03	0.91	0.09	-0.48
Kurtosis	3.95	5.44	1.91	3.67	2.66	2.10
Jarque-Bera	14.21	72.86	10.26	33.41	1.28	15.11
Probability	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.52	0.00
Sum	2966.1	2525.5	1641.6	495.2	1524.0	1332.6
Sum Sq. Dev.	7143.5	2460.2	3865.1	12.20	18.51	78.52
Observations	209	209	209	209	209	209

Source: Author’s own work.

Correlation Matrix Test

Next to the descriptive statistics, the study conducted a test for correlation matrix to examine the degree of correlation among the variables. Findings in Table 2 show that food inflation has a relatively high positive correlation with exchange rate and broad money supply apart from having a low negative correlation with the Treasury bills rate. Monetary policy rate was shown to exhibit low positive correlation with Treasury bills rate and food inflation but a relatively high positive correlation with exchange rate, M2 and bank reserve. Exchange rate has a strong positive correlation with all the variables but exhibited a low negative correlation with Treasury bills rate.

Table 2: Results of Correlation Matrix

	FINFL	MPR	TBR	LEXCHR	LM2	LBRESERV
FINFL	1	0.57	-0.16	0.83	0.79	0.62
MPR	0.57	1	0.31	0.80	0.77	0.76
TBR	-0.16	0.31	1	-0.10	-0.12	-0.06
LEXCHR	0.83	0.80	-0.10	1	0.93	0.84
LM2	0.79	0.77	-0.12	0.93	1	0.94
LBRESERV	0.62	0.76	-0.06	0.84	0.94	1

Source: Author's own work.

Stationarity Test

Results in Table 3 show that under both the ADF and PP, there is an existence of a unit root among the variables at level (that is, they are not stationary). However, after the variables were first differenced, they had no unit root (they became stationary). Thus, under both the ADF and PP, the series became integrated of order one or $I(1)$. This implies that the variables can be used in the analysis since they do not have the tendency to move in similar direction.

Table 3: Results of Stationarity

	ADF		PP	
	LEVEL	FIRST DIFF.	LEVEL	FIRST DIFF.
FINFL	-0.62(0.86)	-2.20(0.02)*	-0.08(0.94)	-2.67(0.00) *
MPR	2.64(0.99)	-7.75(0.00)*	1.83(0.98)	-12.81(0.00) *
EXCHR	0.18(0.73)	-9.39(0.00)*	7.30(0.98)	-8.61(0.00) *
LBRESERV	-1.59(0.48)	-12.70(0.00)*	-1.42(0.57)	-25.43(0.00) *
LM2	-0.34(0.91)	-14.21(0.00)*	-0.35(0.91)	-14.21(0.00) *
TBR	-2.38(0.14)	-19.52(0.00)*	-2.95(0.14)	-20.04(0.00) *

Note: *indicates none acceptance of the null hypothesis at the 5% level

Source: Author's own work.

Cointegration Test

Since the unit root results have shown that the variables are $I(1)$, it suggests that it is proper to estimate the Johansen cointegration to ascertain whether the series have a long-run relationship. Findings in Table 4 indicate that the p-values of both the Trace and Max-

Eigenvalue tests are greater than 5 percent. The implication is that the series do not have long-run relationship at that level of significance. It is proper then for the study to estimate the unrestricted VAR model in order to investigate the short-run relationship. Such will lead to the derivation of the impulse response function as well as the variance decomposition.

Table 4: Results of Johansen Cointegration Test

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)				
Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob. **
None	0.14	89.44	83.93	0.18
At most 1	0.11	58.83	60.06	0.63
At most 2	0.08	35.04	40.17	0.14
At most 3	0.04	17.16	24.27	0.30
At most 4	0.03	8.88	12.32	0.17
At most 5	0.01	2.44	4.12	0.13
Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)				
Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob. **
None	0.14	30.60	36.63	0.21
At most 1	0.11	23.78	30.43	0.26
At most 2	0.08	17.87	24.15	0.28
At most 3	0.04	8.28	17.79	0.67
At most 4	0.03	6.44	11.22	0.30
At most 5	0.01	2.44	4.12	0.13

Source: Author’s own work.

Lag Length Test

Before estimating the VAR model, two tests were conducted, namely: the optimal lag length test and the VAR stability test. The first is conducted to ensure that appropriate lag is chosen with the purpose of ensuring that the random variable follows a white noise. Maddala and Kim (1998) noted that the inclusion of lags in a model could influence the unit root results. In literature, studies have used several information criteria for optimal lag order selection. In this present study, the choice of optimal lag is dictated by both the Schwarz information criterion (SC) and the Hannan Quinn information criterion (HQ) which favoured lag 2 (see Table 5).

Table 5: Results of Lag Length Selection

Endogenous variables: FINFL LM2 LBRESERV EXCHR MPR TBR						
Lag	LogL	LR	FPE	AIC	SC	HQ
0	-2578.2	NA	5922.9	25.7	25.81	25.7
1	-853.2	3329.8	0.00	8.90	9.59	9.18
2	-627.9	421.4	4.53	7.02	8.30*	7.54*
3	-580.1	86.6	4.04*	6.90*	8.78	7.66
4	-545.3	60.9*	4.10	6.91	9.38	7.91
5	-527.9	29.2	4.98	7.10	10.16	8.34
6	-501.1	43.7	5.51	7.19	10.84	8.67
7	-473.8	42.8	6.10	7.28	11.52	8.99
8	-444.2	44.7	6.63	7.34	12.17	9.30

Source: Author’s own work.

Note: * indicates lag order selected by the different information criterion

VAR Stability Test

With the lag length identified, the study conducted a VAR stability test to ensure that the VAR results are valid. In this direction, the inverse root of the autoregressive (AR) characteristic polynomial was used. VAR stability is examined by the position of the roots of AR equation. The [VAR is stable if the roots of the autoregressive equation lie inside the unit circle. In Appendix 1, finding indicates the clustering of the roots of the equation inside the circle, thus confirming the stability of the VAR.

Impulse Response and Variance Decomposition Results

Empirically and theoretically, the influence of monetary policy on food inflation has received some emphases. The monetarists believe that inflation is purely a monetary phenomenon and as such should be fought using monetary policy tools. This present study is thus carried out as an affirmation to this hypothesis. The impulse response function results in Appendixes 2 and 3 (Table and Figure) indicate that food inflation responded negatively to shocks in broad money supply (M2) only in period two but positively in all the other periods. The prolonged positive response is in line with apriori expectation since money supply has been identified in literature to be responsible for inflation (food inflation inclusive). In periods of rising money supply, food supply hardly matches up with food demand, leading to rising prices. This result corroborates the findings of previous studies (Samal, Ummalla & Goyari, 2022; Ashiru, 2022; Ezebilo *et al.* 2023). Findings however reveal that food inflation had a positive response to shocks in bank reserve in period one but a negative response in other periods. The transmission through which bank reserve affects the price level is credit extension. If bank reserve increases, deposit money banks can offer more credit facilities and continuous credit extension has the tendency to raise the price level. In order to guard against such possibility, the monetary authorities often raise the bank reserves using some tools of monetary policy such as cash reserve requirements as a way of reducing liquidity in the banking system. Thus, the negative response of food inflation to bank reserve is an indication that the contractionary monetary policy meant to reduce food inflation via bank reserve is effective within the period under investigation.

Supporting the negative influence of contractionary monetary policy intervention on food inflation, finding revealed that food inflation exhibited a negative response to shocks in monetary policy rate in most of the periods, except only in periods one, seven and eight when the response was positive. In further support to this, the response of food inflation to shocks in TBR was negative in all the periods except in periods one and two when the response was positive. These outcomes corroborate findings of earlier studies conducted in India, Nigeria and Pakistan (Samal & Goyari, 2022; Umar & Umar, 2022; Nadani *et al.*, 2023; Ali *et al.*, 2023) which revealed that the implementation of contractionary monetary policy resulted in a fall in food inflation. The initial positive response of food inflation to shocks in MPR and TBR follow the outcomes of past works which found the implementation of contractionary monetary policy to mount an upward pressure on food inflation (Bhattacharya. 2017; Chileya *et al.*, 2024; Iddrisu & Alagidede, 2020). What the result implies is that the implementation of the contractionary policy first results into an increase in the cost of capital which forces producers to raise the prices of their commodities initially as cost of production increases. However, sustained implementation of contractionary monetary policy results in lower food prices afterwards.

From another perspective, the study found that in all the periods, food inflation exhibited a positive response to shocks in exchange rate. Nigeria is a net importer of food such that any shock arising from exchange rate will impact on food inflation. In recent times, Nigeria's

domestic currency has been depreciating owing to the liberalization of the exchange rate and this is among the reasons food inflation has risen as food importation becomes expensive. This result follows the finding in Nigeria by Umar and Umar (2022) which revealed the existence of a positive nexus between food inflation and exchange rate. Equally in India and Zambia, findings indicated that food inflation has a positive response to shocks in exchange (Samal, Ummalla & Goyari, 2022; Samal & Goyari, 2022; Chileya *et al.*, 2024). Findings equally revealed that exchange rate; MPR and TBR exhibited a positive response to shocks in food inflation. This implies that shocks arising from food inflation led to contractionary monetary policy stance by the monetary policy authorities. MPR's positive response in particular is an indication that a bi-directional causal relationship exists between the two variables. What it implies is that as the monetary policy authorities react to rising food inflation, food inflation also reacts to monetary policy intervention.

In Appendix 4, the variance decomposition results revealed that apart from its own shock which was 100% in period one, broad money supply contributed about 1.8% of shocks in food inflation beginning from the third period which subsequently increased till the last period. Bank reserve contributed about 11.1% of shocks in food inflation in period two and this rose till the last period. In a similar manner, exchange rate was revealed to contribute about 5.9% shocks in food inflation in period two and this rose continuously till the last period. In period two, monetary policy rate contributed to shocks in food inflation by 9.3% and this marginally rose until it approached 3.6% in the last period. However, in period three Treasury bills rate contributed about 0.5% of shocks in food inflation and this rose until it settled at 37.5% in the last period.

Conclusion

The link between food inflation and monetary policy implementation has been a matter of debate among scholars, with some justifying the use of monetary policy to curtail it while some argue that such measures are not necessary. On grounds of this unresolved arguments, this present study used the VAR framework to contribute to the ongoing debate. The VAR was used to capture feedback that arises among the variables.

It was found that food inflation exhibited a positive response to shocks in M2, except in period two but its response to exchange rate was positive in all the periods. Findings equally revealed that while food inflation responded negatively to MPR, TBR and bank reserve in majority of the periods, its response to exchange rate was positive in all the periods. Apart from food inflation responding appropriately to monetary policy implementation, it was found that monetary policy authorities reacted appropriately to food inflation by positively influencing the monetary policy instruments in periods of rising food inflation. The implication of the results is that even though the restrictive monetary policy actions of the CBN are portent to curtail food inflation, the policy could produce an unintended adverse effect. For instance, the fact that food inflation responded positively to shocks in the MPR and TBR in the initial periods is an indication that, perhaps the implementation of these policies resulted in increasing cost of food production via increase in the cost of borrowing, thus giving rise to early rise in food prices.

Consequently, the study is of the view that the use of monetary policy to regulate food prices should be done in synergy with fiscal policy measures so that the adverse consequences of the implementation of monetary policy will be absorbed by the fiscal policies. In addition, food importation should be encouraged temporarily, while the target in the long-run should be to increase domestic food production using various measures. To avoid the adverse

consequences of depreciating exchange rate on the prices of imported food, it is the view of the author that at the moment, exchange rate policy should be made to encourage food importation. This could be achieved through making concessionary exchange rate available to genuine food importers whose activities should be monitored by the relevant agencies so that they do not deviate from the purpose of the policy. Due to high food inflation that ravages the country, the government is mooted the idea of supplying rice to states as a form of palliative. It is the contention of the researcher that such policy lacks sustainability as the distribution may not get to majority of the people. Therefore, the study advises that the short-term measure should be to grant import waivers to identified genuine rice importers while also allowing them to access exchange rate at a concessionary rate such that the price of rice will be affordable to the populace. With the price being affordable, many households will benefit from such short-term intervention.

This study is limited by several factors which future studies should take into consideration. First, the data span excludes pre-2007 global financial crises which affected several world economies including Nigeria. Also, some fiscal variables were omitted partly because their data is not monthly. One of such variable is government expenditure which plays important role in influencing the general inflation. The impact of several government interventions in boosting food productivity were also not captured. Another limitation of the study is the strict assumptions guiding the use of the VAR model. Such include the condition that if the variables are non-stationary, they have to be transformed such as through differencing for them to be stationary. Future studies should also incorporate other variants of the VAR such as the SVAR for robustness check.

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The Role of Agricultural Engineers in Sustainable National Development

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Abstract

Most communities in the Nigerian society especially those in the rural areas are faced with numerous social, economic, cultural and environmental problems. In the most cases, there is a growing concern because only very few farmers or inhabitants in these rural communities are able to follow contemporary, sustainable and environment-friendly methods in their farming systems. The consequences of these are numerous, such as: poverty, migration to urban areas and unplanned suburban settlements. This has a significant impact on the National Economy, Demography, and Environment. In these kinds of situations, sustainable agriculture becomes more critical than ever and the field of Agricultural Engineering play a pivotal role in revolutionizing farming practices, increasing efficiency, and reducing environmental impact. Over the years, Agricultural Engineers have been at the forefront of designing innovative solutions that address the challenges facing modern Agriculture through technological advancements and a deep commitment to environmental stewardship. This paper takes a critical overview at the different solutions the Agricultural Engineer can proffer to National problems ranging from applicable solutions for a sustainable rural development, improved food security and nation building.

Key words: Agricultural Engineer, Sustainable National Development

Introduction

United Nations Development Program (UNDP), in its Annual Report for 2007 (UNDP, 2007), warns the international community of the widening gap between rich and poor citizens of both developed and developing nations, i.e. the richest 2% of the world's adult population now owns more than 50 % of global household wealth whereas the bottom 50% own only 1% and the gains from global growth are highly unequally distributed. Poverty can be simply defined as when citizens end up with poor quality land, water, fuel and other natural resources, which in turn limit soil productivity and lead to environmental degradation. Today, soil erosion, floods, draughts and pollution threaten the livelihoods of 2.6 billion people globally and over a billion people don't have access to portable water. Each year, sub-Saharan Africa loses more in productivity through poor water management than it gains through development aid and debt relief. It is, therefore, imperative to emphasize once again, the roles of Agricultural Engineers under these circumstances.

Engineering, which is the combination of art and science by which the materials and power of nature are made useful to mankind, with the application and advancement of skills based on mathematics, science and technology, integrated with business and management (Asoegwu, 2007) has become a vital tool for infrastructural development, agricultural mechanization and sustainable national growth. In the early years of the Green Revolution, Engineering made many technical contributions to reduce drudgery and help increase labour productivity. Agricultural Engineering which has been described as the Mother of Engineering

incorporates many science disciplines and technology practices for the efficient production and processing of food, feed, fiber, fur, and fuels. It involves disciplines like Mechanical Engineering, Civil Engineering, Electrical and Electronics, Food Engineering, Chemical Engineering, Soil Science, Environmental Engineering, Plant Biology, Animal Science, and much more.

Agricultural Engineers in recent times, have been discussing the present and future position of their profession. They have taken actions like changing the name of the profession and title of the degrees to those more attractive and publicly well-known terminologies or merging with biological systems engineering, bioresources engineering or environmental engineering. However, besides these public awareness efforts, significant focus have also been given to how to realize their roles in sustainable National development as Engineers of Agriculture. Some of the Contributions of Agricultural Engineers can be explained under the following sections.

Sustainable Farming Practices

Agricultural Engineers play a crucial role in promoting sustainable farming practices by developing technologies that reduce the environmental impact of agriculture and help farmers adopt practices that conserve natural resources for overall sustainability in agriculture. We need these machines, systems and processes that conserve energy, reduce drudgery, increase production and enhance efficient and economic processing and storage. Agricultural engineers implement sensor networks and remote sensing technologies to collect data on weather, soil quality, and pest infestations which informs decision making and enables timely interventions.

Development of Eco-Friendly Farming Methods.

Agricultural Engineers design and implement eco-friendly farming methods to minimize pollution and reduce chemical use. They Promote conservation techniques to maintain soil health, biodiversity, and ecosystem functions. They leverage technology to implement precision agriculture for optimized resource usage and minimized environmental harm. Agricultural engineers work on soil and crop management practices to improve soil fertility and reduce erosion, with innovations like no-till farming and cover cropping.

Efficient Post harvest Technologies

Agricultural engineers ensure efficient postharvest handling of crops and livestock products, contributing to food security and economic growth. They design state-of-the-art processing plants and equipment to preserve the quality and nutritional value of perishable crops. They create systems that minimize post-harvest losses, often caused by inadequate processing facilities or improper handling techniques. These systems integrate principles of mechanical and chemical engineering to develop efficient handling systems.

Ensuring Food Safety Standards

Agricultural Engineers implement rigorous standards to prevent contamination and spoilage of stored grains and perishable goods by constructing and maintaining pest resistant and climate-controlled storage structures, building of proper ventilation and humidity control systems to mitigate the growth of mold and bacteria. They also continuously monitor and check quality of food products in collaboration with food scientists and regulatory agencies.

Safe Farm Structures

Agricultural engineers design better animal shelters to house animals. Agricultural engineers are interested in farm structures that improve the health of livestock and create safe and efficient working environments for farmers.

Waste Recycling and Reuse Programs

High demand of natural resources due to rapid urbanization and the disposal problem of agricultural wastes have created opportunities for agricultural engineers to incorporate agro-waste in the construction industry. Many agricultural waste materials are already used in concrete as replacement alternatives for cement, fine aggregate, coarse aggregate and reinforcing materials. Agricultural materials like coconut shells, palm kernel shells, periwinkle shells, oyster shell, corncob, mussel shell, sawdust, rice husk, etc. are been used as coarse aggregates in concrete. These materials partially or fully replace traditional aggregates to reduce costs of putting up farm structures and enhance environmental cleanliness. The concrete made from these agricultural materials are classified as structural lightweight concrete when used to replace common coarse aggregate in concrete production.

Some Best Practices in the Application of Agricultural Engineering in Africa.

Coldhubs

ColdHubs, a Nigerian company, has developed a “plug and play” modular, solar-powered walk-in cold room for 24/7 off-grid storage and preservation of perishable foods. This extends the freshness of fruits, vegetables, and other perishable food from 2 days to about 21 days. The cold room is made of 120mm insulating cold room panels to retain cold. Energy from solar panels mounted on the roof-top of the cold room are stored in high -capacity batteries, these batteries feed an inverter which in turn powers the refrigerating unit.

DENT Agrisystems: Precision Agriculture

DENT Agrisystems, a Ghanaian company, specializes in product design, software and hardware engineering, marketing, agriculture, and business development. They focus on providing low- cost sustainable agricultural technology solutions to smallholder farmers in Africa.

Hwesomame Soil Sensor and Weather Update Service

The soil sensor measures soil parameters like moisture, temperature, salinity, pH, and nutrient contents. This data is cross -referenced against an extensive database of plants and soil, providing personalized predictive insights to farmers via text message and voice call in a local language. farmers receive accurate weather information on atmospheric humidity, temperature, precipitation, and wind speed. This information helps farmers make irrigation event schedules, set pest alarms, plan times for sowing and harvesting

Farmz2U: Data- Driven Agriculture

farmz2U, a Nigerian company, aims to use technology to empower farmers with data analytics that can support core operational processes and key decisions, with access to

relevant stakeholders in the value chain. farmz2U provides tailored expertise that can increase yields using farm-specific data and hardware such as soil sensors and drones. Decision making can be automated with historic data and regression analysis adopt sustainable production methods that ensure high nutritional content of produce. They address threats such as soil degradation and climate change by developing a more efficient farming process and promoting techniques such as fertilizer micro-dosing and swarm robotics.

Sparky Dryer: Post - Harvest Preservation

The sparky dryer is a low-tech food dryer that reduces post-harvest losses in fruits and vegetables by extending the shelf-life of the produce from just 2 days to more than 6 months through dehydration. It is powered by harvest waste from the gardens as clean biofuel (briquettes) with the help of solar-powered energy to dehydrate food in typically 5 hours. It dehydrates 5 times faster than solar dryers and 10 times faster than the open sun drying method while maintaining all the nutrients in the food.

Potential Areas for Exploration

The following areas are potential hotspots open for exploration by the Agricultural Engineers as they seek to contribute their quota to National development.

Developing Rural Electrification

World Bank data showed that 48% of Nigerians are rural dwellers; an indication that Nigeria needs to focus more on rural electrification to steer economic development (UN DESA, 2019). Rural electrification will reduce the burden of overpopulation in urban areas, positively improve the quality of the night life (Olaniyan *et al.*, 2024), reduce mass migration to cities (IEA, 2019) and improve the living condition of rural dwellers (Anandan & Ramaswamy, 2014).

Renewable Energy in Agriculture

Nigeria boasts of abundant renewable energy resources like solar, wind, hydro, and biomass, which could significantly contribute to the country's energy security and reduce reliance on fossil fuels. Agricultural engineers should promote effective utilization of coal, hydropower, wind energy, solar energy, and encourage the production of transport fuels which will include 10% biofuels, to complement the nation's power needs and ensure the much-needed power generation mix. African oil seeds (Jatropha, neem seed, palm oil, soyabean oil, rapeseed oil, sunflower oil, safflower oil, corn oil, coconut oil, peanut oil, canola oil, egusi melon oil and cottonseed oil, etc.) are feedstocks for the production of biofuel, biodiesel, bio gasoline, and kerosene. Likewise, Agricultural waste materials such as animal manure, sugarcane, rice husks, and food waste like onion and potato peelings, can be used to produce biogas which is a renewable energy source that can be used to generate electricity and heat.

Computer-Powered and Solar-Powered Agricultural Equipment.

The emerging synergy effect between solar energy and agricultural practices proves that renewable energy can be used in further advances in this sector, reaching a sustainable trend (Mekhilef *et al.*, 2013). Automation of different farm operations like planting, spraying, weeding, and harvesting can also help to achieve sustainability goals by overcoming labor

shortcomings and minimizing human intervention (Pitla, 2018; Gorjian et al., 2021). Precision agriculture not only increases crop yields but also minimizes wastage and environmental harm.

Farm Automation and Robotics

Automation of different farm operations like planting, spraying, weeding, and harvesting can help to achieve sustainability goals by overcoming labor shortcomings and minimizing human interventions. Agriculture is seeing rapid adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) both in terms of agricultural products and in-field farming techniques.

The Agriculture 4.0 program is the type of agriculture that integrates data and information to monitor field activities by applying remote and proximal sensing and creating a new branch of the Agricultural Industry.

Conclusions and Recommendations

There are many ways the African agricultural engineer can significantly impact their countries. These, he has tried to achieve by developing innovative solutions to address food security challenges, designing technologies that optimize water usage and the mechanization of farming practices. The African agricultural engineer has developed modern infrastructures to provide food, feed, fur, fiber, fuel and other raw materials for industrial development.

However, the Agricultural engineer, besides their common professional activities, should create the awareness of the rural area problems in the society through educational process and media. The multi functionality and non-economic values of agriculture should also be recognized by the society, which includes preventing desertification, preserving the environment whilst enabling more timely operations for better productivity.

As the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) and the Intergovernmental Panels on Climate Change (IPCC) warn about the impacts of global warming and climate change, such as scarcity of food and water supplies, draughts, floods, migrations, increasing frequency of natural disasters, safety of food and water resources, the Agricultural engineer should focus on research bothering on the development of new and renewable forms of energy and innovative environmentally sound technologies to tackle these challenges.

Furthermore, Agricultural engineering must support development of on-farm processing up to getting shelf-ready products especially of traditionally home-made foods. Assurance and control of the safety and quality of this production should also be a concern for the agricultural engineers.

The Agricultural engineer should therefore: ensure adequate and safe food supply for an expanding world population; manage and protect the world's vital water, soil, air and energy resources; make contributions towards food quality, safety, storage, processing, transport, packaging and marketing; help reduce the rural poverty and improve farmers' welfare; avoid environmental degradation; conserve natural resources and control pollution.

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